

Supplementary Online Materials

283,821 concretions, how do you measure the Mazon Creek? Assessing the paleoenvironmental and taphonomic nature of the Braidwood and Essex assemblages

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Appendix 1. Sample manifests by location

Sample manifest notes:

- **Locality numbers:**
 - All localities are numbered as in G.C. Baird's original collections and sample tallies.
 - Mine directory numbers are included where known and appropriate.
 - The original ledgers, as scanned pdfs, are included as Appendix 2.

- **GPS coordinates:**
 - Coordinates were assessed by two of the authors on this work using two different methods:
 - G.C. Baird used Google Earth to locate sampling localities based on memory and original notes.
 - A.D. Muscente converted original Township and Range records to GPS coordinates.
 - Because some of the original sampling localities were difficult to find via Google Earth, the converted records by A.D. Muscente are slightly more complete and were thus used for all figure mapping purposes. There were errors in two converted records, as noted by G.C. Baird, which were corrected and plotted appropriately.
 - All GPS coordinates listed include the corresponding authors' initials.

- **Sample manifests:**
 - A.D. Muscente and M. Laflamme (and student assistants) initially digitized the sample manifests verbatim from the original ledgers. These raw numbers were used for all data analyses.
 - G.C. Baird updated all sample manifests in 2024 in the conversion to document-based records, which makes up the text records included below.
 - Where appropriate, taxon names have been updated from their original recordings if clearer assignments were available over the past 40 years, e.g., the genus *Edmondia* has been replaced by *Mazonomya* and *Septimyalina* by *Myalinella*, etc.
 - We chose to use the raw, un-updated ledger data for all analyses because it reflects the most proximal view of the original collection and identification. As we are aware, this results in minor count discrepancies in some localities, though none that we believe to be large enough to affect the trends observed in our analyses.
 - We are also aware of a locality consolidation issue that merged localities 166, 369, and a formerly unnumbered locality (now included as 414). While locality 166 was excluded by our thresholding, this issue undoubtedly inflated the specimen tallies for locality 369 in the data analysis and should thus be treated with caution.
 - In addition, data from several of the Pit 11 localities collected by Tom Beard were not immediately available for inclusion in our analyses, though notes have been

added to their records here. Pit 11, near the town of Essex, is still well-represented in our included data.

- Some localities include “rejects”, which are not included in the sample tallies. This reflects the abundance of concretions at each sampling locality, whereby Baird and colleagues would focus on collecting already split concretions and others with “well-promising shapes of unsplit nodules” in sites with highly abundant concretions. Where concretion totals were poor, Baird and colleagues collected everything available, with no real selectivity. This latter case could result in “reject” concretions that were generally unable to be split using standard methods.
- **Localities included in the manifest but not tallied for data analysis:**
 - 168, 176, 178, 179, 180–183, 185, 187, 384, 413–415
- **Locality numbers absent from original ledgers:**
 - 12, 115, 117–121, 146–147, 171, 175–183, 185, 187–189, 198, 200, 204, 243–245, 317–319
- *We have included a Microsoft Excel file that contains both the full data sheet and a second sheet with the culled data that reflects the data used in our analyses.*

Locality 1

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Cardiff Coal Company # 1 shaft mine at Cardiff, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/14/24.**
- **Description:** Small spoil cone of abandoned Cardiff Coal Company # 1 deep mine at SW1/4, section 23, T30N, R8E on the Campus 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.052035, -88.285927 (GCB); 41.0559829, -88.28291845 (ADM). Originally listed on the old Illinois mined-out map, but nothing shown at this position on the later Illinois Mine Wiki map. However, fossils were clearly found here. Google Earth imagery cryptic for site.
- Total counts, based on 233 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 5 (2.1% of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 5 (2.1% of total)
 - *Mazonomya* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 2
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.4% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 222 (95.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 113
 - Gray-brown duds = 102
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 7
 - **Rejects:** 243

Locality 2

- **Will-Essex; included—Shaft cone of abandoned Cardiff Coal Company Mine # 2 near Cardiff, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from seven data sheets updated as of 04/08/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil pile of abandoned Cardiff Coal Company # 2 mine northwest of Cardiff, Illinois at NE1/4, SE1/4, Section 22, T30N, R8E on the Campus 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.058759, -88.291307 (GCB); 41.06129448, -88.29522115 (ADM). Mine hill not conclusively recognized using Google Earth. Mine directory number = 757.

- Total counts, based on 1,365 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 281 (20.5% of sample concretions total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 70
 - *Neuropteris* = 32
 - *Annularia* = 18
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 15
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stem = 85
 - Bark = 6
 - *Stigmarioides* = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 4
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - Cone (*Selaginites*?) = 1
 - Cone (indeterminate) = 1
 - Macerated plants = 14
 - Plant fragments = 5
 - Unidentified plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 121 (8.8% of sample concretion total)
 - Blobs = 19
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 10
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - *Belotelson* = 2
 - *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Eocarid shrimp = 1

- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 6
- Unidentified polychaete = 6
- Holothurians = 39
- *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
- *Tullimonstrum* = 1
- Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
- Coprolite = 4
- Trails/traces = 23
- Unidentified animal = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 37 (2.7% of sample concretion total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 32
 - Ghosts-smears = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 926 (67.8% of sample concretion total)
 - Common duds = 567
 - Gray duds = 225
 - Blue-gray duds = 13
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 38
 - Septarial duds = 21
 - Brown duds = 6
 - Weathered duds = 56
- **Rejects:** 903

Locality 3

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Consolidated Coal and Iron Company shaft mine southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/14/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Consolidated Coal and Iron Company deep mine located at NW1/4, NW1/4, section 30, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.142047, -88.239106 (GCB); 41.1398132, -88.23705455 (ADM). Mine hill still visible. Mine directory number = 2533. Mine hill small, but visible on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 510 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 14 (2.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 23 (4.5% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 4
 - Senior blobs = 4
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 11
 - Probable polychaete = 1
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 15 (2.9% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - Ghosts = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 13
 - **Duds:** Total = 458 (89.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 132
 - Gray-brown duds = 172
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 51
 - Blue-gray duds = 103
 - **Rejects:** 442

Locality 4

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Number three Coal Company # 3 Mine South of South Wilmington, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/17/24.
- **Description:** Number Three Coal Company # 3 Mine south of South Wilmington, Grundy County, Illinois at coordinates NW1/4, SE1/4, section 23, T31N, R8E at digital coordinates 41.152141, -88.269694 (GCB); 41.14847108, -88.26842643 (ADM) on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 2337.
- Total counts, based on 753 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 16 (2.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2 6
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1 1
 - Plant stems = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 274 (36.3% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 208
 - Junior blobs = 48
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam) = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Unidentified crustacean = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Ratworm = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Trails/traces = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.3% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 460 (61.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 460
 - **Rejects:** 254

Locality 5

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Mine # 1** southeast of Gardner, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/17/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Mine # 3 at ctr, section 14, T31N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.163633, -88.272521 (GCB); 41.1648593, -88.2715247 (ADM). Mine hill still visible. Mine directory number = 7.
- Total counts, based on 836 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 44 (5.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 11
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Thallites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 165 (19.7% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 37
 - Senior blobs = 53
 - Junior blobs = 36
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 6
 - Horseshoe crab *Paleolimulus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 2
 - Agnathan chordate *Gilpichthys* = 1
 - Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
 - Coprolites = 12
 - Trails/traces = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 36 (4.3% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 24
 - “spots” = 11
 - “discs” = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 591 (70.6% of total).
 - Common duds = 146

- Gray-brown duds = 398
- Dark gray duds = 4
- Blue-gray duds = 7
- Pyrite-cored duds = 32
- Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects:** 473

Locality 6

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion deep mine # 2 at South Wilmington, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from data sheets updated as of 04/13/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil pile of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion # 2 deep mine at SW1/4, SE1/4, Section 11, T31N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.174205, -88.270122 (GCB); 41.17747738, -88.27441473 (ADM). Mine hill apparently levelled. Mine directory number = 260.
- Total counts, based on 823 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 59 (7.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 12
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stem = 2
 - Stems and bark = 14
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Seed? = 1
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - Indeterminate plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 338 (41.0% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 222
 - Junior blobs = 23
 - Indeterminate blobs = 40
 - Box jelly *Anthracomедusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 12
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 7
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 9
 - Eocarid shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Arthropod fragment = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 4
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails/traces = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 33 (4.0% of total)
 - Discs = 13

- Ghosts = 2
- Unidentified nucleus = 18
- **Duds:** Total = 393 (47.7% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 115
 - Gray duds = 207
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 10
 - Septarial duds = 31
 - Weathered duds = 17
 - Septarial duds = 13
- **Rejects:** 188

Locality 7

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Gardner Wilmington Coal Company # 1 Mine, southeast of Gardner, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/21/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Gardner, Wilmington Coal Company # 1 mine at SE1/4, Sec 10, T31N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.178647, -88.287229 (GCB); 41.17541425, -88.28644135 (ADM). Mine hill still visible. Mine directory number = 2336.
- Total counts, based on 826 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 73 (8.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 37
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 3
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 100 (12.1% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 35
 - Junior blobs = 13
 - Indeterminate blobs = 36
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Indeterminate shrimp = 1
 - Insect = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Trails/traces = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 21 (2.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 9
 - Unidentified nucleus = 11
 - Incognitum = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 632 (76.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 254
 - Gray duds = 30

- Gray brown duds = 21
- Pyrite-cored duds = 16
- Dark gray duds = 48
- Blue-gray duds = 181
- Septarial duds = 52
- Weathered duds = 30
- **Rejects:** 488

Locality 8

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Company (Clarke City) shaft mine in Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/15/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Wilmington Coal Company (Clarke City) shaft mine at ctr, NW1/4, section 19, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.153805, -88.238103 (GCB); 41.15457045, -88.2373149 (ADM). Mine hill still visible. Mine directory number = 2531.
- Total counts, based on 710 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 43 (6.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 19
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 14
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 71 (10.0% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 8
 - Senior blobs = 22
 - Junior blobs = 13
 - Indeterminate blobs = 8
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Indeterminate polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 13
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.7% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - “discs” = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 591 (83.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 261
 - Gray-brown duds = 156
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 137
 - Characteristics of additional split duds = 37 (add to total)
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 24
 - Gray-brown duds = 10
 - Mottled interiors = 3
 - **Rejects:** 470

Locality 9

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Unnamed shaft mine “A”, Essex County, Illinois.
Combined summary sample manifest of all six data sheets updated as of 04/05/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned shaft mine “A”, west of Essex, Illinois. Location is west of north end of northern part of abandoned Peobody Coal Co. Northern Mine (Pit 13) at NE1/4, NW1/4, Section 18, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.169599, -88.233867 (GCB); 41.1711731, -88.23046805 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5978.
- Total counts, based on 2,396 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 237 (9.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 110
 - *Neuropteris* = 17
 - *Annularia* = 23
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - Plant stem = 46
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 11
 - Unidentified plant = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 715 (29.8% of total)
 - *Essexella* (category not subdivided) = 393
 - Senior blobs = 115
 - Junior blobs = 48
 - Indeterminate blobs = 28
 - *Etacystis* = 3
 - *Escomasia* (the “wye”) = 1
 - Box Jelly (*Anthracomедusa*) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 9
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - *Strobeus* = 5
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 4
 - *Belotelson* = 27
 - Shrimp (*Kallidectes*) = 4
 - Mantis shrimp (*Tyrranophontes?*) = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Shrimp (*Mamayocaris*) = 1
 - Unidentified shrimps = 6
 - Incognitum arthropod = 1
 - *Didontogaster* (tummy tooth) = 3

- *Astreptoscolex* (plain worm) = 3
- Indeterminate polychaete = 2
- Holothurians = 18
- *Tullimonstrum* = 8
- *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 5
- Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
- Unidentified palaeoniscoid = 1
- Coprolites = 42
- Trails/traces = 7
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 49 (2% of total)
 - Discs = 4
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 45
- **Duds:** Total = 1395 (58.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 932
 - Gray-brown duds = 273
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 106
 - Septarial duds = 6
 - Weathered duds = 78
- **Rejects:** 717

Locality 10

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Spoil cone of abandoned unnamed mine “B” south of East-West Merchant’s Road and adjacent to north end of Pit 13 in Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/17/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned unnamed shaft mine “B” at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 18, T31N, R9E, the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle, digital coordinates 41.171398, -88.229960 (GCB); 41.17126818, -88.2256198 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5970.
- Total counts, based on 778 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (2.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Plant fragments = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 207 (26.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 99
 - Junior blobs = 42
 - Indeterminate blobs = 51
 - Box jelly *Anthracomедusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Peachocaris?* = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails/traces = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 19 (2.4% of total)
 - Discs = 8
 - Unidentified nucleus = 11
 - **Duds:** Total = 532 (68.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 326
 - Gray duds = 9
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 28
 - Red-brown duds = 48
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - Weathered duds = 116
 - **Rejects:** 501

Locality 11

- **Will-Essex; included—Torino, Wilmington & CM & M Company # 6 shaft mine spoil cone. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/09/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Torino, Wilmington, & CM & M Company # 6 shaft mine at SW1/4, section 31, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.207886, -88.238257 (GCB); 41.2051975, -88.2388772 (ADM). Mine hill is currently an island in Braidwood Lake, the cooling lake for the Braidwood reactor. Mine directory number = 3936.
- Total counts, based on 1,045 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 152 (14.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 33
 - *Neuropteris* = 11
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Annularia with Sphenophylloides* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Plant stem = 52
 - Bark/stem = 8
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Spore case = 1
 - Macerated plants = 22
 - Unidentified plants = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 207 (19.8% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 26
 - Senior blobs = 9
 - Junior blobs = 24
 - Indeterminate blobs = 21
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 15
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 9
 - *Myalinella* clusters = 1
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 4
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 14
 - Ostracods = 1

- Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 10
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 2
- Unidentified polychaete = 5
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 18
- Holothurians = 3
- *Tullimonstrum* = 3
- Agnathan fish *Gilpichthys* = 1
- Coprolites = 13
- Trails/traces = 9
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 49 (4.6% of total)
 - Discs = 11
 - Smears = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 33
- **Duds:** Total = 637 (60.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 89
 - Gray-brown duds = 289 122 226
 - Dark gray duds = 8
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 30
 - Septarial duds = 47
- **Rejects:** 479

Locality 13

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Braceville Coal Company # 1 deep mine at Braceville, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 04/17/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Braceville Coal Company # 1 shaft mine does not appear to be where the mine adit is on the mined-out map, but appears to be best positioned at ctr, Section 26, T32N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.224383, -88.275902 (GCB); 41.22449078, -88.27135973 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5519.

- Total counts, based on 258 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 54 (20.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidohylloides* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 3
 - Plant stem = 20
 - Macerated plants = 24
 - **Animals:** Total = 37 (14.3% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 4
 - Junior blobs = 4
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - Unidentified clams = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Holothurian = 6
 - Coprolites = 7
 - Trails/traces = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (1.1% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 164 (63.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 164

Locality 14

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Nicholas Cotton Mine underground mine spoil pile at east edge of Braceville, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest modified from earlier summary sheet updated as of 04/18/24.**
- **Description:** Shaft mine spoil pile, east of Braceville, Illinois and northwest of railroad at NE1/4, SW1/4, NW1/4, section 25, T31N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.234203, -88.251459 (GCB); 41.22461178, -88.26179678 (ADM). No mine hill spotted on Google Earth; it appears to have been removed. Mine directory number = 6671.
- Total counts, based on 1,846 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 156 (8.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 53
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 91
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 628 (34.0% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 214
 - *Mazonomya* = 179
 - *Myalinella* = 10
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - *Aviculopecten* with ribbed bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 4
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 13
 - *Euphemites* with *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Shrimp (pygocephalomorph?) = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 8
 - Insect nymph (Thuysanuran?) = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 10
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 5
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 14
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 5
 - Polychaete Baby Tooth = 3
 - Polychaete Simple jaw = 4
 - Polychaete “fan worm” = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 23
 - Priapulid = 1

- Holothurians = 36
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
- Coprolites = 6
- Trails/traces = 81
- Unidentified animal = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (0.7% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 13
- **Duds:** Total = 1,049 (56.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 749
 - Light gray duds = 147
 - Gray-brown duds = 104
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 11
 - Pelletized duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - Dark gray duds = 31

Locality 15

- **Will-Essex; included—Wilmington Carbon Coal Company (“Rixson”) Mine.**
Combined summary sample manifest of all five data sheets updated as of 03/26/24.
- **Description:** Small spoil cone of Wilmington Carbon Coal Company (“Rixson Mine”), currently beneath water of Lake Braidwood at NW1/4, section 30, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.228706, -88.241820 (GCB); 41.22723155, -88.2394582 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3935.
- Total counts, based on 1801 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 64 (3.5% of total concretions counted)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 12
 - Lycopod stem-twigs = 1
 - Macerated plants = 46
 - Unidentified plant = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 314 (17.4% of total concretions counted)
 - Uncategorized blobs = 84
 - Senior blobs = 106
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - “eyed” blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* = 18
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - *Schizodus* = 25
 - Unidentified bivalve = 3
 - *Belotelson* = 1
 - *Belotelson* (molted) = 2
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Paleocaris* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 25
 - *Didontogaster* (tummy tooth) = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 8
 - Polychaete *Hystricula* = 2
 - Polychaetes = 5
 - *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Trails/traces = 6
 - Coprolites = 8
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 23 (1.2% of total concretions counted)
 - Multiple discs = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 20
 - Discs = 1
 - Smears = 1

- **Duds:** Total = 1400 (77.0% of total concretions counted)
 - Common duds = 1215
 - Gray-brown duds = 154
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 9
 - Septarial duds = 22
- **Rejects:** 463

Locality 16

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “M” deep mine at Godley, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/15/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, and Vermilion “M” or # 3 deep mine at Godley, Will County, Illinois at ctr, SW1/4, section 19, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.234129, -88.240626 (GCB); 41.2345433, -88.23983075 (ADM). Mine hill not located on Google Earth; its position may be the current site of the Godley Public Water Facility.
- Total counts, based on 600 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 58 (9.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Bark = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 36
 - **Animals:** Total = 136 (22.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 75
 - Junior blobs = 12
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - “eyed” blobs = 14
 - Unidentified bivalves = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - *Astreptoscolex* with blob = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 5
 - Probable polychaetes = 3
 - Coprolites = 9
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (1.0% of total)
 - “discs” = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - Incognitum nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 400 (66.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 364
 - Gray-brown duds = 13
 - Septarial duds = 23
 - **Rejects:** 73

Locality 17

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Joliet & Wilmington Coal Company # 2 deep mine at north end of Pit 11 near fossil gate, east of Braidwood Nuclear Power Plant, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from six data sheets updated as of 04/15/24.

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Joliet & Wilmington # 2 deep mine east of Braidwood Nuclear Generating Station at center, NE1/4, NW1/4, section 20, T32N, R9E near north edge of Essex 7.5' quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates at 41.248227, -88.219931 (GCB); 41.2420015, -88.22108615 (ADM). Mine hill not recognized on Google Earth; it may no longer exist. Mine directory number = 3933.

- Total counts, based on 1,373 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 83 (6.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 6
 - *Neuropteris* = 10
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 6
 - Plant stem = 27
 - Bark/stem = 5
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - Indeterminate plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 626 (45.5% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 18
 - Senior blobs = 46
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - Indeterminate blobs = 14
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 345
 - *Mazonomya* (2 + clams) = 92
 - *Mazonomya* (valves closed or single valve) = 33
 - Crushed bivalves = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - *Cyclus* = 5
 - “Roach egg sac” = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 5
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 8
 - Indeterminate worm = 10
 - Holothurians = 5
 - Coprolites = 26

- Trails/traces = 21
- Trails/traces with *Mazonomya* = 2
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 37 (2.6% of total)
 - “discs” = 11
 - Ghosts-smears = 1
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 25
- **Duds:** Total = 627 (45.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 366
 - Gray duds = 58
 - Gray-brown duds = 128
 - Dark gray duds = 16
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 4
 - Septarial duds = 25
 - Weathered duds = 30
- **Rejects:** 387

Locality 18

- **Will-Essex; included—Spoil pile of unnamed, abandoned shaft mine east of Braceville and south-southwest of Godley, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/18/24.**
- **Description:** Small spoil cone of abandoned, unnamed deep mine near the west edge of the Essex 7.5' quadrangle in the NE1/4 of section 25, T32N, R9E at digital coordinates 41.227348, -88.246883 (GCB); 41.22686365, -88.2498795 (ADM). Hill still visible. Mine directory number = 5517.
- Total counts, based on 1,527 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 455 (29.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 51
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 4
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - Seed = 1
 - *Asolanus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 379
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 514 (33.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 308
 - Blob with plant stem = 17
 - Junior blobs = 4
 - Indeterminate blobs = 45
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 18
 - *Aviculopecten* = 29
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 7
 - *Cyclus* = 20
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 6
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 9
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 8
 - “ratworm” = 1
 - Priapulid worm? = 1
 - Holothurians = 14
 - Coprolites = 23
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 30 (1.9% of total)
 - “discs” = 6
 - Ghosts-smears = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 20

- **Duds:** Total = 528 (34.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 246
 - Gray duds = 53
 - Gray-brown duds = 56
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 44
 - Septarial duds = 8
 - Weathered duds = 121
- **Rejects:** 504

Locality 19

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “K” deep mine at southwest edge of Godley, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/18/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil pile of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion shaft mine “K” bordering Illinois Route 53 and the west edge of the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle in the SE1/4, section 24, T32N, R8E at estimated digital coordinates 41.228204, -88.256521 (GCB); 41.2332489, -88.2447084 (ADM). Hill possibly now removed-levelled. Mine directory number = 2354.

- Total counts, based on 695 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 215 (30.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - Plant stems = 24
 - Bark/stems = 18
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 169
 - **Animals:** Total = 103 (14.8% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 26
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - *Mazonomya* = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 18
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Aviculopecten* with hoplocarid shrimp = 1
 - Indeterminate bivalves = 14
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Probable shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 7
 - Holothurians = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Coprolites = 15
 - Trails/traces = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (1.1% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 369 (53.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 359
 - Septarial duds = 10
 - **Rejects:** 88

Locality 20

- **Will-Essex; included—Shaft cone of abandoned Chicago, Milwaukee, & St. Paul Coal Company # 2 Mine, Braceville area, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/06/24.**
- **Description:** Very large spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Milwaukee, & St. Paul Coal Company # 2 shaft mine northwest of Interstate 55 and hamlet of Braceville, Illinois at SE1/4, section 23, T32N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.233594, -88.274169 (GCB); 41.23358945, -88.2693584 (ADM). Mine hill partly removed, but still visible on Google Earth. Mine directory number = 2353.
- Total counts, based on 4,400 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 141 (3.2% of sample concretions total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 17
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 9
 - Plant stems = 49
 - Bark = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 29
 - Unidentified plants = 20
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,293 (29.3% of sample concretion total)
 - Undivided *Essexella* category = 256
 - Senior blobs = 155
 - Junior blobs = 94
 - Indeterminate blobs = 57
 - Circular blobs = 7
 - Blobs with trails/traces = 2
 - “lettuce” = 3
 - *Etacystis?* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 102
 - *Myalinella* = 80
 - Unidentified pectens = 3
 - “hill 20” bivalve = 242
 - Unidentified bivalves = 123
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - *Belotelson* = 2
 - *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 6
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* (tummy tooth) = 5
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 5
 - Incognitum polychaete = 1
 - “fan worm” = 19

- Unidentified polychaete = 29
- Probable polychaete = 1
- Holothurians = 14
- Acorn worm *Balanoglossus* = 1
- *Ilyodes* = 1
- *Palaeoxyris* = 2
- Coprolites = 25
- Trails/traces = 56
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 170 (3.8% of sample concretion total)
 - Kaolinite centers = 78
 - “discs” = 13
 - “bleichen” = 3
 - “smears” = 2
 - Unknown fossils = 28
 - Unidentified nucleus = 46
- **Duds:** Total = 2,796 (63.5% of sample concretion total)
 - Common duds = 2,223
 - Gray duds = 191
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 49
 - Septarial duds = 109
 - Weathered brown duds = 224
- **Rejects:** 403 (these are not added to count)

Locality 21

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Milwaukee, & St. Paul Coal Company # 3 Mine north of Braceville, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/18/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil pile of abandoned Chicago, Milwaukee, & St. Paul Coal Company # 3 Mine at ctr, NW1/4, Section 23, T32N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.242263, -88.274732 (GCB); 41.2372426, -88.2743008 (ADM). Mine spoil pile now apparently reclaimed-destroyed. Mine directory number = 2356.
- Total counts, based on 685 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 21 (3.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 5
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - “lettuce” = 2
 - Scale bark = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 188 (27.4% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 70
 - Junior blobs = 31
 - Indeterminate blobs = 17
 - “eyed” blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 3
 - Clustered *Myalinella* = 1
 - “Hill 20” bivalves = 11
 - Unidentified bivalve = 2
 - Incognitum bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Probable polychaete = 1
 - “Fan Worm” = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 2
 - Coprolites = 18

- Trails/traces = 17
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 16 (2.3% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 16
- **Duds:** Total = 460 (67.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 259
 - Gray duds = 62
 - Blue-gray duds = 36
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 18
 - Red brown duds = 46
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - Weathered duds = 34
- **Rejects:** 272

Locality 22

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Braceville Coal Company # 4 deep mine north of Braceville, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/16 /24.
- **Description:** Large spoil cone of abandoned Braceville Coal Company # 4 shaft mine at NW1/4, Section 24, T32N, R8E on the Gardner 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.242110, -88.260449 (GCB); 41.2356343, -88.2450736 (ADM). Hill still quite visible. Mine directory number = 2355.
- Total counts, based on 1,077 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 32 (2.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - Plant stems = 15
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 341 (31.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 208
 - Junior blobs = 70
 - *Myalinella* = 8
 - “Hill 20” bivalve = 4
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 6
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 3
 - Shrimp parts = 3
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Arachnid = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Cartilaginous fish = 1 (holotype)
 - Coprolites = 18
 - Trails/traces = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (1.0% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 5
 - Incognitum = 6
 - **Duds:** Total = 693 (64.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 621
 - Gray-brown duds = 70
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - **Rejects:** 154

Locality 23

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Braceville Coal Company # 6 deep mine, north of Braceville, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/13/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Braceville Coal Company Mine # 6 at the NW1/4, SE1/4, Section 14, T32N, R8E near the south margin of the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.252059, -88.273396 (GCB); 41.25533935, -88.27976095 (ADM). Mine hill still visible on Google Earth. Mine directory number = 2352.
- Total counts, based on 1,962 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 66 (3.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 15
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - Plant stem = 27
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 17
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 413 (21% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 100
 - Junior blobs = 75
 - Indeterminate blobs = 28
 - “eyed” blobs = 11
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam) = 6
 - *Myalinella* = 24
 - *Myalinella* clusters = 13
 - “Hill 20” bivalves = 10
 - Incognitum bivalves = 8
 - Unidentified bivalves = 53
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Shrimp *Kallidectes* = 2
 - Unidentified hoplocarid shrimp = 1
 - Insect (*Gerarus*) = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 22
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Fish (*Megalichthys* scale) = 1
 - Coprolites 25
 - Trails/traces = 22
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 34 (1.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - “ghosts-smears” = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 31

- **Duds:** Total = 1,449 (73.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 941
 - Gray duds = 125
 - Dark gray duds = 9
 - Red brown duds = 106
 - Septarial duds = 17
 - Weathered duds = 11
 - Breakdown of duds split open (total 231):
 - Gray-brown duds = 191
 - Light brown-gray duds = 9
 - Hard “blue-boy” duds = 10
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - “spots” or mottled = 15
- **Rejects:** 225

Locality 24

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corporation # 2 Mine south of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/19/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corporation # 2 Mine at NE1/4, Section 17, T32N, R9E at estimated digital coordinates 41.256008, -88.212184 (GCB); 41.2566844, -88.21226065 (ADM). Mine dump area appears cryptic on Google Earth; spoil pile may have been removed since original visit. Mine directory number = either 402 or 5963.

- Total counts, based on 1,150 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 168 (14.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 18
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidohylloides* = 4
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - Plant stems = 50
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Marioteris* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Macerated plants = 72
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 273 (23.7% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 36
 - Senior blobs = 40
 - Junior blobs = 43
 - Indeterminate blobs = 14
 - *Octomedusa* = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam) = 60
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams) = 3
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Gastropod *Euphenites* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 9

- Insect = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
- Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 1
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
- Polychaete Baby Tooth = 2
- Unidentified polychaetes = 10
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
- Priapulid worm = 1
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
- Coprolites = 5
- Trails/traces = 26
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 32 (2.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 11
 - Ghosts-smears = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 17
 - Incognitum = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 677 (58.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 255
 - Gray-brown duds = 363
 - Dark gray duds = 41
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 10
 - Pelletal duds = 4
 - Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects:** 535

Locality 25

- **Will-Essex; included—Un-labeled, abandoned shaft mine spoil pile in southwest part of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/19/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned deep mine near southwest margin of Braidwood, Illinois in ctr, NE1/4, section 18, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.257261, -88.232364 (GCB); 41.25636175, -88.2313583 (ADM). Tip heap not readily apparent via Google Earth (position estimated) but indicated on the 1950s quadrangle map. Corresponds to Illinois mine directory number # 5944.

- Total counts, based on 131 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 12 (9.1% of total)
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 6
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 41 (31.2% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 5
 - Junior blobs = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (1 clam) = 19
 - *Mazonomya* (2 clams) = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Trails/traces = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (3.8% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 73 (55.7% of total)
 - Common duds = 26
 - Gray-brown duds = 46
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 26

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Spoil pile of unnamed abandoned shaft mine, southwest of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/19/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned unnamed shaft mine # 5945 in the NW1/4, section 18, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates at 41.255540, -88.241676 (GCB); 41.256147, -88.2411757 (ADM). Spoil cone is southeast of Reed Road exit off of Interstate 55. Mine hill visible on Google Earth.

- Total counts, based on 410 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 34 (8.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 17
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Cone (*Calamostachys*) = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 20 (4.8% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 10
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 1
 - Trails/traces = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (2.6% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 11
 - **Duds:** Total = 345 (84.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 258
 - Gray to brown duds = 81
 - Septarial duds = 6

Locality 27

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Eureka Coal Company # 2 Shaft Mine in southwestern part of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/19/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone (now apparently removed) of abandoned Eureka Coal Company # 2 deep mine in the SW1/4, SE1/4, section 7, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.263482, -88.232545 (GCB); 41.26174178, -88.23404923 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5942.
- Total counts, based on 1,041 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 91 (8.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 18
 - *Neuropteris* = 15
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 15
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - Plant stems = 7
 - Bark = 6
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 231 (22.1% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 48
 - Senior blobs = 14
 - *Mazonomya* (not subdivided) = 70
 - *Mazonomya* (1 clam) = 41
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams) = 6
 - *Aviculopecten* = 5
 - Unidentified bivalve = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 6
 - “fish worm” = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Fish *Acanthodes* = 1
 - Tetrapod (legless amphibian) *Phlegethantia* = 1
 - Coprolites = 14

- Trails/traces = 12
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 16 (1.5% of total)
 - “disc” = 12
 - Ghost-smear = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
- **Duds:** Total = 703 (67.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 353
 - Gray-brown duds = 226
 - Septarial duds = 22
 - Weathered duds = 102
- **Rejects:** 642

Locality 28

- **Will-Essex; included—Eureka Coal Company “E” deep mine at Braidwood, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/06/24.**
- **Description:** Reclaimed (freshly bulldozed at time of collecting) mine spoil area corresponding to abandoned Eureka Coal Company “E” shaft mine adjacent to Interstate 55 Braidwood exit due west of Braidwood, Illinois at SW1/4, Section 7, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.262710, -88.241828 (GCB); 41.26339335, -88.24147095 (ADM). Area remains a flattened vacant lot as viewed through Google Earth. Mine directory number = 5943.
- Total counts, based on 3,099 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 305 (9.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 32
 - *Neuropteris* = 35
 - *Annularia* = 33
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 22
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 2
 - Plant stems = 89
 - Bark = 3
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 54
 - Plant fragments = 5
 - Unidentified plant = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 921 (29.7% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 113
 - Junior blobs = 50
 - Indeterminate blobs = 14
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa* = 1
 - Hydroid *Drevotella* = 4
 - Total *Mazonomya* count from all sheets = 604
 - *Mazonomya* = total 243 (breakdown from one sheet):
 - Clams open (1/nodule) = 223
 - (2/nodule) = 14
 - (3/nodule) = 4
 - Clams closed or single valved = 2
 - *Mazonomya* with blob = 1
 - *Solemya* = 3
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3

- “hill 20” clam = 2
- Indeterminate bivalve = 1
- Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
- Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
- Syncarid? = 1
- *Cyclus* = 1
- Millepede = 1
- *Didontogaster* (tummy tooth) = 2
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 9
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 10
- Unidentified polychaete = 21
- Polychaete/*Mazonomya* = 1
- Probable polychaete = 4
- “fan worm” = 1
- Fish worm = 1
- *Spirorbis* = 4
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 2
- Holothurians = 4
- Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Coprolites = 20
- Trails/traces = 39
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 50 (1.6% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 31
 - Discs = 11
 - “Mottled ghost” = 1
 - “ghost-smears” = 6
 - Incognitum = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 1,823 (58.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 980
 - Gray duds = 78
 - Gray-brown duds = 715
 - Septarial duds = 50
- **Rejects:** 980

Locality 29

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Braceville Coal Company No. 5 Mine southwest of Braidwood, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/20/24.**
- **Description:** Shaft cone of abandoned Braceville Coal Company No. 5 deep mine at the NW1/4, Section 13, T32N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.254177, -88.261516 (GCB); 41.2556842, -88.26056075 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2351. Mine hill visible on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 2,486 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 220 (8.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 17
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 10
 - *Calamites* = 6
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 59
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Cordaitales ('thorn') = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 111
 - **Animals:** Total = 384 (15.4% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 181
 - Junior blobs = 18
 - Indeterminate blobs = 21
 - *Mazonomya* (single, closed valves) = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 7
 - Crushed *Myalinella* clusters = 7
 - "Hill 20" bivalves = 18
 - Incognitum bivalves = 3
 - Unidentified bivalves = 34
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 15
 - Indeterminate arthropod = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 18
 - Brachiopod *Lingula* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 2
 - Palaeoniscoid scales = 1

- Coprolites = 36
- Trails/traces = 13
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 38 (1.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 12
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 26
- **Duds:** Total = 1,844 (74.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 1,526
 - Gray-brown duds = 208
 - Septarial duds = 36
 - Weathered duds = 74
- **Rejects:** 507

Locality 30

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Eureka Coal Company # 4 deep mine, west-southwest of Braidwood, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/20/24.
- **Description:** Small spoil cone of abandoned Eureka Coal Company # 4 shaft mine at SW1/4, section 12, T32N, R9E on the coal city 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.263374, -88.262284 (GCB); 41.26297305, -88.26080855 (ADM). Illinois pit directory number is # 2349. Hill apparently still visible on Google Earth as a small dark area.
- Total counts, based on 571 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 43 (7.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - Plant stems = 6
 - Bark = 3
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 6
 - *Lepidodendron* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Unidentified fern = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 152 (26.6% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 25
 - Senior blobs = 10
 - Junior blobs = 6
 - *Mazonomya* = 24
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - “Hill 20” bivalve = 1
 - Indeterminate bivalves = 8
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 15
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 3
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 14
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 7
 - Coprolites = 19
 - Trails/traces = 12
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 17 (2.9% of total)
 - “discs” = 8

- Indeterminate nucleus = 9
- **Duds:** Total = 359 (62.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 21
 - Gray-brown duds = 308
 - Red brown duds = 23
 - Septarial duds = 7
- **Rejects:** 325

Locality 31

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “R” deep mine, southwest of Braidwood, Illinois. Combined summary sample manifest of data sheets updated as of 04/20/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “R” shaft mine west of nearby Interstate 55 at NE1/4, section 13, T32N, R8E near the southeast corner of the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.253901, -88.251016 (GCB); 41.2559225, -88.2509265 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2350. Mine hill definitely visible on Google Earth.

- Total counts, based on 576 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 76 (13.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 20
 - *Calamostachys* cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 41
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 108 (18.7% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 35
 - Junior blobs = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 23
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam spread valves) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam closed valves) = 2
 - “Hill 20” bivalves = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 18
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Coprolites = 10
 - Trails/traces = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 24 (4.1% of total)
 - Pellets = 4
 - “discs” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 19
 - **Duds:** Total = 368 (63.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 336
 - Gray-brown duds = 20
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 9
 - **Rejects:** 51 (not part of sample count)

Locality 32

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Company “P” shaft mine, west of Braidwood, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/20/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “P” shaft mine, northwest of Reed Road exit from Interstate 55 at SE1/4, section 12, T32N, R9E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.263590, -88.250628 (GCB); 41.26321135, -88.2511743 (ADM). Mine dump visually cryptic – may have been since removed. Mine directory number = 2348.
- Total counts, based on 491 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 67 (13.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 13
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 15
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cordaicarpus?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 18
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 69 (14.0% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 16
 - Junior blobs = 11
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 12
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams) = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - “Hill 20” bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Fish *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trails/traces = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (1.4% of total)
 - “disc” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - Incognitum = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 348 (70.8% of total)

- Common duds = 302
- Gray-brown duds = 35
- Dark gray duds = 1
- Septarial duds = 10
- **Rejects: 57**

Locality 33

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “O” shaft mine west of Braidwood, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/20/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “O” deep mine at NE1/4, section 12, T32N, R8E at the east edge of the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.270181, -88.250633 (GCB); 41.27047605, -88.2513556 (ADM). Hill visible on Google Earth. Mine directory number = # 2335.

- Total counts, based on 245 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 21 (8.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 6
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 60 (24.4% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 5
 - *Mazonomya* (not subdivided) = 5
 - *Mazonomya* subdivided; total = 26:
 - Single clam, spread valves = 18
 - Two or more clams = 8
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Incognitum bivalves = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 8
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 7
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 19 (7.7% of total)
 - “spots” = 6
 - Mottles = 1
 - Incognitum nucleus = 2
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 10
 - **Duds:** Total = 145 (59.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 108
 - Light gray duds = 1
 - Brown duds = 23
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 10

Locality 34

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “G” deep mine in western part of Village of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/21/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “G” shaft mine at NE1/4, section 7, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.269114, -88.232234 (GCB); 41.270881, -88.23195355 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3926. Mine pile cryptic on Google Earth; may have been since reclaimed-levelled.

- Total counts, based on 745 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 116 (15.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 9
 - *Annularia* = 8
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 8
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 2
 - Plant stems = 29
 - Bark = 8
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Sphenopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 23
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 165 (22.1% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 50
 - Junior blobs = 22
 - Indeterminate blobs = 11
 - *Mazonomya* (not subdivided) = 21
 - “*Edmonia*” (single clam) = 12
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Bivalve *Solemya* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 14
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Polychaete Baby Tooth = 2

- Unidentified polychaetes = 6
- Holothurian = 1
- Coprolites = 1
- Trails/traces = 15
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (0.8% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 458 (61.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 303
 - Gray-brown duds = 128
 - Blue-gray duds = 3
 - Mottled duds = 7
 - Septarial duds = 17
- **Rejects:** 228

Locality 35

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Company “H” deep mine at northwest edge of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Combined summary sample manifest of all five data sheets updated as of 04/21/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “H” shaft mine at SE1/4, section 6, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.278462, -88.231525 (GCB); 41.27809785, -88.23218325 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3923. Mine hill cryptic on Google Earth; hill may have been reclaimed and levelled.
- Total counts, based on 2,337 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 558 (23.8% of total concretions counted)
 - *Pecopteris* = 54
 - *Neuropteris* = 60
 - *Annularia* = 56
 - *Calamites* = 18
 - *Calamites* branch end = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 21
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Plant stems = 186
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 5
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 3
 - *Sphenopteris* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 2
 - Seeds = 3
 - Cone = 1
 - Cone *Calamostachys* = 1
 - *Linopteris* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Thallus plant? = 1
 - Macerated plants = 121
 - Unidentified plants = 10
 - **Animals:** Total = 542 (23.1% of total concretions)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 34
 - Senior blobs = 208
 - Junior blobs = 95
 - Indeterminate blobs = 26
 - Partial blobs = 231 = typing error, excluded
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam) = 5
 - *Myalinella* = 8

- *Aviculopecten* = 7
- Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
- Unidentified bivalves = 2
- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 10
- Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 2
- Shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
- Shrimp (pygocephalomorph) = 1
- *Cyclus* = 15
- Flea shrimp = 2
- Gooseneck barnacle *Praeilepis* = 1
- Insect = 1
- Eurypterid? = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 6
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 14
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 27
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 5
- *Tullimonstrum* = 2
- Coprolites = 46
- Trails/traces = 20
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 42 (1.7% of total concretions)
 - “discs” = 13
 - Unidentified nucleus = 29
- **Duds:** Total = 1,195 (51.1% of total concretions)
 - Common duds = 647
 - Gray-brown duds = 411
 - Dark gray duds = 12
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 80
 - Septarial duds = 45
- **Rejects:** 301

Locality 36

- **Will-Essex; included—Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “L” shaft mine tip pile, northwest of Braidwood, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from eleven data sheets updated as of 04/01/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “L” shaft mine at NE1/4, section 6, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle in Will County, Illinois, at digital coordinates 41.284976, -88.230482 (GCB); 41.2852845, -88.2324227 (ADM). Part of mine hill still standing. Mine directory number = 3924.
- Total counts, based on 2,214 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 951 (42.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 89
 - *Neuropteris* = 340
 - *Annularia* = 122
 - *Calamites* = 35
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 26
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Plant stem = 286
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 3
 - *Sphenopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 5
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 4
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1 Unidentified bark = 11
 - Lycopod (scale bark and stems) = 2
 - Branch tufts = 7
 - Seeds = 1
 - Spore case = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 20
 - **Animals:** Total = 351 (15.8% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 69
 - Junior blobs = 38
 - Indeterminate blobs = 23
 - Other *Essexella* types = 3
 - *Myalinella* = 41
 - *Aviculopecten* = 14
 - *Mazonomya* = 6
 - Unidentified bivalve = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 2
 - Indeterminate shrimps = 3
 - *Cyclus* = 2

- Pygocephalomorph (the “lobster”) = 1
- Millepede (*Xyliulus*) = 1
- Millepede (*Euphoberia*) = 1
- Insect = 1
- Incognitum arthropod = 1
- Palaeoniscoid (bony fish) = 1
- Shark (*Bandringa*) = 1
- Fish scale (*Megalichthys*) = 2
- *Didontogaster* = 7
- *Astreptoscolex* = 2
- *Esconites* = 10
- *Spirorbis* = 2
- Indeterminate polychaete = 18
- Trails/traces = 12
- Coprolites = 83
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 66 (2.9% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 53
 - “discs” = 11
 - Incognitum organism = 2
- **Duds:** Total = 846 (38.2% of total)
 - Gray duds = 733
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 82
 - Septarial duds = 31
- **Rejects:** 284

Locality 37

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “J” mine, northwest of Braidwood, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/22/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “J” southwest of Coal City exit of Interstate 55 at NW1/4, Section 6, T32N, R9E at digital coordinates 41.287112, -88.236117 (GCB); 41.2849809, -88.24211185 (ADM). Mine hill still visible on Google Earth. Mine directory number = 3925.

- Total counts, based on 1,073 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 275 (25.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 36
 - *Neuropteris* = 29
 - *Annularia* = 15
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 6
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 80
 - Bark = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Bergeria* = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 81
 - Unidentified plants = 12
 - **Animals:** Total = 292 (27.2% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 140
 - Junior blobs = 87
 - Indeterminate blobs = 20
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 4
 - *Myalinella* cluster = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 4
 - Insect = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
 - Unidentified polychaete = 5
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinosclex* = 2

- Coprolites = 6
- Trails/traces= 9
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 26 (2.4% of total)
 - Discs = 7
 - Smears = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 18
- **Duds:** Total = 480 (44.7% of total)
 - Common duds = 285
 - Gray-brown duds = 147
 - Dark gray duds = 15
 - Pyrite corded duds = 17
 - Septarial duds = 16

Locality 38

- **Will-Essex; included—Chicago, Wilmington & Vermilion “N” shaft mine.**
Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/08/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington & Vermilion “N” shaft mine adjacent to the Coal City Road exit on Interstate 55 at SE1/4, section 31, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.291865, -88.233041 (GCB); 41.29257265, -88.23286605 (ADM). Mine hill is still visible. Mine directory number = 3937.
- Total counts, based on 854 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 175 (20.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 26
 - *Neuropteris* = 13
 - *Annularia* = 14
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 37
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - Plant stem = 55
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Spores = 1
 - Macerated plants = 17
 - Unidentified plant = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 92 (10.7% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 5
 - Junior blobs = 4
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - *Myalinella* = 26
 - *Myalinella* cluster = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 11 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified clams = 12
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - *Cyzicus* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Probable polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 16
 - Trails/traces = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 36 (4.2% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 25

- Discs = 11
- Incognitum = 3
- **Duds:** Total = 551 (64.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 142
 - Gray-brown duds = 105
 - Blue-gray duds = 228
 - Light gray duds = 28
 - Septarial duds = 48

Locality 39

- **Will-Essex; included—Murphy, Linskey & Kasher # 4 deep mine. Combined summary sample manifest of all four data sheets updated as of 04/08/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Murphy, Linskey & Kasher # 4 deep mine along fence line on north side of East Coal City Road at SE1/4, SW1/4, Section 32, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.289355, -88.220918 (GCB); 41.29100093, -88.2208561 (ADM). Mine hill is still visible on Google Earth. Mine directory number = 224.
- Total counts, based on 973 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 390 (40.0% of total concretions collected)
 - *Pecopteris* = 110
 - *Neuropteris* = 36
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 27
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 74
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 19
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 3
 - Plant stem = 28
 - Stem/bark = 43
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - Unidentified fern = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - Seed = 2
 - Macerated plants = 34
 - **Animals:** Total = 88 (9% of total concretions collected)
 - Senior blobs = 4
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - *Myalinella* = 17
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Nonmarine clams = 15
 - Unidentified bivalve = 5
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Unidentified shrimp? = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Coprolites = 33

- Trail/trace = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 38 (3.9% of total concretions collected)
 - Discs = 4
 - Ghosts (degraded blobs) = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 29
 - Pelletal nodule = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 457 (46.9% of total concretions collected)
 - Common duds = 78
 - Gray-brown duds = 270
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 12
 - Dark gray duds = 44
 - Blue-gray duds = 42
 - Septarial duds = 11

Locality 40

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Skinner Brother Slope? Mine, north-northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/22/24.
- **Description:** Very small spoil pile of the abandoned Skinner Brothers Slope? Mine north of Coal City Road at SW1/4, SW1/4, section 33, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.290164, -88.205460 (GCB); 41.2912627, -88.20649783 (ADM). Present mine position cryptic on Google Earth. Mine directory number = 5953.
- Total counts, based on 135 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 74 (54.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 12
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 6
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 15
 - Bark = 5
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - *Psaronius* stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 11
 - **Animals:** Total = 4 (2.9% of total)
 - Crushed bivalves in coprolite = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.4% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 55 (40.7% of total)
 - Common duds = 27
 - Gray-brown duds = 25
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 41

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Skinner Brothers # 1 deep mine, north-northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/23/24.
- **Description:** Spoil deposit of abandoned Skinner Brothers # 1 deep mine, both bordering and overlapping the western margin of the Pit 4 strip mine at SW1/4, SW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle, with digital coordinates approximated at 41.277724, -88.207463 (GCB); 41.27871985, -88.20358535 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3916. At the time of sampling, a new road had been punched through both the Pit 4 and Skinner mine deposits, resulting in an unknown amount of mixing of the spoil content. Site is presently overridden by further development and is generally inaccessible.
- Total counts, based on 236 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 82 (34.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 13
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 24
 - Bark = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Macerated plants = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 19 (8% of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 14
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (2.1% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 130 (55% of total)
 - Common duds = 43
 - Gray-brown duds = 76
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 9

Locality 42

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “D” deep mine north of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from nine data sheets updated as of 04/16/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, and Vermilion “D” shaft mine at SW1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.283161, -88.221920 (GCB); 41.2828347, -88.22156035 (ADM). Mine hill still visible on Google Earth. Mine directory number = 3919.

- Total counts, based on 2,097 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 716 (34.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 100
 - *Neuropteris* = 186
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 56
 - *Calamites* = 21
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 60
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stem = 151
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 6
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Cordaites?* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 3
 - Cone = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus?* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Seed *Trigonocarpus* = 1
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - Macerated plant = 92
 - Unidentified plants = 18
 - **Animals:** Total = 464 (22.1% of total)
 - *Essexella* (undivided) = 26
 - Senior blobs = 187
 - Junior blobs = 17
 - Indeterminate blobs = 13
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 27
 - *Aviculopecten* = 4

- *Dunbarella* = 1
- Nonmarine bivalves = 4 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
- “Hill 20” bivalve = 1
- “crushed-eaten” clam = 1
- Unidentified bivalves = 11
- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 11
- Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 3
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 2
- Small shrimp *Essoidea* = 1
- *Cyclus* = 9
- Insect = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 3
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 11
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 18
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 2
- *Tullimonstrum* = 1
- Indeterminate fish = 1
- Coprolites = 98
- Trails/traces = 9
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 50 (2.3% of total)
 - “discs” = 3
 - Ghosts = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 42
- **Duds:** Total = 867 (41.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 496
 - Gray-brown duds = 156
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 32
 - Blue-gray duds = 51
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Weathered duds = 52
 - Septarial duds = 65
- **Rejects:** 103

Locality 43

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “B” deep mine at north margin of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/23/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “B” shaft mine at NW1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.278725, -88.221875 (GCB); 41.2783203, -88.222598 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3919. Mine pile not spotted using Google Earth, but it may be camouflaged by vegetation.

- Total counts, based on 1,517 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 124 (8.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 14
 - *Neuropteris* = 28
 - *Annularia* = 19
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 14
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Bark/stems = 8
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris*/stem = 1
 - *Linopteris?* = 1
 - *Cardaicarpus?* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Scale twig = 1
 - Macerated plants = 15
 - Indeterminate plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 195 (12.8% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 32
 - Senior blobs = 62
 - Junior blobs = 22
 - Indeterminate blobs = 17
 - *Myalinella* = 5
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 5
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 6
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 10

- Lungfish *Conchopoma* = 1
- Coprolites = 12
- Trails/traces = 9
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 24 (1.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 7
 - “smears” = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 15
- **Duds:** Total = 1,174 (77.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 603
 - Gray-brown duds = 469
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 30
 - Dark gray duds = 6
 - Blue-gray duds = 40
 - Septarial duds = 26
- **Rejects:** 351

Locality 44

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned unnamed deep mine in Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/23/24.
- **Description:** Spoil pile of abandoned, unnamed shaft mine near the east edge of Braidwood, Illinois at NW1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.270146, -88.211751 (GCB); 41.26950885, -88.21044903 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5962. Mine hill does not show up on Google Earth; it may have been removed.
- Total counts, based on 562 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 88 (15.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 19
 - *Neuropteris* = 15
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 6
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 5
 - Plant stems = 20
 - Bark = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 14
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 57 (10.1% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 17
 - Senior blobs = 7
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 1
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails/traces = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (1.2% of total)
 - “disc” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 6
 - **Duds:** Total = 410 (72.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 303
 - Gray-brown duds = 96
 - Dark gray duds = 1
 - Pyrite-cored dud = 8

- Septarial duds = 2

Locality 45

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining & Manufacturing Company Diamond # 3 deep mine southeast of Diamond, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/22/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of Wilmington Coal Mining & Manufacturing Company Diamond # 3 shaft mine at SE1/4, Section 1, T32N, R9E near the east edge of the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle, west of Interstate 55 at digital coordinates 41.275919, -88.242742 (GCB); 41.277685, -88.25151715 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2341. Mine hill visible on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,231 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 147 (11.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 11
 - *Neuropteris* = 11
 - *Annularia* = 10
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Calamites* tuber = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 34
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Plant stems = 46
 - Bark = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Cones = 2
 - Cone *Calamostachys?* = 1
 - Scale branch = 1
 - Root mass = 1
 - Megaspores = 1
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - Unidentified plant = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 181 (14.7% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 47
 - Junior blobs = 33
 - Indeterminate blobs = 27
 - “ragged” or “lettuce” blobs = 10
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 15
 - Millepede *Acantherpestes* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4

- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 7
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 4
- Brachiopod *Lingula* = 2
- Coprolites = 4
- Trails/traces = 15
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 33 (2.6% of total)
 - “discs” = 11
 - Pellets = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 20
 - Incognitum = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 870 (70.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 556
 - Gray-brown duds = 264
 - Dark gray duds = 8
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 10
 - Septarial duds = 32
- **Rejects:** 308

Locality 46

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining & Manufacturing Co., Diamond # 2 deep mine, near Diamond, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/24/24.**
- **Description:** Low spoil cone of abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining & Manufacturing Co., Diamond # 2 shaft mine near hamlet of Diamond, Illinois at SW1/4, SW1/4, section 31, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.292762, - 88.245428 (GCB); 41.2923262, -88.2424205 (ADM). Mine hill is east of north-south Will Road. Mine directory number = 2342. Mine hill still visible, but overgrown.
- Total counts, based on 1,867 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 765 (40.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 130
 - *Neuropteris* = 119
 - *Annularia* = 96
 - *Calamites* = 29
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 37
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 5
 - Plant stems = 227
 - Bark = 3
 - *Lepidodendrom* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 8
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 2
 - Spores = 2
 - Seeds = 4
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 76
 - Unidentified plants = 19
 - **Animals:** Total = 537 (28.7% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 49
 - Senior blobs = 135
 - Junior blobs = 61
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 17
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam) = 4
 - *Myalinella* = 25
 - Crushed *Myalinella* (cluster) = 3
 - *Myalinella* with *Spirorbis* = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 8
 - *Dunbarella* = 2

- Bivalve *Euchondria* = 1
- Nonmarine bivalves = 5 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
- Nonmarine bivalve with *Spirorbis* = 1
- Incognitum clam = 1
- Unidentified bivalves = 16
- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 7
- Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
- Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 2
- Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 2
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 2
- Shrimp pygocephalomorph = 1
- Unidentified shrimp = 1
- Unidentified marine shrimp = 1
- *Cyclus* = 18
- Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
- Insect = 1
- Indeterminate arthropod = 2
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 6
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 24
- Unidentified polychaetes = 33
- Polychaete with blob = 1
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 2
- *Spirorbis* with plant stem = 1
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 2
- Phosphatic shelled organism = 1
- Arrow worm = *Paucijaculum* = 2
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Agnathan chordate *Gilpichthys* = 1
- Coprolites = 45
- Coprolites with acanthodian scales = 2
- Trails/traces = 47
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 67 (3.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 18
 - Ghosts = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 47
- **Duds:** Total = 498 (26.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 53
 - Gray-brown duds = 264
 - Gray duds = 83
 - Dark gray duds = 20
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 30
 - Septarial duds = 48
- **Rejects:** 945

Locality 47

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned unnamed mine at Diamond, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/24/24.**
- **Description:** Low, largely flattened mine area (at time of sampling) south of West Coal City Road in the hamlet of Diamond, Illinois at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 1, T32N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5 quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.287889, -88.248005 (GCB); 41.284791, -88.25174705 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5941. I understand that this was the site of a major mine disaster as marked by a nearby monument. No trace of the collecting area evident on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,363 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 211 (15.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 19
 - *Neuropteris* = 29
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 26
 - *Calamites* = 13
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 81
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Scale twig with leaves = 1
 - Macerated plants = 26
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 203 (14.8% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 24
 - Junior blobs = 38
 - Indeterminate blobs = 24
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) (single clam) = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 4
 - Unidentified bivalves = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 14
 - Insect = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 4

- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 9
- Polychaete *Hystricula?* = 1
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 2
- Unidentified polychaetes = 11
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 3
- Brachiopod *Lingula?* = 1
- Coprolites = 29
- Trails/traces = 26
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 52 (3.8% of total)
 - “discs” = 18
 - Unidentified nucleus = 34
- **Duds:** Total = 897 (65.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 457
 - Gray-brown duds = 373
 - Dark gray duds = 11
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 8
 - Septarial duds = 46
 - Pelletal duds = 2
- **Rejects:** 424

Locality 48

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining & Manufacturing Co., Diamond # 4 deep mine southwest of Diamond, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from six data sheets updated as of 04/25/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining & Mfg. Co., Diamond # 4 shaft mine at NW1/4, section 1, T32N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.285671, -88.261939 (GCB); 41.2846502, -88.2613019 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3556. Mine hill apparently visible on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,778 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 325 (18.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 53
 - *Neuropteris* = 23
 - *Annularia* = 19
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 24
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Plant stems = 69
 - Bark = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Asterophyllites?* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 110
 - Unidentified plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 469 (26.3% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 30
 - Senior blobs = 150
 - Junior blobs = 66
 - Indeterminate blobs = 68
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*):
 - Open valves (1 clam/concretion) = 40
 - Open valves (2 or more clams/concretion) = 5
 - Single valve = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - Bivalve *Lima?* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Pygocephalomorph shrimp = 2
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 4
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 13
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 15
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1

- Unidentified polychaetes = 20
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 2
 - Amphibian *Saurapleura?* = 1
 - Coprolites = 20
 - Trails/traces = 19
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 48 (2.6% of total)
 - “discs” = 18
 - Trails-ghosts = 3
 - Ghosts = 1
 - Pellets = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 25
- **Duds:** Total = 936 (52.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 680
 - Gray-brown duds = 130
 - Dark gray duds = 62
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 7
 - Septarial dud = 57
- **Rejects:** 150

Locality 49

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining & Manufacturing Co., Diamond # 5 deep mine south of Diamond, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/26/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining & Manufacturing Co., Diamond # 5 shaft mine south of Diamond, Grundy County, Illinois at NW1/4, section 12, T32N, R8E on the coal City 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.272754, -88.263333 (GCB); 41.2703944, -88.2609454 (ADM). Mine directory number = 4973. On Google Earth, mine hill appears to have been reclaimed-removed.
- Total counts, based on 1,583 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 68 (4.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 18
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidohylloides* = 5
 - Plant stems = 20
 - Scaly twig = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria?* = 1
 - *Trigonocarpus* (in sandstone) = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - Unidentified plant = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 608 (38.4% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 14
 - Senior blobs = 9
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*); Total = 471
 - Spread valves (one clam) = 364
 - Spread valves (two or more clams) = 50
 - Single or closed valves = 57
 - *Aviculopecten* = 4
 - Bivalve *Acharax* (*Solemya*) *radiata* = 1
 - Incognitum bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 3
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1

- Unidentified polychaete = 21
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
- Holothurian = 2
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Coprolites = 9
- Trails/traces = 46
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 34 (2.1% of total)
 - “discs” = 9
 - “spots” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 24
- **Duds:** Total = 873 (55.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 281
 - Gray-brown duds = 498
 - Light gray duds = 8
 - Dark gray duds = 1
 - Blue-gray duds = 11
 - Spots and mottles = 6
 - Septarial duds = 68
- **Rejects:** 67

Locality 50

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, and Vermilion “E” shaft mine cone in Braidwood Town Park, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from six data sheets updated as of 04/16/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion “E” shaft mine in Braidwood Town Park at SE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 8, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.268060, -88.219394 (GCB); 41.26843173, -88.21868295 (ADM). Mine hill has apparently been levelled, paved over for recreational park facilities. Mine directory number = 3929.
- Total counts, based on 1,363 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 224 (16.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 21
 - *Neuropteris* = 20
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 34
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 16
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 11
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 2
 - Plant stems = 73
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 20
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 6
 - Seed = 1
 - *Aphlebia?* = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 170 (12.4% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 7
 - Senior blobs = 20
 - Junior blobs = 25
 - Indeterminate blobs = 32
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 9
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* with polychaete = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - “odd bivalve” = 2
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidectes* = 1

- “paddle shrimp” = 1
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 2
- *Cyclus* = 9
- Arachnid = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
- Unidentified polychaete = 8
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
- Agnathan vertebrate *Gilpichthys* = 1
- Coprolites = 23
- Trails/traces = 15
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 63 (4.6% of total)
 - “discs” = 25
 - Unidentified nucleus = 38
- **Duds:** Total = 906 (66.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 286
 - Gray-brown duds = 436
 - Dark gray duds = 10
 - Blue-gray duds = 15
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 54
 - Septarial duds = 103
 - Pelletal duds = 1
- **Rejects:** 525

Locality 51

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Co. “C” deep mine in village park in Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/26/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil hill of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Co. “C” shaft mine at NE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 8, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.269817, - 88.219755 (GCB); 41.27025368, -88.21876043 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3931. Mine hill no longer visible on Google Earth. Its earlier position appears to coincide with the Skate Park facility in Braidwood Town Park.
- Total counts, based on 1,003 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 106 (10.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 8
 - *Neuropteris* = 15
 - *Annularia* = 11
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 9
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Plant stems = 30
 - Bark = 4
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 15
 - Unidentified plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 132 (13.1% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 37
 - Junior blobs = 13
 - Indeterminate blobs = 21
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Mazonomya (Edmondia)* = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - “Paddle shrimp” = 2
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 8
 - *Cyzicus* = 1
 - Unidentified arthropod = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 10
 - Coprolites = 12

- Trails/traces= 14
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 32 (3.1% of total)
 - “discs” = 16
 - Unidentified nucleus = 16
- **Duds:** Total = 733 (73.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 163
 - Gray duds = 173
 - Blue-gray duds = 36
 - Gray-brown duds = 207
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 24
 - Septarial duds = 15
 - Weathered duds = 115
- **Rejects:** 780

Locality 52

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Co. “F” deep mine, northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/26/24.
- **Description:** Very small spoil hill of abandoned Chicago, Wilmington, & Vermilion Coal Co. “F” shaft mine at NE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.287527, -88.210501 (GCB); 41.2874673, -88.21091775 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3922. Hill low and subdued at time of sampling. Still evident on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,203 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 829 (68.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 333
 - *Neuropteris* = 40
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 57
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 115
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 169
 - Bark = 7
 - *Alethopteris* = 9
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 6
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Crossotheca* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Cone (*Calamostachys*) = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 3
 - Lycopod? Bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 30
 - Unidentified plants = 31
 - **Animals:** Total = 36 (2.9% of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 4
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 10 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Fragmental bivalves = 1
 - “chewed” bivalves = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 8
 - Incognitum bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified arthropod = 1

- “roach egg sac” = 1
- *Palaeoxyris* = 2
- Coprolites = 6
- Shrimp in coprolite = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 21 (1.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 19
- **Duds:** Total = 319 (26.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 79
 - Gray-brown duds = 117
 - Blue-gray dud = 26
 - Septarial duds = 93

Locality 53

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Skinner Brothers underground Slope Mine # 2, northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/15/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Skinner Brothers underground Slope Mine # 2 at NW1/4, NW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.288733, -88.207980 (GCB); 41.28756848, -88.20613908 (ADM). Spoil pile now removed for new housing development. Mine directory number = 3917.
- Total counts, based on 653 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 399 (61.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 122
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 33
 - Plant stems = 96
 - Fine stems = 8
 - Plant stem/bark = 45
 - Bark-trunk = 4
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 7
 - Seed? = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 61
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 32 (4.9% of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 6 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 10
 - Syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Arachnid? = 1
 - Probable polychaete = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 9
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (1.9% of total)
 - “discs” = 6
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 209 (32.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 101

- Gray-brown duds = 51
- Dark gray duds = 6
- Septarial duds = 49
- Large septarial duds = 2
- **Rejects: 7**

Locality 54

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Murphy, Keenan & Co., Murphy and Keenan # 3 deep mine northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/27/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned Murphy, Keenan & Co., Murphy and Keenan # 3 deep mine at NW1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.284443, -88.212539 (GCB); 41.28477463, -88.21206155 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3921. Mine hill still visible on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,529 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 666 (43.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 217
 - *Neuropteris* = 46
 - *Annularia* = 33
 - *Calamites* = 12
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 73
 - *Lepidophylloides* clusters = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 12
 - Plant stems = 198
 - Bark = 7
 - *Lepidodendron* = 6
 - *Alethopteris* = 6
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 5
 - *Stigmaria* = 7
 - Seeds = 4
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Cone (unidentified) = 1
 - Macerated plant = 27
 - Plant fragments = 3
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 172 (11.2% of total)
 - *Essexella* = 1
 - Senior blobs = 6
 - Indeterminate blobs = 1
 - “eyed” blob = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 27
 - *Myalinella* hash cluster = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 28 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Dunbarella* = 1
 - “small” bivalves = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 36

- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
- *Cyclus* = 3
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
- Unidentified polychaete = 1
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Coprolites = 53
- Trails/traces = 2
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 103 (6.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 2
 - Ghosts-smears = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 32
 - Weathered obliterated fossils = 67
- **Duds:** Total = 588 (38.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 223
 - Gray-brown duds = 6
 - Blue-gray duds = 28
 - Dark gray duds = 136
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 50
 - Septarial duds = 114
 - Weathered duds = 31
- **Rejects:** 676

Locality 55

- **Will-Essex; included—Shaft cone of abandoned unnamed deep mine north of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/07/24.**
- **Description:** Small, low debris cone originally referred to as the abandoned Star Coal Company deep mine, but now unnamed. Mine is west of Novy Road at SW1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.279602, -88.211370 (GCB); 41.27942795, -88.21196758 (ADM). Mine hill still clearly visible. Mine directory number = 5958.
- Total counts, based on 2,353 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 642 (27.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 211
 - *Neuropteris* = 50
 - *Annularia* = 20
 - *Calamites* = 13
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 58
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 6
 - Plant stems = 157
 - Bark = 2
 - Macerated plants = 93
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 5
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Seed (*Trigonocarpus?*) = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 16
 - **Animals:** Total = 323 (13.7% of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Probable blob = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 144
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 1
 - *Myalinella* with *Spirorbis* = 1
 - Nonmarine clams = 16
 - “ribbed” clam = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 20
 - Large unidentified clams = 78
 - “odd bivalves” = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (molted) = 1
 - Pygocephalomorph shrimp = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 1

- Indeterminate arthropod = 1
- *Didontogaster* (tummy tooth) = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 5
- Probable polychaete = 3
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Coprolites = 41
- Trail/trace = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 48 (2% of total)
 - “Discs” = 8
 - Ghost-smear = 1
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 39
- **Duds:** Total = 1,340 (56.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 642
 - Gray duds = 310
 - Dark gray duds = 8
 - Blue-gray duds = 95
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 123
 - Septarial duds = 139
 - Weathered duds = 23
- **Rejects:** 708

Locality 56

- **Braidwood; included**—Shaft cone of abandoned William Maltby Mine. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/05/24.
- **Description:** Shaft cone spoil pile of abandoned William Maltby deep mine at CTR, NW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle, north-northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois, with digital coordinates 41.287547, -88.205812 (GCB); 41.28584875, -88.20371065 (ADM). Mine dump now removed; its former position corresponds to intersection of Tully Monster and Dinosaur Roads in new housing subdivision. Mine directory number = 6946.
- Total counts, based on 2,570 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1,736 (67.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 666
 - *Pecopteris* (fertile) = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 58
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 2
 - *Annularia* = 69
 - *Calamites* = 24
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 197
 - Plant stem = 425
 - Bark = 53
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 22
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 4
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 15
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 6
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Crossotheca* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 15
 - *Stigmarioides* = 1
 - Indeterminate cone = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Seed? = 1
 - Spore case = 1
 - *Cordaicarpus* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 111
 - Unidentified plants = 48
 - **Animals:** Total = 73 (2.8% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 18 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Euproops* = 4

- Unidentified syncarid = 1
- *Cyzicus* = 1
- Ostracods = 2
- *Spirorbis* = 1
- Coprolites = 43
- Trails/traces = 3
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 41 (1.5% of total)
 - Discs = 17
 - Unidentified nucleus = 24
- **Duds:** Total = 720 (28.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 319
 - Gray duds = 218
 - Blue-gray duds = 27
 - Septarial duds = 156
- **Rejects:** 70

Locality 57

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned unnamed shaft mine “F” north of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/28/24.
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned unnamed shaft mine “F” north-northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois at NW1/4, NE1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.288268, -88.215289 (GCB); 41.28739758 -88.21570248 (ADM). This mine may be part of the nearby C., W. & V. Coal Co. shaft mine (see locality # 52). Mine directory number for locality 57 is 3918. Mine hill is still visible on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,258 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 677 (53.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 210
 - Multiple *Pecopteris* (“forest litter”) = 15
 - *Neuropteris* = 42
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Annularia* = 29
 - *Calamites* = 23
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 57
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 20
 - Plant stems (small) = 146
 - Large plant stems and bark = 47
 - Bark = 12
 - *Alethopteris* = 10
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - Unidentified seed? = 1
 - Macerated plants = 44
 - Unidentified plants = 16
 - **Animals:** Total = 69 (5.4% of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 24 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 10
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 2
 - Coprolites = 32
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (0.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 6
 - **Duds:** Total = 502 (39.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 188
 - Gray duds = 177

- Weathered duds = 96
- Septarial duds = 41
- Sectioned concretions (sectioned = add to rejects) = 6
- **Rejects: 183**

Locality 58

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned unnamed shaft mine “G”. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/28/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned unnamed shaft mine “G” in the SE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.276545, -88.209858 (GCB); 41.27677395, -88.2107298 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5959. Mine hill still visible via Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,362 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 336 (24.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 95
 - *Neuropteris* = 74
 - *Annularia* = 17
 - *Calamites* = 6
 - *Lepidophyllites* = 18
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Plant stems = 77
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 37
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 171 (12.5% of total)
 - *Essexella* = 1
 - Senior blobs = 4
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 66
 - Crushed *Myalinella* cluster = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 15 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Incognitum bivalve = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 23
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Eupoops* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Coprolites = 35
 - Trails/traces = 8

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 34 (2.4% of total)
 - “discs” = 9
 - Ghosts-smears = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 21
 - Incognitum = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 821 (60.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 290
 - Gray duds = 169
 - Dark gray duds = 21
 - Blue-gray duds = 247
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 46
 - Septarial duds = 48
- **Rejects:** 1312 (not counted in sample total)

Locality 59

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned unnamed shaft mine in the northeast corner of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/29/24.
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned unnamed shaft mine at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.274421, -88.210158 (GCB); 41.27315915, -88.21060325 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5960. Hill now removed for new housing development according to Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,448 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 464 (32.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 69
 - *Neuropteris* = 115
 - *Annularia* = 29
 - *Calamites* = 14
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 29
 - Plant stem = 117
 - Bark = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Crossotheca* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 61
 - Unidentified plants = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 179 (12.3% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 34
 - Senior blobs = 1
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 83
 - *Myalinella* crushed clusters = 6
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 5
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Unidentified hoplocarid shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 5
 - Incognitum crustacean = 1

- Arachnid = 1
- Indeterminate arthropod = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 10
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* with bark = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 5
- Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
- Coprolites = 11
- Trail/trace = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 39 (2.6% of total)
 - “discs” = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 34
- **Duds:** Total = 766 (52.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 324
 - Gray-brown duds = 218
 - Dark gray duds = 77
 - Blue-gray duds = 131
 - Septarial duds = 16
- **Rejects:** 229

Locality 60

- **Will-Essex; included**—Unnamed shaft mine “i” in the northeast part of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/02/24.
- **Description:** Total recovered sample from spoil cone of abandoned shaft mine “i” at NW1/4, NE1/4, Section 8, T32N, R9E in northeast part of Braidwood, Illinois on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle, digital coordinates 41.273817, -88.214230 (GCB); 41.27306055, -88.2153309 (ADM). At the time of sampling, this mine hill was being knocked down for subdivision development. Hill now removed. Mine directory number = 5967.
- Total counts, based on 2,476 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 599 (24.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 107
 - *Neuropteris* = 107
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Annularia* = 47
 - *Calamites* = 20
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 16
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stem = 200
 - Bark = 8
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Sphenopteris?* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Seed case = 1
 - Macerated plant = 68
 - Unidentified plant = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 387 (15.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 108
 - Junior blobs = 40
 - Indeterminate blobs = 21
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - “micro-blobs” = 2
 - *Octomedusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 68
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 3
 - *Myalinella* cluster = 4

- *Aviculopecten* = 4
- Incognitum bivalve = 7
- Unidentified bivalves = 19
- Nonmarine clams = 5
- *Strobeus* = 2
- *Belotelson* (molted) = 4
- *Kallidectes* (shrimp) = 1
- *Acanthotelson* = 2
- Unidentified syncarid = 1
- Pygocephalomorph (the “lobster”) = 1
- *Cyclus* = 8
- Insect = 1
- *Didontogaster* (Tummy tooth) = 4
- *Esconites* = 2
- *Spirorbis* = 1
- *Spirorbis/Myalinella* = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 16
- Probable polychaete = 2
- Holothurian? = 1
- *Lingula* = 1
- *Esconichthys* (“blade”) = 1
- Fish (*Megalichthys*) = 1
- Fish scale (*Ctenodus*) = 1
- Bone? Fragment = 1
- Coprolites = 33
- Trails/traces = 15
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 66 (2.6% of total)
 - Discs = 14
 - Pyritic discs = 3
 - Smears = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 46
- **Duds:** Total = 1424 (57.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 845
 - Gray-brown duds = 166
 - Dark gray duds = 17
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 65
 - Blue-gray duds = 14
 - Septarial duds = 15
 - Weathered duds = 316
- **Rejects:** 871

Locality 61

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned, unnamed shaft mine “J” north of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/29/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned unnamed shaft mine “J” north of north edge of Braidwood at SW1/4, SE1/4, section 5, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.277692, -88.214406 (GCB); 41.27667535 -88.21545745 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5965. Mine hill hard to make out on Google Earth; probably overgrown.
- Total counts, based on 1,326 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 354 (26.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 40
 - *Neuropteris* = 99
 - *Annularia* = 10
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - Plant stems = 116
 - Bark/stem = 9
 - Bark = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Taeniophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 56
 - Unidentified plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 119 (8.9% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 7
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia* – single clam, spread valves) = 2
 - Crushed *Mazonomya* = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 38
 - *Myalinella* cluster = 1
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 5
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 8 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 9
 - Shrimp *Essoidea?* = 1
 - Indeterminate shrimp = 1
 - Indeterminate crustacean = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Ostracods = 1

- Insect = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 4
- Coprolites = 26
- Trails/traces = 3
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 41 (3.0% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 41
- **Duds:** Total = 812 (61.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 716
 - Gray-brown duds = 53
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 27
 - Septarial duds = 14
- **Rejects:** 215

Locality 62

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company “E” Mine north of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from eight data sheets updated as of 04/30/24.**
- **Description:** Large spoil cone of abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company “E” Mine at ctr, SW1/4, section 26, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.306996, -88.283713 (GCB); 41.30593215, -88.2810867 (ADM). Mine directory number = 6. Hill visible on Google Earth, but heavily overgrown.
- Total counts, based on 2,206 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 547 (24.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 118
 - *Neuropteris* = 37
 - *Annularia* = 31
 - *Calamites* = 7
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 117
 - *Lepidophylloides* (cluster) = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 105
 - Stems/bark = 24
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 4
 - *Spheonophyllum* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Cordaites* stem = 1
 - *Stgmaria* = 1
 - *Stigmarioides* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 71
 - Incognitum plants = 3
 - Unidentified plants = 14
 - **Animals:** Total = 190 (8.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 20
 - Junior blobs = 12
 - Indeterminate blobs = 23
 - *Myalinella* = 18
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 7 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 2
 - Fragmental bivalves = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 7
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1

- Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
- Hoplocarid? shrimp = 1
- Unidentified marine shrimp = 1
- Pygocephalomorph shrimp = 1
- Shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 3
- Unidentified shrimp = 1
- *Cyclus* = 4
- “non-*Cyclus*” = 1
- Insect (cockroach) = 1
- Arachnid = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 11
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 16
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
- Palaeoniscoid fish (eaten-gastric spattle) = 1
- Fish scale *Megalichthys* = 1
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Coprolites = 37
- Trails/traces = 10
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 91 (4.1% of total)
 - “discs” = 12
 - Trails-ghosts = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 74
- **Duds:** Total = 1,378 (62.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 344
 - Gray duds = 25
 - Gray-brown duds = 214
 - Light blue-gray duds = 7
 - Blue-gray duds = 644
 - Dark gray duds = 24
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 14
 - Septarial duds = 47
 - Weathered duds = 16
 - Additional split duds (total = 43):
 - Hard, conchoidal, blue-gray duds = 22
 - Gray-brown duds = 21
- **Rejects:** 318

Locality 63

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company Maria Mine north of hamlet of Eileen, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from eight data sheets updated as of 05/01/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil hill of abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company Maria Mine at NE1/4, section 35, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.299614, -88.270035 (GCB); 41.29887935, -88.27125205 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2381. Mine hill site possibly reclaimed or modified as viewed on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 3,302 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 854 (25.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 129
 - *Neuropteris* = 188
 - *Annularia* = 43
 - *Calamites* = 17
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 142
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 6
 - Plant stems = 160
 - Bark = 6
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 12
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Cones = 2
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - “thorn” plant = 1
 - Seed *Trigonocarpus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 98
 - Unidentified plants = 41
 - **Animals:** Total = 265 (8.0% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 11
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 11
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*, not characterized) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia* with valves closed) = 3
 - *Myalinella* = 22
 - *Myalinella* cluster = 2
 - “Hill 20” bivalve = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 6 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 21
 - Fragmental bivalve = 1

- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 14
- Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
- *Cyclus* = 3
- Horseshoe crab *Paleolimulus* = 1
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 3
- Unidentified arthropod = 3
- Insect = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 4
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 11
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 3
- *Spirorbis* with *Neuropteris* stem = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 23
- *Ilyodes* = 2
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Fish scale = 1
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Amphibian *Amphibamus grandiceps* = 1
- Coprolites = 90
- Shells in coprolite = 2
- Trails/traces = 16
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 128 (3.8% of total)
 - “discs” = 21
 - “spots” = 11
 - “circle” = 1
 - Ghosts-smears = 7
 - Incognitum = 1
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 87
- **Duds:** Total = 2,055 (62.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 843
 - Gray duds = 28
 - Dark gray duds = 76
 - Gray-brown duds = 151
 - Hard, blue-gray duds = 322
 - Light, interior duds = 1
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 20
 - Septarial duds = 152
 - Weathered duds = 462
- **Rejects:** 701

Locality 64

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington No. 3 Mine north of Diamond, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 05/02/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington No. 3 Mine at NE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 36, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.299304, -88.257255 (GCB); 41.29904905, -88.2616707 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2382. Mine appears to be reclaimed (blanched leveled area) on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 1,391 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 262 (18.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 36
 - *Neuropteris* = 48
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 22
 - *Calamites* = 7
 - *Lepidophyllites* = 30
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 7
 - Plant stems = 59
 - Bark = 2
 - *Stigmarioides (Asolanus)* = 1
 - *Sporangites?* = 2
 - Seed = 2
 - Seed (*Trigonocarpus – Carpolithus*) = 1
 - Macerated plants = 30
 - Unidentified plants = 12
 - **Animals:** Total = 214 (15.3% of total)
 - *Essexella* (category not subdivided) = 7
 - Senior blobs = 11
 - Junior blobs = 9
 - Indeterminate blobs = 12
 - *Myalinella* = 46
 - Crushed *Myalinella* cluster = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 8
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 6 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 9
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 9
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - “flea shrimp” = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 4
 - Indeterminate arthropod = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 19

- Indeterminate polychaetes = 17
- Fish spine *Acanthodes?* = 1
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Coprolites = 24
- Trails/traces = 23
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 50 (3.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 11
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 39
- **Duds:** Total = 865 (62.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 263
 - Common dud batch = total 132:
 - Blue-gray duds = 104
 - Gray-brown duds = 28
 - Gray-brown duds = 194
 - Dark gray duds = 172
 - Blue-gray duds = 64
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 38
 - Pelletal duds = 1
- **Rejects:** 585

Locality 65

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington No. 4 shaft mine, northeast of Carbon Hill, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/02/24.**

- **Description:** Small spoil mound of abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington No. 4 shaft mine at NE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 27, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.30385495, -88.29303423 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2375. Mine hill apparently levelled (reclaimed) as seen on Google Earth.

- Total counts, based on 113 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 40 (35.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 11
 - Plant stems = 15
 - Macerated plants = 11
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (1.7% of total)
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.8% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 70 (61.9% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 4
 - Dark gray duds = 57
 - Blue-gray duds = 9

Locality 66

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington No. 5 Mine (tall hill) west of Carbon Hill, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 05/02/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington # 5 Mine at ctr, NE1/4, Section 33, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.296876, -88.308279 (GCB); 41.29808545, -88.30966715 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2378. Mine area strongly blanched on Google Earth; it appears to have been partly reclaimed (removed).

- Total counts, based on 965 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 172 (17.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 47
 - *Neuropteris* = 43
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 20
 - Plant stems = 28
 - Stems and bark = 5
 - Bark = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - *Aphlebia?* = 1
 - Scale branch = 1
 - Unidentified fern = 2
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 92 (9.5% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 17
 - Senior blobs = 24
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*, one valve only) = 1
 - Unidentified pecten = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Incognitum arthropod = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 6
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 7
 - Probable worm = 1

- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 5
- Holothurians = 1
- Fish spine *Acanthodes* = 1
- Coprolites = 10
- Coprolite with indeterminate blob = 1
- Trails/traces = 4
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 31 (3.2% of total)
 - “discs” = 10
 - Smears = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 20
- **Duds:** Total = 670 (69.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 333
 - Gray-brown duds = 211
 - Dark gray duds = 104
 - Septarial duds = 22
- **Rejects:** 87

Locality 67

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington deep mine No. 1 at Eileen, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/03/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil cone of abandoned Big Four Wilmington Coal Company, Big Four Wilmington no. 1 shaft mine at SE1/4, section 35, T33N, R8 E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.292810, -88.270420 (GCB); 41.29163865, -88.2710953 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2379. Vegetated over mine pile still apparently present along railroad track as seen via Google Earth.

- Total counts, based on 801 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 123 (15.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 24
 - *Neuropteris* = 15
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 13
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 38
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - Incognitum plant = 2
 - Macerated plants = 14
 - Unidentified plants = 1 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 107 (13.3% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 24
 - Junior blobs = 11
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; 1 clam, spread valves) = 3
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - *Euchondria* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 4 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp pygocephalomorph = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 4
 - “non-*Cyclus*” = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 6
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1

- Holothurian = 1
- Coprolites = 11
- Trails/traces = 13
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 38 (4.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 7
 - Ghosts-smears = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 29
- **Duds:** Total = 533 (66.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 280
 - Gray-brown duds = 183
 - Dark gray duds = 50
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 14
- **Rejects:** 475

Locality 68

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Star Coal Company, Star no. 1 shaft mine near northwest edge of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/03/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil hill of abandoned Star Coal Company, Star # no. 1 shaft mine in the NW1/4, SW1/4, section 35, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.296381, -88.280126 (GCB); 41.2914451, -88.2807512 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2380. Spoil mound not identified on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 538 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 78 (14.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 14
 - *Neuropteris* = 12
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 24
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Cordaitid seed = 1
 - Megaspore = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - Unidentified plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 26 (4.8% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 1
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - Unidentified bivalves = 1
 - Fragmental bivalve = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - Unidentified animal = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 42 (7.8% of total)
 - “discs” = 9
 - Ghosts-smears = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 29
 - **Duds:** Total = 392 (72.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 36
 - Gray-brown duds = 215

- Dark gray duds = 38
- Blue-gray duds = 21
- “green” pyritic duds = 13
- Septarial duds = 18
- Split duds (total) = 49:
 - Gray-brown duds = 22
 - Dark gray duds = 27
- **Rejects:** 340

Locality 69

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Coal City Coal Company, Coal City no. 1 shaft mine, northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/03/24.
- **Description:** Small spoil mound of abandoned Coal City Coal Company, Coal City no. 1 shaft mine bordering North Jugtown Road at NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 28, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.313360, -88.323752 (GCB); 41.31421875, -88.32210815 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2376. Mine hill removed for housing subdivision as observed via Google Earth. Locality extremely marginal for concretions. Lithology was flaggy to chippy siltstone.
- Total counts, based on concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 0
 - None found
 - **Duds:** Total = 2
 - Pyritic duds = 2

Locality 70

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Star Coal Company, Star no. 2 shaft mine, south-southeast of Carbon Hill, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/03/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned Star Coal Company, Star no. 2 shaft mine at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 34, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.292223, -88.297315 (GCB); 41.2910265, -88.29994675 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3360. Position of mine hill cryptic on Google Earth; it may be thoroughly vegetated over.

- Total counts, based on 971 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 159 (16.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 29
 - *Neuropteris* = 24
 - *Annularia* = 15
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - Plant stems = 39
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 11
 - Spore case = 1
 - Macerated plants = 26
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 70 (7.2% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 16
 - Junior blobs = 6
 - Indeterminate blobs = 12
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 2
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 4
 - Millepede *Aminilyspes* = 1
 - Millepede (unidentified) = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaete = 3
 - Probable worm = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Coprolites = 7
 - Trails/traces = 10
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 61 (6.2% of total)
 - “discs” = 9
 - “spots” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 51
 - **Duds:** Total = 681 (70.1% of total)

- Common duds = 469
- Gray-brown duds = 116
- Dark gray duds = 49
- Septarial duds = 47
- **Rejects:** 112

Locality 71

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Wilmington Star Mining Company, Wilmington Star no. 4 shaft mine at the south end of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/04/24.**

- **Description:** Small spoil mound of abandoned Wilmington Star Mining Company, Wilmington Star no. 4 shaft mine on the NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 11, T32N, R8E east of South Broadway Street on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.272558, -88.284498 (GCB); 41.27177538, -88.28259413 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2344. Blanched area in extreme northwest corner of section, visible on Google Earth, may be site of mine mound position.

- Total counts, based on 159 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (1.2 % of total)
 - Plant stems = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 20 (12.5% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 10
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - Unidentified marine shrimp = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (3.1% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 132 (83.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 82
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - Split duds (total) = 48:
 - Gray-brown duds = 41
 - Blue-gray duds = 4
 - Greenish, pyritic duds = 3

Locality 72

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Wilmington Star Mining Company, Wilmington Star no. 3 shaft mine, near east edge of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/04/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned Wilmington Star Mining Company, Wilmington Star no. 3. shaft mine in the ctr, NW1/4, section 2, T32N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.284284, -88.280258 (GCB); 41.28429895, -88.2805765 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2347. Mine hill not spotted on Google Earth; it's former position might be near the present position of the Coal City water tower in the railroad area near east edge of Coal City.
- Total counts, based on 290 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (6.8% of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Plant stems = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 39 (13.4% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 2
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 7
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaete = 5
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 1
 - Trails/traces = 13
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 36 (12.4% of total)
 - “discs” = 4
 - “spots” = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 28
 - **Duds:** Total = 195 (67.2% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 159
 - Light gray duds = 2
 - Blue-gray duds = 16
 - Dark gray-black duds = 1
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 14

Locality 73

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Wilmington Star Mining Company, Wilmington Star no. 5 shaft mine in Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/04/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned Wilmington Star Coal Company, Wilmington Star no. 5 shaft mine on the NE1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 3, T32N, R8E o the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.279449, -88.288359 (GCB); 41.2822287, -88.2925286 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2345. Former mine site not located on Google Earth. It appears to have been in an industrial area, northwest of the railroad tracks.
- Total counts, based on 286 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 54 (18.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 11
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - Unidentified plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 42 (14.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 5
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single valve) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (no further description) = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 5
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 5
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 2
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails/traces = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 28 (9.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 11
 - “ghosts” = 1
 - “spots” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 15
 - **Duds:** Total = 162 (56.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 63
 - Gray-brown duds = 65
 - Dark gray duds = 22

- Septarial duds = 12
- **Rejects:** 125

Locality 74

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Wilmington Star Coal Company, Wilmington Star no. 6 shaft mine west of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/05/24.
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned Wilmington Star Coal Company, Wilmington Star no. 6 shaft mine at SE1/4, NE1/4, section 4, T32N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.282237, -88.307425 (GCB); 41.2836237, -88.30932855 (ADM). Mine directory number = 259. Mine hill not spotted on Google Earth. Its former position appears to be where a house now stands.
- Total counts, based on 330 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 26 (7.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 5
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 38 (11.5% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Trails/traces = 8
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 22 (6.6% of total)
 - “discs” = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 18
 - **Duds:** Total = 244 (73.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 198
 - Septarial duds = 14
 - Split duds (total) = 16:
 - Gray-brown duds = 13
 - Blue-gray duds = 3

Locality 75

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Wilmington Star Mining Company, Wilmington Star no. 7 shaft mine, approximately 1.5 miles west of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/05/24.
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned Wilmington Star Mining Company, Wilmington Star no. 7 shaft mine on the NE1/4, section 5, T32N, R8E, west of South Jugtown Road on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.282722, -88.327999 (GCB); 41.283227, -88.3285095 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5. Mine hill still visible on Google Earth, but appears to be heavily overgrown.
- Total counts, based on 583 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 59 (10.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 7
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 9
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Spore *Triletes* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 17
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 36 (6.1% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 7
 - Senior blobs = 1
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, closed valves) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris*? = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified Polychaetes = 2
 - Coprolites = 12
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (1.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 479 (82.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 410
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - Split duds (total) = 67:

- Gray-brown duds = 41
- Dark gray duds = 10
- Blue-gray duds = 9
- Greenish pyritic duds = 3
- Pyrite-cored duds = 2
- Septarial duds = 1
- Light gray duds = 1

Locality 76

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “H”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from Single data sheet updated as of 06/27/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “H”) at Ctr, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 10, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at approximate digital coordinates 41.273337, -88.178153 (GCB); 41.2736979, -88.17730775 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 10 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 4 (40.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (10.0 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 5 (50.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 5

Locality 77

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “i”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/27/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “i”) at NW1/4, NE1/4, NW1/4, section 10, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.275856, -88.183630 (GCB); 41.2745682, -88.18336038 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 36 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 13 (36.1 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 23 (63.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 15
 - Dark gray duds = 8

Locality 78

- **Braidwood; included**—Very small, abandoned strip pit (Haskett Mine) east southeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/10/24.
- **Description:** Very small, abandoned strip pit (Haskett Mine) east of Pit 5. Mine is located on the NW1/4, SE1/4, section 10, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.266269, -88.177893 (GCB); 41.266404, -88.17693013 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5947.
- Total counts, based on 203 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 65 (32% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 19
 - *Annularia* = 10
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 16
 - Plant stems = 15
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Psaronius?* Stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (0.9% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (4.9% of total)
 - “discs” = 6
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 126 (62.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 97
 - Gray-brown duds = 18
 - Dark gray duds = 4
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - **Rejects:** 11

Locality 79

- **Braidwood; included**—Shaft cone of abandoned William Maltby Mine. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/27/24.
- **Description:** Shaft cone spoil pile of abandoned William Maltby deep mine at CTR, NW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle north-northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois, estimated digital coordinates 41.287547, -88.205812 (GCB); 41.28768378, -88.2012809 (ADM). Mine dump now removed; its former position corresponds to intersection of **Tully Monster** and **Dinosaur** Roads in new housing subdivision. Mine directory number is 6946. This locality is presumed synonymous with locality 56 and could be merged to it. Steve Sroka made the count, but never realized this overlap. Taxonomic sample composition essentially identical with that from “hill 56”.
- Total counts, based on 180 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 117 (65.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 48
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Bark = 14
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 17
 - **Animals:** Total = 10 (5.5 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Ostracodes = 2
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 53 (29.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 53

Locality 80

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp. strip mine (“McIlvaine Mine”) corresponding to South Wilmington Sportsman’s Club northwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/27/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corporation strip mine (“McIlvaine Mine”) at Ctr, SW1/4, NW1/4, section 33, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.207364, -88.202240 (GCB); 41.21128785, -88.20318053 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402.

- Total counts, based on 93 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 7 (7.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* (fertile) = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 30 (32.2 % of total)
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”)? = 1
 - *Strobeus* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Phyllocarid *Kellibrooksia* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Hystricula*? = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Holothurians = 2
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (6.4 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Smears = 3
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 50 (53.7 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 48
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 2

Locality 81

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station A”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station A”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, section 28, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.315360, -88.322513 (GCB); 41.31421875, -88.32210815 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 303 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 99 (32.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 11
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 57
 - Plant stems = 13
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 4 (1.3 % of total)
 - Coprolites = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.6 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 198 (65.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 165
 - Split duds; total = 33:
 - Gray-brown duds = 22
 - Dark gray duds = 4
 - Pyritic duds = 7
 - **Rejects:** 18

Locality 82

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, Station “A”) at east edge of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/27/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, station “A”) at NW1/4, section 9, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.273965, -88.206204 (GCB); 41.27145905, -88.2033901 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 454 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 58 (12.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 7
 - *Neuropteris* = 20
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 15
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant fragments = 2
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 85 (18.7 % of total)
 - *Essexella* = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 73
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 6
 - Trails = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (2.2 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
 - **Duds:** Total = 301 (66.2 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 16
 - Light gray duds = 2
 - Gray-brown duds = 229
 - Dark gray duds = 41
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 8
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - **Rejects:** 244

Locality 83

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “A”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/27/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “A”) at SW1/4, SW1/4, section 9, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.264221, -88.203505 (GCB); 41.26229383, -88.20539083 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 498 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 19 (3.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 9
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 51 (10.2 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 13
 - Senior blobs = 12
 - Junior blobs = 6
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.6 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 425 (85.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 195
 - Gray-brown duds = 21
 - Total duds split from bucket = 209:
 - Gray-brown duds = 60
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 148
 - Dark blue-gray duds = 1

Locality 84

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “B”)** east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/27/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “B”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 9, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.265897, -88.201059 (GCB); 41.26602308, -88.20077248 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 280 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 19 (6.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 8
 - Bark = 1
 - Lycopod twig = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 48 (17.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 9
 - Junior blobs = 4
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam in nodule) = 15
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams in nodule) = 3
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites?* = 1
 - Isopod *Hesslerella* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Probable polychaete = 2
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 14 (5.0 % of total)
 - Smears = 5
 - Disc = 1
 - Incognitum organisms = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 6
 - **Duds:** Total = 199 (71.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 184
 - Dark gray duds = 12
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1

- Septarial duds = 2
- **Rejects:** 8

Locality 85

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station A”), southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station A”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, section 17, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.170299, -88.222962 (GCB); 41.17134705, -88.2208361 (ADM). This is currently the Sun Recreation Club. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,059 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 65 (6.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 11
 - *Neuropteris* = 18
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 22
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 532 (50.2% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 404
 - Junior blobs = 57
 - Indeterminate blobs = 38
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Indeterminate polychaete = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 8
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 17
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (1.8% of total)
 - “discs” = 18
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 442 (41.7% of total)
 - Common duds = 113
 - Gray duds = 276
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 31
 - Septarial duds = 22
 - **Rejects:** 282

Locality 86

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “A”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/27/24.**

- **Description:** Largely submerged strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “A”) at N1/2, SE1/4, SW1/4 section 21, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle in currently partly flooded area of Braidwood Lake near northeast margin of Pit 11 at approximate digital coordinates 41.232589, -88.201880 (GCB); 41.23340375, -88.1991008 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 333 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 17 (5.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Plant fragments = 2
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 57 (17.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 6
 - *Mazonomya* (not subdivided-characterized) = 18
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, spread valves) = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule, spread valves) = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, closed valves) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3
 - Holothurian = 1
 - “fish eggs” = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (3.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 8
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 246 (73.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 128
 - Gray-brown duds = 47
 - Gray duds = 23
 - Weathered duds = 45

- Septarial duds = 2
- Pelletal nodule = 1
- **Rejects: 215**

Locality 87

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “B”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/28/24.**
- **Description:** Partly submerged strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “B”) at W1/2, NW1/4, NE1/4 section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle in currently partly flooded area of Braidwood Lake near northeast margin of Pit 11 at approximate digital coordinates 41.229710, -88.195842 (GCB); 41.22975733, -88.19893738 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,326 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 82 (6.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 10
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 14
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - Stems/bark = 22
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Asolanus* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 326 (24.5 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 13
 - Senior blobs = 21
 - Junior blobs = 56
 - Indeterminate blobs = 20
 - Blob with plant = 1
 - *Drevotella?* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (not subdivided-characterized) = 96
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, spread valves) = 33
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, closed valves) = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams, spread valves) = 8
 - *Aviculoecten* = 3
 - *Schizodus* = 1
 - Small round bivalve = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Chewed bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 3

- *Cyclus* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 4
- Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 4
- Unidentified polychaetes = 3
- Holothurian = 6
- Coprolites = 10
- Trails = 23
- Pelletal nodules-trails = 4
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 17 (1.2 % of total)
 - Discs = 8
 - Incognitum organism = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
- **Duds:** Total = 901 (67.9 % of total)
 - Common duds = 540
 - Gray duds = 149
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Weathered duds = 200
 - Septarial duds = 7
 - Sphalerite cored dud = 1
- **Rejects:** 665

Locality 88

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “C”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/28/24.**
- **Description:** Partly submerged strip mine terrain near extreme northeast corner of abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine, station “C” at SW1/4, SW1/4, NW1/4 section 21, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle in present day Lake Braidwood area at approximate digital coordinates 41.238680, -88.206141 (GCB); 41.24402063, -88.20447233 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 40 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 4 (10.0 % of total)
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 3 (7.5 % of total)
 - Junior blob = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (7.5 % of total)
 - Discs = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 30 (75.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 20
 - Dark gray duds = 6
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Pyritic duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 89

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “D”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/28/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine, station “D” at NE1/4, NE1/4 section 5, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle, west of the South Wilmington basketball court at digital coordinates 41.200359, -88.208531 (GCB); 41.20039305, -88.20761878 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 1,238 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 212 (17.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 44
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Plant stems = 62
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Plant fragments = 2
 - Macerated plants = 63
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 458 (36.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 88
 - Junior blobs = 125
 - Indeterminate blobs = 56
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - *Etacystis* (the aitch) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 12
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 5
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 50
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Peachocaris?* = 2
 - Essoid shrimp = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Phyllocarid *Kellibrooksia* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Millepede *Amynilyspes* = 1
 - Insect = 1

- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 5
- *Tullimonstrum* = 26
- Coprolites = 47
- Trails = 23
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 109 (8.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 62
 - Ghosts-smears = 17
 - Incognitum organism = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 28
- **Duds:** Total = 459 (37.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 198
 - Gray duds = 58
 - Gray-brown duds = 77
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 96
 - Septarial duds = 30
- **Rejects:** 354

Locality 90

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “E”, Will-Kankakee Counties, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/28/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine, station “E” at NW1/4, NE1/4 section 5, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.201617, -88.212595 (GCB); 41.20390423, -88.21242733 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 658 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 125 (18.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 25
 - *Neuropteris* = 10
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 51
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Caulopteris* (branch scar) = 1
 - Plant fragments = 2
 - Macerated plants = 22
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 254 (38.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 21
 - Junior blobs = 43
 - Indeterminate blobs = 23
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa?* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the aitch) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 3
 - *Myalinella* = 10
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 16
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Essoid shrimp = 4
 - Flea shrimp = 3
 - *Cyclus* = 11
 - Unidentified crustacean = 1

- Unidentified arthropod = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 3
- Polychaete *Hystricula* = 1
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 3
- Unidentified polychaetes = 9
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 2
- *Tullimonstrum* = 16
- *Acanthodes* with ostracodes = 1
- Coprolites = 32
- Trails = 35
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 57 (8.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 35
 - Ghosts-smears = 7
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 14
- **Duds:** Total = 222 (33.7 % of total)
 - Common duds = 41
 - Gray duds = 71
 - Gray-brown duds = 81
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 19
 - Septarial duds = 10
- **Rejects:** 210

Locality 91

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned R. Condon no. 2 shaft mine, north-northwest of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/05/24.
- **Description:** Small, residual stump of spoil mound of abandoned R. Condon no. 2 shaft mine southwest of the Lisbon Road in the NE1/4, NW1/4, section 20, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.411534, -88.453668 (GCB); 41.41315565, -88.4542334 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5522. Mine site not presently recognizable on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 55 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 8 (14.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Plant stems = 3
 - Macerated plants = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0% of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0% of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 47 (85.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 45
 - Pyritic nodules = 2

Locality 92

- **Braidwood; excluded—Abandoned Clayton Brothers? Shaft mine, Illinois.**
Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/05/24.

- **Description:** Very small, residual stump of spoil mound of abandoned Clayton Brothers? Shaft mine at NW1/4, SW1/4, section 28, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates 41.396802, -88.442848 (GCB); 41.39167468, -88.43930728 (ADM). Mine directory number = 750. Mine position solely known from mined-out map. No trace of this mine observed on Google Earth or remembered from visit.

- Total counts, based on 13 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 3 (23.0% of total)
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0% of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (7.6% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 9 (69.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 9

Locality 93

- **Braidwood; excluded—Abandoned Bell shaft mine(s), north of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/05/24.**
- **Description:** Very small, residual spoil stump of abandoned James Bell Shaft no. 2 mine west of the Interstate 80 cloverleaf at SW1/4, SE1/4, section 28, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.387986, -88.430546 (GCB); 41.38825238, -88.42954118 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2386. Mine only questionably identified via Google Earth near Menard's discount store at the north edge of Morris.
- Total counts, based on 72 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 8 (11.1% of total)
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0% of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0% of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 64 (88.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 58
 - Septarial duds = 3
 - Pyritic nodules = 3

Locality 94

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Abandoned Mitchell Mine (or R. Condon shaft mine “B”) at the north edge of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/06/24.**

- **Description:** Small spoil mound of abandoned Mitchell Mine (or R. Condon shaft mine “B”) at SW1/4, SE1/4, section 28, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.387025, -88.430503 (GCB); 41.37321235, -88.44861215 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5526. Numerous earlier overlapping pits are indicated in the area west of the Interstate 80 Morris interchange, an area of “big box” businesses, where development has erased much or all record of earlier mining. The current Illinois “mined-out” map is ambiguous as to where the Mitchell or Condon mines were once located.

- Total counts, based on 564 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 27 (4.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 11
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 9 (1.5% of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - Coprolites = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 14 (2.4% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 14
 - **Duds:** Total = 514 (91.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 208
 - Gray-brown duds = 301
 - Dark gray duds = 4
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 95

- **Will-Essex; included—Probable Chicago Fireproofing Company, Chicago Fireproofing Mine shaft mine near the southwest edge of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/06/24.**

- **Description:** Spoil debris of probable Chicago Fireproofing Company, Chicago Fireproofing Mine at NW1/4, SW1/4, section 4, T33N, R7E on the Morris 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.362396, -88.434916 (GCB); 41.36257083, -88.43852295 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2361. Cluster of small unlabeled shaft mines makes any precise identification of this pit difficult. The Fireproofing pit is an uncertain best call for this locality.

- Total counts, based on 798 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 45 (5.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 16
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 15
 - **Animals:** Total = 80 (10.0% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 4
 - Junior blobs = 15
 - Indeterminate blobs = 18
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 6
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3
 - Holothurians = 4
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails/traces = 22
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 30 (3.7% of total)
 - “discs” = 8
 - Unidentified nucleus = 22
 - **Duds:** Total = 643 (80.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 256
 - Gray-brown duds = 363
 - Dark gray duds = 6
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 4
 - Pyritic duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 9

- **Rejects: 241**

Locality 96

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned, unnamed shaft mine in the southwestern part of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/06/24.
- **Description:** Very small, residual spoil stump of abandoned unnamed shaft mine at or near Goold Park in southwest part of Morris at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 4, T33N, R7E on the Morris 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.363788, -88.430289 (GCB); 41.36267815, -88.43366008 (ADM). Mine directory number = 6989. Mine site not spotted using Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 216 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 19 (8.7% of total)
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - Plant stem = 11
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 22 (10.1% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 1
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; 1 clam, spread valves) = 1
 - Pygocephalomorph shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Coprolites = 6
 - Trails/traces = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (3.7% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 167 (77.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 104
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - Split duds (total) = 58:
 - Gray-brown duds = 18
 - Blue-gray duds = 17
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 12
 - Pyrite duds = 5
 - Weathered duds = 6

Locality 97

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned unnamed shaft mine “N” southwest of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/06/24.

- **Description:** Small residual spoil stump of abandoned “N” shaft mine on the SE1/4, SE1/4, section 5, T33N, R7E on the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.361280, -88.444596 (GCB); 41.35882238, -88.44320978 (ADM). Mine directory number = 5458. Mine site scar no longer recognizable.

- Total counts, based on 263 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 8 (3.0% of total)
 - Plant stems = 3
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 10 (3.8% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 1
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (1.1% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 242 (92.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 211
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - Split duds (total) = 27:
 - Gray-brown duds = 11
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 10
 - Gray “flinty” duds = 6

Locality 98

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Burrill and Dixon shaft mine at the northeast edge of Seneca, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/07/24.**

- **Description:** Small, residual spoil stump of abandoned Burrill and Dixon shaft mine at ctr, NW1/4, section 24, T33N, R5E on the Seneca 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.323262, -88.602109 (GCB); 41.32209755, -88.60559815 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2709. Mine site no longer evident on Google Earth. Minimal fossil yield.

- Total counts, based on 286 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 0 (% of total)
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (0.6% of total)
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.6% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 282 (98.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 282

Locality 99

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned unnamed shaft mine, at north edge of Seneca, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/07/24.**

- **Description:** Small, residual spoil stump of abandoned unnamed shaft mine at SW1/4, NW1/4, section 24, T33N, R5E on the Seneca 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.320744, -88.605233 (GCB); 41.3202457, -88.60792453 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2708. Mine site no longer discernable on Google Earth. Fossil yield extremely minimal.

- Total counts, based on 690 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 7 (1.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - Plant stems = 3
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (0.2% of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.2% of total)
 - “zinc disc” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 679 (98.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 679

Locality 100

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Seneca Coal Company Seneca shaft mine at northwest edge of Seneca, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/07/24.
- **Description:** Residual spoil stump of abandoned Seneca Coal Company shaft mine at SE1/4, NE1/4, section 23, T33N, R5E, on the Seneca 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.318575, -88.613847 (GCB); 41.3219604, -88.615289 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 1,489 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 31 (2.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 53 (3.5% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 10
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Peachocaris?* = 2
 - Possible mantis shrimp *Tyrannophontes* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Probable *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 10
 - Trails/traces = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 31 (2.0% of sample)
 - “discs” = 7
 - Unidentified nucleus = 24
 - **Duds:** Total = 1,374 (92.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 1270
 - Gray-brown duds = 44
 - Dark gray blue duds = 38
 - Pyritic duds = 15
 - Septarial duds = 7
 - **Rejects:** 344

Locality 101

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Unnamed shaft mine east of Seneca, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from data sheets updated as of 05/07/24.
- **Description:** Small residual spoil stump of abandoned unnamed shaft mine at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 24, T33N, R5E on the Seneca 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.31492115, -88.59543585 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2707. Mine site not recognized on Google Earth. Fossil yield was minimal.
- Total counts, based on concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 0
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0
 - **Duds:** Total = 503
 - Common duds = 502
 - Septarial dud = 1

Locality 102

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Silver Clay & Coal Company, Silver Mine shaft mine west of Seneca, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/07/24.**

- **Description:** Small, residual spoil stump of abandoned Silver Clay & Coal Company Silver Mine shaft mine at NW1/4, section 21, T33N, R5E on the Marseilles 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.320403, -88.662459 (GCB); 41.32141315, -88.663788 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2704.

- Total counts, based on 486 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 11 (2.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 3
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 3 (0.6% of total)
 - *Essexella* = 1
 - *Etacystis?* = 1
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (1.0% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 467 (96.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 435
 - Split duds (total) = 32:
 - Gray duds = 26
 - Blue-gray duds = 3
 - Sandy duds = 3

Locality 103

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Marseilles Cooperative Coal Company, Marseilles Co-operative shaft mine, south of Marseilles, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/07/24.

- **Description:** Small spoil mound of abandoned Marseilles Co-operative Coal Company, Marseilles Co-operative shaft mine at NW1/4, NE1/4, section 25, T33N, R4E on the Marseilles 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.311053, -88.711140 (GCB); 41.3087249, -88.7120326 (ADM). Mine directory number = 404. Mine hill heavily overgrown as seen via Google Earth. This locality should be combined into Locality # 104 as the two localities appear to be the same locality.

- Total counts, based on 264 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 9 (3.4% of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 3
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 4 (1.5% of total)
 - *Essexella?* = 3
 - Marine shrimp *Belotelson?* = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (1.8% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 246 (93.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 97
 - Gray-brown duds = 123
 - Dark gray duds = 7
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 16
 - Pyritic duds = 3
 - **Rejects:** 114

Locality 104

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Marseilles Cooperative shaft mine, Marseilles, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/15/24.

- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned Marseilles Co-operative deep mine south of Marseilles, LaSalle County, Illinois at SE1/4, NE1/4, section 25, T33N, R4E on the Marseilles 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.310878, -88.711213 (GCB); 41.30510563, -88.70715508 (ADM). This locality could possibly be combined with Locality # 103 as they appear to be the same place.

- Total counts, based on 437 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 7 (1.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 4 (0.9% of total)
 - Junior blob = 2
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - Unidentified marine shrimp = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (0.9% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 422 (96.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 143
 - Gray-brown duds = 24
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 5
 - **Rejects:** 250

Locality 105

- **Will-Essex; included**—“Chowder flat” Station E west of Morris, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/12/24.
- **Description:** Strip mine spoil piles of Morris Coal and Mining Company strip mine (“Creek Mine”) near southeast pit corner at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T34N, R7E on the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.372621, -88.441846 (GCB); 41.37334893, -88.44379093 (ADM). This mine has been erased by development (expansion of Morris).
- Total counts, based on 1,684 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 72 (4.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 20
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 5
 - Plant stem = 17
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 5
 - Macerated plants = 12
 - **Animals:** Total = 640 (38.0% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 118
 - Senior blobs = 126
 - Junior blobs = 74
 - Indeterminate blobs = 94
 - Multiple blobs = 5
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 68
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams) = 3
 - *Aviculopecten* = 8
 - Uncategorized pectinids = 8
 - *Schizodus* = 1
 - Indeterminate bivalves = 4
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Paleolimulus* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 6
 - Indeterminate polychaetes = 4
 - Acorn worm *Balanoglossus* = 1
 - Holothurians = 5
 - Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
 - Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Coprolites = 15

- Trails/traces = 90
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (0.6% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 11
- **Duds:** Total = 961 (57.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 440
 - Gray duds = 169
 - Dark gray duds = 42
 - Red-brown duds = 7
 - Pyritic duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 1
 - Weathered duds = 244
- **Rejects:** 261

Locality 106

- **Will-Essex; included—Morris Coal and Mining Company (“chowder flats”) west of Morris, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/12/24.**
- **Description:** Strip mine spoil piles of Morris Coal and Mining Company strip mine (“Creek Mine”) near northern pit corner at NE1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T34N, R7E on the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.374446, -88.441958 (GCB); 41.37334893, -88.44379093 (ADM). This mine has been erased by development (expansion of Morris).
- Total counts, based on 1,650 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 436 (26.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 94
 - *Neuropteris* = 19
 - *Annularia* = 76
 - *Calamites* = 24
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 41
 - Plant stems = 109
 - Bark/stem = 22
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - *Pinnularia* = 2
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Crossotheca* = 1
 - Branch tufts = 4
 - Macerated plants = 30
 - Plant fragments = 4
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 212 (12.8% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 20
 - Senior blobs = 41
 - Junior blobs = 9
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 15
 - *Mazonomya* (fragment) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 5
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (shelled) = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (molted) = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (fragment) = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid = 1

- Pygocephalomorph shrimp = 1
- Unidentified marine shrimp = 1
- *Cyclus* = 2
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 11
- Polychaete *Hystricula* = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 5
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 10
- Holothurians = 23
- *Tullimonstrum* = 1
- Coprolites = 22
- Trails/traces = 25
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (1.2% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 20
- **Duds:** Total = 982 (59.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 433
 - Gray duds = 77
 - Dark gray duds = 130
 - Pyritic duds = 11
 - Septarial duds = 17
 - Weathered duds = 324
- **Rejects:** 218

Locality 107

- **Will-Essex; included—Morris Coal and Mining Company (“chowder flats”, station C) west of Morris, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/13/24.**
- **Description:** Strip mine spoil piles of Morris Coal and Mining Company strip mine (“Creek Mine”) near western pit corner at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T34N, R7E on the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.372524, -88.444412 (GCB); 41.37334893, -88.44379093 (ADM). This mine has been erased by development (expansion of Morris).
- Total counts, based on 648 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 52 (8.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 21
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 19
 - Indeterminate plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 128 (19.7% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 24
 - Senior blobs = 12
 - Junior blobs = 4
 - Indeterminate blobs = 12
 - “grooved” blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 25
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 7
 - *Schizodus* = 6
 - “Hill 20” clam = 1
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Dryptoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Trails/traces = 17
 - Coprolites = 10
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (1.3% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 7
 - Smears-ghosts = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 459 (70.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 132
 - Gray-brown duds = 111
 - Dark gray duds = 4

- Pyritic duds = 9
- Weathered duds = 203
- **Rejects:** 107

Locality 108

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Company No. 2 strip mine (“Creek Mine” – north end) at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 33, T34N, R7E west of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/09/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company No. 2 strip mine at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 33, T34N, R7E near the south edge of the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at estimate digital coordinates 41.376406, -88.434370 (GCB); 41.37723525, -88.43417158 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625. Mine erased by urban spread of Morris.

- Total counts, based on 391 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 169 (43.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 49
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 14
 - Plant stems = 43
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 18
 - Macerated plants = 35
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (0.5% of total)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.2% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 219 (56.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 141
 - Dark gray pyritic duds = 10
 - Pyritic duds = 37
 - Weathered duds = 29
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 109

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company No. 2 strip mine (“Creek Mine”) at west edge of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/09/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company No. 2 strip mine (“Creek Mine” – south end) at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 33, T34N, R7E at the north edge of the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.375406, -88.434155 (GCB); 41.3774959, -88.4244515 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625. Strip mine now erased by spread of subdivisions.

- Total counts, based on 417 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 167 (40.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 49
 - Plant stems = 34
 - *Asterophyllites* = 8
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Lycopod branch = 2
 - Macerated plants = 43
 - Unidentified plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 5 (1.1% of total)
 - Coprolites = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 245 (58.7% of total)
 - Common duds = 148
 - Pyritic duds = 2
 - Yellowish-brown duds = 20
 - Green-gray duds = 23
 - Greenish pyritic duds = 21
 - Hard, blue-gray duds = 31

Locality 110

- **Will-Essex; included—H. K. Porter Coal Strip Mine, east of Ottawa, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/14/24.**
- **Description:** Unreclaimed spoil pile terrain of abandoned H. K. Porter coal strip mine west of intersection of Illinois Routes 6 and 71 at NW1/4, SW1/4, section 5, T33N, R4E on the Ottawa 7.5' quadrangle, east of Ottawa, LaSalle County, Illinois at digital coordinates 41.355516, -88.803289 (GCB); 41.35919813, -88.80044925 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 951 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 41 (4.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 13
 - *Neuropteris* = 11
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 228 (23.9 % of total)
 - Indeterminate blobs? = 2
 - *Mazonomya* = 101
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex?* = 1
 - Holothurians? = 54
 - Coprolite = 7
 - Trails = 61
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 82 (8.6 % of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 82
 - **Duds:** Total = 600 (63 % of total)
 - Common duds = 189
 - Gray duds = 86
 - Gray-brown duds = 131
 - Gray, flinty duds = 101
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 8
 - Septarial duds = 72
 - Weathered duds = 13
 - **Rejects:** 321

Locality 111

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Company strip mine east of Ottawa, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/15/24.
- **Description:** Spoil pile terrain in abandoned Wilmington Coal Company strip mine (station A) east of Ottawa, Illinois at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 12, T33N, R3E on the Ottawa 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.351807, -88.814156 (GCB); 41.3499836, -88.82202515 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 90 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 3 (3.3% of total)
 - Plant stem = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 16 (17.7% of total)
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 13
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (4.4% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 67 (74.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 28
 - Gray, flinty, hard duds = 20
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - Weathered duds = 14
 - **Rejects:** 79

Locality 112

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Company Coal Mines Inc., Wilmington no. 4 strip mine (“station B”), east of Ottawa, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Company Coal Mines Inc., no. 4 strip mine (“station B”) at ctr, section 7, T33N, R4E on the Ottawa 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.346470, -88.806166 (GCB); 41.3464181, -88.8098288 (ADM). Mine directory number = 657.
- Total counts, based on 197 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 13 (6.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - Plant stems = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Indeterminate plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 12 (6.0% of total)
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; one clam) = 7
 - Trails/traces = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (2.5% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 167 (84.7% of total)
 - Common duds = 35
 - Gray duds = 10
 - Gray, flinty, hard duds = 69
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 3
 - Weathered duds = 47
 - Septarial duds = 3
 - **Rejects:** 108

Locality 113

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Company Inc., Wilmington No. 4 strip mine (“station C”) east of Ottawa, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/10/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Company Inc., Wilmington no. 4 strip mine (“station C”) at the current site of the ADM terminal on the SE1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T33N, R4E on the Ottawa 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.336077, -88.774919 (GCB); 41.34112533, -88.7947841 (ADM). Mine directory number = 657.

- Total counts, based on 788 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 123 (15.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 41
 - *Neuropteris* = 23
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 35
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Macerated plants = 9
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 120 (15.2% of total)
 - *Essexella* = 1
 - Possible *Essexella* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; one clam) = 50
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - *Schizodus* (megaclam) = 1
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 3
 - Holothurian = 13
 - Probable holothurians = 4
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Ottawa incognitum (possible holothurian) = 6
 - Trails/traces = 37
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 39 (4.9% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 39
 - **Duds:** Total = 506 (64.2% of total)
 - Common duds = 75
 - Gray duds = 44
 - Gray-brown duds = 118
 - Hard, gray, flinty duds = 208
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 16

- Septarial duds = 45
- **Rejects:** 471

Locality 114

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mines Inc., Wilmington # 4 strip mine, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Company Inc., Wilmington # 4 strip mine at SE1/4, section 8, T33N, R4E on the Ottawa 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.334356, -88.770109 (GCB); 41.34277365, -88.7876471 (ADM). Mine directory number = 657.
- Total counts, based on 170 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 8 (4.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - Plant stem = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 13 (7.6% of total)
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; one clam) = 6
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Trails/traces = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (3.5% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 6
 - **Duds:** Total = 143 (84.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 27
 - Gray duds = 12
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 32
 - Gray, flinty, hard duds = 53
 - Weathered duds = 11
 - Septarial duds = 8
 - **Rejects:** 101

Locality 116

- **No assignment; excluded**—Abandoned Osage Coal Company, Osage strip mine (“station B”), west of Ottawa, LaSalle County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Osage Coal Company, Osage strip mine (“station B”), north of Starved Rock State Park on the SE1/4, NW1/4, section 17, T33N, R3E on the Starved Roak 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.333928, -88.911401 (GCB); 41.33323343, -88.90588408 (ADM). Mine directory number = 370. Westernmost mine visited in greater Ottawa-Illinois Valley area.
- Total counts, based on 104 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (1.9% of total)
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (0.9% of total)
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 101 (97.1% of total)
 - Gray duds = 35
 - Hard gray, flinty duds = 16
 - Septarial duds = 10
 - Weathered duds = 40

Locality 122

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Ramsdell’s “holothurian hill”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/27/24.**

- **Description:** Strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (Ramsdell’s holothurian hill” now partly to mostly submerged under Braidwood Lake) at Ctr., SE1/4 section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.206729, -88.211111 (GCB); 41.20576435, -88.2101484 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Whole concretions collected and counted by the Ramsdells.

- Total counts, based on 104 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 23 (22.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 17
 - **Animals:** Total = 61 (58.6)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 45
 - Multiple blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Polychaete *Hystriacula* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Holothurians = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.9 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 18 (17.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 15
 - Pyritic duds = 2
 - Septarial dud = 1

Locality 123

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Ramsdell’s “roost area”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/27/24.**

- **Description:** Strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (Ramsdell’s roost area” now partly to mostly submerged under Braidwood Lake) at SE1/4, NE1/4 section 30, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.225666, -88.227075 (GCB); 41.22558933, -88.22744405 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Whole concretions collected and counted by Ramsdells.

- Total counts, based on 88 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 3 (3.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 72 (81.8 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 12
 - *Mazonomya* = 19
 - Pectens = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Holothurians = 4
 - Coprolites = 19
 - Trails = 13
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (7.9 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 6 (6.8 % of total)
 - Pyritic duds = 6

Locality 124

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11 station “F”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/27/24.**

- **Description:** Strip mine terrain (now submerged) in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “F”) at SE1/4, SW1/4 section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.205386, -88.219618 (GCB); 41.20380773, -88.2171171 (ADM). Most of this area currently under Lake Braidwood. Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 326 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 48 (14.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 7
 - Plant stems = 14
 - *Maripteris* – *Odontopteris* = 3
 - Macerated plants = 22
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 133 (40.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 19
 - Junior blobs = 50
 - Indeterminate blobs = 24
 - *Etacystis* (the Aitch) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Ammonoid *Wiedeyoceras* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 4
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Unidentified arthropod = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* on leathery plant = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 3
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Coprolites = 8
 - Trails = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (3.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 6
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 134 (41.1 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 117
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 8
 - Septarial duds = 9

Locality 125

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company, northern strip mine (Pit 15: Station “A”). Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/11/24.**

- **Description:** Tip heaps of abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine within Pit 15, Kankakee County, Illinois. Collecting site is at SW1/4, NE1/4, section 19, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.151898, -88.229055 (GCB); 41.15284368, -88.23002685 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 771 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 51 (6.6% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 9
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 11
 - Bark = 2
 - Lycopod bark = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Neuroteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - Indeterminate plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 272 (35.2% of total)
 - *Essexella* = 3
 - Senior blobs = 147
 - Junior blobs = 36
 - Indeterminate blobs = 18
 - *Mazonomya* = 5
 - *Strobeus* = 7
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 7
 - Coprolites = 41
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - Pelletized blobs = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (1.1% of total)
 - “discs” = 3
 - Spots = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 439 (56.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 195
 - Gray-brown duds = 112

- Pyrite-cored duds = 118
- Septarial duds = 14

Locality 126

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Strip Mine (Pit 15, “station B”) southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from six data sheets updated as of 05/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Strip Mine (Pit 15, “station B”) in the Lake Shannon area at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 19, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.155551, -88.225618 (GCB); 41.15666163, -88.22526895 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,094 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 102 (9.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 28
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 19
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 8
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Plant stems = 30
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 373 (34.0% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 247
 - Junior blobs = 36
 - Indeterminate blobs = 29
 - Pelletized blobs = 2
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa* = 1
 - *Octomedusa* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 6
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 11
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 27
 - Trails/traces = 10
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 12 (1.0% of total)
 - “discs” = 4
 - Smear = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 607 (55.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 479
 - Gray-brown duds = 54

- Pyrite-cored duds = 64
- Septarial duds = 10
- **Rejects:** 12
- Additional taxa collected by W. Wennlund (not itemized in this sample):
 - Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
 - Millepede (platydesmid holotype) = 1
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 1

Locality 127

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, northern strip mine (Pit 15, “station C”) southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, northern strip mine (Pit 15, “station C”) in Lake Shannon Area at NW1/4, NE1/4, section 19, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.155887, -88.229143 (GCB); 41.15657053, -88.23010245 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 458 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (4.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Plant stems = 7
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 226 (49.3% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 133
 - Junior blobs = 19
 - Indeterminate blobs = 32
 - Pelletized blobs = 6
 - Box jelly *Anthracomедusa* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 4
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 3
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Insect = 1
 - Coprolites = 20
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - Burrow “mottles” = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.6% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 209 (45.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 205
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 128

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station B”), southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station B”) at NE1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 18, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.164751, -88.225135 (GCB); 41.16491939, -88.2242549 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 336 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 18 (5.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 6
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Cone = 1
 - *Spiropteris-Aphlebia?* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 157 (46.7% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 108
 - Junior blobs = 20
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - *Etacystis* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Probable shrimp = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Coprolites = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.2% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 160 (47.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 145
 - Gray-brown duds = 7
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 8

Locality 129

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, northern mine (“station C” = “chiton hill” in Pit 13). Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/04/24.
- **Description:** Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 13, “station C”) west of Essex, Illinois at coordinates SE1/4, SW1/4, NW1/4, section 17, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle, with digital coordinates approximated at 41.166812, -88.220027 (GCB); 41.1668125, -88.21954373 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1140 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 27 (2.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Neuropteris rarineruis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Plant stems = 5
 - *Thallites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - Unidentified plant = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 250 (21.9% of total)
 - *Essexella* category not subdivided = 17
 - Senior blobs = 69
 - Junior blobs = 64
 - Indeterminate blobs = 21
 - Pelletized blob = 1
 - Faulted blob = 1
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 2
 - *Escumasia* (“Y”) = 3
 - *Mazonomya* = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 5
 - Pecten = 1
 - *Strobeus* = 3
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 34
 - *Belotelson* = 3
 - Shrimp *Peachocaris* (complete) = 1
 - Gooseneck barnacle *Praeilepis* on *Myalinella* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
 - Coprolites = 13

- Trails/traces = 3
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 15 (1.3% of total)
 - “eggs” – “eyes” = 1
 - Incognitum = 1
 - Bleichen = 1
 - Spots = 1
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
- **Duds:** Total = 848 (74.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 509
 - Gray-brown duds = 156
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 181
 - Septarial duds = 2
- **Rejects:** 350

Locality 130

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned, Peobody Coal Company, northern mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station D”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from seven data sheets updated as of 05/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, northern mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station D”) at NE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 17, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.168225, -88.221083 (GCB); 41.16863296, -88.21958796 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,643 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 91 (5.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 25
 - *Neuropteris* = 25
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - Multiple *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Calamites* stem = 1
 - Plant stems = 17
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Odontopterid?* = 1
 - Lycopod scale = 1
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,012 (61.5% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 155
 - Senior blobs = 422
 - Junior blobs = 232
 - Indeterminate blobs = 119
 - Box jelly *Anthracomédusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 8
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 9
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Shrimp *Peachocaris* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - “roach” egg sac = 1
 - Crustacean exuvia = 5
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 10
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 4

- Coelocanth fish *Rhabdoderma* = 1
- Coprolites = 23
- Trails/traces = 9
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (1.2% of total)
 - “discs” = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 17
- **Duds:** Total = 520 (31.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 370
 - Gray-brown duds = 25
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 99
 - Septarial duds = 26
- **Rejects:** 209

Locality 131

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, northern mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station E”), southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine “station E”) at SE1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 18, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.166774, -88.224895 (GCB); 41.16673985, -88.22429914 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 239 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 19 (7.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - Plant stem = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 94 (39.3% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 58
 - Junior blobs = 9
 - Indeterminate blobs = 20
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (1.6% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 122 (51.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 108
 - Septarial duds = 12
 - Vertical tube-shaped concretions = 2

Locality 132

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station F”) southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station F”) at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 18, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.160376, -88.225821 (GCB); 41.1603454, -88.22535438 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 398 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 32 (8.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 14
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - Plant stems = 6
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 149 (37.4% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 28
 - Senior blobs = 71
 - Junior blobs = 15
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - Pelletized blob = 1
 - Faulted bob = 1
 - *Etacystis?* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; one clam) = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Insect = 1
 - Coprolites = 12
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (1.0% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 213 (53.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 150
 - Gray-brown duds = 3
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 35
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - Vertical tube-pipe concretions = 22
 - **Rejects:** 99

Locality 133

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND A”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/14/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine “station POND A” south of West Road and Monster Lake in Ponderosa Sportsman’s Club) at ctr, NE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.184023, -88.227477 (GCB); 41.1838687, -88.2284837 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 2,541 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 244 (9.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 110
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 28
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 75
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Stigmarioides* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,151 (45.2 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 540
 - Junior blobs = 271
 - Indeterminate blobs = 59
 - “micro” blobs = 8
 - Churned, pelletized blobs = 4
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 11
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 8
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 19
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Mantis shrimp *Tyranophontes* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 3
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - “non-*Cyclus*” = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 6
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 7

- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
- Polychaete Baby Tooth = 1
- Polychaete Oliver Hardy? = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 9
- “shovel-nose” polychaete = 1
- Indeterminate polychaete = 1
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 5
- Priapulid worm = 1
- Holothurians = 26
- *Tullimonstrum* = 8
- *Palaeoxyris* = 1
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
- Coelocanths *Rhabdoderma* = 2
- Coprolites = 99
- Trails/traces = 20
- Trace *Diplocraterion* = 22
- Trace *Chondrites* = 1
- “pellet-string” traces = 4
- Unidentified animal = 2
- Incognitum animal = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (0.7 % of total)
 - “discs” = 9
 - Unidentified nucleus = 11
- **Duds:** Total = 1,126 (44.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 975
 - Gray-brown duds = 66
 - Septarial duds = 85
- **Note:**
 - Fossils collected by avocational paleontologists in this same area, but not included in this count, include: Nematode, teuthid *Jeletzkyia*, box jelly *Anthracom edusa*, shrimp *Mamayocaris*, centipede.

Locality 134

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal Company strip mine (“station A”) at northeast edge of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/14/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal Company strip mine (“station A”) at ctr, Section 34, T34N, R7E near the south edge of the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.380682, -88.413995 (GCB); 41.379598, -88.4124055 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.
- Total counts, based on 993 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 520 (52.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 238
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 14
 - *Neuropteris* = 25
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 15
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 87
 - Plant stems = 75
 - Bark = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Cone? = 1
 - Macerated plants = 40
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 18 (1.8% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Nonmarine bivalve with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Coprolites = 11
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.3% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 452 (45.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 225
 - Dark gray duds = 80
 - Pyritic duds = 57
 - Septarial duds = 1
 - Weathered duds = 90

Locality 135

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned strip mine area, Pit 1 “Goldblatts collecting area, northwest of Interstate 55. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/11/24.
- **Description:** Spoil pile terrain in abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 1 easternmost margin), known informally by collectors as “Goldblatts collecting area. Mine area is east of N-S South Kavanaugh Road at NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, Section 28, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5/ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.311124, -88.207475 (GCB); 41.31204834, -88.20841189 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 893 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 603 (67.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 118
 - *Neuropteris* = 40
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 26
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Neuropteris* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 51
 - *Calamites* = 38
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 77
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 14
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - Plant stem = 130
 - Bark = 17
 - *Alethopteris* = 6
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - *Cordaicarpus* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 6
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Seed case = 1
 - Macerated plants = 53
 - Indeterminate plant = 12
 - **Animals:** Total = 46 (5.1 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 4
 - Indeterminate bivalves = 1
 - Shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 9
 - “Roach egg sac” = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - Coprolites = 29

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (1.0 % of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 9
- **Duds:** Total = 253 (26.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 67
 - Gray-brown duds = 153
 - Dark gray duds = 15
 - Blue-gray duds = 14
 - Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects:** 32

Locality 136

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes, station “A”). Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 07/01/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes station “A”) at NW1/4, SW1/4, section 12, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle, estimated digital coordinates 41.350743, -88.265667 (GCB); 41.3517267, -88.2653811 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 522 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 198 (37.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 48
 - *Neuropteris* = 9
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 40
 - Plant stems = 31
 - Bark = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Dicranophyllum* = 1
 - *Sphenopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobohyllum* = 5
 - *Equisetites* = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 2
 - Giant seed = 1
 - Spore bearing organ = 1
 - Macerated plants = 34
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 31 (5.9 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Very large unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Ostracode = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Xenocanth shark tooth = 2
 - Coprolites = 23
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 26 (4.9 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 26
 - **Duds:** Total = 267 (51.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 94
 - Gray-brown duds = 60

- Dark gray duds = 69
- Massive pyritic duds = 5
- Septarial duds = 4
- Split duds (total = 35):
 - Gray duds = 5
 - Pyritic duds = 27
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 137

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes, station “B”) Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 07/01/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes station “B”) at Ctr, NE1/4, section 14, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.342173, -88.274919 (GCB); 41.3424762, -88.2723678 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 972 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 334 (34.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 93
 - *Neuropteris* = 12
 - *Annularia* = 16
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 116
 - Plant stems = 43
 - Bark = 5
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 24
 - Unidentified plants = 17
 - **Animals:** Total = 61 (6.2 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 6 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Fish scale (*Megalichthys*) = 1
 - Coprolites = 53
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 16 (1.6 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 16
 - **Duds:** Total = 561 (57.7 % of total)
 - Common duds = 143
 - Gray-brown duds = 17
 - Dark gray duds = 132
 - Pyritic duds = 108
 - Septarial duds = 9
 - Weathered duds = 94
 - Split duds (total= 58):
 - Common duds = 14
 - Pyritic duds = 27
 - Septarial duds = 17
 - **Rejects:** 163

Locality 138

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Nicholson, McKee, and Peart strip mine (or Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 7 strip mine) across from Goose Lake Club property, northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/17/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Nicholson, McKee, & Peart strip mine (or Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine Pit 7 strip mine) north of Pine Bluff Road, kitty corner from Goose Lake Club property at SE1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 10, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.347056, -88.299954 (GCB); 41.34640963, -88.30244098 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 251 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 121 (48.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 29
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 47
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Bark = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Cone? = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Spore case? = 1
 - Macerated plant = 6
 - Unidentified plant = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 14 (5.5 % of total)
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 12
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (3.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
 - **Duds:** Total = 107 (42.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 46
 - Dark gray duds = 33
 - Pyritic duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 1
 - Weathered duds = 25

- **Rejects: 81**

Locality 139

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station B”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station B”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 21, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.318517, -88.312050 (GCB); 41.31878688, -88.32101444 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 40 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 13 (32.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (2.5 % of total)
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 26 (65.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 17
 - Pyritic duds = 6
 - Sandy duds = 3

Locality 140

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes, station “C”). Summary sample manifest from six data sheets updated as of 07/01/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes station “C”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 14, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.338011, -88.279506 (GCB); 41.33685813, -88.27940143 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 1,113 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 309 (27.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 62
 - *Neuropteris* = 20
 - *Annularia* = 14
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 60
 - Plant stems = 64
 - Bark = 4
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 5
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 5
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 2
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 49
 - Unidentified plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 104 (9.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 6 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 2
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Ostracodes = 1
 - Millepede (*Acantherpestes*) = 1
 - Coprolites = 93
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.4 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 695 (62.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 392
 - Dark gray duds = 247
 - Pyritic duds = 38
 - Weathered duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 12

- **Rejects: 201**

Locality 141

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station G”), southwest of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company, Northern Mine (Pit 13 strip mine, “station G”) at NW1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 17, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.161793, -88.223813 (GCB); 41.1613179, -88.22177458 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 387 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 39 (10.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 12
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Calamites* stem = 1
 - Plant stems = 13
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 75 (19.3% of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 22
 - Senior blobs = 15
 - Junior blobs = 6
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - *Etacystis?* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Pygocephalomorph shrimp = 1
 - Crustacean exuvium = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum?* = 1
 - Coprolites = 10
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (3.3% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 13
 - **Duds:** Total = 260 (67.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 257
 - Gray-brown dud = 1
 - Vertical pipe-tube concretions = 2
 - **Rejects:** 389

Locality 142

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, “Essex Hills” area, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) in the “Essex Hills” area at E1/2, NE1/4, section 5, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.198081, -88.213052 (GCB); 41.198549, -88.20991085 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 348 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 36 (10.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - Unidentified plants = 14
 - **Animals:** Total = 232 (66.6 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 174
 - Double blobs = 1
 - Blob with plant stem = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 2
 - *Myalinella* (= “*Septimyalina*”) = 1
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 12
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp “*Peachella*” = 8
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Esoid shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Goose neck barnacle *Praeilepis* = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Hystricula* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 3
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Coprolites = 13
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.8 % of total)
 - Smears = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 76 (21.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 76

Locality 143

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Ramsdell’s “Blaster Ridge” area, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/02/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) in Ramsdell’s “Blaster Ridge” area at SE1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 5, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.199593, -88.211995 (GCB); 41.19942278, -88.2111097 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 342 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 55 (16.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 6
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Bark = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 24
 - Unidentified plants = 12
 - **Animals:** Total = 184 (53.8 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 100
 - *Octomedusa* with Tully = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (= “Edmondia”) = 1
 - *Myalinella* (= “Septimyalina”) = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 21
 - Shrimp *Kallidectes* = 2
 - Shrimp “*Peachella*” = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Gooseneck barnacle *Praeepis* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Polychaete *Hystriacula* = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 2
 - Acorn worm = 1
 - Holothurians = 3
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 8
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the “blade”) = 1
 - Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
 - Coprolites = 17
 - Trails = 13

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
- **Duds:** Total = 102 (29.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 102

Locality 144

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (Will County) northwest of Essex, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (Will County) at NE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.204050, -88.206514 (GCB). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 111 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 23 (20.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plant = 14
 - **Animals:** Total = 40 (36.0 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 18
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 2
 - Myalinid = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 6
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Phyllocarid *Kellibrooksia* = 1
 - Centipede *Letzelia* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 48 (43.2 % of total)
 - Common duds = 46
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 2

Locality 145

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample “T-4” collected by Tom Beard. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/02/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NE1/2, NW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.210473, -88.220470 (GCB); 41.21377664, -88.21865983 (ADM). Area currently mostly submerged under Lake Braidwood. Sample “T-4” collected by Tom Beard. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 488 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 19 (3.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Bark = 7
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 98 (20.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 10
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= “*Edmondia*”; one clam in concretion) = 14
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 5
 - Holothurians = 4
 - Coprolites = 15
 - Trails = 46
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 370 (75.8 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 366
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 4

Locality 148

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample “T-7” collected by Tom Beard. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/02/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.205176, -88.214463 (GCB); 41.20297416, -88.21356679 (ADM). Area currently mostly under Lake Braidwood. Sample “T-7” collected by Tom Beard. Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 623 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 35 (5.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - Plant stem = 11
 - Macerated plants = 19
 - **Animals:** Total = 199 (31.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 41
 - Junior blobs = 16
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - Multiple blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 34
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 9
 - Holothurians = 12
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 4
 - Coprolites = 10
 - Trails = 56
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 387 (62.1 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 316
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 63
 - Septarial duds = 8

Locality 149

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample “T-8” collected by Tom Beard. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/02/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.208979, -88.217396 (GCB); 41.20852311, -88.20669263 (ADM). Area is currently on reclaimed island in Lake Braidwood. Sample “T-8” collected by Tom Beard. Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 997 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 97 (9.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 24
 - *Neuropteris* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 19
 - Plant stems = 44
 - **Animals:** Total = 170 (17.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 8
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (= “*Edmondia*”; one clam per nodule) = 6
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 28
 - Holothurians = 14
 - Coprolites = 28
 - Trails = 76
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 726 (72.8 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 417
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 277
 - Septarial duds = 32

Locality 150

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-9 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/05/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.20659791, -88.21369871 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 733 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 26 (3.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 8
 - Plant stem = 2
 - Macerated plants = 14
 - **Animals:** Total = 234 (31.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 29
 - Junior blobs = 44
 - Indeterminate blobs = 18
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 27
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule) = 13
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 11
 - Holothurians = 19
 - Coprolites = 6
 - Trails = 62
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 473 (64.5 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 423
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 40
 - Septarial duds = 10

Locality 151

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-10 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/05/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21014426, -88.21853039 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,201 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 52 (4.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 17
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 9
 - Plant stems = 26
 - **Animals:** Total = 135 (11.2 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 5
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 5
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 11
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 16
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 4
 - Holothurians = 7
 - Coprolites = 15
 - Trails = 72
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 14 (1.1 % of total)
 - Discs = 14
 - **Duds:** Total = 1,000 (83.2 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 732
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 247
 - Septarial duds = 21

Locality 152

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-11 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/05/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.20844756, -88.21140733 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 947 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 35 (3.6 % of total)
 - *Annularia* = 11
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 7
 - Macerated plants = 16
 - **Animals:** Total = 293 (30.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 33
 - Junior blobs = 59
 - Indeterminate blobs = 31
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 38
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule) = 19
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 9
 - Holothurians = 23
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails = 84
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 619 (65.3 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 548
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 61
 - Septarial duds = 10

Locality 153

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-12 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/05/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21386131, -88.21157281 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 840 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 31 (3.6 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 10
 - Plant stems = 19
 - **Animals:** Total = 214 (25.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 12
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - *Octomedusa* = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 6
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule) = 2
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 5
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 13
 - Holothurians = 39
 - Coprolites = 27
 - Trails = 87
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (0.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 588 (70.0 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 431
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 123
 - Septarial duds = 34
 - **Rejects:** 119

Locality 154

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-13 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21747373, -88.2140549 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,080 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 151 (13.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 19
 - *Annularia* = 21
 - Plant stems = 62
 - Macerated plants = 49
 - **Animals:** Total = 290 (26.8 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 17
 - Junior blobs = 31
 - Indeterminate blobs = 29
 - Multiple blobs = 36
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 16
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule) = 4
 - *Aviculopecten* = 13
 - Indeterminate bivalves = 4
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 7
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 15
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 3
 - Holothurians = 59
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 6
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 47
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (0.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 10
 - **Duds:** Total = 629 (58.2 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 529
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 71
 - Septarial duds = 29

Locality 155

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-14 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21212591, -88.20679963 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 867 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 39 (4.4 % of total)
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stems = 31
 - Macerated plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 292 (33.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 14
 - Junior blobs = 15
 - Indeterminate blobs = 33
 - *Octomedusa* = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 5
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 15
 - Holothurians = 49
 - Coprolites = 39
 - Trails = 102
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (0.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 6
 - **Duds:** Total = 530 (61.1 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 366
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 128
 - Septarial duds = 36

Locality 156

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-15 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21392731, -88.20926896 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 732 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 16 (2.1 % of total)
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Macerated plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 342 (46.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 25
 - Junior blobs = 19
 - Indeterminate blobs = 21
 - *Octomedusa* = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (1 clam per nodule) = 6
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams per nodule) = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 5
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 6
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 17
 - Holothurians = 53
 - Coprolites = 35
 - Trails = 142
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (1.0 % of total)
 - Discs = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 366 (50.0 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 75
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 252
 - Septarial duds = 39

Locality 157

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-16 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.216088, -88.210430 (GCB); 41.21570049, -88.20926896 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Sample T-16 of Tom Beard, but specimens collected by GCB. Locality currently borders east edge of submerged area of Braidwood Lake.
- Total counts, based on 708 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 141 (19.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 17
 - *Neuropteris* = 14
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 12
 - Plant stems = 55
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Lepidodendron* = 5
 - Macerated plants = 19
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 225 (31.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 11
 - Junior blobs = 29
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - Multiple blobs = 13
 - *Mazonomya* = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 17
 - Unidentified bivalve = 7
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 15
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 13
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 15
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 13
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 18
 - Coprolites = 21
 - Trails = 41

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 19 (2.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 7
 - Smears = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
- **Duds:** Total = 323 (45.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 99
 - Gray duds = 210
 - Pelletal nodules = 2
 - Septarial duds = 12

Locality 158

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-17 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22122561, -88.20944579 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 482 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 29 (6.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 9
 - Plant stems = 20
 - **Animals:** Total = 162 (33.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 17
 - Junior blobs = 15
 - Indeterminate blobs = 12
 - Multiple blobs = 8
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 10
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Holothurians = 18
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Agnathan *Gilpichthys?* = 1
 - Coprolites = 13
 - Trails = 62
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 291 (60.3 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 236
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 36
 - Septarial duds = 17

Locality 159

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-18 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.2193786, -88.20939426 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 655 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 87 (13.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 39
 - Plant stems = 18
 - Macerated plants = 30
 - **Animals:** Total = 213 (32.5 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 21
 - Junior blobs = 25
 - Indeterminate blobs = 37
 - Multiple blobs = 16
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 4
 - *Cyclus* = 9
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 18
 - Holothurians = 6
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Trails = 76
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 355 (54.1 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 264
 - Dark gray duds = 48
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 43
 - **Rejects:** 142

Locality 160

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-19 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.2211988, -88.21182064 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 863 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 67 (7.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 10
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Bark = 14
 - Macerated plants = 20
 - **Animals:** Total = 454 (52.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 59
 - Junior blobs = 32
 - Indeterminate blobs = 13
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 35
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 14
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 12
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 19
 - Holothurians = 15
 - Coprolites = 37
 - Trails = 218
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 16 (1.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 16
 - **Duds:** Total = 326 (37.7 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 286
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 12
 - Septarial duds = 28
 - **Rejects:** 274

Locality 161

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-20 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW 1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.223019, -88.21182064 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 785 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 64 (8.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 29
 - *Neuropteris* = 19
 - *Annularia* = 16
 - **Animals:** Total = 283 (36.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 37
 - Junior blobs = 30
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 44
 - *Myalinella* = 17
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 18
 - Holothurians = 14
 - Coprolites = 19
 - Trails = 89
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 438 (55.7 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 396
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 12
 - Septarial duds = 30

Locality 162

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-21 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.230365, -88.223726 (GCB); 41.23026279, -88.22404798 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Sample T-21 of Tom Beard, but specimens collected by GCB. Most of collecting area currently submerged under Braidwood Lake.
- Total counts, based on 472 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 10 (2.1 % of total)
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 4
 - *Sphenopteris?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 128 (27.1 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 9
 - Senior blob = 13
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - *Mazonomya* (not characterized) = 33
 - *Mazonomya* (1 clam per nodule) = 35
 - *Mazonomya* (2 clams per nodule) = 4
 - “Razor clam” = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Coprolites = 18
 - Trails = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (1.4 % of total)
 - Smear = 1
 - Discs = 4
 - Spots = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 327 (69.2 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 109
 - Gray-brown duds = 213
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - **Rejects:** 117

Locality 163

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-22 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/08/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.20852311, -88.20669263 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 310 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 41 (13.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 16
 - Macerated plants = 18
 - **Animals:** Total = 106 (34.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 12
 - Junior blobs = 34
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - Multiple blobs = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 4
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - *Cyclus* = 4
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 6
 - Holothurians = 7
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 163 (52.5 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 146
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 14
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 164

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-23 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/09/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.20650141, -88.21838849 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 322 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 15 (4.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Macerated plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 123 (38.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 14
 - Junior blobs = 11
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 15
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams per nodule) = 6
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 6
 - Holothurians = 12
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 4
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails = 46
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 184 (57.1 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 135
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 47
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 165

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-24 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/09/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21202214, -88.21387666 (ADM). Mine directory number 834. Sample T-24 of Tom Beard, but some specimens collected by GCB.
- **Note:** *Original ledger data transcribed by ADM and ML had too few specimens to be included.*
- Total counts, based on 323 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 56 (17.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 8
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 19
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 21
 - **Animals:** Total = 157 (48.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 18
 - Junior blobs = 54
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - Multiple blobs = 16
 - *Aviculopecten* = 4
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 8
 - *Cyclus* = 7
 - “non-*Cyclus*”? = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 6
 - Unidentified polychaete = 3
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 7
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 3
 - Coprolites = 12
 - Trail = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 19 (5.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 9
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10

- **Duds:** Total = 91 (28.1 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 80
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 8
- **Rejects:** = 147

Locality 166

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-25 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/24/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.2174455, -88.21641724 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Sample T-25 of Tom Beard.
- **Note:** This locality has the same township and range coordinates as Locality # 414 (Frank Greene's "*Solemya* spot" in Will County Pit Eleven) which is entered separately.
- Total counts, based on 206 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 41 (19.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 15
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - Seed case = 1
 - Macerated plants = 13
 - **Animals:** Total = 66 (32.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 4
 - Junior blobs = 9
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - Multiple blobs = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule) = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 1
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 13
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 3
 - Trails = 8
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (4.3 % of total)
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Disc = 1
 - Ghosts-smears = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 90 (43.6 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 66

- Dark gray duds = 10
- Pyrite-cored duds = 10
- Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects: 57**

Locality 167

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-26 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/09/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.2192657, -88.21884361 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Original ledger data transcribed by ADM and ML had too few specimens to be included.*
- Total counts, based on 295 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (6.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 11
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 104 (35.2 % of total)
 - Senior bobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 22
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - Multiple blobs = 9
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”)? = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 5
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete Oliver Hardy = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 22
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Coprolites = 9
 - Trails = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 18 (6.1 % of total)
 - Discs = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 13

- Incognitum organism = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 153 (51.8 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 123
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 26
 - Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects:** 75

Locality 168

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-27 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/09/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 79 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 7 (8.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 32 (40.5 % of total)
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphamites* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Holothurians = 17
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Trails = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (5.0 % of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 36 (45.5 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 20
 - Pyrite cored duds = 8
 - Septarial duds = 8
 - **Rejects*** = 26 (not included in sample count)

Locality 169

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-28 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/09/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21750195, -88.21169256 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 22 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 6 (27.2 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 16 (72.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Holothurians = 3
 - Trails = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)

Locality 170

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-29 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/09/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21932215, -88.21411894 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 19 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (10.5 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 17 (89.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 3
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)

Locality 171

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-30 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/09/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Missing original ledger data.*
- Total counts, based on 21 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1 (4.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 5 (23.8 % of total)
 - *Mazonomya* (1 clam per nodule) = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (4.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 14 (66.6 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 14
 - **Rejects:** = 19

Locality 172

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-31 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/09/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22486601, -88.21429854 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Sample T-31 of Tom Beard.
- **Note:** *Original ledger data transcribed by ADM and ML had too few specimens to be included.*
- Total counts, based on 238 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 8 (3.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - Plant stems = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 127 (53.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 9
 - Junior blobs = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - “eyed” blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 36
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 5
 - Holothurian = 4
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails = 49
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (2.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 96 (40.3 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 90
 - Septarial duds = 6
 - **Rejects:** 99

Locality 173

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-32 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/10/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22299078, -88.21660935 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Original ledger data transcribed by ADM and ML had too few specimens to be included.*
- Total counts, based on 194 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 5 (2.5 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 117 (60.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - Blob with trails = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 39
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Holothurian = 2
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 52
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (4.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 63 (32.4 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 57
 - Septarial duds = 6
 - **Rejects:** = 61

Locality 174

- **Will-Essex; included—Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (McIlvaine Pit), T-33 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/10/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine at NW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.221704, -88.196176 (GCB); 41.21966311, -88.19499576 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402. Formerly part of South Wilmington Sportsman's Club. Now partly submerged under Braidwood Lake.
- **Note:** *Single page locality # 175 has same coordinates as this locality and has been merged with this sample in the GCB update. ADM and ML transcription includes only original Locality 174. Locality 175 is missing.*
- Total counts, based on 237 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 7 (2.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - Plant stems = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* with trail = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 118 (49.7 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 3
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* with holothurian = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Holothurians = 19
 - Coprolites = 1
 - Trails = 86
 - *Diplocraterion* = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (2.5 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 106 (44.7 % of total)
 - Light gray duds = 30
 - Gray duds = 19
 - Gray-brown duds = 53
 - Dark gray duds = 2

- Septarial duds = 2
- **Rejects:** 46

Locality 176

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-35 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Missing original ledger data.*
- Total counts, based on 76 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 10 (13.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 24 (31.5 % of total)
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Trails = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (6.5 % of total)
 - Ghosts = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 37 (48.6 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 24
 - Dark gray duds = 8
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - **Rejects:** 26

Locality 178

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-36 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Missing original ledger data.*
- Total counts, based on 108 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 4 (3.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stem = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 47 (43.5 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 2
 - Junior blobs = 6
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 2
 - Arthropod *Cyzicus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 4
 - Trails = 25
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (3.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 53 (49.0 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 48
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - **Rejects:** 105

Locality 179

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-37 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834. Sample T-37 of Tom Beard.
- **Note:** *Missing original ledger data.*
- Total counts, based on 234 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 16 (6.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 8
 - Plant fragments = 3
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 64 (27.3 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 3
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 2
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 3
 - Polychaete Rat worm = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3
 - Holothurians = 11
 - Coprolites = 8
 - Trails = 20
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (3.4 % of total)
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 146 (62.3 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 46
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 92
 - Septarial duds = 8

- **Rejects: 103**

Locality 180

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-38 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Missing original ledger data.*
- Total counts, based on 231 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 24 (10.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - Plants stems = 10
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 46 (19.9 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 1
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites?* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 2
 - Coprolites = 6
 - Trails = 24
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 15 (6.4 % of total)
 - Discs = 5
 - Ghost-smear = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
 - **Duds:** Total = 146 (63.2 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 57
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 80

- Septarial duds = 9
- **Rejects:** 203

Locality 181

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-39 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Missing original ledger data.*
- Total counts, based on 146 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 6 (4.1 % of total)
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 55 (37.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 6
 - Junior blobs = 11
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - “eyed” blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 6
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams per nodule) = 3
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 4
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trails = 13
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (5.4 % of total)
 - Ghosts = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 6
 - **Duds:** Total = 77 (52.7 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 65
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 11
 - Septarial duds = 1
 - **Rejects:** 53

Locality 182

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-40 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** *Missing original ledger data.*
- Total counts, based on 299 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 12 (4.0 % of total)
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stems = 5
 - Plant fragments = 5
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 92 (30.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 3
 - Junior blobs = 4
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Polychaete “fan worm”? = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Holothurians = 17
 - Coprolites = 10
 - Trails = 36
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (2.6 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Ghosts-smears = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 187 (62.5 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 93
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 80
 - Septarial duds = 14

- **Rejects:** 149

Locality 183

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-41 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 234 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 12 (5.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 78 (33.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 13
 - Junior blobs = 6
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - “lettuce” = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 5
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 2
 - Gastropod *Euphemites?* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 4
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex?* = 1
 - Holothurians = 6
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trails = 29
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (4.7 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
 - **Duds:** Total = 133 (56.8 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 101
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 28
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - **Rejects:** 176

Locality 184

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-42 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/11/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21572871, -88.20690663 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 769 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 21 (2.7 % of total)
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - Plant stems = 15
 - **Animals:** Total = 322 (41.8 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 37
 - Junior blobs = 29
 - Indeterminate blobs = 42
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 54
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams per nodule) = 6
 - *Aviculopecten* = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 4
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 14
 - Holothurians = 18
 - Coprolites = 26
 - Trails = 32
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 421 (54.7 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 341
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 47
 - Septarial duds = 33

Locality 185

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-43 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 184 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (1.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 90 (48.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 6
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - “eyed” blobs = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 40
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams per nodule) = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Holothurians = 4
 - Coprolite = 2
 - Trails = 22
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (3.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 85 (46.1 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 82
 - Septarial duds = 3
 - **Rejects:** 114

Locality 186

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-44 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/11/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.21024896, -88.21146083 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 390 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 30 (7.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 18
 - **Animals:** Total = 126 (32.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 12
 - Junior blobs = 49
 - Indeterminate blobs = 17
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - *Cyclus* = 6
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 7
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 12
 - Holothurians = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Coprolites = 10
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 234 (60.0 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 226
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 187

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-45 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 90 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1 (1.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 32 (35.5 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 7
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 9
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Holothurians = 2
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trails = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (5.5 % of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 52 (57.7 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 42
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - **Rejects:** 47

Locality 188

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-46 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 157 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (1.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 78 (49.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 34
 - Junior blob = 11
 - Indeterminate blobs = 19
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 1
 - *Cyclus?* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Agnathan *Gilpichthys?* = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (5.0 % of total)
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Discs = 4
 - Ghost-smear = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 69 (43.9 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 29
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 35
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - **Rejects:** 16

Locality 189

- **No assignment; excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-47 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 125 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 4 (3.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 58 (46.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 5
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - “eyed” blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 6
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trails = 39
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.6 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 61 (48.8 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 51
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 4
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - Pelletal dud = 1
 - **Rejects*** = 31

Locality 190

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-48 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/11/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22486601, -88.21429854 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Collected by Tom Beard and GCB.
- Total counts, based on 1,487 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 37 (2.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 8
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 6
 - Plant stems = 10
 - Bark = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 462 (31.0 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 19
 - Senior blobs = 78
 - Junior blobs = 23
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam with spread valves) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam with closed valves) = 12
 - *Mazonomya* (1 clam per nodule) = 22
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams per nodule) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (not subdivided) = 18
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 3
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 9
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - “Ghost worms” (*Balanoglossus?*) = 12
 - Holothurians = 14

- Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
- Coprolites = 32
- Trails = 198
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 54 (3.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 49
- **Duds:** Total = 934 (62.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 745
 - Gray duds = 30
 - Light gray duds = 10
 - Red brown duds = 31
 - Gray-brown duds = 78
 - Pyrite-cored dud = 1
 - Septarial duds = 23
 - Weathered duds = 16
- **Rejects:** 365

Locality 191

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-49 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/11/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22494645, -88.20717399 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** Coordinate discrepancy between locality manifest and individual sheets for this locality: SE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, sec. 29 on list versus Ctr., SW1/4, NW1/4, sec. 29 on sheet.
- Total counts, based on 184 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 6 (3.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Bark = 1
 - Bark with pyrite lumps = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 103 (55.9 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 3
 - Senior blobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (category not subdivided) = 8
 - Bivalve *Lima* = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 3
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 3
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* on bark = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Holothurian = 2
 - Holothurian with blob = 1
 - Coprolites = 6
 - Trails = 56
 - Trails or ghost worms = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (4.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 67 (36.4 % of total)

- Gray-brown duds = 63
- Pyrite-cored duds = 2
- Septarial duds = 2
- **Rejects: 93**

Locality 192

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-50 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/11/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.2192657, -88.21884361 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** Township and Range coordinates are corrected values in locality manifest. They are different from those on locality sheets.
- Total counts, based on 311 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 33 (10.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 6
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Stems/bark = 6
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 91 (29.2 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 6
 - Junior blobs = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams per nodule) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 6
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - Elongate bivalve = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Paleolimulus* (prosoma) = 1
 - Insect = 1
 - Arachnid = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 5
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Polychaete Oliver Hardy worm = 1

- Polychaete *Spirorbis* on bark = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 7
- Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 6
- Holothurians = 4
- Coprolites = 5
- Trails = 21
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (6.4 % of total)
 - Discs = 6
 - Ghosts = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 11
- **Duds:** Total = 167 (53.6 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 122
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 39
 - Septarial duds = 6
- **Rejects:** 244

Locality 193

- **Will-Essex; included**—Northern part of Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (McIlvaine Pit), T-51 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine at Ctr., NW1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.2278407, -88.2012605 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402. Possibly former part of South Wilmington Sportsman's Club. Now largely submerged under Braidwood Lake. Sample collected by Tom Beard and GCB.
- Total counts, based on 1,043 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 86 (8.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 15
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Annularia* = 20
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - Plant stems = 17
 - Stems/bark = 11
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 3
 - *Taeniophyllum?* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Totals = 377 (36.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 14
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - *Drevotella* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam per nodule, closed valves) = 18
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam per nodule, spread valves) = 11
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam per nodule) = 134
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams per nodule) = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (not characterized) = 85
 - *Mazonomya* with burrow = 5
 - *Mazonomya* with polychaete = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - “megaclam” (possibly *Schizodus*) = 2

- Unidentified pecten = 2
- Unidentified bivalve = 3
- Gastropod *Euphemites* = 3
- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
- *Cyclus* = 1
- “non-*Cyclus*” = 1
- Arthropod *Thuysanuran* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 4
- Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 2
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
- Polychaete “fish worm” = 6
- Unidentified polychaete = 8
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
- Holothurian = 1
- “fish” eggs = 1
- Coprolites = 25
- Trails = 28
- **Miscellaneous:** Totals = 25 (2.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 11
 - Unidentified nucleus = 14
- **Duds:** Totals = 555 (53.2 % of total)
 - Common duds = 66
 - Gray duds = 256
 - Light gray duds = 90
 - Red brown duds = 38
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 4
 - Weathered duds = 90
 - Septarial duds = 11
- **Rejects:** 892

Locality 194

- **Will-Essex; included**—Northwestern margin of Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (McIlvaine Pit), T-52 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine at NE1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.23059086, -88.20255214 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402. Possibly former northernmost part of South Wilmington Sportsman's Club. Now largely submerged under Braidwood Lake. Sample collected by Beard and GCB.
- **Note:** Township and Range coordinates typed onto locality manifest are different from those on typed locality sheets. Coordinates used here are taken from the manifest.
- Total counts, based on 1,051 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 70 (6.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 8
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 14
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 8
 - Stems/bark = 12
 - Bark = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Plant fragment = 4
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 350 (33.3 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not characterized) = 16
 - Senior blobs = 7
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (not characterized) = 47
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule, closed valves) = 76
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule, spread valves) = 19
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 71
 - *Mazonomya* (to or more clams per nodule) = 2
 - *Mazonomya* with polychaete = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1

- Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 1
- “megaclam” (probably *Schizodus*) = 8
- Clam with burrow = 2
- Unidentified bivalve = 1
- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
- Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
- *Cyclus* = 2
- Insect nymph = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
- *Didontogaster* with *Mazonomya* = 1
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 5
- Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 6
- Unidentified polychaetes = 10
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 3
- Holothurian = 2
- Holothurian with pecten = 1
- Coprolites = 32
- Trails = 16
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 26 (2.4 % of total)
 - Discs = 13
 - Unidentified nucleus = 13
- **Duds:** Total = 595 (56.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 157
 - Gray duds = 319
 - Gray-brown duds = 54
 - Dark gray duds = 6
 - Weathered duds = 36
 - Septarial duds = 23
- **Rejects:** 359

Locality 195

- **Will-Essex; included**—Northwestern margin of Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (McIlvaine Pit), T-53 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine at Ctr., NW1/4, NW1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22963255, -88.2037137 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402. Possibly former northernmost part of South Wilmington Sportsman's Club. Now largely submerged under Braidwood Lake. Sample collected by Tom Beard and GCB.
- Total counts, based on 323 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 18 (5.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 6
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Sphenopteris?* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 89 (27.5 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not characterized) = 1
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (not further characterized) = 27
 - *Mazonomya* (1 clam per nodule) = 27
 - *Mazonomya* (2 or more clams per nodule) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* with trail = 1
 - "megaclam" (probably *Schizodus*) = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Rare arthropod *Kottixerxes* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 7
 - Trails = 11

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (3.0 % of total)
 - Discs = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 206 (63.7 % of total)
 - Common duds = 103
 - Gray duds = 35
 - Gray-brown duds = 16
 - Blue-gray duds = 19
 - Weathered duds = 20
 - Septarial duds = 13
- **Rejects:** 178

Locality 196

- **Will-Essex; included**—Northwestern margin of Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (McIlvaine Pit), T-54 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/12/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine at NE1/4, SW1/4, NW1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22683445, -88.20483725 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402. Possibly former northernmost part of South Wilmington Sportsman's Club. Now partly to largely submerged under Braidwood Lake. Sample collected by Tom Beard and GCB.

- Total counts, based on 739 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 35 (4.7 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 14
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - Macerated plant = 7
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 172 (23.2 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 11
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blob = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (not further categorized) = 56
 - *Mazonomya* with burrow = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 4
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 2
 - Holothurians = 5
 - Coprolites = 27
 - Coprolite with holothurian spicules and gastropods = 1
 - Trails = 53
 - Unidentified animal = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 25 (3.3 % of total)

- Discs = 2
- Unidentified nucleus = 23
- **Duds:** Total = 507 (68.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 96
 - Gray duds = 117
 - Weathered duds = 275
 - Septarial duds = 19
- **Rejects:** 432

Locality 197

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-55 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/15/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22864048, -88.20971705 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Collecting area within Pit 11 but close to the northwest limit of the Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (McIlvaine pit). Collecting area currently partly submerged under Braidwood Lake.

- Total counts, based on 462 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (4.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stem = 3
 - Bark = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 161 (34.8 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 21
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (not further characterized) = 73
 - *Mazonomya* with burrow = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - “megaclam” (probably *Schizodus*) = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 3
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 7
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 3
 - *Balanoglossus?* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Holothurian with *Euphemites* = 1
 - Coprolites = 18
 - Trails = 16
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (2.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 6

- Smears = 1
- Unidentified nucleus = 4
- **Duds:** Total = 270 (58.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 78
 - Gray duds = 129
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 32
 - Weathered duds = 12
 - Septarial duds = 19
- **Rejects:** 258

Locality 199

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, T-57 locality of Tom Beard, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/15/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.22491964, -88.20954884 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 78 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 3 (3.8 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 31 (39.7 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 8
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
 - *Euphemites* with holothurian = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Coprolites = 7
 - Trails = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (6.4 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 39 (50.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 37
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - **Rejects:** 27

Locality 201

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “G”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/02/24.**

- **Description:** Unreclaimed strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11, station “G”) at SW1/4, NE1/4, section 5, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.197840, -88.212364 (GCB); 41.19670495, -88.21220293 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 241 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 22 (9.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 10
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 85 (35.2 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 26
 - Junior blobs = 21
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - *Myalinella* with plant = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - *Paucijaculum* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 9
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 9
 - Trails = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (2.9 % of total)
 - Smears = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 127 (52.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 76
 - Gray-brown duds = 49
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 202

- **Braidwood; included**—Benson Farm section on Mazon River. Combined summary sample manifest of all seven data sheets updated as of 04/02/24.
- **Description:** Classic Francis Creek shale exposure along Mazon River on Russell Benson property at SE1/4, SE1/4, Section 13, T33N, R7E, Coal City 7.5' quadrangle, digital coordinates 41.334281, -88.366572 (GCB); 41.33143535, -88.36558035 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 1860 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1263 (67.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 504
 - *Pecopteris/Annularia* = 3
 - *Pecopteris/Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - *Pecopteris/bark* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 450
 - *Neuropteris rarineuris* = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 59
 - *Calamites* = 14
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 43
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 5
 - Stem/bark = 88
 - Macerated plant = 26
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 17
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 5
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - *Stigmarioides* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 3
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - Neuropterid-Odontopterid ferns = 10
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Sphenophylloides* = 1
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - “fiddle head fern” = 1
 - *Crossotheca* = 1
 - Seed case = 2
 - Unidentifiable cones = 4
 - Branch tuft = 4
 - Unidentified plant = 6
 - **Animals:** total = 188 (10.1% of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Tiny clam = 1
 - *Euproops danae* = 10

- *Acanthotelson* = 9
- *Palaeocaris* = 6
- Undescribed syncarid shrimp = 1
- Pygocephalomorph shrimp = 1
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 3
- Unidentified shrimp = 1
- *Gerarus* (insect) = 1
- Odonate nymph (insect) holotype = 1
- Nymph (insect) with bristlecone plant = 1
- Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
- Vertebrate? = 1
- Xenacanth tooth = 1
- *Ctenodus* (lungfish) scale = 2
- *Palaeoxyris* egg capsules = 3
- Coprolites = 144
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (0.5% of total)
 - Incognitum (significant unknown form) = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
- **Duds:** Total = 398 (21.3% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 193
 - Light brown duds = 13
 - Blue-gray duds = 35
 - Gray duds = 70
 - Light gray duds = 64
 - Dark gray duds = 16
 - Pyritic duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 3
 - Weathered duds = 2

Locality 203

- **Braidwood; included**—Carr’s Farm section on Mazon River, Grundy County, Illinois. Combined summary sample manifest of two data sheets updated as of 05/08/24.

- **Description:** Francis Creek shale and siltstone exposures along Mazon River, accessed via dead-end Oxbow Road, near Carr’s Farm property at SE1/4, NW1/4, section 30, T33N, R8E, on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.308915, -88.356573 (GCB); 41.30986613, -88.35540803 (ADM).

- Total counts, based on 158 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 109 (68.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 71
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 14
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 16 (10.1% of total)
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp: 1 (coll. By S. Awramik)
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Coprolites = 14
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (2.5% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 29 (18.3% of total)
 - Common duds = 5
 - Gray-brown duds = 24

Locality 205

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Bank of Mazon River north of White Tie Road.**
Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/04/24.

- **Description:** Northwest-facing exposure of Francis Creek Shale yielding in-situ Essex animal-bearing concretions at W1/2, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 29, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.309225, -88.338222 (GCB); 41.31024936, -88.33751583 (ADM). Thin, concretion-rich level spatially restricted to 50'-wide lateral area on shale bank. Side creek entering Mazon River north of White Tie Road has now been reengineered to new position, largely destroying the original nodule-bearing exposure, which was precisely at the present side channel confluence with Mazon River. Property of the Rainbow Council Boy Scout Reservation, access restricted.

- Total counts, based on 299 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 30 (10% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Plant stem = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - Unidentified plant = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 154 (51.5% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 62
 - Junior blobs = 27
 - Indeterminate blobs = 35
 - Multiple blobs = 10
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Probable polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran (*Coprinoscolex*) = 12
 - Coprolites = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (4.3% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 13
 - **Duds:** Total = 102 (34.1% of total)
 - Gray to light gray duds = 60
 - Gray-brown duds = 41
 - Dark gray duds = 1

Locality 206

- **Will-Essex; included—Wilmington Coal Mining Corp, Wilmington No. 2 Mine (“McIlvaine Mine”, Station “H”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/02/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp, Wilmington No. 2 Mine (McIlvaine Mine (“station H”) at NW1/4, SE1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.227007, -88.195327 (GCB); 41.22246253, -88.19388178 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402.
- Total counts, based on 404 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 35 (8.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Stems/bark = 13
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - Fertile fern (*Crossotheca?*) = 1
 - Macerated plant = 2
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 55 (13.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 5
 - Junior blobs = 7
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - Blob with coprolite = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= “*Edmondia*”) = 12
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Unidentified pecten = 1
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Holothurians = 3
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails = 11
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 12 (2.9 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Pyrite disc = 1

- Smears = 6
- Unidentified nucleus = 4
- **Duds:** Total = 302 (74.7 % of total)
 - Common duds = 253
 - Gray-brown duds = 48
 - Septarial duds = 1
- **Rejects:** 92

Locality 207

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “I”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/12/24.**
- **Description:** Reclaimed (levelled) strip mine terrain along east edge of abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) bordering north end of the McIlvain Club property and bordering present-day Lake Braidwood (cooling pond). This site is at SW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.221255, -88.194973 (GCB); 41.21781479, -88.19493468 (ADM). Site freshly bull dozed at time of sampling. Notable for abundance of holothurians.
- Total counts, based on 1,119 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 26 (2.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - Plant stems = 10
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 622 (55.5 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 15
 - Junior blobs = 26
 - Indeterminate blobs = 13
 - *Mazonomya* = 11
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 8
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptocolex* = 5
 - Indeterminate polychaetes = 5
 - “worm impression” = 1
 - Acorn worm *Balanoglossus* = 3
 - Holothurians = 100
 - Probable holothurians = 4
 - *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1

- Rhizomorph fish = 1
- Coprolites = 10
- Trails = 406
- *Diplocraterion* = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 38 (3.3 % of total)
 - “discs” = 6
 - “ghosts” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 27
 - Pelletal nodule = 1
 - Incognitum = 3
- **Duds:** Total = 433 (38.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 280
 - Gray duds = 147
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects:** 631

Locality 208

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11, Station “j”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/03/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11, “station j” at NE1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.224419, -88.217902 (GCB); 41.22299078, -88.21660935 (ADM). Location currently an island in Braidwood Lake. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 952 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 11 (1.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Stems/bark = 3
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 372 (39.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 31
 - Junior blobs = 6
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - “eyed” blobs = 5
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 53
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 4
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 3
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw? = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 11
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 9
 - Coprolites = 14
 - Trails = 222
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 36 (3.7 % of total)
 - Discs = 18
 - Ghosts = 2
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 15
 - **Duds:** Total = 533 (55.9 % of total)
 - Common duds = 348

- Gray duds = 152
- Pyrite-cored duds = 1
- Septarial duds = 32
- **Rejects:** 226

Locality 209

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “K”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/03/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11, sampling station “K”) at SE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.228615, -88.218159 (GCB); 41.22483391, -88.21668703. Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 1,249 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 34 (2.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 9
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stems = 11
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - Macerated plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 356 (28.5 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 60
 - Junior blobs = 23
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 48
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams per nodule) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 4
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 8
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 10
 - Coprolites = 17
 - Trails = 164
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 43 (3.4 % of total)
 - Discs = 16
 - Spots = 1

- Unidentified nucleus = 26
- **Duds:** Total = 816 (65.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 596
 - Gray-brown duds = 127
 - Gray duds = 69
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Pyrite cored duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 17
- **Rejects:** 173

Locality 210

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “L”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/03/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11, sampling station “L”) at SW1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.224743, -88.220820 (GCB); 41.2248004, -88.219063. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 457 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (4.3 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 6
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Asolanus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 202 (44.2 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 79
 - Junior blobs = 19
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - “eyed” blobs = 8
 - *Mazonomya* (not characterized) = 23
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule) = 8
 - *Myalinella* preserved as crushed cluster = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 4
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 4
 - Ratworm polychaete = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurian = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 32
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (2.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 7
 - Unidentified nucleus = 6

- **Duds:** Total = 222 (48.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 159
 - Gray duds = 26
 - Weathered duds = 30
 - Septaial duds = 7
- **Rejects:** 44

Locality 211

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station Pond B, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/10/24.**
- **Description:** Unreclaimed strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) bordering south side of West Road in northwest corner of Ponderosa Sportsman’s Club at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 41.186293, -88.227061 (GCB); 41.18570675, -88.2261134 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 2,189 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 60 (2.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 13
 - *Neuropteris* = 9
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Multiple *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stem = 7
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Thallites* = 2
 - Lycopd scale = 1
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,229 (56.1 % of total)
 - *Essexella* undivided category = 91
 - Senior blobs = 580
 - Junior blobs = 187
 - Indeterminate blobs = 162
 - “eyed” blob = 1
 - All blobs (*Essexella*) total = 1021
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - *Essexella* with attached *Strobeus* = 2
 - *Strobeus* = 3
 - *Mazonomya* = 1
 - “toothed scallop” = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 26
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 2

- Horseshoe crab = *Palaeolimulus* = 1
- *Cyclus* = 1
- Crustacean exuvia = 4
- Gooseneck barnacle *Praeilepis* = 1
- Insect (holotype?) = 1
- Polychaete Simple jaw = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 1
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 26
- Holothurian = 1
- *Tullimonstrum* = 2
- *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
- Coprolites = 104
- Trails/traces = 12
- *Diplocraterion* = 3
- Pellet burrow slabs = 8
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 37 (1.6 % of total)
 - “discs” = 12
 - “gas vent tubes” = 6
 - Unidentified nucleus = 18
 - Incognitum = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 863 (39.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 852
 - Gray-brown duds = 9
 - Septarial duds = 2
- **Rejects:** 147

Locality 212

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, station “M” at north end of “insect hills” in Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/05/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit Eleven (sampling station “M” at the north end of “insect hills”) at Ctr, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle in Will County, northwest of Essex, Illinois at estimated digital coordinates 41.214213, -88.213283 (GCB); 41.21296995, -88.2103624 (ADM). Collecting area is unmodified strip mine terrain on island surrounded by Lake Braidwood. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 733 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 69 (9.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 15
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 5
 - Plant stems = 11
 - Bark = 6
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 6
 - Lycopod bark = 2
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - **Animals:** Total = 226 (30.8 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 20
 - Senior blobs = 31
 - Junior blobs = 28
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - Multiple blobs = 3
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (not characterized) = 13
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, spread valves) = 14
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, closed valves) = 1
 - *Myalinella* (= “*Septimyalina*”) = 5
 - Crushed *Myalinella* cluster = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 6
 - Clam *Schizodus* = 1
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 1
 - Coleoid cephalopod *Jeletskia* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2

- Unidentified shrimp = 1
- *Cyclus* = 1
- Insect = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 3
- Unidentified polychaetes = 4
- Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 11
- Holothurians = 14
- Fish Scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Coprolites = 18
- Trails = 27
- Unidentified animal = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 32 (4.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 13
 - Ghosts-smears = 8
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
- **Duds:** Total = 406 (55.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 133
 - Gray duds = 3
 - Gray-brown duds = 114
 - Pyrite cored duds = 149
 - Septarial duds = 7
- **Rejects:** 103

Locality 213

- **Will-Essex; included—Wilmington Coal Mining Corp, Wilmington No. 2 Mine (“McIlvaine Mine”, Station “N”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/05/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp, Wilmington No. 2 Mine (McIlvaine Mine (“station N”) at SE1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.217545, -88.202277 (GCB); 41.21765324, -88.20216839 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402. Area in South Wilmington Sportman’s Club.

- Total counts, based on 140 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 5 (3.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stem = 2
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 72 (51.4 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not characterized) = 2
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= “*Edmondia*”; one clam per nodule) = 3
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - *Balanoglossus* = 1
 - Holothurians = 3
 - Trails = 60
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 62 (44.2 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 43
 - Dark gray duds = 4
 - Pyrite cored duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - Weathered duds = 11
 - **Rejects:** 133

Locality 214

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, station “O”.** Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/09/24.
- **Description:** Unreclaimed spoil piles in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit Eleven (sampling station “O”) at W1/2, SE1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 5, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle in Kankakee County, west of Essex, Illinois. Area is north of east-west West Road at estimated digital coordinates 41.190628, -88.214498 (GCB); 41.18866406, -88.21077228 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 2,351 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 148 (6.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 14
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Plant stem = 3
 - Bark = 4
 - Incognitum plant = 4
 - Macerated plants = 108
 - **Animals:** Total = 835 (35.5% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 395
 - Junior blobs = 206
 - Indeterminate blobs = 57
 - “micro-blobs” = 4
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Box jellies *Anthracomедusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* = 4
 - *Myalinella* = 10
 - *Dunbarella?* = 1
 - *Strobeus* = 4
 - *Belotelson* (shelled) = 10
 - *Belotelson* (molted) = 8
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 2
 - Phyllocarid arthropod *Dithyrocaris* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Palaeolimulus* = 1
 - Gooseneck barnacle *Praeepis* = 1
 - Gooseneck barnacle *Praeepis* on *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1

- Polychaete *Hystricula* (simple jaw) = 2
- Unidentified polychaetes = 6
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 3
- Holothurian = 2
- *Tullimonstrum* = 7
- *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 3
- *Gilpichthys* (another agnathan) = 1
- Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
- Fish scale = 1
- Coprolites = 87
- Trails/traces = 8
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 60 (2.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 21
 - Unidentified nucleus = 39
- **Duds:** Total = 1,308 (55.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 709
 - Gray-brown duds = 345
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 28
 - Blue-gray duds = 30
 - Septarial duds = 206
- **Rejects:** 182

Locality 215

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station A”), Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/15/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station A”) at NW1/4, SE1/4, section 31, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.296009, -88.235520 (GCB); 41.29432618, -88.23531108 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 559 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 281 (50.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 77
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 14
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 33
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 9
 - Plant stems = 79
 - Bark = 3
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 4
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 40
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 39 (6.9 % of total)
 - Senior blob? = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 4
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2
 - Bivalve cluster = 2
 - Unidentified bivalves = 5
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 2
 - “non-*Cyclus*” = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - *Spirorbis* with spore case = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 16
 - Trails = 2

- *Rhizocorallium* = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (1.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
- **Duds:** Total = 230 (41.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 70
 - Gray-brown duds = 4
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 13
- **Separate count of duds from split concretion sample (total = 140):**
 - Gray-brown duds = 40
 - Flinty gray duds = 36
 - Blue-gray duds = 47
 - Discs = 2
 - Sandy duds = 6
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Disseminated pyrite = 1
 - Pyrite-filled septaria = 1
 - Septarial duds = 6

Locality 216

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station C”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station C”) at NW1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 27, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.313816, -88.299316 (GCB); 41.311923, -88.29929623 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 516 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 253 (49.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 96
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 34
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 39
 - Bark = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Cones = 2
 - Macerated plants = 53
 - Unidentified plants = 11
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (0.3 % of total)
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - Trace/trail = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 259 (50.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 144
 - Split duds (total = 115):
 - Sandy, gray-brown duds = 96
 - Blue-gray duds = 19

Locality 217

- **Braidwood; included—Abandoned strip mine at east edge of Morris, Illinois.**
Combined summary sample manifest of all six data sheets updated as of 04/05/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal Company strip mine (collecting “station “B”) at east edge of Morris, Illinois at NW1/4, NE1/4, NW1/4, section 3, T33N, R7E near north edge of the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle, digital coordinates 41.371768, -88.415588 (GCB); 41.37046668, -88.41461408 (ADM). This area, on McIlvaine property, is adjacent to, and east of, residual east-facing mine headwall section notable for abundant plants and nonmarine clams.
- Total counts, based on 3,021 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1335 (44.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 221
 - *Neuropteris* = 223
 - *Annularia* = 35
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 317
 - Plant stems = 104
 - Bark = 2
 - Lycopod underbark = 2
 - Scale tree bark = 1
 - *Calamites* = 12
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 22
 - Macerated plants = 225
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 48
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 36
 - *Lepidodendron* = 3
 - Lycopod stem = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 4
 - “thorn” = 1
 - *Dicranophyllum* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Spores in fructification = 3
 - Seed = 4
 - Unidentified neuropterid fern = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 63
 - **Animals:** Total = 240 (7.9% of total)
 - Bivalvia: Total = 212
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 138 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Nonmarine clam clusters = 12
 - Unidentified bivalves = 62
 - *Euproops* = 4

- *Acanthotelson* = 5
- *Palaeocaris* = 5
- Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 2
- Ostracodes = 1
- Millepede = 1
- Insect = 1
- Insect? = 1
- *Ctenodus* lungfish scale = 2
- Xenacanth tooth = 1
- Fish (Iniopterygian?) = 1
- *Palaeoxyris* = 2
- Coprolites = 95
- Trail/trace = 1
- Nonmarine clam/trail/trace = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 49 (1.6% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 49
- **Duds:** Total = 1302 (43% of total)
 - Common duds = 762
 - Gray-brown duds = 167
 - Gray duds = 7
 - Dark gray duds = 267
 - Pyritic duds = 40
 - Septarial duds = 43
 - Sandy duds = 10
 - Solid pyritic concretions = 6

Locality 218

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station C”) east of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/18/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station C”) at SW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 34, T34N, R7E on the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.382205, -88.411757 (GCB); 41.3805253, -88.41120869 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.
- Total counts, based on 301 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 151 (50.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 55
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 21
 - Plant stems = 32
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 21
 - Unidentified plants = 10
 - **Animals:** Total = 33 (10.9% of total)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Millepede *Euphoberia* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 4
 - Cartilage = 1
 - Coprolites = 25
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (2.3% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 110 (36.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 68
 - Gray-brown duds = 14
 - Dark gray duds = 15
 - Pyritic duds = 13

Locality 219

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris no. 2 strip mine (“station D”) east of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/18/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris no. 2 strip mine (“station D”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 34, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.377501, -88.410118 (GCB); 41.37773295, -88.41477725 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.
- Total counts, based on 41 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 16 (39.0% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Bark = 2
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (4.8% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Coprolites = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 23 (56.0% of total)
 - Dark gray duds = 15
 - Pyritic duds = 8

Locality 220

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris no. 2 strip mine, east of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/18/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris no. 2 strip mine at NE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 34, T34N, R7E at the border of the Morris and Lisbon 7.5' quadrangles at digital coordinates 41.376407, -88.411117 (GCB); 41.37505395, -88.41352015 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.
- Total counts, based on 1,639 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 720 (43.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 205
 - *Neuropteris* = 101
 - Compound Neuropterid? fern = 1
 - *Annularia* = 32
 - *Calamites* = 14
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 191
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 14
 - Plant stems = 67
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 4
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 6
 - Seeds = 2
 - Cones = 5
 - Scale stem = 2
 - *Dicranophyllum* = 3
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - “thallus plant” = 1
 - Spores = 1
 - *Stigmarioides* = 1
 - Lycopod stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 46
 - Unidentified plants = 18
 - **Animals:** Total = 189 (11.5% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 16 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Nonmarine bivalve clusters = 3
 - Unidentified bivalves = 20
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 4
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimps = 3
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 2

- Millepede *Acantherpestes?* = 1
- Unidentified millepedes = 2
- *Palaeoxyris* = 5
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 2
- Coprolites = 130
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 27 (1.6% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 27
- **Duds:** Total = 703 (42.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 531
 - Gray duds = 6
 - Dark gray duds = 102
 - Pyritic duds = 41
 - Septarial duds = 17
 - Weathered duds = 6

Locality 221

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes, station “D”). Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 07/01/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 10, Dresden Lakes station “D”) at SE1/4, SW1/4, section 14, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.332993, -88.279930 (GCB); 41.33323008, -88.2792944 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 1,530 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 457 (29.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 122
 - *Neuropteris* = 12
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 107
 - Plant stems = 92
 - Bark = 3
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - Seeds = 3
 - Cone = 2
 - Fructification = 2
 - “roach egg sac” = 2
 - Macerated plants = 76
 - Unidentified plants = 12
 - **Animals:** Total = 118 (7.7 % of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 11 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 2
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Millepede (*Acantherpestes*) = 1
 - Coprolites = 102
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 27 (1.7 % of total)
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 26
 - **Duds:** Total = 928 (60.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 474
 - Gray duds = 5

- Dark gray duds = 287
- Pyritic duds = 159
- Septarial duds = 3

Locality 222

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 9, “station A”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/15/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 9 strip mine (“station A”) at SE1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 27, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.311800, -88.287270 (GCB); 41.31035473, -88.28724004 (ADM). Property is in the Fireman’s Club. Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 1,395 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 493 (35.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 94
 - *Neuropteris* = 33
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 51
 - *Calamites* = 18
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 101
 - Plant stems = 126
 - Bark = 4
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 5
 - *Sphenopteris?* = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Lycopod stem = 1
 - “Roach egg sac” = 2
 - Macerated plants = 31
 - Unidentified plants = 14
 - **Animals:** Total = 164 (11.7 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 39
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Bivalve *Dunbarella* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 4
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (probably *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1

- Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
- *Cyclus* = 3
- Millepedes = 2
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 9
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
- *Spirorbis* with bark = 1
- Unidentified polychaetes = 9
- Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
- *Ilyodes* = 1
- Coprolites = 70
- Trails = 11
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 23 (1.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Ghosts-smears = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 18
- **Duds:** Total = 715 (51.2 % of total)
 - Common duds = 207
 - Gray duds = 25
 - Gray-brown duds = 201
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Blue-gray duds = 63
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 27
 - Septarial duds = 11
- **Split duds in sample** (summed categories = 178):
 - Light gray duds = 16
 - Gray, flinty duds = 145
 - Dark gray flinty = 6
 - Septarial duds = 10
 - Disc = 1

Locality 223

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 9, “station B”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/16/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 9 strip mine (“station B”) on the Fireman’s Club property at NE1/4, SE1/4, section 26, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.308720, -88.270546 (GCB); 41.308027, -88.26910175 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 328 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 196 (59.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 69
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 18
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 40
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 8
 - *Asterophyllites* = 4
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - Cones = 2
 - Macerated plants = 28
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 12 (3.6 % of total)
 - Nonmarine clam = 1 (probably *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (1.2 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 116 (35.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 49
 - Gray-brown duds = 34
 - Blue-gray duds = 17
 - Pyritic duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 9
 - Pelletal nodule = 1

Locality 224

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 9, “station C”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 07/16/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 9 strip mine (“station C”) on the Fireman’s Club property at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 23, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.322763, -88.279079 (GCB); 41.32236468, -88.2791029 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 2,861 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1,834 (64.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 415
 - *Neuropteris* = 27
 - “Compound” *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 71
 - *Annularia* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 44
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 260
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 6
 - Plant stems = 229
 - Bark = 3
 - *Alethopteris* = 9
 - *Cyclopteris* = 10
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 17
 - *Sphenopyllum* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 5
 - *Equisetites* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - “rose bush” = 1
 - Seeds = 8
 - Macerated plants = 668
 - Unidentified plants = 52
 - **Animals:** Total = 105 (3.6 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 8 (probably *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 2
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimps = 5
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 2
 - Millepedes = 2
 - Millepede (*Xyliolus*) = 1
 - Unidentified arthropod = 1

- *Palaeoxyris* = 2
- Coprolites = 77
- Unidentified animals = 5
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 29 (1.0 % of total)
 - Pellets = 1
 - Discs = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 25
- **Duds:** Total = 893 (31.2 % of total)
 - Common duds = 461
 - Gray-brown duds = 213
 - Dark gray-black duds = 188
 - Sandy duds = 7
 - Septarial duds = 24

Locality 225

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station A”), Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/16/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station A”) on CECO Club property at NE1/4, SW1/4, section 24, T33N, R9E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.322425, -88.259976 (GCB); 41.32277155, -88.25989795 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 32 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 22 (68.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 3 (9.3 % of total)
 - Incognitum animal = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (3.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 6 (18.7 % of total)
 - Common duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 226

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station F”) east of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/19/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station F”) at SE1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 34, T34N, R7E near the south edge of the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.377374, -88.404033 (GCB); 41.37708641, -88.40390444 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.

- Total counts, based on 50 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 14 (28% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 5
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 3 (6.0% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve? = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (4.0% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 31 (62.0% of total)
 - Dark gray duds = 16
 - Pyrite core duds = 14
 - Sandy duds = 1

Locality 227

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company, Morris no. 2 strip mine (“Black’s Farm locality”), northeast of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from ten data sheets updated as of 05/15/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company, Morris no. 2 Strip Mine (“Black’s Farm locality”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 35, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.386035, -88.391676 (GCB); 41.38635746, -88.39197668 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625. This area yielded abundant large concretions, somewhat in the manner of the renown “pits one and six areas” visited by George Langford in the 1940s.

- Total counts, based on 2,287 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1,345 (58.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 312
 - *Neuropteris* = 289
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Annularia* = 157
 - *Annularia* with *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 49
 - *Calamites* with *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 235
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* with seed = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 30
 - Plant stems = 58
 - Bark = 8
 - *Asterophyllites* = 22
 - *Alethopteris* = 13
 - *Cyclopteris* = 11
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 5
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 6
 - *Crossotheca* = 1
 - Fructifications = 4
 - Scale twigs = 2
 - Unopened foliage-cone = 1
 - *Dicranophyllum* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Stigmarioides?* = 1
 - *Cordaicarpus* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Thallites* (Thallus plant) = 1
 - Seeds = 8
 - Seed *Trigonocarpus* = 1

- Cordaitid seeds = 2
- Cones = 7
- Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
- Cone *Calamostachys* = 1
- Cone? = 1
- Macerated plants = 53
- Incognitum plants = 4
- Unidentified plants = 50
- **Animals:** Total = 216 (9.4% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 9 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 3
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 2
 - Ostrocods = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 6
 - Millepede = 1
 - Centipede = 1
 - Insects = 3
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 4
 - Lungfish scales *Ctenodus* = 2
 - Coprolites = 183
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 21 (0.9% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 20
- **Duds:** Total = 705 (30.8% of total)
 - Common duds = 587
 - Dark gray duds = 86
 - Pyritic duds = 20
 - Septarial duds = 12

Locality 228

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris Strip Mine, northeast of Morris Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/15/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris Strip Mine at NE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 35, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.386354, -88.384344 (GCB); 41.38559108, -88.38594073 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2391.
- Total counts, based on 1,483 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 571 (38.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 161
 - *Neuropteris* = 32
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 55
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 72
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 18
 - Plant stems = 107
 - Bark = 8
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 17
 - *Lepidodendron* = 7
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Allethopteris* = 1
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 6
 - *Odontopteris?* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 3
 - Fructification = 1
 - Branch tuft = 6
 - Seeds = 8
 - Cone scale with spores = 1
 - Macerated plants = 30
 - Unidentified plants = 23
 - **Animals:** Total = 175 (11.8% of total)
 - *Myalinella?* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 9 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 7
 - Crushed bivalve cluster = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 2
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 10
 - *Cyzicus* = 1

- *Palaeoxyris* = 12
- Coprolites = 132
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 34 (2.2% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 34
- **Duds:** Total = 703 (47.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 346
 - Gray-brown duds = 45
 - Gray duds = 22
 - Dark gray duds = 224
 - Pyritic duds = 54
 - Septarial duds = 12
- **Rejects:** 92

Locality 229

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 9, “station D”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/16/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 9 strip mine (“station D”), property is in the Fireman’s Club, at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 23, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.318933, -88.270247 (GCB); 41.3187419, -88.27905138 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 421 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 284 (67.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 48
 - *Neuropteris* = 10
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 98
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - Plant stems = 29
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 5
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* with *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - Odontopterid ferns? = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Probable seeds = 2
 - Spore cases = 2
 - Macerated plants = 53
 - Unidentified plants = 10
 - **Animals:** Total = 22 (5.2 % of total)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Xenocanth shark tooth = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 2
 - Coprolites = 17
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (1.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 110 (26.1 % of total)

- Common duds = 39
- Gray-brown duds = 27
- Dark gray duds = 17
- Blue-gray duds = 8
- Septarial duds = 19

Locality 230

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 9, “station E”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/16/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 9 strip mine (“station E”), property is in the Fireman’s Club and borders southwest end of linear Dresden Lakes strip pit (Pit 10), at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 22, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.329593, -88.288684 (GCB); 41.32937058, -88.28882598 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 1,437 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1,038 (72.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 128
 - *Neuropteris* = 9
 - *Annularia* = 51
 - *Calamites* = 46
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 102
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 6
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Plant stems = 116
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 8
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 4
 - *Ulodendron* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 538
 - Unidentified plants = 16
 - **Animals:** Total = 79 (5.4 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (probably *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Arthropod *Cyzicus* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 2
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Shark cartilage? = 1

- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 2
- Palaeoniscoid fish = 1* (collected and kept by Tom Testa)
- Coprolites = 66
- Trail = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 26 (1.8 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 26
- **Duds:** Total = 294 (20.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 77
 - Gray-brown duds = 144
 - Blue-gray duds = 25
 - Dark gray duds = 35
 - Pyritic duds = 11
 - Sandy duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 231

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 9, “station F”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/17/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 9 strip mine (“station F”), property is in the Fireman’s Club, at SE1/4, NE1/4, section 23, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.325655, -88.270219 (GCB); 41.326229, -88.26954553 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 1,167 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 901 (77.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 299
 - *Neuropteris* = 23
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - “compound” *Neuropteris* = 11
 - *Annularia* = 35
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 166
 - Plant stems = 77
 - Stems/bark = 31
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 8
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - “patterned” stems = 2
 - Cones = 2
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Odontopterid fern? = 1
 - Macerated plants = 206
 - Incognitum plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 16
 - **Animals:** Total = 68 (5.8 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 2
 - Millepede *Xylioulus* = 1
 - Lungfish scales *Ctenodus* = 2

- Fish scale (new species) = 1
- Coprolites = 59
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.4 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 193 (16.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 178
 - Gray-brown duds = 9
 - Septarial duds = 6
- **Rejects:** 34

Locality 232

- **Will-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 9, “station G”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from six data sheets updated as of 07/17/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 9 strip mine (“station G”), property is in the Fireman’s Club, at Ctr., SE1/4, section 22, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.319745, -88.290266 (GCB); 41.32028005, -88.29109285 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 1,026 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 291 (28.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 35
 - *Neuropteris* = 19
 - *Annularia* = 22
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 112
 - Plant stems = 39
 - Stems/bark = 8
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Odontopterid fern? = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Fructification = 1
 - Seed = 2
 - Macerated plants = 21
 - Unidentified plants = 14
 - **Animals:** Total = 158 (15.3 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 39
 - Probable *Essexella* = 22
 - Indeterminate blobs = 13
 - *Aviculopecten* = 3
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 10 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - *Myalinella* with *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 8
 - Syncarid shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 3
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 6

- Millepede *Euphoberia* = 1
- Arachnids = 2
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 3
- Probable oligochaete = 1
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Coprolites = 35
- Trails = 6
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 43 (4.1 % of total)
 - Incognitum organisms = 2
 - Discs = 8
 - Bleichen = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 31
- **Duds:** Total = 534 (52.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 303
 - Dark gray duds = 135
 - Pyritic duds = 43
 - Septarial duds = 53

Locality 233

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND C”), west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/21/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND C”) at ctr., SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.177947, -88.228987 (GCB); 41.17666345, -88.2282341 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 2,422 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 241 (9.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 109
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 32
 - *Calamites* = 12
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 6
 - Plant stems = 48
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - *Thallites* = 1
 - “roach egg sac” = 1
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total animal count (with blobs) = 1,659 (68.4 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 1
 - Senior blobs = 642
 - Junior blobs = 618
 - Indeterminate blobs = 113
 - “odd” blobs = 15
 - Multiple blobs = 7
 - Total blob count = 1,396
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Box jellies *Anthracomedusa* = 3
 - Jellyfish *Reticulomedusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* = 32
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 5
 - *Myalinella* = 7
 - Multiple *Myalinella* = 1

- *Aviculopecten* = 1
- Bivalve *Dunbarella* = 1
- Bivalve *Schizodus* = 1
- “ribbed clam” = 1
- Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
- Gastropod *Strobeus* = 10
- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 53
- Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 4
- Syncarid shrimp = 1
- *Cyclus* = 2
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites?* = 1
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 5
- Polychaete Baby Tooth = 1
- Probable polychaete = 1
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
- *Tullimonstrum* = 17
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 6
- Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
- *Acanthodes* spine = 1
- Coprolites = 75
- Pellet burrows = 2
- Trails-ghosts = 25
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 22 (0.9 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 22
- **Duds:** Total = 500 (20.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 500
- **Note:**
 - Lungfish and polychaete *Pieckonia*, collected by others in group are not included in the above list.

Locality 234

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northeastern Illinois Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station C”, Morris landfill), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/17/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northeastern Illinois Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station C”), Morris landfill at NE1/4, section 3, T33N, R7E on the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.371129, -88.407161 (GCB); 41.36879555, -88.40733565 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2391.
- Total counts, based on 453 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 142 (31.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 32
 - *Neuropteris* = 13
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 26
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 19
 - Spore case with enclosed spores = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - Lycopod stem = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Cones (three types) = 3
 - Macerated plants = 21
 - Unidentified plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 50 (11% of total)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 4
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 3
 - Unidentified arthropod = 2
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 2
 - Xenocanth shark tooth = 1
 - Coprolites = 37
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (1.5% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 254 (56.0% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 3

- Dark gray duds = 192
- Pyritic duds = 42
- Weathered duds = 13
- Septarial duds = 4

Locality 235

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station C”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station C”) at W1/2, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle north of White Tie Road at digital coordinates 41.311490, -88.333068 (GCB); 41.3094546, -88.33271235 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 527 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 95 (18.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 28
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 32
 - Plant stems = 15
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 13
 - **Animals:** Total = 27 (5.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 2
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 4
 - Coprolites = 9
 - Traces/trails = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 14 (2.6 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 14
 - **Duds:** Total = 391 (74.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 381
 - Septarial duds = 10

Locality 236

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station D”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/10/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station D”) at SW1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle north of (across mine lake) from White Tie Road at digital coordinates 41.309435, -88.328792 (GCB); 41.30956528, -88.32793305 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 1,493 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 586 (39.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 142
 - *Neuropteris* = 98
 - *Annularia* = 21
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - *Lepidohylloides* = 161
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 13
 - Plant stem = 64
 - Bark = 4
 - *Lepidodendron* = 4
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 4
 - *Sigillaria* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 6
 - Fiddle head fern = 1
 - Unidentified fern = 2
 - Cone = 2
 - Cone base = 1
 - Macerated plants = 35
 - Unidentified plants = 11
 - **Animals:** Total = 81 (5.4 % of total)
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Isopod *Hesslerella* = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 3
 - Coprolites = 67
 - Traces/trails = 3

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 14 (0.9 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 12
 - Botryoidal mineral = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 812 (54.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 647
 - Gray-brown duds = 123
 - Blue-gray duds = 30
 - Pyritic duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 11
- **Rejects:** 189

Locality 237

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station E”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station E”) at Ctr, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 29, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle north of White Tie Road at digital coordinates 41.310731, -88.335863 (GCB); 41.31027593, -88.33632015 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 755 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 135 (17.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 13
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 7
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 75
 - Plant stems = 10
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 9
 - Unidentified plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 65 (8.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 13
 - Indeterminate blobs = 16
 - Faulted blob = 1
 - Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - *Cyzicus* = 2
 - Arachnid = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 6
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Fish scale = 1
 - Coprolites = 7
 - Trails = 3
 - Pelletal trail = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 18 (2.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 18
 - **Duds:** Total = 537 (71.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 494
 - Gray-brown duds = 39
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Pyritic duds = 2

Locality 238

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station D”), northeast of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/17/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station D”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, NW1/4, section 35 on the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.381791, -88.395388 (GCB); 41.38259435, -88.3991536 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2391.
- Total counts, based on 400 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 130 (32.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 34
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 6
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 30
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 30
 - Bark = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - Seed = 1
 - Seed *Trigonocarpus?* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - “fern fiddle” = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Lycopod branch = 1
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - Indeterminate plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 29 (7.2% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid? shrimp = 1
 - Millepede = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Coprolites = 25
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.5% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 239 (59.7% of total)
 - Common duds = 76
 - Gray duds = 3
 - Dark gray duds = 82
 - Pyritic duds = 71
 - Septarial duds = 1
 - Weathered duds = 6

Locality 239

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station E”) northeast of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/17/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station E”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 35, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.379435, -88.400730 (GCB); 41.37894041, -88.40151473 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2391. Mine area appears to have been extensively reclaimed/covered over.
- Total counts, based on 932 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 347 (37.2% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 145
 - *Neuropteris* = 69
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 23
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Plant stems = 49
 - Bark = 12
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Unidentified fern = 1
 - Macerated plants = 21
 - Unidentified plant = 13
 - **Animals:** Total = 124 (13.3% of total)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 2
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 4
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - *Spirorbis* in coprolite = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Acanthodian spine = 1
 - Coprolites = 109
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 32 (3.4% of total)
 - “discs” = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 29
 - **Duds:** Total = 429 (46.0% of total)
 - Common duds = 201

- Gray duds = 39
- Dark gray duds = 30
- Blue-gray duds = 31
- Pyritic duds = 110
- Septarial duds = 18
- **Rejects:** 16

Locality 240

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station F”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/11/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station F”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.315393, -88.332282 (GCB); 41.3148824, -88.33288313 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 115 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 42 (36.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 18
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 11
 - Plant stems = 5
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 3 (2.6 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 70 (60.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 70
 - **Rejects:** 32

Locality 241

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station G”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/11/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station G”) at SE1/4, SW1/4, section 20, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.317794, -88.335435 (GCB); 41.31753328, -88.33652418 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 208 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 48 (23 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 8
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 15
 - Plant stems = 19
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 4 (1.9 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.9 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 154 (74.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 154

Locality 242

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Station “P” at south end of the “insect hills”, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/17/24.**
- **Description:** Partly modified strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.209807, -88.215775 (GCB); 41.20840979, -88.21135383 (ADM). Area currently appears to be an island in Lake Braidwood.
- Total counts, based on 473 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 49 (10.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 10
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 9
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - “thallus plant” = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 13
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 238 (50.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 82
 - Junior blobs = 74
 - Indeterminate blobs = 26
 - Multiple blobs = 13
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 4
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Insect (cockroach) = 1* collected by Larry Osterberger
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 3
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 7
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1

- Palaeoniscoid = 1* collected by amateur associate Larry Osterberger
- Coprolites = 10
- Trails = 3
- Unidentified animals = 5
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (4.2 % of total)
 - Discs = 11
 - Smears = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
- **Duds:** Total = 166 (35.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 79
 - Light gray duds = 74
 - Septarial duds = 13

Locality 246

- **No assignment; excluded**—Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris Strip Mine (northeastern-most sampled area, northeast of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet as of 05/16/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris Strip Mine (formerly listed as “W. Ets strip mine” on earlier Illinois mined-out directory) at SW1/4, section 25, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.393066, -88.379764 (GCB); 41.39116655, -88.3788029 (ADM). Current Mine directory number = 2391.
- Total counts, based on 100 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 4
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 8
 - Burrowed sideritic concretions = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 88
 - Gray-brown duds = 88
 - **Notes:**
 - Concretions are abundant at this locality but are virtually all barren of recognizable fossils. Concretions are typically irregular to slabby in shape. Black shale is common in the eastern 2/3 of this pit, suggesting a major eastward stratigraphic change above the Colchester Coal level. Braidwood-type fossils (plants and sparse animals) appear in force in the next pit to the west in section 26 as well as to the southwest. The Braidwood association becomes spectacularly abundant at the “Black’s Farm locality” (Locality 227), 0.6 miles to the southwest of locality 246.
 - The lack of body fossils (plants and animals) and the presence of infaunal trace fossils suggested that the Francis Creek has undergone a severe (shoreward?) facies change or that a different stratigraphic unit is expressed in this pit. This black shale may be the one reported above a 3’-thick coal seam (Colchester?) immediately east of this strip mine at the bend of Aux Sable Creek (Bradley, 1977).
 - In any case, the content of this box is significant and greatly out of sync with “typical” Francis Creek deposits in the Morris area.

Locality 247

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station D”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station D”) at SE1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 27, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.337350, -88.320207 (GCB); 41.313691, -88.30175758 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 626 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 340 (54.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 55
 - *Neuropteris* = 13
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 13
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 100
 - Plant stems = 50
 - Bark = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 3
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Sphenopteris?* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - Fertile fern = 1
 - Cone? = 1
 - Skinny cone = 1
 - Cone with round megaspores = 6
 - Macerated plants = 49
 - Unidentified plants = 22
 - **Animals:** Total = 7 (1.1 % of total)
 - Indeterminate blobs? = 3
 - Coprolites = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (1.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
 - **Duds:** Total = 269 (42.9 % of total)
 - Common duds = 107
 - Gray-brown duds = 134
 - Dark gray duds = 25
 - Pyritic duds = 3

- **Rejects: 10**

Locality 248

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (“station D”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/21/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (“station D”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, NW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’, quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.182564, -88.219984 (GCB); 41.18310068, -88.220045 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,594 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 67 (4.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 23
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - Plant stems = 5
 - Stem/bark = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Spiropteris?* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 20
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total (blobs plus the rest) = 787 (49.3 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (undivided) = 62
 - Senior blobs = 417
 - Faulted senior blob = 1
 - Junior blobs = 163
 - Indeterminate blobs = 23
 - Multiple blobs = 16
 - “septarial” blobs = 2
 - *Essexella* total in sample is 684
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 4
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 25
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Shrimp “*Peachella*” = 2
 - Essoid shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Insect (nymph wing?) = 1

- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Polychaete *Hystricula* = 2
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 2
- Unidentified polychaetes = 3
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 2
- Brachiopod *Lingula* = 2
- *Tullimonstrum* = 3
- Fish scale = 1
- Acanthodian spine = 1
- Coprolites = 41
- Trails/traces = 4
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 12 (0.7 % of total)
 - Discs = 6
 - Smears = 4
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 728 (45.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 529
 - Gray duds = 184
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 11
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 249

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11: Station “Pond E”).** Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/11/24.

- **Description:** Tip heaps of abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine within premises of the Ponderosa Sportsman’s Club, Kankakee County, Illinois. Collecting site is at CTR, NW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.183063, -88.219132 (GCB); 41.18310068, -88.220045 (ADM). This is a small, low hill north of the club entrance road, northwest of the club center boat ramp area. It is “*Lingula* hill”.

- Total counts, based on 961 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 15 (1.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - Plant stems = 6
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 338 (35.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 50
 - Junior blobs = 87
 - Indeterminate blobs = 28
 - Multiple blobs = 8
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Crushed *Myalinella*? = 2
 - *Lingula* = 130
 - *Lingula* (with pedicle traces) = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (shelled) = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (molts) = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (not categorized) = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete Simple jaw = 1
 - Indeterminate polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trails/traces = 11
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (1.1 % of total)
 - “discs” = 3
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 597 (62.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 462
 - Gray-brown duds = 135

Locality 250

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND F”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/22/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND F”) at SE1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.184918, -88.218681 (GCB); 41.18490199, -88.2201074 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,405 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 33 (2.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 17
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plate stems = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 900 (includes blobs and all other animals) (64.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 335
 - Junior blobs = 361
 - Indeterminate blobs = 84
 - Multiple blobs = 34
 - Blob with “knobs” = 1
 - Total *Essexella* count = 815
 - *Reticulomedusa* = 3
 - *Etacystis* = 18
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 24
 - Insect = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Incognitum organism with fish scales = 1
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 2* = collected by K. Ramsdell
 - Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
 - Coprolites = 25
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - *Diplocraterion* = 1

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 27 (1.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 7
 - Ghosts-smears = 1
 - Blob-“H”-trail smears = 7
 - Pelletal nodules = 4
 - Faulted concretions = 3
 - Incognitum organism = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 445 (31.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 286
 - Gray duds = 118
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 38
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 251

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND G”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/22/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND G”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.180568, -88.222792 (GCB); 41.17989908, -88.22288755 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 470 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 11 (2.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - Plant stems = 3
 - *Thallites* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 182 (38.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 84
 - Junior blobs = 11
 - Indeterminate blobs = 27
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 10
 - Shrimp *Kallidectes* = 2
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Holothurian with blob = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Fish *Megalichthys* (articulated) = 1
 - Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
 - Coprolites = 33
 - Trails/traces = 8
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 27 (5.7 % of total)
 - Discs = 17
 - Ghosts = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
 - **Duds:** Total = 250 (53.1 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 197
 - Dark gray duds = 1
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 36
 - Septarial duds = 16
 - **Rejects:** 18 (includes “antler concretions” – not included in sample count)

Locality 252

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned, Morris Coal and Mining Company, Morris No. 2 strip mine, northeast of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/15/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company, Morris No. 2 strip mine at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 26, T34N, T7E on the Lisbon 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.389267, -88.386597 (GCB); 41.38920485, -88.38601488 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.
- Total counts, based on 791 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 410 (51.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 205
 - *Neuropteris* = 18
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Calamites* = 15
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 24
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 72
 - Bark/stem = 18
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Fertile fern = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Fructification/megaspores = 1
 - Megaspores = 1
 - Indeterminate cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 33
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 73 (9.2% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Incognitum arthropod = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 69
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (0.5% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 304 (38.4% of total)
 - Common duds = 293
 - Septarial duds = 11
 - **Rejects:** 117

Locality 253

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station G”) east of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/19/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Northwestern Coal Corporation, Morris strip mine (“station G”) at NE1/4, NW1/4, Section 34, T34N, R7E on the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.381495, -88.414335 (GCB); 41.3849487, -88.41492903 (ADM). Mine directory number = 2391.
- Total counts, based on 387 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 145 (37.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 53
 - *Neuropteris* = 12
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 19
 - Plant stems = 17
 - Bark = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Cone (*Lepidostrobus*) = 1
 - Macerated plants = 22
 - Unidentified plant = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 36 (9.3% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 1
 - Syncarid shrimps = 2
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - *Euproops* fragment? = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* (two kinds) = 4
 - Coprolites = 23
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (2.0% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 198 (51.1% of total)
 - Common duds = 101
 - Gray-brown duds = 5
 - Dark gray duds = 33
 - Pyritic duds = 56
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 254

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company, no. 2 strip mine at east edge of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 05/17/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal & Mining Company, no. 2 strip mine (“station H”) at SW1/4, NE1/4, NW1/4, section 3, T33N, R7E near the north edge of the Morris 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.369662, -88.416150 (GCB); 41.36951254, -88.41578959 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.
- Total counts, based on 987 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 412 (41.7% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 91
 - *Neuropteris* = 36
 - *Annularia* = 20
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 103
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 12
 - Plant stems = 37
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 3
 - Lycopod stem = 2
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Spiropteris?* = 1
 - Cone? = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 70
 - Unidentified plants = 20
 - **Animals:** Total = 80 (8.1% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 24 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Ostracod cluster = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops?* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 2
 - Coprolites = 51
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (0.4% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 491 (49.7% of total)

- Common duds = 205
- Gray-brown duds = 40
- Gray duds = 4
- Dark gray duds = 157
- Pyritic duds = 82
- Weathered duds = 3
- **Rejects: 3**

Locality 255

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND H” – “jellyfish hill”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 05/20/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND H” – “jellyfish hill”) at NE1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E south of West Road on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.186672, -88.212150 (GCB); 41.18686861, -88.21071639 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 3,695 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 398 (10.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 49
 - *Neuropteris* = 12
 - *Annularia* = 28
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 99
 - Bark = 7
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Cone *Calamostachys?* = 1
 - Cone? = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Asolanus* = 1
 - *Thallites* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 2
 - Macerated plants = 175
 - Unidentified plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,377 (37.2 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 277
 - Senior blobs = 175
 - Junior blobs = 358
 - Indeterminate blobs = 100
 - Multiple blobs = 8
 - Shredded blobs = 2
 - Box jelly *Anthracomедusa* = 1
 - *Octomedusa* = 190
 - Multiple *Octomedusa* = 22
 - *Etacystis* (the “Aitch”) = 59
 - *Etacystis* with *Octomedusa* = 2

- *Reticulomedusa* = 1
- *Myalinella* = 1
- *Aviculopecten* = 3
- Indeterminate bivalve = 2
- Gastropod *Strobeus* = 11
- Gastropod *Euphemites* = 2
- Unidentified bellerophontid gastropod = 1
- Cephalopod *Paleocadmus* = 1
- Shrimp *Belotelson* = 27
- Shrimp *Kallidectes* = 4
- Shrimp *Mamayocaris* = 2
- Shrimp “*Peachella*” = 5
- Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
- Flea shrimps = 5
- Essoid shrimp = 1
- Unidentified shrimp = 3
- *Cyclus* = 10
- Insect (cockroach) = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 5
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 3
- Polychaete *Hystricula* = 3
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* on myalinid bivalve = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 5
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 6
- Arrow worm *Paucijaculum* = 2
- Holothurian = 1
- *Tullimonstrum* = 14
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 5
- *Esconichthys* with blob = 1
- Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
- Coprolites = 45
- Trails/traces = 8
- *Diplocraterion* = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 254 (6.8 % of total)
 - Ghosts-smears = 15
 - *Etacystis* – *Octomedusa* – blob smears = 145
 - Discs = 26
 - Pelletal nodule = 1
 - Spots = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 64
- **Duds:** Total = 1,666 (45.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 1,284
 - Gray duds = 144
 - Gray-brown duds = 171

- Pyrite-cored duds = 53
- Septarial duds = 14

Locality 256

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station POND i”), west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/22/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11 strip mine, “station i”), at NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.186351, -88.222708 (GCB); 41.18666386, -88.2225312 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 619 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 10 (1.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Annularia* with blob = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Bark = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 261 (42.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 134
 - Junior blobs = 52
 - Indeterminate blobs = 24
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 6
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - *Megalichthys* fish scale = 1
 - Coprolites = 32
 - Fecal pellet concretions = 2
 - Sand-sized fecal pellets = 1
 - Trails/traces = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 42 (6.7 % of total)
 - Discs = 31
 - Unidentified nucleus = 11
 - **Duds:** Total = 306 (49.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 146
 - Gray duds = 51
 - Gray-brown duds = 81
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 23
 - Septarial duds = 5

Locality 257

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11: Station “Pond J”).** Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/10/24.

- **Description:** Tip heaps of abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine within premises of the Ponderosa Sportsman’s Club, Kankakee County, Illinois. Collecting site is at SW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.181562, -88.216198 (GCB); 41.18141919, -88.21289684 (ADM). Some of these counts are really “off the charts” in terms of cnidarian yield, Tullies, *Belotelson* and other exotics. It is also notable for a low proportion of duds. These data are all the more significant in that this area was visited only once.

- Total counts, based on 1,935 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 120 (6.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 51
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 6
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 5
 - Plant stem = 25
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 1489 (76.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 863
 - Junior blobs = 380
 - Multiple blobs = 25
 - *Essexella* total = 1,268
 - *Octomedusa* = 7
 - Box jelly *Anthracommedusa* = 3
 - *Reticulomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “H”) = 45
 - “blob-“H”-Octo smears = 19
 - Hydroids = 3
 - *Mazonomya* = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - *Strobeus* = 7
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 73
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1

- Phyllocarid *Kellibrooksia* = 1
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 6
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
- Polychaete Simple jaw = 2
- Unidentified polychaete = 1
- *Nemavermes?* = 1
- *Tullimonstrum* = 21
- *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 2
- Coprolites = 10
- Trails/traces = 6
- *Diplocraterion* = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 14 (0.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - Incognitum = 9 = potentially important undescribed organisms
- **Duds:** Total = 312 (16.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 217
 - Gray-brown duds = 95

Locality 258

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND K”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/22/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND K”) at SW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.183750, -88.223028 (GCB); 41.18486255, -88.2224688 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,681 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 43 (2.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 19
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Bark/stems = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophylloides* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant tufts = 2
 - Macerated plants = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,145 (68.1 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 42
 - Senior blobs = 655
 - Junior blobs = 254
 - Indeterminate blobs = 73
 - Multiple blobs = 3
 - *Reticulomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 9
 - Unidentified shrimp = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Crustacean exuvium = 1
 - Unidentified horseshoe crab = 1
 - Unidentified arthropod = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Indeterminate polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - *Acanthodian* = 1
 - Coprolites = 81

- Trails/traces = 7
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 49 (2.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 25
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - Blob-“H”-trail smears = 14
 - Incognitum organisms = 3
- **Duds:** Total = 444 (26.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 411
 - Gray-brown duds = 18
 - Septarial duds = 12
 - “gas vent” duds = 3
- **Rejects:** 96

Locality 259

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris no. 2 strip mine (“station i”), east of Morris, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/19/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal and Mining Corporation, Morris no. 2 strip mine (“station i”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 34, T34N, R7E near the south edge of the Lisbon 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.376601, -88.412705 (GCB); 41.37543128, -88.41653826 (ADM). Mine directory number = 625.
- Total counts, based on 468 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 190 (40.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 58
 - *Neuropteris* = 38
 - *Annularia* = 11
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 17
 - Plant stems = 17
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Cone (*Selaginites?*) = 2
 - Cone? = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Spore case = 1
 - Macerated plants = 17
 - Unidentified plant = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 75 (16.0 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarids = 4
 - Arachnid = 1
 - “spiny” myriopod (undescribed) = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 4
 - Fish? bone = 1
 - Coprolites = 61
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (2.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 11
 - **Duds:** Total = 192 (41.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 53
 - Dark gray duds = 78

- Pyritic duds = 53
- Weathered duds = 4
- Septarial duds = 4

Locality 260

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND L”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/23/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND L”) at S1/2, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.183750, -88.223028 (GCB); 41.17965511, -88.21047616 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 576 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 11 (1.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 260 (45.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 201
 - Junior blobs = 27
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 4
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Indeterminate arthropod = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Trails/traces = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (0.6 % of total)
 - “ghost” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 301 (52.2 % of total)
 - Common duds = 251
 - Gray-brown duds = 44
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 261

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND M”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 05/23/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND M”) at NE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.186587, -88.206457 (GCB); 41.18695051, -88.20599046 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 224 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 3 (1.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - Plant stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 125 (55.8 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 42
 - Junior blobs = 44
 - Indeterminate blobs = 18
 - Blob with gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 9
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 3
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trails-ghosts = 4
 - *Diplocraterion* = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 96 (42.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 82
 - Gray-brown duds (split concretions) = 14

Locality 262

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND O”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/23/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND O”) at E1/2, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.176048, -88.219650 (GCB); 41.17497505, -88.2209449 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 824 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 90 (10.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 41
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - Bark and stems = 23
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plants = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 306 (37.1 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 9
 - Senior blobs = 144
 - Junior blobs = 58
 - Indeterminate blobs = 15
 - *Octomedusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Unidentified myalinids = 4
 - Unidentified bivalve? = 1
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 12
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Flea shrimp = 2
 - Crustacean exuvium = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Paleolimulus* = 1
 - Holothurian = 4
 - *Paleocampa* (incertae sedis animal with phosphatic spines) = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 24
 - Trails/traces = 19
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 35 (4.2 % of total)
 - Discs = 4

- Smears-blobs – “H” blurs = 19
- Indeterminate nucleus = 9
- Incognitum organism = 3
- **Duds:** Total = 393 (47.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 385
 - Gray-brown duds = 3
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 4
 - Septarian duds = 1
- **Rejects:** 44

Locality 263

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND P”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 05/24/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND P”) at SW1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.174139, -88.223677 (GCB); 41.17405468, -88.2220944 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. This locality is the eastern end of a line of high, south-facing strip mine dumps north of waterway between Merchant’s Road and the south end of Pit 11 known as the “great wall of China” by the amateurs.
- Total counts, based on 1,563 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 202 (12.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 81
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 27
 - *Calamites* = 13
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - Plant stems = 4
 - Stems/bark = 53
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant? = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 713 (45.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 371
 - Junior blobs = 154
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Reticulomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* = 12
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 7
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - *Myalinella* with attached plant = 1
 - Unidentified myalinid = 4
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 18
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 29
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 4

- Flea shrimp = 3
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
- Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
- Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* on bark = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 2
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 3
- Holothurians = 21
- *Tullimonstrum* = 2
- Onychophoran? = 1
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 7
- Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
- Coprolites = 35
- Trails/traces = 15
- *Diplocraterion* = 3
- Burrowed pelletal slab = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 64 (4.0 % of total)
 - Discs = 12
 - Blob-“H”-indet smears = 34
 - Unidentified nucleus = 16
 - Incognitum organisms = 2
- **Duds:** Total = 584 (37.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 291
 - Gray duds = 240
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 49
 - Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects:** 80
- **Note:**
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 1 (collected by amateur – not included in count)

Locality 264

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND Q”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 05/24/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND Q”) at NW1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.176890, -88.228021 (GCB); 41.17578116, -88.22698655 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,813 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 183 (10.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 51
 - *Neuropteris* = 37
 - *Annularia* = 11
 - *Calamites* = 21
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 14
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Stems/bark = 42
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,301 (71.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 1112
 - Junior blobs = 8
 - Indeterminate blobs = 11
 - Box jelly *Anthracomедusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “Aitch”) = 48
 - Blobs with attached gastropod *Strobeus* = 8
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 6
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 17
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 10
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 6
 - Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
 - Coprolites = 45
 - Trails/traces = 22
 - *Diplocraterion* = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 24 (1.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 24
 - **Duds:** Total = 305 (16.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 305

- **Note:**
 - One specimen of box jelly *Anthracomedusa* and one specimen of *Glaphurochiton* collected by volunteers in our group in this area.

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Locality 265

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND R”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/28/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND R”) at NW1/4, SW1/4, NW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.183928, -88.223735 (GCB); 41.18306124, -88.2224064. Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 805 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 67 (8.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 22
 - *Neuropteris* = 21
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 2
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - Stems/bark = 17
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Indeterminate plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 422 (52.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 237
 - Junior blobs = 87
 - Indeterminate blobs = 2
 - Faulted blobs = 2
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 3
 - *Escomasia* (the “wye”) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Chiton *Glaphurochiton* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 6
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Polychaete Oliver Hardy worm? = 2
 - Polychaete “fan worm” = 3
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 2
 - Coprolites = 49
 - Trails/traces = 18
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (1.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 6
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 305 (37.8 % of total)

- Common duds = 59
- Gray duds = 233
- Pyrite-cored duds = 6
- Septarial duds = 7
- **Rejects: 57**

Locality 266

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND S”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/28/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND S”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.183960, -88.211329 (GCB); 41.18326296, -88.21059471 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,693 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 223 (13.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 65
 - *Neuropteris* = 10
 - *Annularia* = 19
 - *Calamites* = 6
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 19
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Bark/stems = 49
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 3
 - Cone = 1
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plants = 39
 - **Animals:** Total = 733 (43.2 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 302
 - Junior blobs = 255
 - Indeterminate blobs = 31
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - Blob/coprolite = 1
 - *Octomedusa* = 3
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 58
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 4
 - Myalinid bivalves = 2
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 33
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 2
 - Phyllocarid *Kellibrooksia* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 2

- Unidentified polychaetes = 4
- Incognitum worm = 1
- *Tullimonstrum* = 2
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 2
- Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
- Coprolites = 10
- Trails/traces = 8
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 46 (2.7 % of total)
 - Discs = 6
 - Unidentified nucleus = 40
- **Duds:** Total = 691 (40.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 591
 - Gray duds = 64
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 36

Locality 267

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND T” – “chiton-*Praeilepis* hill”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 05/28/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND T” – “chiton-*Praeilepis* hill”) at ctr, SW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.181637, -88.215292 (GCB); 41.18141919, -88.21289684 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 514 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 11 (2.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 136 (26.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 14
 - Junior blobs = 42
 - Indeterminate blobs = 24
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 4
 - *Escamasia* (the “wye”) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 16
 - *Myalinella* with attached gooseneck barnacle *Praeilepis* = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 2
 - Chiton *Glaphurochiton* = 14
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Coprolites = 4
 - “eggs” = 1
 - Trails/traces = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (1.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 359 (69.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 276
 - Gray-brown duds = 79
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 2

Locality 268

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND U”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND U”) at SE1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.181600, -88.208288 (GCB); 41.18241775, -88.2070261 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 272 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 9 (3.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 136 (50.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 49
 - Junior blobs = 55
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Incognitum jellyfish = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 6
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - *Diplocraterion* = 1
 - Incognitum animal = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 15 (5.5 % of total)
 - Discs = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 14
 - **Duds:** Total = 112 (41.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 65
 - Gray-brown duds = 43
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 4

Locality 269

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND V”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND V”) at ctr, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.179339, -88.212660 (GCB); 41.17784665, -88.21042158 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 2,100 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 42 (2.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Stems/bark = 8
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 974 (46.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 520
 - Junior blobs = 286
 - Indeterminate blobs = 56
 - Odd blobs = 5
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 9
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 52
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 2
 - *Cyzicus* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab = *Paleolimulus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete Baby Tooth = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Polychaete “Oliver Hardy worm” = 1
 - Polychaete “ratworm” = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 6
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 4
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 5
 - Coelacanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
 - Coprolites = 11

- Trails/traces = 1
- Unidentified animal = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 17 (0.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 9
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
- **Duds:** Total = 1, 074 (51.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 1,067
 - Septarial duds = 7

Locality 270

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND W”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND W”) at ctr, SW1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.178270, -88.215445 (GCB); 41.17780983, -88.21277985 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 802 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 18 (2.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 6
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 8
 - “thorn plant” = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 288 (35.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 111
 - Junior blobs = 103
 - Indeterminate blobs = 40
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 10
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 1
 - *Nemavermes* (worm taxon) = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Trails/traces = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (1.2 % of total)
 - Smear = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 486 (60.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 343
 - Gray duds = 132
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 10
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 271

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND X”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND W”) at ctr, SE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.181856, -88.213620 (GCB); 41.18145753, -88.210537 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 119 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 6 (5.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 1
 - Odontopterid? fern = 1
 - Incognitum fern = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 63 (52.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 20
 - Junior blobs = 19
 - Indeterminate blobs = 14
 - Collared blob = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Probable shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete Baby Tooth = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Trail/trace = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (2.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 47 (39.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 23
 - Gray-brown duds = 15
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 7
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 272

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND Y”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/30/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND Y”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.179762, -88.215587 (GCB); 41.17961375, -88.21042158 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 391 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 18 (4.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Stems/bark = 3
 - Plant stems = 4
 - *Thallites* = 1
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 172 (43.9 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 60
 - Junior blobs = 61
 - Indeterminate blobs = 19
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 7
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 3
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails/ghosts = 10
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (1.0 % of total)
 - Ghost = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 197 (50.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 136
 - Gray-brown duds = 42
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 19

Locality 273

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND Z”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/30/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND Z”) at NE1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.179277, -88.216141 (GCB); 41.17957693, -88.2151974 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,156 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 58 (5.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 17
 - *Neuropteris* = 10
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Bark/stems = 9
 - Stems = 1
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - Plant with spores = 1
 - Incognitum plants = 2
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 891 (77.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 615
 - Junior blobs = 154
 - Indeterminate blobs = 1
 - Multiple blobs = 21
 - *Octomedusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 5
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 51
 - Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Polychaete Oliver Hardy = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Worm *Nemavermes* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 5
 - Coprolites = 17
 - Trails/traces = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 23 (1.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 12

- Unidentified nucleus = 11
- **Duds:** Total = 184 (15.9 % of total)
 - Common (gray-brown) duds = 184
- **Rejects:** 30

Locality 274

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 A”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/30/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 A”) at SW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.178698, -88.221844 (GCB); 41.1776573, -88.2222192 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 923 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 79 (8.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 48
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Bark/stems = 13
 - Plant with spores = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 586 (63.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 192
 - Junior blobs = 18
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 2
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 12
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 4
 - Polychaete *Fossundecima* = 1
 - Polychaete *Dryptoscolex mattiesae* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 45
 - Chaetognath *Balanoglossus* = 3
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 2
 - Coprolites = 30
 - Crushed bivalves in coprolite = 1
 - Trails/traces = 215
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.1 % of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 257 (27.8 % of total)
 - Brown duds = 210

- Gray-brown duds = 45
- Septarial duds = 2

Locality 275

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 B”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/31/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 B”) at NE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.177887, -88.223695 (GCB); 41.1758179, -88.22691558 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 2,004 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 356 (17.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 173
 - *Neuropteris* = 25
 - *Annularia* = 57
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 13
 - Plant stems = 12
 - Bark = 1
 - Bark/stems = 59
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 583 (29.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 185
 - Junior blobs = 97
 - Indeterminate blobs = 12
 - Blob with *Strobeus* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 2
 - *Myalinella* = 10
 - Pecten = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 47
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Insect = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 3
 - Polychaete (“ratworm”) = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 4
 - Holothurians = 25
 - Chaetognath *Balanoglossus* = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 5

- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 3
- Coprolites = 72
- Trails/traces = 85
- *Diplocraterion* = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (0.9 % of total)
 - Incognitum organisms = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 16
- **Duds:** Total = 1,045 (52.1 % of total)
 - Brown duds = 732
 - Gray-brown duds = 311
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 276

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 C” – “great wall of China”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/03/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 C”) at SE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with digital coordinates estimated at 41.174393, -88.224739 (GCB); 41.1744761, -88.22507974 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 1,763 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 350 (19.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 192
 - *Neuropteris* = 27
 - *Annularia* = 33
 - *Calamites* = 23
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Bark/stems = 61
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 5
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 923 (52.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 369
 - Junior blobs = 218
 - Indeterminate blobs = 24
 - Faulted blobs = 12
 - “weird” blobs = 22
 - *Octomedusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 45
 - *Escomasia* (the “wye”) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 12
 - Myalinids = 13
 - Blobs with attached gastropod *Strobeus* = 13
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 53
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Larval shrimp = 1
 - Indeterminate shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 4
 - Millepede = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete Baby Tooth = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3

- *Tullimonstrum* = 4
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 8
- Acanthodian? Fragment = 1
- Coprolites = 30
- Trails/traces = 81
- *Diplocraterion* = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (0.3 % of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 6
- **Duds:** Total = 484 (27.4 % of total)
 - Brown duds = 484

Locality 277

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 D”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/03/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 D”) at NW1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.176528, -88.222362 (GCB); 41.17585599, -88.2221568 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 472 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 16 (3.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 7
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Plant fragment = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 166 (35.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 48
 - Junior blobs = 22
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 3
 - *Etacystis* or *Escomasia* (the “wye”) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*, one clam, spread valves) = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 12
 - Flea shrimp = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 3
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 16
 - Coprolite with fish bone = 1
 - Trails/traces = 47
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (1.6 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 282 (59.7 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 282

Locality 278

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 E”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/03/24,
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 E”) at NW1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.177285, -88.226170 (GCB); 41.1758179, -88.22691558 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 181 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 5 (2.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - *Sphenopteris* = 1
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 66 (36.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 4
 - Indeterminate blobs = 10
 - Arthropod fragment = 1
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 29
 - Trails/traces = 4
 - Indeterminate animal = 2
 - Chewed remains = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.1 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 108 (59.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 34
 - Gray-brown duds = 38
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 34
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 279

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 F”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/03/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 F”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.179281, -88.221909 (GCB); 41.17945861, -88.2222816 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,224 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 50 (4.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 26
 - *Neuropteris* = 9
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Bark/stems = 11
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 644 (52.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 405
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - *Myalinella* (crushed) = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 21
 - Flea shrimp = 6
 - Unidentified shrimp = 2
 - Gooseneck barnacle *Praeilepis* = 1
 - Cockroach nymph = 1
 - Centipede? Segment = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Polychaete *Hystriacula* = 1
 - Polychaete “Oliver Hardy worm” = 1
 - Polychaete “ratworm” = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - Echiuran *Capronoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 8
 - Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
 - Coprolites = 82
 - Trails/traces = 101
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (0.3 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 526 (42.9 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 525

- Septarial duds = 1

Locality 280

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 G”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/03/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 G”) at NE1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.180639, -88.219682 (GCB); 41.17949805, -88.2199202 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,172 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 57 (4.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 20
 - *Neuropteris* = 13
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Stems/bark = 9
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - Marine plant? = 1
 - Thallus plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 818 (69.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 548
 - Junior blobs = 157
 - Indeterminate blobs = 18
 - Multiple blobs = 15
 - Unusual blob = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 2
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 3
 - Coleoid cephalopod *Jeletzkyia* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 41
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Phyllocarid *Kellibrooksia?* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 4
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 1
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Agnathan *Gilpichthys?* = 1
 - Coprolites = 8
 - Trails/traces = 11

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 45 (3.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 40
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 252 (21.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 162
 - Gray-brown duds = 82
 - Septarial duds = 6
 - Mottled duds = 2

Locality 281

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 H”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/04/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 H”) at NE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.176855, -88.215975 (GCB); 41.17596908, -88.21507885 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 745 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 17 (2.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Bark/stems = 7
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 356 (47.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 195
 - Junior blobs = 77
 - Indeterminate blobs = 18
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 29
 - Unidentified shrimp = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 2
 - Coprolites = 15
 - Trails/traces = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (1.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 362 (48.5 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 356
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 6

Locality 282

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 i” = north of “great wall of China”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/04/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 i”) at N1/2, SE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.174904, -88.224444 (GCB); 41.1744761, -88.22507974 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 1,254 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 165 (13.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 72
 - *Neuropteris* = 18
 - *Annularia* = 24
 - Multiple *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Calamites* stems = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - Plant stems = 7
 - *Stigmarioides* = 3
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Lycopod scale = 1
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plants = 14
 - **Animals:** Total = 746 (59.4 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 152
 - Senior blobs = 335
 - Junior blobs = 93
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - Multiple blobs = 3
 - *Reticulomedusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 8
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; single clam, spread valves) = 30
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* with polychaete = 1
 - Bivalve *Dundarella* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Blobs with gastropod *Strobeus* = 10
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 25
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 3
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Crustacean exuvium = 1

- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
- Unidentified polychaete = 1
- Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 5
- Holothurians = 5
- *Tullimonstrum* = 6
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 6
- Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 1
- Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
- Coprolites = 20
- Trails/traces = 22
- Furoid = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 50 (3.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 44
 - Unidentified nucleus = 6
- **Duds:** Total = 293 (23.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 87
 - Gray-brown duds = 205
 - Septarial duds = 1
- **Rejects:** 131

Locality 283

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 J”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/05/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 J”) at SW1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.175209, -88.219578 (GCB); 41.17412833, -88.21737785 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 68 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Animal:** Total = 18 (26.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 4
 - Junior blobs = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Trails/traces = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (5.8 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 46 (67.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 34
 - Gray-brown-split duds = 12

Locality 284

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 K”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 06/05/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 K”) at SE1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 8, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.174593, -88.219617 (GCB); 41.1740915, -88.21973613 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 287 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 24 (8.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 9
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stem = 2
 - Bark = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 82 (28.5 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 9
 - Junior blobs = 19
 - Indeterminate blobs = 19
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 4
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 1
 - Holothurians = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails/traces = 18
 - *Diplocraterion* = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 12 (4.1 % of total)
 - Discs = 4
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 169 (58.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 108
 - Gray duds = 40
 - Brown duds = 7
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 12
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - **Rejects:** 40

Locality 285

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 L”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/05/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 L”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.177210, -88.229494 (GCB); 41.17573363, -88.22941068 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 2,390 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 160 (6.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 64
 - *Neuropteris* = 14
 - *Annularia* = 11
 - *Calamites* = 7
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 6
 - Bark/stems = 42
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 1,896 (79.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 1,486
 - Junior blobs = 55
 - Indeterminate blobs = 55
 - Multiple blobs = 9
 - Faulted blobs = 4
 - Unusual blobs = 16
 - Total *Essexella* count = 1,625
 - Box jellies *Anthracomedusa* = 2
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 43
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) = 6
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* with *Essexella* = 8
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 72
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson?* = 1
 - Flea shrimp = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 1

- *Tullimonstrum* = 14
- Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 4
- Agnathan *Gilpichthys* = 2
- Agnathan lamprey *Mayomyzon* = 1
- Coprolites = 103
- Trails/traces = 3
- Unidentified animal = 2
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.2 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
- **Duds:** Total = 329 (13.7 % of total)
 - Brown duds = 309
 - Gray-brown duds = 20
- **Note:**
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa*, shrimp *Mamayocaris*, and articulated lungfish
* collected by amateurs (Frank Greene, Stephen Sroka, Karlene Ramsdell)
in this same area. These specimens not included in sample count.

Locality 286

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 M”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/06/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 M”) at Ctr, SE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.178087, -88.228327 (GCB); 41.17666345, -88.2282341 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 181 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (1.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 88 (48.6 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 11
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 1
 - Chewed up scallop = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Disarticulated fish = 1
 - Coprolites = 42
 - Trails-ghosts = 8
 - Bedded siderite with pellet trails and hair trails = 10
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 89 (49.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 61
 - Hammer split duds (total = 28):
 - Gray-brown duds = 22
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Blue-gray duds = 3

Locality 287

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 N”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/06/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 N”) at NE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.186506, -88.224769 (GCB); 41.18708529, -88.22433568 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 180 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 3 (1.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 89 (49.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 9
 - Junior blobs = 12
 - Indeterminate blobs = 32
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Box jelly *Anthracomedusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 2
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 18
 - Trails/traces = 8
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (5.5 % of total)
 - Discs = 6
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 78 (43.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 76
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 288

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 O”) west of Essex, Kankakee County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/06/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 11 strip mine (station “POND 2 O”) at S1/2, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 7, T31N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.182604, -88.225708 (GCB); 41.17932545, -88.2295269 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834.
- Total counts, based on 305 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 6 (1.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - Bark = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 218 (71.4 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 175
 - Box jelly *Anthracomедusa* = 1
 - *Etacystis* (the “aitch”) = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 4
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson?* = 1
 - Coprolites = 35
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 81 (26.5 % of total)
 - Brown duds = 81
 - **Note:**
 - Horseshoe crab *Palaeolimulus** = 1 (collected by amateur and not included in count)

Locality 289

- **Will-Essex; included—northern part of Pit 8 bordering Jugtown Road. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/06/24.**
- **Description:** Temporary bulldozed area in abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine bordering west side of North Jugtown Road on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates 41.233594, -88.274169 (GCB); 41.34055455, -88.32379041 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 926 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 291 (31.4% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 57
 - *Neuropteris* = 11
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 117
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 7
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Plant stem = 33
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 3
 - *Lycopodites* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - Neuropterid-Odontopterid ferns = 3
 - *Stigmarioides* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Lycopod trunk = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Seed case? = 1
 - Macerated plant = 41
 - Unidentified plant = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 104 (11.2% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 9
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blobs = 9
 - *Aviculopecten* = 10
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 12 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 5
 - Clam with trail/trace = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Mantis shrimp *Tyrranophontes?* = 1

- Unidentified arthropod = 1
- Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 5
- Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
- Polychaete Oliver Hardy worm = 6
- Unidentified polychaetes = 11
- Acorn worm *Balanoglossus?* = 1
- Coprolites = 21
- Trails/traces = 7
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 49 (5.2% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 48
 - Smear = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 482 (52.0% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 352
 - Dark gray duds = 82
 - Pyritic duds = 13
 - Blue-gray duds = 6
 - Sandy duds = 16
 - Weathered duds = 13

Locality 290

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “C”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/18/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “C”), appears to be currently in the Meneoka Club area, at SE1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 3, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.277031, -88.183007 (GCB); 41.27995988, -88.18576199 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.

- Total counts, based on 242 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 146 (60.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 63
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 7
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 21
 - Plant stems = 19
 - Stems/bark = 6
 - Bark = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plant = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 9 (3.7 % of total)
 - Coprolites = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 7 (2.8 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 7
 - **Duds:** Total = 80 (33.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 23
 - Gray-brown duds = 30
 - Dark gray duds = 15
 - Blue-gray duds = 2
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 5
 - Pelletal nodule = 1
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 291

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station H”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station H”) at Ctr, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 17, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.335799, -88.333259 (GCB); 41.33584673, -88.33208255 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 78 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 36 (46.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 26
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (2.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 40 (51.2 % of total)
 - Common duds = 32
 - Septarial duds = 8

Locality 292

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station i”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/11/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station i”) at Ctr, SE1/4, section 20, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.319658, -88.329261 (GCB); 41.32040931, -88.33060849 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 142 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 26 (18.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 13
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 19 (13.3 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 3
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 1
 - Probable blobs = 2
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Traces/trails = 8
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 97 (68.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 87
 - Split duds (total = 10):
 - Gray-brown duds = 7
 - Pyritic duds = 3

Locality 293

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station j”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/12/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station j”) at S1/2, SE1/4, section 20, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.318068, -88.328068 (GCB); 41.31681808, -88.32815576 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 489 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 63 (12.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 18
 - *Neuropteris* = 14
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 18
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 6
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 89 (18.2 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 21
 - Junior blob = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 8
 - Probable blobs = 10
 - “odd” blob = 1
 - *Octomedusa* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve with burrow = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 5
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex?* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 12
 - Traces/trails = 22
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 11 (2.2 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
 - Incognitum organism = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 326 (66.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 168
 - Gray-brown duds = 54
 - Split duds (total = 104):
 - Gray-brown duds = 78
 - Pyrite cored duds = 10
 - Light gray = 8

- Pyrite suffused = 6
- Mottled = 2

Locality 294

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station K”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/12/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station K”) at NW1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 16, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.333120, -88.323662 (GCB); 41.3332963, -88.32364046. Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 169 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 47 (27.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 9
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 18
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* with bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 5 (2.9 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 115 (68.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 92
 - Dark gray duds = 9
 - Pyritic duds = 13
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 295

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station L”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, “station L”) at NE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 20, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.326831, -88.330404 (GCB); 41.32587025, -88.33069043 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 70 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (28.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 11
 - Plant stem = 3
 - Cone? = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (1.4 % of total)
 - Coprolites = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 49 (70.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 49

Locality 296

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station M”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/12/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station M”) at NE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.315035, -88.325256 (GCB); 41.3150568, -88.32572445 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 33 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 4 (12.1 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 5 (15.1 % of total)
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - Traces/trails = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (15.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 19 (57.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 19

Locality 297

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/13/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 21, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.329889, -88.324076 (GCB); 41.32966481, -88.3235692 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 40 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 13 (32.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 3 (7.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (2.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 23 (57.5 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 8
 - Dark gray (blue-black) duds = 10
 - Pyritic duds = 5

Locality 298

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at NE1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 16, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.333051, -88.320498 (GCB); 41.33333921, -88.32125233 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 47 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 22 (46.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Compound (“Pit 9-type”) neuropterid fern = 3
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 8
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (2.1 % of total)
 - Arachnid = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (6.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 21 (44.6 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 14
 - Dark gray duds = 7

Locality 299

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data updated sheet as of 06/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at NE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 21, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.319724, -88.316211 (GCB); 41.318875, -88.31623689 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 34 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 5 (14.7 % of total)
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Bark = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (2.9 % of total)
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (2.9 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 27 (79.4 % of total)
 - Sandy, gray-brown duds = 13
 - Sandy, dark gray duds = 5
 - Sandy, pyritic duds = 9

Locality 300

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/13/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at NE1/4, NW1/4, section 21, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.328796, -88.316513 (GCB); 41.33123858, -88.20317815 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 95 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 28 (29.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Plant stems = 5
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (1.0 % of total)
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (3.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 63 (66.3 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 57
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Pyritic duds = 4

Locality 301

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, Station “B”) at east edge of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/18/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, station “B”) at W1/2, SW1/4, section 3, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.277919, -88.188273 (GCB): 41.2781382, -88.18817281 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.

- **Note:** The township and range coordinates for this area shows that this locality is actually in Pit 5, not 4.

- Total counts, based on 410 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 240 (58.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 87
 - *Neuropteris* = 19
 - Compound Neuropterid ferns = 3
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 41
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - Plant stems = 10
 - Stems/bark = 22
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 2
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Macerated plants = 34
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 23 (5.6 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 3
 - Coprolites = 17
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (1.9 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 139 (33.9 % of total)
 - Common duds = 75
 - Gray-brown duds = 21
 - Septarial duds = 10

- **Separate compiled breakdown of split duds** (total = 33):
 - Gray-brown duds = 22
 - Dark gray duds = 4
 - Pyritic duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - Discs = 2
- **Rejects:** 12

Locality 302

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 4, Station “C”) northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/16/24.
- **Description:** Strip mine terrain near western margin of abandoned Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine (Pit 4, Station “C”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.281192, -88.207023 (GCB); 41.28129944, -88.20722799 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 741 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 307 (41.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 49
 - *Neuropteris* = 27
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 49
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 54
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 12
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* with *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Plant stems = 42
 - Stem/bark = 15
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Sphenopteris?* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 36
 - Incognitum plant = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 117 (15.7 % of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 26
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 46 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalves = 10
 - Unidentified fragmental bivalves = 29
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 94 (12.6 % of total)
 - Discs = 2

- Ghosts (possible blobs) = 3
- Ghosts = 2
- Unidentified nucleus = 86
- Incognitum = 1
- **Duds:** Total = 223 (30.0 % of total)
 - Common duds = 21
 - Light gray duds = 25
 - Gray-brown duds = 92
 - Dark gray duds = 11
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 1
 - Septarial duds = 73

Locality 303

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/14/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at W1/2, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 22, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.322034, -88.302167 (GCB); 41.32182272, -88.30431781 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 49 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 17 (34.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stems = 5
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (4.0 % of total)
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (2.0 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 29 (59.1 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 27
 - Pyrite-cored dud = 1
 - Septarial dud = 1

Locality 304

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/14/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at SE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 21, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.316877, -88.305341 (GCB); 41.31723106, -88.30665659 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 93 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 35 (37.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 10
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 12
 - Plant stems = 9
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 7 (7.5 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (1.0 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 50 (53.7 % of total)
 - Common duds = 50

Locality 305

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/18/24.**

- **Description:** Strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.213592, -88.206947 (GCB); . 41.21212591, -88.20679963 (ADM). Presently emergent area bordering east edge of Braidwood Lake. Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 170 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (11.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 3
 - *Sphanophyllum* = 1
 - *Pinnularia?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 53 (31.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 8
 - Junior blobs = 16
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - *Etacystis* (the aitch) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, spread valves) = 1
 - *Myalinella* (with macerated plant) = 1
 - *Myalinella* with blob = 1
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 96 (56.4 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 80
 - Dark gray duds = 11

- Pyrite-cored duds = 1
- Septarial duds = 4
- **Rejects: 33**

Locality 306

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/18/24.**

- **Description:** Strip mine terrain in abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 21, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.236682, -88.206723 (GCB); 41.23593224, -88.20522041 (ADM). Area presently is a small island in Braidwood Lake near the northern end of Pit 11. Mine directory number = 834.

- Total counts, based on 127 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 9 (7.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 70 (55.1 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 2
 - Junior blobs = 3
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - Mosaics (septarialized blobs) = 3
 - *Mazonomya* = 57
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Trail = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (7.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 38 (29.9 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 30
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Pyrite-core dud = 1
 - Septarial duds = 5

Locality 307

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/14/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at Ctr, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 21, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.322936, -88.310056 (GCB); 41.32175695, -88.30790808 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 72 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 21 (29.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 4
 - Plant stems = 6
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (1.3 % of total)
 - Possible blob = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (2.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 48 (66.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 48

Locality 308

- **Braidwood; included**—Bed and banks of Mazon River by Rainbow Council Boy Scout reservation Combined summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 04/04/24.
- **Description:** Southeast-facing exposure of Francis Creek Shale in bed and bank along Mazon River (“new Benson’s locality”) southwest of headquarters of the Rainbow Council Boy Scout Reservation at CTR., section 19, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle, digital coordinates estimated at 41.324339, -88.348951 (GCB); 41.31722315, -88.35082365 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 803 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 587 (73.1% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 341
 - *Neuropteris* = 91
 - *Neuropteris rarinervis* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 55
 - *Lepidistrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stem = 53
 - Bark = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 4
 - *Asolanus* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobus* (cones) = 3
 - Cone (*Calamostachys?*) = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Incognitum plant = 2
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - Indeterminate plant = 6
 - **Animals:** Total = 50 (6.2% of total)
 - *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - *Palaeocaris* = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp = 2
 - Arachnid = 1
 - Unidentified arthropod = 1
 - Coprolites = 44
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.3% of total)
 - Incognitum = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 163 (20.2% of total)

- Common duds = 15
- Dark gray duds = 125
- Pyritic duds = 23

Locality 309

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station N”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/12/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 8 strip mine, “station N”) at NE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, section 17, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.341278, -88.334739 (GCB); 41.34031105, -88.33577199 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 348 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 151 (43.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 53
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - Compound Neuropterid fern = 4
 - *Annularia* = 11
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 26
 - Plant stems = 17
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 20
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 4 (2.6 % of total)
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 193 (55.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 108
 - Split duds (total = 75):
 - Gray-brown duds = 65
 - Dark gray duds = 10
 - **Rejects:** 11

Locality 310

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/14/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 28, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.315002, -88.306841 (GCB); 41.31448313, -88.3077755 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 40 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 6 (15.0 % of total)
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 1 (2.5 % of total)
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (5.0 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 31 (77.5 % of total)
 - Sandy gray-brown duds = 12
 - Sandy pyritic duds = 11
 - Dark gray duds = 8

Locality 311

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/14/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at NW1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 16, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.336452, -88.319977 (GCB); 41.33701125, -88.31893916 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 46 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 10 (21.7 % of total)
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (2.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 35 (76.0 % of total)
 - Sandy gray-brown duds = 26
 - Dark gray duds = 7
 - Pyritic duds = 2

Locality 312

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/14/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at SW1/4, SW1/4, section 22, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.317677, -88.301305 (GCB); 41.31820788, -88.30307478 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 29 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 8 (27.5 % of total)
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (6.8 % of total)
 - Coprolite = 1
 - Microburrow = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (3.4 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 18 (62.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 16
 - Dark gray dud = 1
 - Pyritic dud = 1

Locality 313

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 2, “station A”), Wilmington Town Landfill, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/19/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 2 strip mine (“station A”) at Ctr., NW1/4, section 33, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.298874, -88.207054 (GCB); 41.30036865, -88.20437165 (ADM). Property is at the Wilmington Landfill site. Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 343 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 219 (63.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 50
 - *Neuropteris* = 12
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris rarineruis* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 10
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 31
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Plant stems = 31
 - Stems/bark = 33
 - Bark = 9
 - Lycopod bark = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Odontopterid-Neuropterid fern = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* with *Lycopodites* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 26
 - **Animals:** Total = 14 (4.0 % of total)
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Coprolites = 13
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (2.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 100 (29.1 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 64
 - Dark gray duds = 18
 - Sandy dud = 1
 - Septarial duds = 17

Locality 314

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 1B, composite count from Steve Sroka collecting stations 5 and 8), Lake Point Club property, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/19/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1B strip mine (“station 5 and 8”) at Ctr., section 29, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.311800, -88.220818 (GCB); 41.3109555, -88.2191189 (ADM). Property is on the Lake Point Club property. Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 583 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 457 (78.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 65
 - *Neuropteris* = 54
 - *Annularia* = 31
 - *Calamites* = 11
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 44
 - Plant stems = 106
 - Bark = 60
 - *Alethopteris* = 10
 - *Cyclopteris* = 4
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - *Lepidodendron* = 4
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - *Stigmaria* = 11
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Crossotheca* = 1
 - *Odontopteris?* = 2
 - *Cordaites* (pith cast) = 1
 - *Lepidophloios* = 1
 - *Selaginellites* = 2
 - *Cordaicarpus* = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 3
 - Macerated plants = 37
 - **Animals:** Total = 23 (3.9 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 8 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Insect (Palaeodictyoptera) = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 13
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 103 (17.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 103

Locality 315

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 1B, composite count from Steve Sroka collecting stations 9, 10, and 12), Lake Point Club property, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/19/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1B strip mine (“station 9, 10, and 12”) at SW1/4, NW1/4, section 29, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.313163, -88.229573 (GCB); 41.31265583, -88.22633398 (ADM). Property is on the Lake Point Club property. Mine directory number = 359.

- Total counts, based on 540 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 404 (74.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 145
 - *Neuropteris* = 43
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 37
 - Plant stems = 60
 - Bark = 60
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - Cone (*Paleostachya*) = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 32
 - **Animals:** Total = 18 (3.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Insect (Palaeodictyoptera) = 1
 - Insect (cockroach) = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* with *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Coprolites = 12
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 114 (21.1 % of total)
 - Common duds = 114

Locality 316

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 1B, composite count from Steve Sroka collecting stations 1-4, 6, and 7), Lake Point Club property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/19/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1B strip mine (“stations 1-4, 6, and 7”) at SE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 30, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.315197, -88.235113 (GCB); 41.31530825, -88.23241206 (ADM). Property is on the Lake Point Club property. Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 1,566 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 1,013 (64.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 469
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 58
 - *Annularia* = 22
 - *Calamites* = 20
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 73
 - Plant stems = 146
 - Bark = 60
 - *Alethopteris* = 14
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 4
 - *Lepidodendron* = 5
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 12
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Cordaicarpus* = 2
 - *Holospernum* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 3
 - Unidentified fern = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Calamites* cone = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Macerated plants = 108
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 115 (7.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 21 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Unidentified arthropod = 1
 - Coprolites = 92

- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 6 (0.3 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
- **Duds:** Total = 432 (27.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 392
 - Gray duds = 18
 - Gray-brown duds = 10
 - Light gray duds = 8
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 320

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company (Pit 11). Sample manifest from single data sheet as of 03/31/24.**
- **Description:** Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 11) in F-2 area, Will County. Collected by Steve and Daniel Sroka on 5/80 (Sroka station in F-2 grid area, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 31, T32N, R9E, Essex 7.5' quadrangle). Digital coordinates estimated at 41.20726143, -88.22672883 (ADM).
- Total counts, based on 248 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 33 (13.3% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - Plant stem = 13
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 47 (18.9% of total)
 - *Essexella* = 18
 - *Mazonomya* = 2
 - Ghost shrimps = 3
 - *Cyclus* = 5
 - Polychaetes = 5
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 3
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 3
 - Trails/traces = 2
 - Coprolites = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.8% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 166 (66.9% of total)
 - Common duds = 156
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 10

Locality 321

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/25/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at “F-3” grid area, corresponding to NW1/4, SW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.20735408, -88.22194878 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Material collected by Steve and Daniel Sroka on 5/80.
- Total counts, based on 46 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 9 (19.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Plant stems = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 12 (26.0 % of total)
 - Hydroids (*Drevotella?*) = 2
 - Unidentified pecten = 1
 - “Ghost shrimps” (flea shrimps?) = 4
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Head of acanthodian fish = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 25 (54.3 % of total)
 - Common duds = 25

Locality 322

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/25/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at “F-4” grid area, corresponding to SE1/4, SW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.20380773, -88.2171171 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Material collected by Steve Sroka.
- Total counts, based on 458 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 35 (7.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 10
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 7
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 109 (23.7 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 48
 - *Mazonomya* = 10
 - Unidentified pecten = 7
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* with blobs = 4
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Paleocaris* = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 6
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 5
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 4
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 5
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Holothurians = 2
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 3
 - Agnathan *Esconichthys* (the blade) = 1
 - Shark *Dabasacanthus* = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trail = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 314 (68.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 314

Locality 323

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/25/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at “G-5” grid area, corresponding to SW1/4, SE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.20390423, -88.21242733 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Material collected by Steve Sroka.
- Total counts, based on 106 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 21 (19.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 12
 - **Animals:** Total = 11 (10.3 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 3
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 2
 - Coprolites = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.8 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 72 (67.9 % of total)
 - Common duds = 46
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 23
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 324

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (McElvain Pit, “roundworm hill”), Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/19/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corp., Wilmington No. 2 strip mine (“roundworm hill”) at NW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 33, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at approximate digital coordinates 41.213635, -88.196429 (GCB); 41.21236188, -88.19476429 (ADM). Formerly part of South Wilmington Sportsman’s Club. Mine directory number = 402.

- Total counts, based on 180 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 18 (10.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 63 (35.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 26
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 5
 - Multiple blobs = 6
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam per nodule, spread valves) = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - “roundworms” = 5
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (4.4 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Smears = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
 - **Duds:** Total = 91 (50.5 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 91

Locality 325

- **Braidwood**; excluded—Sample from northeast end of abandoned linear strip mine (part of Peobody Coal Company Pit 6 strip mine), formerly known as “Aquacadia” for a defunct water resort, bordering the south side of Lorenzo Road near the west edge of Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/22/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned linear-trending strip mine comprising part of Peobody Coal Company Pit 6 strip mine at NW1/4, section 18, T33N, R9E near the west edge of the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.345936, -88.243407 (GCB); 41.34314425, -88.2437579 (ADM). Formerly part of a resort called Aquacadia that existed prior to my visiting this site. Harold Hill property at the time of visit. Mine directory number = 359.
- **Note:** Concretions largely irregular and of low yield.
- Total counts, based on 56 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 9 (16.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 47 (83.9 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 42
 - Septarial duds = 5
 - White-cored duds = 5
 - **Rejects:** (Irregular sideritic nodules) = 3

Locality 326

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station B”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/22/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station B”) at NW1/4, NE1/4, section 31, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.301338, -88.236732 (GCB); 41.30064526, -88.23669384 (ADM). Miner’s Club property. Mine directory number = 359.

- Total counts, based on 90 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 37 (41.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 13
 - Plant stems = 7
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 2 (2.2 % of total)
 - Coprolites = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (3.3 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Incognitum organisms = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 48 (53.3 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 34
 - Dark (blue-gray) duds = 12
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 327

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station C”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/23/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station C”) at SE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 25, T33N, R8E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.305135, -88.248307 (GCB); 41.30378769, -88.24871816 (ADM). Miner’s Club property. Mine directory number = 359.

- Total counts, based on 72 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 36 (50.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 10
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 2
 - Plant stems = 7
 - Bark = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Sphenopteris?* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 36 (50.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 25
 - Dark gray duds = 7
 - Calcareous dud = 1
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 328

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station D”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/23/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station D”) at Ctr, NW1/4, section 30, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.313579, -88.248307 (GCB); 41.31411915, -88.24293805 (ADM). Miner’s Club property. Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 596 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 419 (70.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 109
 - *Neuropteris* = 9
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 16
 - *Calamites* = 14
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 64
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 87
 - Bark = 11
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Odontopterid-Mariopterid ferns = 2
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - *Spiropteris?* = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 2
 - Unidentified fern = 1
 - Seed? = 1
 - Macerated plants = 79
 - Unidentified plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 19 (3.1 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (probably *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Coprolites = 16
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.8 % of total)
 - Discs = 3
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 153 (25.6 % of total)
 - Common duds = 12
 - Gray-brown duds = 111
 - Dark gray duds = 18
 - Septarial duds = 12

Locality 329

- **Kankakee-Essex; excluded**—Small, unnamed abandoned strip mine on Russell Honrud property, east-southeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 05/10/24.
- **Description:** Small, unnamed abandoned strip mine on Russell Honrud property, south of Route 113 in the NE1/4, NE1/4, section 16, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle with estimated digital coordinates 41.259468, -88.191101 (GCB); 41.2588764, -88.1907981 (ADM). Mine directory number = 402.
- Total counts, based on 273 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (0.7% of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 44 (16.1% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 12
 - Junior blobs = 9
 - Indeterminate blobs = 17
 - Crushed bivalves = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Coprolites = 1
 - Trails/traces = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (1.0% of total)
 - “discs” = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 224 (82.0% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 176
 - Blue-gray duds = 19
 - Dark blue-gray duds = 17
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 12

Locality 330

- **Will-Essex; included—Shaft cone of abandoned shaft mine “O”. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 04/03/24.**
- **Description:** Small, largely vegetated over shaft mine tip heap of abandoned deep mine “O” at SE1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T32N, R9E, on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle, in village of Braidwood, Illinois, estimated digital coordinates 41.270096, -88.211358 (GCB); 41.26857323, -88.2115922 (ADM). Mine not relocated using Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 384 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 125 (32.5% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 22
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Plant stem = 41
 - Bark = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Pinnularia?* = 1
 - “odd fern” = 1
 - Seed? = 1
 - Macerated plant = 18
 - Unidentified plant = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 53 (13.8% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 14
 - Junior blob = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 4
 - “odd blob” = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam) = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 7
 - *Myalinella* cluster (crushed) = 1
 - Crushed *Myalinella* = 1
 - *Myalinella* with plant stem = 1
 - “Hill 20 clam” = 2
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Indeterminate bivalve with associated trail/trace = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* (molted) = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Millepede = 1
 - *Didontogaster* (tummy tooth) = 5
 - Indeterminate polychaete = 2

- Trail/trace = 1
- Coprolites = 3
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (3.3% of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 12
- **Duds:** Total = 194 (50.5% of total)
 - Common duds = 46
 - Gray-brown duds = 111
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 28
 - Septarial duds = 9
- **Rejects:** 10

Locality 331

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, Station “D”) at east edge of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/23/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, station “D”) at SW1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.278598, -88.205646 (GCB); 41.27733631, -88.20535968 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3916, suggests that this is the record of a shaft mine within the larger area of Pit 4.
- Total counts, based on 119 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 55 (46.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 13
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 6
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - Plant stems = 7
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - Macerated plants = 8
 - **Animals:** Total = 4 (3.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (8.4 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Incognitum organism = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 50 (42.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 39
 - Septarial duds = 11

Locality 332

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, Station “E”) at east edge of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/23/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 4 strip mine, station “E”) at CTR, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at approximate digital coordinates 41.281933, -88.204999 (GCB); 41.28043958, -88.20601378 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 250 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 153 (61.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 34
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 26
 - Plant stems = 25
 - Bark = 8
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - *Cordaites* = 1
 - Cones = 2
 - Macerated plants = 11
 - Unidentified plants = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 8 (3.2 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (4.0 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
 - **Duds:** Total = 79 (31.6 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 56
 - Dark gray duds = 8
 - Weathered duds = 8
 - Septarial duds = 7

Locality 333

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 3 strip mine, Station “A”) northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/23/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 3 strip mine, station “A”) at SE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 33, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at approximate digital coordinates 41.301197, -88.190420 (GCB); 41.301565, -88.19116446 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 510 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 356 (69.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 68
 - *Neuropteris* = 27
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 4
 - *Annularia* = 28
 - *Calamites* = 15
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 34
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - Plant stems = 24
 - Bark = 2
 - Stems/bark = 48
 - *Alethopteris* = 5
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Alethopteris sullivanti* = 4
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 7
 - *Sphenopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - *Lycopodites* = 4
 - *Aphlebia* = 3
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - Immature *Calamites* foliage = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Cone (*Calamostachys?*) = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Seed (*Trigonocarpus?*) = 1
 - Macerated plants = 57
 - Unidentified plants = 11
 - **Animals:** Total = 34 (6.6 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 4 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Nonmarine bivalve with plant stem = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 3
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 3
 - *Euproops* cluster = 1

- Ostracodes = 1
- Polychaete *Spirorbis* on bark = 2
- Coprolites = 19
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
- **Duds:** Total = 115 (22.5 % of total)
 - Common duds = 51
 - Gray-brown duds = 55
 - Dark gray duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 334

- **Will-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, Goose Lake Club, “Beaver Lakes area”), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 06/17/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine, Goose Lake Club, “Beaver Lakes area”) at SW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 16, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.341273, -88.323769 (GCB); 41.34236911, -88.3238279 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 166 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 56 (33.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 7
 - *Neuropteris* = 10
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stems = 13
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 12
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 27 (16.2 % of total)
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*; valves closed) = 11
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Xenocanth shark tooth = 1
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Traces/trails = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (6.0 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
 - **Duds:** Total = 73 (43.9 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 61
 - Dark gray duds = 5
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 335

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned shaft mine near southeast margin of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 04/30/24.
- **Description:** Small, vegetated over spoil mound of abandoned shaft mine at center, SW1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 9, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.261536, -88.205616 (GCB); 41.26229383, -88.20539083 (ADM). No mine recorded at this position (outside of the southwest margin of Pit 5) on latest mine directory, but mine shown on original directory from the 1980s. Hill possibly still discernable on Google Earth.
- Total counts, based on 123 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 6 (4.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - Plant stems = 3
 - Macerated plants = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 7 (5.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 1
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (= *Edmondia*) showing multiple clams) = 1
 - Chiton *Glaphurochiton*: 1 (found here, but not recorded in this lot)
 - Echiuran *Caprinoscolex* = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (2.4% of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 107 (86.9% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 96
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 11

Locality 336

- **Will-Essex; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “D”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/24/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “D”) at CTR, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 9, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.263237, -88.191422 (GCB); 41.26252265, -88.1909708 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 196 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 7 (3.5 % of total)
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stems = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 19 (9.6 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blobs = 2
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - Probable blobs = 2
 - *Mazonomya* (one clam per nodule, spread valves) = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Trails = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 169 (86.2 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 136
 - Dark gray duds = 17
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 12
 - Septarial dud = 4

Locality 337

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “E”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/24/24.**

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “E”) at SW1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 9, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.264206, -88.198432 (GCB); 41.26516704, -88.19712039 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.

- Total counts, based on 96 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 11 (11.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 3
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 25 (26.0 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 3
 - Junior blobs = 5
 - Indeterminate blobs = 6
 - Hydroid *Drevotella* = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Coelocanth *Rhabdoderma* = 1
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Trails = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (3.1 % of total)
 - Smears = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 57 (59.3 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 29
 - Blue-gray duds = 25
 - Pyrite-cored dud = 1
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 338

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “F”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/24/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “F”) at NE1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 9, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at approximate digital coordinates 41.270951, -88.189967 (GCB); 41.2708186, -88.19030936 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 21 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 12 (57.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 5
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (9.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 7 (33.3 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 4
 - Blue-gray duds = 3

Locality 339

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine behind Drake’s Restaurant, Goose Lake Club property), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/17/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine behind Drake’s Restaurant, barren hills on Goose Lake Club property) at SE1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 16, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.342307, -88.313709 (GCB); 41.34259833, -88.31191696 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 21 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 5 (23.8 % of total)
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 16 (76.1 % of total)
 - Gray-brown sandy duds = 11
 - Dark gray sandy duds = 5
 - **Note:**
 - This mine area is notably barren, non-vegetated, and appears to display acid mine leaching. Dump ridges display silty, flaggy lithology with sideritic platelets. Decent, collectable concretions are nearly absent. This area appears to be proximal to a coastal channel.

Locality 340

- **Braidwood; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Station “G”) east of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/24/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, station “G”) at SE1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 3, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.276820, -88.184834 (GCB); 41.27636644, -88.18580641 (ADM). Location immediately southwest of Meneoka Club area. Mine directory number = 359.

- Total counts, based on 94 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 25 (26.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - Plant stem = 1
 - Bark = 1
 - Macerated plants = 17
 - **Animals:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 69 (73.4 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 21
 - Blue-gray duds = 47
 - Septarial dud = 1

Locality 341

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corporation, Wilmington Mine northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/24/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Wilmington Coal Mining Corporation, Wilmington Mine at CTR, section 3, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.283803, -88.177992 (GCB); 41.2827252, -88.1797697 (ADM). Located in the Meneoka Club area. Mine directory number = 3915/402.
- Total counts, based on 151 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 89 (58.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 16
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Stems/bark = 9
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - Mariopterid-Odontopterid fern = 2
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Unidentified fern = 1
 - Macerated plants = 31
 - **Animals:** Total = 5 (3.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 55 (36.4 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 53
 - Dark gray dud = 1
 - Septarial dud = 1

Locality 342

- **Essex indeterminate; excluded—Abandoned Co-operative Coal Company, co-operative shaft mine in the eastern part of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 04/30/24.**
- **Description:** Spoil mound of abandoned, Co-operative Coal Company, co-operative shaft mine, east of the Braidwood Town Park at NW1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 8, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.268849, -88.215362 (GCB); 41.26897189, -88.21456581 (ADM). Mine directory number = 3930. Mine hill cryptic on Google Earth. If present, it is highly grown over by trees.
- Total counts, based on 304 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 58 (19% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 7
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Plant stems = 14
 - Stem/bark = 2
 - Bark = 8
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* trunk = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 1
 - Indeterminate plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 81 (26.6% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 16
 - Junior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalves = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve with spore case = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 4
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Coprolites = 7
 - Trails/traces = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (6.5% of total)
 - “discs” = 5
 - Unidentified nucleus = 15

- **Duds:** Total = 145 (47.6% of total)
 - Common duds = 8
 - Gray duds = 18
 - Gray-brown duds = 72
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 41
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - Pelletal dud = 1
- **Rejects:** 97

Locality 343

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Hidden Lakes Fee Fishing Concession area) northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/25/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine at Hidden Lakes Fee Fishing Concession Area) at NW1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 3, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.285435, -88.177552 (GCB); 41.28549275, -88.17862374 (ADM). Mine directory number is uncertain.

- Total counts, based on 467 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 292 (62.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 92
 - *Neuropteris* = 14
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 15
 - *Calamites* = 11
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 37
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 49
 - Stems/bark = 17
 - Bark = 11
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 4
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - *Psaronius* stem? = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 5
 - Seed = 2
 - Macerated plants = 13
 - Unidentified plant = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 30 (6.4 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* (two individuals in nodule) = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 2
 - Fish tooth or scale = 1
 - Coprolites = 22
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (2.1 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
 - **Duds:** Total = 135 (28.9 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 126
 - Dark gray duds = 2

- Blue-gray duds = 2
- Septarial duds = 5

Locality 344

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station E”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/25/24.
- Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station E”), Miner’s Club property, at NE1/4, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 30, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.308690, -88.228751 (GCB); 41.30624825, -88.23201664 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 295 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 202 (68.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 74
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Annularia* with *Calamites* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 19
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 12
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 42
 - Bark = 14
 - *Alethopteris sullivanti* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 5
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 15 (5.0 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 3
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 8
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (1.0 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 75 (25.4 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 32
 - Weathered brown duds = 30
 - Septarial duds = 13

Locality 345

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station F”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/25/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station F”), Miner’s Club property, at SE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 31, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.300684, -88.229503 (GCB); 41.30081211, -88.22952416 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 702 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 479 (68.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 204
 - *Neuropteris* = 26
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Annularia* = 18
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 41
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - Plant stems = 79
 - Bark = 30
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Spiropteris* with *Lepidophylloides* = 1
 - *Odontopteris?* = 1
 - Cones = 2
 - Seed *Trigonocarpus* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 35
 - Unidentified plants = 7
 - **Animals:** Total = 47 (6.6 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 5 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconaia*)
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 39
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 4 (0.5 % of total)
 - Discs = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 172 (24.5 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 18

- Gray-brown duds = 41
- Dark gray duds = 5
- Blue-gray duds = 22
- Weathered duds = 81
- Septarial duds = 5

Locality 346

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station B”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from four data sheets updated as of 07/25/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station B”), CECO Club property, at CTR, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 25, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.312719, -88.254190 (GCB); 41.31189958, -88.25486593 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 783 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 366 (46.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 88
 - *Neuropteris* = 18
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 16
 - *Calamites* = 16
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 37
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 4
 - Plant stems = 21
 - Stems/bark = 13
 - Bark = 42
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 7
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 4
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 4
 - *Stigmaria* = 4
 - Cone = 1
 - Seeds = 2
 - Seed (*Samaropsis*) = 1
 - Macerated plants = 78
 - Unidentified plant = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 111 (14.1 % of total)
 - *Myalinella* with nonmarine clams and ostracodes = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 11 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified shrimp = 2
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 3
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* (prosoma) = 1
 - *Euproops* in coprolite = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1

- Coprolites = 89
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 10 (1.2 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 10
- **Duds:** Total = 296 (37.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 148
 - Blue-gray duds = 137
 - Dark gray duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 5
- **Rejects:** 12

Locality 347

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station C”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/26/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station C”), CECO Club property, at NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 25, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.307558, -88.256813 (GCB); 41.30595191, -88.25650427 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 394 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 242 (61.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 49
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 13
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 43
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster with bark = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Plant stems = 17
 - Bark = 31
 - Stems/bark = 12
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* or *Lepidophloios* = 4
 - *Lepidophloios*- *Stigmarioides*? = 4
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - Cones = 2
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Seed in coprolite = 1
 - Fructification = 1
 - Macerated plants = 34
 - Unidentified plants = 5
 - **Animals:** Total = 30 (7.6 % of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 5 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 2
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Millepede *Euphoberia* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 18
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3

- **Duds:** Total = 119 (30.2 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 35
 - Weathered duds = 40
 - Blue-gray duds = 19
 - Dark gray duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 20

Locality 348

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station D”), Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/26/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station D”), CECO Club property, at CTR, SW1/4, section 19, T33N, R9E near west edge of the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.320894, -88.243663 (GCB); 41.32139165, -88.2431391 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.

- Total counts, based on 382 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 265 (69.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 52
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Calamites* = 12
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 53
 - Plant stems = 58
 - Bark = 28
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 16
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - Seed = 2
 - Macerated plants = 15
 - Unidentified plant = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 38 (9.9 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Meiofaunal arthropod *Cyzicus* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 2
 - Coprolites = 33
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 76 (19.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 49
 - Weathered duds = 19
 - Septarial duds = 8

Locality 349

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station E”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/26/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station E”), CECO Club property, at NW1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 25, T33N, R8E near east edge of the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.316426, -88.250810 (GCB); 41.31649226, -88.25138866 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 300 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 194 (64.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 31
 - *Neuropteris* = 11
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 6
 - *Annularia* = 24
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 19
 - Plant stems = 32
 - Bark = 20
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 2
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 44
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 22 (7.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Ostracods in coprolite = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Coprolites = 17
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 83 (27.6 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 36
 - Weathered duds = 14
 - Gray-brown duds = 6
 - Blue-gray duds = 8
 - Dark gray duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 13

Locality 350

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station F”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station F”), CECO Club property, at CTR, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 25, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.316696, -88.264781 (GCB); 41.31542683, -88.26456113 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 695 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 345 (49.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 66
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 11
 - *Annularia* = 25
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 81
 - Plant stems = 31
 - Bark = 17
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Odontopterid fern = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 4
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - Seeds = 3
 - Macerated plants = 85
 - Unidentified plant = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 65 (9.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 6 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 3
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 4
 - Unidentified syncarids = 4
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 3
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 7
 - Coprolites = 38
 - Incognitum animal = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (0.7 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 5
 - **Duds:** Total = 280 (40.2 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 58
 - Dark gray duds = 11
 - Weathered duds = 199
 - Sandy duds = 12

Locality 351

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station G”), Grundy County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station G”), CECO Club property, at NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 25, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.309079, -88.265254 (GCB); 41.30901436, -88.26553451 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 536 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 327 (61.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 153
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 13
 - *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 38
 - *Lepidophylloides* clusters = 2
 - Plant stems = 32
 - Bark = 16
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Mariopteris* – *Odontopteris*? = 1
 - *Stigmaia* = 3
 - Macerated plants = 42
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 29 (5.4 % of total)
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Unidentified myriopod = 1
 - Coprolites = 23
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 177 (33.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 42
 - Dark gray duds = 5
 - Weathered duds = 119
 - Sandy duds = 7
 - Septarial duds = 3
 - Sphalerite centered dud = 1

Locality 352

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station G”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station G”), Miner’s Club property, at SW1/4, SW1/4, section 30, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.306082, -88.245458 (GCB); 41.30498765, -88.24518093 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 532 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 361 (67.8 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 110
 - *Neuropteris* = 17
 - *Annularia* = 24
 - *Calamites* = 21
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 43
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - Plant stems = 83
 - Bark = 29
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 27
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Caulopteris* (stem joint?) = 1
 - *Aphlebia?* = 1
 - Seed = 2
 - Cone? = 1
 - Macerated plants = 37
 - Unidentified plants = 10
 - **Animals:** Total = 39 (7.3 % of total)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson?* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 2
 - Millepede *Acantherpestes?* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 2
 - *Palaeoxyris* with *Calamites* = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Coprolites = 30
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 8 (1.5 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 8
 - **Duds:** Total = 124 (23.3 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 6
 - Gray-brown duds = 75

- Blue gray duds = 20
- Dark gray duds = 2
- Septarial duds = 21

Locality 353

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station H”), Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station H”), CECO Club property, at NW1/4, NE1/4, SE1/4, section 24, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.323992, -88.250879 (GCB); 41.32380778, -88.25153975 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 106 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 64 (60.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 12
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Plant stem = 13
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Seeds = 1
 - Macerated plants = 14
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 6 (5.6 % of total)
 - Millepede (*Euphoberia*) = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 36 (33.9 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 29
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Sandy duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 354

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 6 (“station i”), Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/29/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 6 strip mine (“station i”), CECO Club property, at NW1/4, SW1/4, SW1/4, section 19, T33N, R9E near west edge of the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.321158, -88.245945 (GCB); 41.3204059, -88.246654 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 173 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 137 (79.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 27
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 28
 - *Calamites* = 7
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 44
 - Plant stems = 14
 - Bark = 6
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Seed case = 1
 - Incognitum plant (segmented) = 1
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plant = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 12 (6.9 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Coprolites = 6
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 24 (13.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 20
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 355

- **Kankakee-Essex; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station H”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/29/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station H”), Miner’s Club property, at NW1/4, NE1/4, SW1/4, section 31, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.294284, -88.241048 (GCB); 41.29508344, -88.24130953 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.

- Total counts, based on 144 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 63 (43.7 % of total)
 - *Pecepteris* = 21
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 8
 - Plant stems = 6
 - Bark = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 12
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 8 (5.5 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Coprolites = 5
 - Trail = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.6 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 72 (50.0 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 62
 - Blue-gray duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 7

Locality 356

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 3 strip mine, Station “B”) northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from five data sheets updated as of 07/30/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 3 strip mine, station “B”) at NE1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 34, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.301736, -88.186412 (GCB); 41.30350053, -88.18638961 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 433 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 293 (67.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 48
 - *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 29
 - *Calamites* = 12
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 67
 - *Lepidophylloides* cluster = 1
 - Plant stems = 44
 - Bark = 10
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 2
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 3
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Asolanus* = 1
 - Branch tuft = 2
 - Plant fructification = 1
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - Cones = 3
 - Seed? = 1
 - Macerated plants = 33
 - Unidentified plants = 13
 - **Animals:** Total = 11 (2.5 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Nonmarine bivalve with horseshoe crab *Euproops* = 1
 - Ammonite (goniatite) = 1

- Millepede *Amyndes*? = 1
- Coprolites = 7
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (1.1 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 4
- **Duds:** Total = 124 (28.6 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 114
 - Dark gray duds = 9
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 357

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, strip mine No. 1 (“station i”), Miner’s Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/30/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1 strip mine (“station i”), Miner’s Club property, at CTR, NW1/4, section 32, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.301091, -88.226351 (GCB); 41.3000167, -88.22351975 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 172 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 120 (69.7 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 25
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 7
 - *Calamites* = 4
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 21
 - Plant stems = 23
 - Bark = 11
 - *Alethopteris* = 3
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - Sideritized internal cast of lycopod trunk = 1
 - Macerated plants = 13
 - **Animals:** Total = 11 (6.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 4 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Coprolites = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.1 % of total)
 - Lumpy nodule = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 39 (22.6 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 31
 - Blue-gray duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 3

Locality 358

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 3 strip mine, Station “C”, “Piano Hill” arachnid locality) northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/30/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 3 strip mine, station “C”, Piano Hill arachnid locality) at E1/3, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 33, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.292408, -88.190041 (GCB); 41.29341781, -88.19330961 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 312 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 211 (67.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 46
 - *Neuropteris* = 11
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 7
 - *Annularia* = 12
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 22
 - Plant stems = 48
 - Bark = 4
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 4
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 5
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - *Stigmaria?* = 1
 - Seed = 2
 - Seed (*Cordaites*) = 1
 - Macerated plants = 28
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 19 (6.0 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* (very large specimen) = 1
 - Coprolites = 17
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (0.9 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 79 (25.3 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 64
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Blue-gray duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 7

Locality 359

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 1B, Greine’s Property, Station “A”), Lake Point Club property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 07/30/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1B strip mine (station “A” = big hill under power lines south of waterway), Greine’s property, at E1/2, SE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 19, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.319000, -88.237362 (GCB); 41.3187527, -88.238934 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 535 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 376 (70.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 80
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 21
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 24
 - *Annularia* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 25
 - *Calamites* with foliage = 1
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 22
 - Plant stems = 67
 - Bark = 40
 - Bark with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 24
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Odontopterid* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - *Spiropteris* = 1
 - *Pinnularia* = 1
 - *Cordaites* = 1
 - *Psaronius?* (trunk) = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Lycopodites* = 3
 - *Lycopodites* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Mariopteris?* = 1
 - Jointed plant stem = 1
 - Cone *Lepidostrobus* = 1
 - Cone *Salaginites?* = 1
 - Cone? (cluster) = 1

- Seed *Trigonocarpus* = 1
- Seeds = 3
- Macerated plants = 27
- Unidentified plants = 8
- **Animals:** Total = 74 (13.8 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 3
 - Fin spine (shark-fish?) = 1
 - Lungfish scale *Ctenodus* = 1
 - Coprolites = 68
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
- **Duds:** Total = 85 (15.8 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 59
 - Gray-brown duds = 24
 - Dark gray duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 360

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 1B, Greine’s Property, Station “B”), Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/30/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1B strip mine (station “B”), Greine’s property, at NE1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 30, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.316603, -88.236252 (GCB); 41.31702123, -88.2347654 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 233 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 173 (74.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 58
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Annularia* with compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 2
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 37
 - Plant stems = 20
 - Bark = 6
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 5
 - *Asterophyllites* = 3
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 2
 - *Aphlebia* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Seed? = 1
 - Large seed with elastic cuticle = 1
 - Macerated plants = 18
 - Unidentified plants = 9
 - **Animals:** Total = 15 (6.4 % of total)
 - Coprolites = 15
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.4 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 44 (18.8 % of total)
 - Dark gray duds = 32
 - Pyritic duds = 6
 - Septarial duds = 6

Locality 361

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 1B, Greine’s Property, Station “C”), Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/31/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 1B strip mine (station “C”), Greine’s property, at NE1/4, SE1/4, NW1/4, NE1/4, section 30, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.314739, -88.231789 (GCB); 41.31564446, -88.23532172 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 113 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 82 (72.5 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 11
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 3
 - *Annularia* = 10
 - *Calamites* = 8
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 5
 - Plant stems = 6
 - Bark = 3
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 2
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Megaspores in coprolite = 1
 - Macerated plants = 23
 - Unidentified plants = 3
 - **Animals:** Total = 9 (7.9 % of total)
 - Coprolites = 9
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 22 (19.4 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 5
 - Blue-gray duds = 12
 - Dark gray duds = 4
 - Septarial duds = 1

Locality 362

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 2, “station B”), Wilmington Recreation Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/31/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 2 strip mine (“station B”), Wilmington Recreation Club property, at SW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 33, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.292623, -88.199227 (GCB); 41.2905427, -88.19809656 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 673 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 485 (72.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 211
 - *Neuropteris* = 28
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 16
 - *Annularia* = 23
 - *Calamites* = 9
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 38
 - Plant stems = 95
 - Bark = 8
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Alethopteris sullivanti* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Odontopteris* = 2
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - *Cordaicarpus?* = 1
 - Lycopod bark = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 6
 - *Lycopodites* = 4
 - Fructification = 1
 - Cone (*Selaginites?*) = 1
 - Unidentified cone = 1
 - Seed = 1
 - Macerated plants = 22
 - Unidentified plants = 10
 - **Animals:** Total = 33 (4.9 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve and ostracod = 1
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 2
 - Syncarid shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - Arachnid = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* with *Calamites* = 1
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1

- Coprolites = 26
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.2 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
- **Duds:** Total = 153 (22.7 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 112
 - Dark gray duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 38

Locality 363

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 2, “station C”), Wilmington Recreation Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/31/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 2 strip mine (“station C”), Wilmington Recreation Club property, at NE1/4, NW1/4, SE1/4, section 33, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.296817, -88.195570 (GCB); 41.29603006, -88.19584088 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 187 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 127 (67.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 14
 - *Pecopteris* with *Annularia* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 9
 - *Calamites* = 5
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 23
 - Plant stems = 47
 - Bark = 7
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 3
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Lycopodites* with *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Cone (*Selaginites?*) = 2
 - Macerated plants = 9
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 16 (8.5 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalve = 1 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Coprolites = 14
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 3 (1.6 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 2
 - **Duds:** Total = 41 (21.9 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 37
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 364

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 5 strip mine, Lake Will Recreation Club “Crow’s Nest area”) northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/31/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 5 strip mine at Lake Will Recreation Club, “Crow’s Nest area” at E1/2, SE1/4, SE1/4, section 3, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.277919, -88.171649 (GCB); 41.27922679, -88.17380054 (ADM). Mine directory number appears to be 3915/402.
- Total counts, based on 323 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 252 (78.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 162
 - *Neuropteris* = 6
 - Compound *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 22
 - Plant stems = 30
 - Bark = 4
 - *Alethopteris* = 2
 - *Alethopteris sullivanii* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Psaronius?* Stem = 1
 - Macerated plants = 7
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 8 (2.4 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 3 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Unidentified syncarid shrimp* = 1 (collected by amateur in our group)
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 4
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (0.3 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 62 (19.1 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 57
 - Septarial duds = 5

Locality 365

- **No assignment; excluded**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine), northwest of Coal City, Grundy County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/14/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine (Pit 7 strip mine) at SE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 22, T33N, R8E on the Coal City 7.5' quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.317502, -88.298207 (GCB); 41.31743091, -88.29705686 (ADM). Mine directory number = 675.
- Total counts, based on 120 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 47 (39.1 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 12
 - *Neuropteris* = 5
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 7
 - Plant stem = 11
 - Bark = 1
 - *Sphenophyllum* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 2
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 10 (8.3 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Palaeoniscoid fish = 1
 - Coprolites = 3
 - Traces/trails = 2
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (1.6 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 61 (50.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 50
 - Dark gray duds = 7
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 366

- **Braidwood; included**—Modified Northern Illinois Coal Company strip mine area (Pit 4) northeast of Braidwood, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 06/13/24.
- **Description:** Fresh north-south road excavation through unreclaimed, heavily vegetated, westernmost part of Pit 4 strip mine area at SW1/4, NW1/4, section 4, T32N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.284862, -88.206686 (GCB). This road corresponds to present-day Hole-in-the-Wall Court (road in housing subdivision). At the time the fresh excavation revealed an abundance of medium to large concretions in the road bed.
- Total counts, based on 417 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 300 (71.9 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 132
 - *Neuropteris* = 30
 - *Annularia* = 25
 - *Calamites* = 10
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 14
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 6
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - Bark and stems = 42
 - *Alethopteris* = 4
 - *Cyclopteris* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 2
 - Cones = 2
 - Macerated plants = 30
 - Indeterminate plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 15 (3.5 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 2 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Indeterminate bivalves = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - *Spirorbis* = 1
 - Coprolites = 10
 - **Duds:** Total = 102 (24.4 % of total)
 - Common duds = 89
 - Septarial duds = 13

Locality 367

- **Braidwood; included**—Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 2, “station D”), Wilmington Recreation Club Property, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from two data sheets updated as of 07/31/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine, Pit 2 strip mine (“station D”), Wilmington Recreation Club property, at CTR, SE1/4, section 32, T33N, R9E on the Wilmington 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.294478, -88.210708 (GCB); 41.29293625, -88.2137362 (ADM). Mine directory number = 359.
- Total counts, based on 553 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 415 (75.0 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 161
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 16
 - *Annularia* = 16
 - *Calamites* = 21
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 19
 - Plant stems = 42
 - Bark = 26
 - *Alethopteris* = 11
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - *Stigmaria* = 9
 - *Aphlebia* = 2
 - *Lycopodites* = 1
 - Seed (*Trigoncarpus*) = 2
 - Macerated plants = 82
 - Unidentified plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 37 (6.6 % of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 6 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp *Paleocaris* = 1
 - Horseshoe crab *Euproops* (fragment) = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* = 2
 - *Palaeoxyris* = 1
 - Coprolites = 26
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 2 (0.3 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - Unidentified nucleus = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 99 (17.9 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 38
 - Weathered duds = 61

Locality 368

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/31/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SW1/4, SE1/4, NE1/4, section 20, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.239507, -88.216095 (GCB); 41.23943605, -88.21019654 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Northern end of Pit 11. Much of collecting area currently submerged under Braidwood Lake.
- Total counts, based on 170 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 16 (9.4 % of total)
 - *Annularia* = 2
 - Plant stems = 2
 - *Lepidostrobophyllum* = 1
 - Macerated plants = 10
 - Unidentified plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 15 (8.8 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 1
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - Multiple blobs = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 7
 - *Myalinella* = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Coprolite = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 5 (2.9 % of total)
 - Discs = 2
 - Unidentified nucleus = 3
 - **Duds:** Total = 134 (78.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 105
 - Light gray duds = 12
 - Dark gray duds = 10
 - Blue-gray dud = 1
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 2
 - Septarial duds = 4
 - **Rejects:** 32

Locality 369

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, “station 3 – page two”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 08/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11, “station 3 = page two”) at SW1/4, SW1/4, SE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.218443, -88.217563 (GCB); 41.2174455, -88.21641724 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Part of collecting area currently submerged under Braidwood Lake.
- **Note:** Entry #369 originally consisted of five census sheets, three of which represented “locality 166” (T-25 locality of Tom Beard, now relocated to its proper ordered sequence), one additional page with same coordinates as # 166, but entered as “Greenland” (now listed as sample # 414), and one last page with coordinates different than the remaining four. This page solely represents that last page of the five census sheets. Owing to these issues, in our data analyses, locality 166 did not meet our filtering threshold for inclusion. The tallies for 369, on the other hand, were inflated as a combination of three different collections and should thus be viewed with caution.
- Total counts, based on 426 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 20 (4.6 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 2
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - Stems/bark = 5
 - *Lepidodendron* = 2
 - Macerated plants = 4
 - **Animals:** Total = 195 (45.7 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 17
 - Junior blobs = 48
 - Indeterminate blobs = 7
 - Multiple blobs = 2
 - Hydroid *Drevotella* = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (spread valves) = 14
 - *Mazonomya* (closed valves) = 12
 - *Mazonomya* with burrow = 1
 - Unidentified clam with burrow = 1
 - Crushed bivalve = 1
 - Gastropod *Euphemites* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 3
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 10
 - Polychaete Simple Jaw? = 1
 - Polychaete *Pieckonia* = 2

- Holothurians = 22
- Coprolites = 12
- Trails = 39
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 13 (3.0 % of total)
 - Spots = 5
 - Discs = 8
- **Duds:** Total = 198 (46.4 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 91
 - Pyrite-cored duds = 63
 - Weathered duds = 42
 - Septarial duds = 2

Locality 370

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 08/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, SW1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.21205036, -88.21151433 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Part of collecting area currently emergent as island in Braidwood Lake. Sample collected by Mary Phillips.
- **Note:** This tally should be read with caution. Although the animal counts appear reasonable, plants were not cited and the duds and rejects were merged into a single total.
- Total counts, based on 634 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - None reported = 0
 - **Animals:** Total = 45 (7.0 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 11
 - *Mazonomya* = 10
 - *Aviculopecten* = 1
 - Gastropod *Strobeus* = 1
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 2
 - *Cyclus* = 3
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 3
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 2
 - Holothurians = 3
 - Coprolites = 2
 - Trails = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 9 (1.4 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 9
 - **Duds:** Total = 580 (91.4 % of total)
 - Duds and rejects grouped together = 580

Locality 371

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 08/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at NE1/4, NE1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.216104, -88.209768 (GCB); 41.21480913, -88.20805855 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Collecting area currently partly submerged under Braidwood Lake.
- **Note:** This tally should be read with caution as the findings are not at a high enough resolution.
- Total counts, based on 175 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 32 (18.2 % of total)
 - Not subdivided (total = 32)
 - **Animals:** Total = 19 (10.8 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 4
 - Unidentified shrimps = 3
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Holothurians = 3
 - Trails = 7
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 12 (6.8 % of total)
 - Unidentified nucleus = 12
 - **Duds and rejects:** Total = 112 (64.0 % of total)
 - Duds and rejects combined = 112

Locality 372

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 08/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SE1/4, section 20, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5' quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.231752, -88.209487 (GCB); 41.23230468, -88.20741091 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Part of collecting area currently emergent as island in Braidwood Lake.
- Total counts, based on 68 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 3 (4.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 28 (41.1 % of total)
 - Senior blob = 1
 - Junior blob = 1
 - Indeterminate blob = 1
 - *Mazonomya* (spread valves) = 8
 - *Mazonomya* (closed valves) = 10
 - *Mazonomya* (two clams, one open and one closed valves) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* with burrow = 3
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Trail = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (1.4 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 36 (52.9 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 32
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 373

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, “station 4”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 08/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11, “station 4”) at NE1/4, NE1/4, NE1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.230074, -88.209840 (GCB); 41.23048749, -88.20732856 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Part of collecting area currently emergent as island in Braidwood Lake.
- Total counts, based on 55 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 4 (7.2 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - Plant stem = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 26 (47.2 % of total)
 - Indeterminate blobs = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (clam with spread valves) = 4
 - *Mazonomya* (clam with closed valves) = 12
 - Two or more *Mazonomya* per nodule with spread valves = 2
 - Bivalve *Schizodus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Trails = 3
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (1.8 % of total)
 - Disc = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 24 (43.6 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 17
 - Weathered duds = 3
 - Septarial duds = 4

Locality 374

- **Will-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, “station 2”, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 08/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11, “station 2”) at NW1/4, NW1/4, NW1/4, section 28, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.230459, -88.206554 (GCB); 41.23052848, -88.2049403 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Collecting area currently submerged under Braidwood Lake.
- Total counts, based on 325 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 14 (4.3 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - *Annularia* = 4
 - Plant stems = 2
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Asterophyllites* = 1
 - *Lepidodendron* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 168 (51.6 % of total)
 - Senior, Junior, and Intermediate blobs = ?*
 - blob entries were left out; discrepancy of 15 counts short between sample total compiled (340 total concretions at the time of original entry)
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, closed valves) = 99
 - *Mazonomya* (single clam, valve spread) = 33
 - *Mazonomya* (two or more clams per nodule, valves spread) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* with burrow = 1
 - *Mazonomya* with polychaete = 1
 - *Myalinella* (= “*Septimyalina*”) = 1
 - “Megaclam” (*Schizodus*) = 3
 - Unidentified bivalve = 1
 - Shrimp *Mamayocaris* = 1
 - Polychaete *Spirorbis* on bark = 1
 - Unidentified polychaetes = 2
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Holothurian = 1
 - Coprolites = 16
 - Trails = 5
 - Burrow = 1
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 143 (44.0 % of total)
 - Gray duds = 132
 - Weathered duds = 5
 - Septarial duds = 6

Locality 375

- **Kankakee-Essex; included—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, “Hydroid Hill” at east end of “Tully Port” area, Will County, Illinois. Summary sample manifest from three data sheets updated as of 08/01/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11, “Hydroid Hill” at east end of “Tully Port” area) at NW1/4, NW1/4, SW1/4, section 32, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at estimated digital coordinates 41.20824544, -88.22315919 (ADM). Mine directory number = 834. Collecting area currently largely submerged under Braidwood Lake.
- Total counts, based on 369 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 46 (12.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 10
 - *Neuropteris* = 4
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 4
 - *Annularia* = 1
 - *Calamites* = 1
 - Plant stems = 18
 - Bark = 2
 - *Alethopteris* = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 2
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 119 (32.2 % of total)
 - Senior blobs = 27
 - Junior blobs = 35
 - Indeterminate blob = 5
 - *Reticulomedusa* = 1
 - Hydroid *Drevotella* = 4
 - Bivalve *Dunbarella* = 1
 - Unidentified pecten = 1
 - Unidentified bivalve = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 14
 - Shrimp *Kallidecthes* = 1
 - Shrimp *Acanthotelson* = 1
 - *Cyclus* = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 1
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 3
 - Unidentified polychaete = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 3
 - *Tullimonstrum* = 4
 - Coprolites = 14
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 20 (5.4 % of total)
 - Incognitum organism = 1

- Discs = 11
- Unidentified nucleus = 8
- **Duds:** Total = 184 (49.8 % of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 71
 - Gray duds = 42
 - Weathered duds = 70
 - Septarial dud = 1

Locality 384

- **No assignment; excluded**—Durrill Farm strip mine, Windsor, Missouri. Combined summary sample manifest of all eight data sheets updated as of 03/24/24.
- **Description:** Shale above Croweburg Coal. Abandoned strip mine on Durrill Farm property west of Windsor, Henry County, Missouri at coordinates S1/2, SW1/4, section T43N, R24W, Windsor 7.5' quadrangle with digital coordinates approximated at 38.530544, -93.584604 (GCB).
- Total counts from 835 concretions:
 - **Plants:** Total = 25 (2.9% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 7
 - *Neuropteris* = 1
 - *Annularia* = 5
 - *Calamites* = 3
 - Plant stem = 7
 - Macerated plant = 1
 - Indeterminate plant = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 207 (24.7% of total)
 - Senior blobs = 15
 - Junior blobs = 9
 - Indeterminate blobs = 12
 - Probable blobs = 3
 - Odd blobs = 2
 - *Etacystis* = 3
 - *Mazonomya* (all open-valved) = 53
 - *Mazonomya* (multiple) = 2
 - *Dundarella* & *Mazonomya* = 1
 - Crushed myalinids in coprolite = 1
 - Indeterminate pecten = 1
 - Indeterminate bivalve = 1
 - *Strobeus* on blob = 11
 - *Glaphurochiton* = 5
 - *Belotelson* (whole) = 8
 - Indeterminate shrimp = 1
 - Tummy tooth = 4
 - Polychaete (“simple jaw”?) = 1
 - “Oliver Hardy” worm = 1
 - Polychaete (*Hystricula*) = 1
 - “fan worm” = 2
 - Indeterminate polychaete = 1
 - Holothurian = 21
 - *Rhabdoderma* (coelacanth) = 1
 - *Esconichthys* (“blades”) = 2
 - “Blade” or *Gilpichthys* agnathan fish = 1

- Coprolites = 39
- Trails/traces = 4
- Pellets = 1
- **Miscellaneous:** Total = 17 (2.0% of total)
 - Indeterminate nucleus = 15
 - Incognitum = 2
- **Duds:** Total = 585 (70% of total)
 - Gray-brown duds = 533
 - Septarial duds = 2
 - Weathered duds = 50
- Additional taxa collected by T.V. Testa (not itemized in this sample):
 - Chitons = 2

Locality 413

- **No assignment; excluded**—Headwall shale exposure bordering abandoned Morris Coal Company strip mine at east edge of Morris, Illinois. Summary sample manifest of single data sheet as of 05/07/24.

- **Description:** Abandoned Morris Coal Company strip mine (collection from accessible mine headwall) at east edge of Morris, Illinois at NW1/4, NE1/4, NW1/4, section 3, T34N, R7E near north edge of the Morris 7.5' quadrangle, digital coordinates 41.372115, -88.416887 (GCB). This partly submerged, east-facing, headwall exposure, on McIlvaine property is notable for abundant plants and nonmarine clams. I am not sure if this exposure still exists, but it was still productive when visited as part of the spring North-Central Geological Society of America field trip in 1990. Mine highwall sample collected and split by S. Sroka on 08/82.

- Total counts, based on 177 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 67 (37.8% of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 1
 - Fertile *Pecopteris* = 1
 - *Neuropteris* = 8
 - *Neuropteris* stem = 1
 - *Annularia* = 3
 - *Lepidophylloides* = 10
 - Plant stem = 1
 - *Cyclopteris* = 3
 - *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Cone = 1
 - Macerated plants = 37
 - **Animals:** Total = 47 (26.5% of total)
 - Nonmarine bivalves = 31 (most likely *Anthraconaia* and/or *Anthraconauta*)
 - Syncarid shrimp = 1
 - Ostracods and macerated plants = 3
 - Insect wing = 1
 - Coprolites = 11
 - **Duds:** Total = 63 (35.5% of total)
 - Dark gray duds = 63

Locality 414

- **Will-Essex; excluded—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11, “Greenland *Solemya* clam (*Acharax*) spot” of Frank Greene in Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 07/24/24.**
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11) at SE1/4, SE1/4, SW1/4, section 29, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at digital coordinates 41.2174455, -88.21641724 (ADM). This is Frank Greene’s “*Solemya* clam spot” in the Will County part of Pit Eleven. Mine directory number = 834.
- **Note:** This locality has the same township and range coordinates as Locality # 166 (T-25 locality of Tom Beard) which is entered separately.
- Total counts, based on 82 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 2 (2.4 % of total)
 - Unidentified plants = 2
 - **Animals:** Total = 52 (63.4 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 9
 - Multiple *Essexella* = 1
 - *Drevotella* (hydroid) = 1
 - *Mazonomya* = 3
 - Solemyid bivalve *Acharax* = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinosclex* = 1
 - Nemertean *Archisymplectes* = 1
 - Acorn worm *Balanoglossus* = 2
 - Holothurians = 7
 - Coprolites = 4
 - Trails = 20
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 1 (1.2 % of total)
 - Discs = 1
 - **Duds:** Total = 27 (32.9 % of total)
 - Common duds = 27

Locality 415

- **No assignment, excluded**—Peobody Coal Company Northern Mine: Pit 11 in western part of “Hydroid Hill” - “Tully Port” area, Will County, Illinois. Sample manifest from single data sheet updated as of 08/01/24.
- **Description:** Abandoned Peobody Coal Company Northern strip mine (Pit 11 in the western part of the “Hydroid Hill” - “Tully Port” area) at NE1/4, SE1/4, section 31, T32N, R9E on the Essex 7.5’ quadrangle at approximated digital coordinates 41.207713, -88.225973 (GCB). Mine directory number 834. Collecting area currently largely submerged under Braidwood Lake. Sample collected by the Ramsdells.
- **Note:** This single sheet was originally part of four sheets comprising “Locality 375” (“Tully Port area”), but the coordinates for this page are not in section 32, but in section 31, some distance farther to the west. Hence, a new locality number is now given to this sample.
- Total counts, based on 124 concretions gathered, split, and counted:
 - **Plants:** Total = 8 (6.4 % of total)
 - *Pecopteris* = 4
 - Bark = 3
 - *Odontopteris* = 1
 - **Animals:** Total = 110 (88.7 % of total)
 - *Essexella* (not subdivided) = 55
 - Hydroid *Drevotella* = 1
 - *Myalinella* = 2
 - Unidentified pecten = 2
 - Shrimp *Belotelson* = 23
 - *Belotelson* with *Stigmaria* = 1
 - Shrimp “*Peachella*” = 1
 - Polychaete *Esconites* = 4
 - Polychaete *Astreptoscolex* = 2
 - Polychaete *Didontogaster* = 1
 - Polychaete *Hystriacula* = 1
 - Echiuran *Coprinoscolex* = 1
 - Coprolites = 16
 - **Miscellaneous:** Total = 0 (0.0 % of total)
 - **Duds:** Total = 6 (4.8 % of total)
 - Common duds = 6

Figure S1: *Map of sample localities, labeled as they appear in Appendix 1.*

Appendix 2. Taxon list

Table S1: Information for all included animal taxa.

Call ID	Phylum	Class	Other information	Genus	Clade	Habitat	Tissue
ACAN	Chordata	Chondrichthyes		<i>Acanthodes</i>	Fish	Marine	Vertebrate
AICH	Incertae sedis	Incertae sedis	the H animal	<i>Etacystis</i>	Other/Incertae sedis	Marine	Dermis
AMPH	Chordata	Amphibia		Incertae sedis	Amphibian	Freshwater	Dermis
ANMD	Cnidaria	Cubozoa	Order Carybdeida	<i>Anthracomедusa</i>	Cnidarian	Marine	Dermis
ARAC	Arthropoda	Arachnida		Incertae sedis	Terrestrial Arthropod	Terrestrial	Chitin
ARTH	Arthropoda	Incertae sedis	Indet. arthropod	Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Intermediate	Chitin
BELO	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Belotelsonidea	<i>Belotelson</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
BLOB	Cnidaria	Scyphozoa	Order Rhizostomeae	NA	Cnidarian	Marine	Dermis
CAEN	Arthropoda	Malacostraca		<i>Acanthotelson</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Freshwater	Chitin
CBAR	Arthropoda	Maxillopoda		Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CCYC	Arthropoda	Maxillopoda		<i>Cyclus</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CCYZ	Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Superorder Diplostraca	<i>Cyzicus</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Freshwater	Chitin
CESS	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Eocaridacea	<i>Essoidea</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CFLE	Arthropoda	Incertae sedis		Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CHOP	Arthropoda	Malacostraca		Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CKAL	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Aeschronectida	<i>Kallidectes</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CKEL	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Hoplostraca	<i>Kellibrooksia</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CMES	Arthropoda	Malacostraca		<i>Hesslerella</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CMRS	Arthropoda	Malacostraca		Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
COST	Arthropoda	Ostracoda		Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Freshwater	Chitin
CPAL	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Tanaidacea	<i>Anthracocaris</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Freshwater	Chitin
CPEA	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Lophogastrida	<i>Peachocaris</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CPYG	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Pygocephalomorpha	Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Intermediate	Chitin
CSYN	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Superorder Syncarida	Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Freshwater	Chitin
CTYR	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Order Stomatopoda	<i>Tyrannophontes</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
CUND	Arthropoda	Incertae sedis	Indet. crustacean remains	Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Intermediate	Chitin
EDMO	Mollusca	Bivalvia		<i>Mazonomya</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
EGGS	Incertae sedis	Incertae sedis	Eggs	Incertae sedis	Other/Incertae sedis	Marine	Unknown
ESSX	Cnidaria	Scyphozoa	Order Actiniaria	<i>Essexella</i>	Cnidarian	Marine	Dermis
ETAC	Incertae sedis	Incertae sedis		<i>Etacystis</i>	Hemichordate	Marine	Dermis
EUCH	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Order Pectinida	<i>Euchondria</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
EUPR	Arthropoda	Xiphosura		<i>Euproops</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Freshwater	Chitin
FCRT	Chordata	Chondrichthyes	Indet. cartilagenous fish	Incertae sedis	Fish	Intermediate	Vertebrate
FCTN	Chordata	Sarcopterygii	Class Dipnoi	<i>Ctenodus</i>	Fish	Freshwater	Vertebrate
FESC	Chordata	Sarcopterygii	Order Ceratodontiformes	<i>Esconichthys</i>	Fish	Marine	Vertebrate
FGIL	Chordata	Myxini	Order Myxiniiformes	<i>Gilpichthys</i>	Fish	Marine	Vertebrate

FISH	Chordata	Incertae sedis	Indet. fish	Incertae sedis	Fish	Intermediate	Vertebrate
FMEG	Chordata	Sarcopterygii	Subclass Crossopterygii	<i>Megalichthys</i>	Fish	Freshwater	Vertebrate
FPAL	Chordata	Actinopteri	Order Palaeonisciformes	Incertae sedis	Fish	Intermediate	Vertebrate
FRHB	Chordata	Sarcopterygii	Order Coelacanthiformes	<i>Rhabdoderma</i>	Fish	Marine	Vertebrate
FWCL	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Indet. freshwater clam	Incertae sedis	Mollusk	Freshwater	Shell
FXNT	Chordata	Chondrichthyes	Xenocanth tooth	Incertae sedis	Fish	Freshwater	Vertebrate
HDEV	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa		<i>Drevotella</i>	Cnidarian	Marine	Dermis
HFTR	Arthropoda	Chilopoda	Indet. centipede	Incertae sedis	Terrestrial Arthropod	Terrestrial	Chitin
HOLT	Echinodermata	Holothuroidea		Incertae sedis	Echinoderm	Marine	Dermis
INSC	Arthropoda	Insecta	Indet. insects	Incertae sedis	Terrestrial Arthropod	Terrestrial	Chitin
KOTT	Arthropoda	Incertae sedis	Order Euthycarcinida	<i>Kottixes</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
LIMU	Arthropoda	Xiphosura		<i>Paleolimulus</i>	Aquatic Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
LING	Brachiopoda	Lingulata		<i>Lingula</i>	Brachiopod	Marine	Shell
MBCR	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Indet. crushed bivalves	Incertae sedis	Mollusk	Freshwater	Shell
MCEP	Mollusca	Cephalopoda	Indet. cephalopod	Incertae sedis	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MCHT	Mollusca	Polyplacophora	Indet. chiton	Incertae sedis	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MDUN	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Order Pectinida	<i>Dunbarella</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MEUP	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Order Bellerophonitida	<i>Euphemites</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MHTW	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Unique undescribed clam	Incertae sedis	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MLIM	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Order Pectinida	<i>Lima</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MSCZ	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Order Trigonitida	<i>Schizodus</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MSOL	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Subclass Protobranchia	<i>Solemya</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MSTR	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Suborder Murchisoniina	<i>Strobeus</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
MUND	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Indet. clam	Incertae sedis	Mollusk	Intermediate	Shell
MYAL	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Order Pteriida	<i>Myalina</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
NCYC	Arthropoda	Incertae sedis	Indet. arthropod	Incertae sedis	Arthropod	Marine	Chitin
OCTO	Cnidaria	Scyphozoa	Order Coronatida	<i>Octomedusa</i>	Cnidarian	Marine	Dermis
PECT	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Order Pectinida	<i>Pecten</i>	Mollusk	Marine	Shell
PLXS	Chordata	Chondrichthyes	Shark egg case	<i>Palaeoxyris</i>	Fish	Freshwater	Vertebrate
REGC	Arthropoda	Insecta	Roach egg case	Incertae sedis	Terrestrial Arthropod	Terrestrial	Chitin
SHRP	Arthropoda	Malacostraca		Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod	Intermediate	Chitin
TFTR	Arthropoda	Diplopoda	Indet. millipede	Incertae sedis	Terrestrial Arthropod	Terrestrial	Chitin
TMON	Incertae sedis	Incertae sedis		<i>Tullimonstrum</i>	Other/Incertae sedis	Marine	Unknown
WBLN	Hemichordata	Enteropneusta		<i>Balanoglossus</i>	Hemichordate	Marine	Dermis
WCAP	Annelida	Polychaeta	Subclass Echiura	Incertae sedis	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WDRY	Annelida	Polychaeta	group Phyllocoemorpha	<i>Dryptoscolex</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WESC	Annelida	Polychaeta	group Phyllocoemorpha	<i>Esconites</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WFAN	Annelida	Polychaeta	Indet. fan worm	Incertae sedis	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WFSH	Annelida	Polychaeta	group Phyllocoemorpha	<i>Pieckonia</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WHYS	Annelida	Polychaeta	group Phyllocoemorpha	<i>Hystriaciola</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WILY	Arthropoda	Incertae sedis	Subphylum Myriapoda	<i>Ilyodes</i>	Terrestrial Arthropod	Terrestrial	Chitin
WNEM	Chordata	Cyclostomi	Class Myxini	<i>Squirmarius</i>	Fish	Marine	Vertebrate
WOLH	Annelida	Polychaeta	Oliver Hardy worm	Incertae sedis	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WPJM	Chaetognatha	Incertae sedis		<i>Paucijaculum</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WPLN	Annelida	Polychaeta	group Phyllocoemorpha	<i>Astreptoscolex</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WPRI	Priapulida	Incertae sedis	Indet. priapulid	Incertae sedis	Worm	Marine	Dermis

WSJW	Incertae sedis	Incertae sedis	Simple jaw remains	Incertae sedis	Other/Incertae sedis	Marine	Unknown
WSPR	Annelida	Polychaeta	Order Sabellida	<i>Spirorbis</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WTTH	Annelida	Polychaeta	group Phyllocoemorpha	<i>Didontogaster</i>	Worm	Marine	Dermis
WUND	Annelida	Polychaeta	Indet. polychaete	Incertae sedis	Worm	Marine	Dermis
YWHY	Incertae sedis	Incertae sedis	the Y animal	<i>Escumasia</i>	Other/Incertae sedis	Marine	Unknown

Table S2: List of included plant taxa.

Call ID	Genus or other info
ALTH	<i>Alethopteris</i>
ANNL	<i>Annularia</i>
ASTR	<i>Asterophyllites</i>
LEPD	<i>Lepidodendron</i>
LSTP	<i>Lepidostrobophyllum</i>
LSTR	<i>Lepidostrobus</i>
LYCO	<i>Lycopodites</i>
NEUR	<i>Neuropteris</i>
ODON	<i>Odontopteris</i>
PAPH	Aphlebiae
PASO	<i>Asolanus</i>
PBRK	Indet. bark
PCAL	<i>Calamites</i>
PCON	Cone
PCRC	<i>Cardaicarpus</i>
PCRD	<i>Cordaites</i>
PCRS	<i>Crossothea</i>
PCYC	<i>Cyclopteris</i>
PDRN	<i>Dicranophyllum</i>
PECO	<i>Pecopteris</i>
PFUN	Indet. fern
PLEP	<i>Lepidophyllums</i>
PLIN	<i>Linopteris</i>
PMAC	Macerated plant remains
PMAR	<i>Mariopteris</i>
PPIN	<i>Pinnularia</i>
PSAR	<i>Psaronius</i>
PSEL	<i>Selaginellites</i>
PSPR	<i>Spiropteris</i>
PSTM	Indet. stem fragment
PSUL	<i>Alethopteris</i>
PTAE	<i>Taeniophyllum</i>
PUND	Indet. plant remains
SCBR	Indet. scale branch
SEED	Indet. seed
SPFR	Indet. spores in fruit
SPHN	<i>Sphenophyllum</i>
SPMG	Indet. megaspores
SPRS	Indet. spores
STIG	<i>Stigmaria</i>
TCAR	<i>Trigonocarpus</i>
TFBR	Indet. branch tuft
THAL	Indet. thallus plant
THRN	Indet. thorn
TWSC	Indet. scale twig

Table S3: List of included traces and other taxa.

Call ID	Genus or other info
INCG	“Incognito” – tag given for demonstrable fossils with no clear identification
LETT	Indet. cnidarian or algae – noted for lettuce-like appearance
FCOP	Ichnofossil – coprolites
TDPL	Ichnofossil – <i>Diplocraterion</i>
TPEL	Ichnofossil – pellets
TRAL	Ichnofossil – trails

Table S4: List of dud descriptors.

Call ID	Description
DBLB	Blue boy
DBLG	Blue-gray
DBRN	Brown
DCOM	Common
DDBL	Blue
DDGB	Dark gray-brown
DDGF	Dark gray flint
DDGR	Dark gray
DFGR	Flinty gray
DGBR	Gray-brown
DGGR	Green-gray
DGRB	Gray-brown
DGRF	Gray flinty
DGRY	Gray
DLBG	Light brown-gray
DLBR	Light brown
DLGH	Light
DLGR	Light gray
DMOT	Mottled
DODD	Odd
DPYC	Pyrite core
DREJ	Siderite reject
DSBR	Sandy brown
DSEP	Septarial
DSGB	Sandy gray-brown
DSGR	Sandy gray
DSLK	Sandy light gray
DSND	Sandy
DSPH	Sphalerite
DWTH	Weathered
DYLB	Yellow brown
DUDS	General
DTOT	Total

Table S5: List of excluded concretions.

Call ID	Kingdom	Phylum	Other information	Genus	Clade
ASLN	Plantae			<i>Asolanus</i>	Plant
CDIT	Arthropoda	Malacostraca		<i>Dithyocaris</i>	Aquatic Arthropod
CPAD	Arthropoda	Malacostraca		Incertae sedis	Aquatic Arthropod
CPRA	Animalia	Arthropoda	Class Malacostraca	<i>Praenaspides</i>	Aquatic Arthropod
DISC			Discs		Other
DSPT			Spots		Other
FINO	Chordata	Chondrichthyes	Order Iniopterygiformes	Incertae sedis	Fish
FLUN	Chordata	Sarcopterygii	Indet. lungfish	Incertae sedis	Fish
FLAM	Animalia	Chordata	Order Petromyzontida	Incertae sedis	Fish
JELF	Cnidaria	Incertae sedis	Indet. jellyfish	Incertae sedis	Cnidarian
MIND	Mollusca	Incertae sedis	Indet. mollusk	Incertae sedis	Mollusk
MODD	Mollusca	Incertae sedis	Indet. mollusk	Incertae sedis	Mollusk
MRZC	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Indet. razor clam	Incertae sedis	Mollusk
MRIB	Animalia	Mollusca	Indet. ribbed clam	Incertae sedis	Mollusk
NUND			Poorly split nodule		Other
ONYC	Animalia	Onychophora		Incertae sedis	Other
PBER	Plantae			<i>Bergeria</i>	Plant
PCAU	Plantae			<i>Caulopteris</i>	Plant
PODD	Plantae			“Odd plant”	Plant
PSIG	Plantae			<i>Sigillaria</i>	Plant
SMER			Bleached surface		Other
SPHT			Description missing		Other
TCON	Ichnofossil			<i>Chondrites</i>	Trace
TRHZ	Ichnofossil			<i>Rhizocorallium</i>	Trace
ULOD	Plantae			<i>Ulodenron</i>	Plant
WOLI	Annelida	Clitellata	Subclass Oligochaeta	Incertae sedis	Worm
WPAL	Annelida	Polychaeta	Order Aciculata	Incertae sedis	Worm
WRND	Nematoda	Incertae sedis	Indet. round worm	Incertae sedis	Worm

Table S6: List of merged call IDs.

New ID	Original IDs merged	Kingdom	Phylum	Other info	Genus	Clade
BLOB	BLCR, BLGR, BLMI	Animalia	Cnidaria	Class Scphyzoa		Cnidarian
ESSX	BLEY, BLIN, BLJR, BLMT, BLOD, BLPL, BLSR, BLTR, RTMD, BTOT [total] deleted	Animalia	Cnidaria	Class Scphyzoa	<i>Essexella</i>	Cnidarian
BELO	CBLM, CBLT	Animalia	Arthropoda	Class Malacostraca	<i>Belotelson</i>	Aquatic Arthropod
SHRP	CPRT, CSUN	Animalia	Arthropoda	Class Malacostraca	Indet. shrimp	Aquatic Arthropod
ACAN	FACN, FASP	Animalia	Chordata	Chondrichthyes	<i>Acanthodes</i>	Fish
FISH	FPRT, FUND, FTOT [total] deleted	Animalia	Chordata	Indet. fish		Fish
LYCO	PLYB, PLYC, PLYU, LYBR, LYCD	Plantae		Class Lycopodiopsida		Plants
EDMO	MEDC, MEDM, MEDS	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	<i>Mazonomya</i>	Mollusk
FWCL	MFWC, MFWM	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Indet. freshwater clams	Mollusk
MYAL	MMCR, MMSI, MMSM	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	<i>Myalina</i>	Mollusk
PECT	MPCR, MPEC	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	<i>Pecten</i>	Mollusk
PECO	PECF, PECP	Plantae			<i>Pecopteris</i>	Plants

Appendix 3. Original ledgers

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 3		LOC 4		LOC 5		LOC 6		LOC 7		LOC 8		LOC 9		LOC 10		LOC 11	
LOC 1	LOC 2	LOC 3	LOC 4	LOC 5	LOC 6	LOC 7	LOC 8	LOC 9	LOC 10	LOC 11	LOC 12	LOC 13	LOC 14	LOC 15	LOC 16	LOC 17	LOC 18	LOC 19	LOC 20
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES
SUM 476	SUM 2370	SUM 1388	SUM 1249	SUM 1302	SUM 1011	SUM 1314	SUM 1177	SUM 3223	SUM 1279	SUM 1710									
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
DCOM 113	ALTH 2	ALTH 1	ANHL 2	ALTH 1	ATCH 1	ALTH 2	ALTH 1	ALTH 4	ANMD 1	ALTH 1									
DGBR 102	ANHL 18	ANHL 1	BLIN 11	ANHL 9	ALTH 1	ANHL 12	ANHL 1	ANHL 1	ANHL 2	ANHL 13									
DISC 1	BLIN 1	BLIN 11	BLJR 52	BLIN 9	ANMD 1	BLIN 36	BLIN 8	ANHL 23	ASTR 1	BLIN 21									
DPYC 7	BLJR 1	BLJR 2	BLSR 78	BLJR 36	ANHL 12	BLJR 13	BLJR 13	BLIN 100	BLIN 51	BLJR 24									
DREJ 243	BLSR 1	BLSR 4	BTOT 104	BLSR 53	BLIN 40	BLSR 35	BLSR 19	BLJR 161	BLJR 42	BLHT 2									
HOLT 2	BTOT 18	BTOT 21	CBLM 2	BTOT 40	BLJR 23	CAEN 1	BTOT 8	BLSR 399	BLSR 99	BLSR 9									
MEDS 1	CBLM 2	DBLB 206	CKAL 2	CBLM 2	BLSR 222	CBLT 1	CBLT 1	CBLT 4	CBLT 1	BTOT 26									
NEUR 1	CBLT 2	DCOM 264	CUND 1	CBLT 4	CBLM 6	CSUN 1	DCOM 261	CBLT 23	CKAL 1	CAEN 1									
ODON 1	CPAL 1	DGBR 172	DCOM 460	DBLB 7	CBLT 3	CSYN 1	DGBR 156	CBLT 23	CKAL 1	CAEN 1									
PBRK 1	CSUN 1	DGRB 122	DDGR 7	DCOM 146	CPAL 1	DBLB 181	DGBR 10	CFLE 1	CPEA 1	CBLM 1									
PCAL 1	DBLB 13	DISC 2	DGBR 33	DDGR 4	CUND 2	DCOM 254	DISC 2	CPYG 1	DGBR 48	CCYC 14									
PMAC 1	DBRN 6	DPYC 86	DPYC 4	DGBR 203	DGBR 115	DDGR 48	DHDT 3	CSUN 6	DGRY 9	CKAL 2									
TRAL 1	DCOM 666	DREJ 442	DREJ 254	DGRB 195	DGRY 207	DGBR 21	DPYC 161	CTYR 1	DISC 8	COST 1									
HPLN 1	DGRY 225	NEUR 2	DSEP 1	DISC 1	DISC 13	DGRY 30	DREJ 470	DGBR 273	DPYC 28	CSYN 1									
	DPYC 38	HUND 26	DUDS 187	DMOT 11	DPYC 10	DISC 9	FCOP 13	DISC 4	DREJ 501	DCOM 89									
	DREJ 903	PECP 3	ETAC 2	DPYC 31	DREJ 188	DPYC 16	HSTR 1	DPYC 106	DSEP 5	DDGR 8									
	DSEP 22	PSTH 2	FCOP 3	DREJ 473	DSEP 44	DREJ 488	NEUR 5	DREJ 717	DWTH 116	DGBR 348									
	DWTH 56	PUND 17	MEDS 1	DSEP 4	DWTH 17	DSEP 52	NUND 3	DSEP 6	ETAC 2	DGBR 289									
	FCOP 4	SMER 1	HUND 1	FCOP 12	FCOP 5	DWTH 30	PCAL 1	DUDS 932	FCOP 5	DISC 11									
	FESC 1	TRAL 1	NEUR 2	FESC 3	LSTP 1	FCOP 2	PECP 19	DWTH 78	MMSI 1	DPYC 30									
	FPAL 1	HUND 2	NUND 7	FPAL 1	MEDS 12	INCG 1	PLEP 2	ETAC 3	HSTR 1	DREJ 479									
	HOLT 39	PCAL 3	LINU 1	MSTR 7	INSC 1	PMAC 1	FCOP 46	NEUR 8	NEUR 8	DSEP 47									
	LSTP 1	PECP 10	LSTP 1	MUND 1	MMSI 2	PSTH 14	FESC 5	NUND 11	FCOP 11	FCOP 13									
	MEDS 10	PSTH 8	NEUR 3	NEUR 8	NEUR 6	TRAL 3	FPAL 1	PECP 4	FGIL 1										
	MEUP 2	SPHN 1	NUND 11	NUND 18	NUND 11	WUND 1	FRIB 1	PLEP 1	HOLT 3										
	HUND 1	THON 2	PAPH 1	PCAL 3	PBRK 2		HOLT 18	PHAC 2	MEDM 1										
	NEUR 36	TRAL 5	PCAL 3	PECP 12	PCAL 5		INCG 38	PSTH 2	MEDS 15										
	HUND 32	WCAP 1	PCYC 1	PLEP 3	PECP 37		MCHT 4	TRAL 2	MEUP 1										
	ODON 2	WDRY 2	PECP 11	PHAC 1	PLEP 4		MMSI 9		MFHC 1										
	PBRK 6	WSJW 2	PHAC 4	PSTH 16	PSTM 3		MFEC 2		MMCR 2										
	PCAL 9	WTHH 1	PSTH 9	PUND 2	PUND 2		HSTR 5		MMSI 9										
	PCON 2		PUND 4	SEED 1	TRAL 2		HUND 17		MMSH 1										
	PCYC 2		THAL 1	SMER 2	WCAP 1		NEUR 1		HPEC 4										
	PECP 70		TRAL 4	THON 4	WTHH 1		HUND 8		HUND 3										
	PLEP 15		WESC 1	TRAL 6	HUND 3		PBRK 1		NEUR 11										
	PLYC 1		WTHH 1	WESC 1	WTHH 2		PCAL 9		NUND 33										
	PMAC 19		HUND 1	WTHH 2	WUND 1		PCYC 2		PECP 33										
	FFIN 1						PECP 110		PLEP 10										
	RSPR 1						PLEP 7		PHAC 22										
	PSTH 85						PMAC 11		PPIN 1										
	PUND 7						PPIN 2		PSTH 60										
	SMER 5						PSTH 46		PUND 1										
	SPHN 2						PUND 5		SMER 5										
	STIG 2						SMER 4		SPFR 1										
	THON 1						THON 8		THON 3										
	TRAL 23						TRAL 7		TRAL 19										
	HESC 1						WPLN 3		WCAP 18										
	HPLN 6						WTHH 3		HESC 2										
	HTTH 1						WUND 2		WSJW 2										
	WUND 6						YHYY 1		HTTH 10										
									HUND 6										

LISTING BY LOCATION

LOC 13 ALL PAGES	LOC 14 ALL PAGES	LOC 15 ALL PAGES	LOC 16 ALL PAGES	LOC 17 ALL PAGES	LOC 18 ALL PAGES	LOC 19 ALL PAGES	LOC 20 ALL PAGES	LOC 21 ALL PAGES	LOC 22 ALL PAGES	LOC 23 ALL PAGES
SUM 258 ID COUNT	SUM 1847 ID COUNT	SUM 2190 ID COUNT	SUM 674 ID COUNT	SUM 1633 ID COUNT	SUM 2097 ID COUNT	SUM 785 ID COUNT	SUM 4797 ID COUNT	SUM 973 ID COUNT	SUM 1224 ID COUNT	SUM 2185 ID COUNT
ANNL 1	ANNL 1	BLEY 3	BLEY 14	ALTH 2	ALTH 1	BLIN 6	ALTH 1	ANNL 2	ALTH 1	BLEY 11
BLIN 4	BTOT 214	BLIN 2	BLIN 6	ANNL 10	ANNL 3	BLJR 2	ANNL 4	ASTR 1	ANNL 3	BLIN 28
BLJR 4	CBLT 3	BLJR 7	BLJR 12	BLIN 14	BLIN 45	BLSR 26	ELCR 7	BLEY 2	ARAC 1	BLJR 75
BLSR 4	CCYC 8	BLSR 96	BLSR 76	BLJR 7	BLJR 4	CBLM 1	BLIN 57	BLIN 17	BLJR 70	BLSR 100
CBLM 1	CPYG 1	BTOT 84	CBLH 1	BLMT 1	BLSR 325	CBLT 1	BLJR 94	BLJR 31	BLSR 208	CBLM 5
CCYC 1	DCOM 747	CBLH 2	CBLT 2	BLSR 46	CBLM 3	CCYC 3	BLSR 155	BLSR 70	CBLT 6	CHOP 1
DCOM 164	DDGR 31	CBLT 1	CCYC 2	BTOT 15	CBLT 4	CHOP 1	BLTR 2	CBLM 1	CHOP 1	CKAL 2
FCOP 7	DGRB 104	CCYC 22	CKAL 1	CBLM 2	CCYC 20	CSUN 1	BTOT 256	CBLT 1	CKAL 2	DBLB 10
HOLT 6	DLGR 147	CPAL 1	DCOM 364	CBLT 1	DCOM 246	DCOM 359	CAEN 1	CCYC 6	CSUN 3	DCOM 944
MUND 2	DPYC 11	CSUN 1	DGBR 13	CCYC 5	DGBR 56	DREJ 88	CBLT 2	CKAL 1	CSYN 1	DDGR 9
NUND 3	DSEP 4	DCOM 1163	DISC 2	DCOM 308	DGRY 53	DSEP 10	CCYC 6	DBLB 36	DCOM 621	DGBR 297
PCAL 2	FCOP 6	DGBR 154	DREJ 73	DDGR 16	DISC 6	FCOP 15	DCOM 2223	DCOM 259	DGBR 70	DGRY 125
PECP 2	FESC 1	DISC 2	DSEP 23	DGBR 128	DPYC 44	HOLT 1	DGRY 191	DGBR 46	DREJ 154	DISC 1
PLEP 5	INCG 14	DPYC 9	FCOP 9	DGRY 58	DREJ 504	HEDS 1	DISC 13	DGRY 62	DSEP 2	DLGH 9
PMAC 24	INSC 1	DREJ 463	MUND 2	DISC 11	DSEP 8	HFWC 1	DPYC 49	OPYC 18	FCOP 18	DMOT 15
PSTH 20	MEOS 179	DSEP 22	NUND 4	DPYC 4	DWTH 121	HMSI 18	DREJ 403	DREJ 272	FCRT 1	DPYC 2
TRAL 6	MEUP 14	FCOP 7	PBRK 2	DREJ 387	FCOP 23	HPEC 1	DSEP 187	DSEP 5	INCG 8	DREJ 225
MUND 2	MMSI 10	FCTH 1	FCYC 1	DSEP 25	HOLT 14	MUND 14	DWTH 224	DWTH 34	MHTW 4	DSEP 23
	MPEC 4	LYBR 1	PECP 5	DWTH 30	HEDS 18	NUND 8	ETAC 1	FCOP 18	MMSI 8	DWTH 11
	MUND 5	HEDS 16	PLEP 2	FCOP 8	MPEC 24	PECP 3	FCOP 25	HOLT 1	NEUR 3	FCOP 25
	NEUR 1	MMSI 2	PMAC 36	HOLT 5	MUND 6	PLEP 1	HOLT 16	LETT 2	NUND 5	FMEG 1
	OCTO 1	MPEC 1	PSTH 12	LSTP 1	NUND 20	PMAC 169	LETT 3	HEDS 1	PBRK 1	INSC 1
	PCAL 1	HSCZ 25	TRAL 1	MEDM 92	PASO 1	PSTH 42	HEDS 102	MEUP 1	PECP 5	MEDM 2
	PECP 4	MUND 3	HPLN 3	HEDS 318	PECP 6	THON 1	MEUP 2	MHTW 11	PLEP 3	HEDS 4
	PLEP 2	NEUR 1	MUND 8	NUND 1	PLEP 8	TRAL 4	MHTW 242	HIND 1	PSTH 15	MHTW 10
	PMAC 91	NUND 20	NEUR 8	PMAC 379	NUND 1	HPLN 1	MMSI 80	MMSI 4	TRAL 2	MMSI 37
	PSTH 53	PMAC 44	NUND 25	PSTH 120	MUND 7	HPEC 3	HSTR 2	HUND 8	MUND 61	MUND 61
	PUND 1	PSTH 12	FBRK 5	PUND 3		MUND 123	MUND 18		NEUR 4	NEUR 4
	SPHN 1	PUND 4	PCAL 8	SEED 1		NEUR 3	NEUR 5		NUND 31	NUND 31
	STIG 1	SMER 1	PCYC 1	SMER 4		NUND 73	NUND 16		PECP 15	PECP 15
	TPEL 3	TRAL 4	PECP 6	STIG 2		PBRK 9	PBRK 1		FLEP 1	FLEP 1
	TRAL 81	WCAP 1	PLEP 6	TRAL 2		PECP 17	PECP 3		PLXS 6	PLXS 6
	WCAP 36	WHYS 2	PLYC 1	WDRY 1		PLEP 9	PLXS 2		PMAC 17	PMAC 17
	WESC 10	WPLN 8	FSTH 27	HPLN 7		PLXS 3	PSTH 5		PSTH 27	PSTH 27
	WFAH 1	HTTH 2	FUND 3	HPRI 1		PMAC 35	PUND 1		PUND 2	PUND 2
	WFSH 5	HUND 3	REGC 1	HTTH 6		PSTH 49	SPHN 1		SMER 2	SMER 2
	WHYS 3		SMER 1	HUND 8		FUND 1	TRAL 17		TRAL 22	TRAL 22
	WPLN 14		TRAL 22			SMER 5	WCAP 1		WESC 1	WESC 1
	WPRI 1		WPLN 5			TRAL 56	WFAH 1		WPLN 1	WPLN 1
	WSJH 4		HSJH 2			WBLN 1	HPLN 1		HTTH 3	HTTH 3
	HTTH 5		HTTH 2			WESC 2	MUND 1		HUND 22	HUND 22
	HUND 23		HUND 15			WFAH 19				
						WILY 1				
						HPLN 5				
						HTTH 5				
						HUND 32				

LISTING BY LOCATION

LOC 24 ALL PAGES	LOC 24 ALL PAGES	LOC 25 ALL PAGES	LOC 26 ALL PAGES	LOC 27 ALL PAGES	LOC 28 ALL PAGES	LOC 28 ALL PAGES	LOC 29 ALL PAGES	LOC 30 ALL PAGES	LOC 31 ALL PAGES	LOC 32 ALL PAGES
ID: COUNT	SUM 1625 ID COUNT	SUM 131 ID COUNT	SUM 411 ID COUNT	SUM 1683 ID COUNT	ID COUNT	SUM 4081 ID COUNT	SUM 3049 ID COUNT	SUM 1769 ID COUNT	SUM 627 ID COUNT	SUM 554 ID COUNT
ALTH 1	HPRI 1	BLIN 3	ANNL 2	AMPH 1	ALTH 2	HTTH 2	ALTH 5	ALTH 6	ANNL 2	ALTH 2
ANNL 18	HSJW 1	BLJR 5	BTOT 10	ANNL 12	ANND 1	WUND 26	ANNL 10	ANNL 16	BLIN 23	ANNL 7
BLIN 14	HTTH 2	BLSR 5	CCYC 1	BLSR 14	ANNL 33		BLIN 21	BLIN 38	BLJR 5	BLIN 10
BLJR 43	WUND 10	CCYC 2	DCOM 258	BTOT 48	ASTR 2		BLJR 37	BLJR 34	BLSR 35	BLJR 11
DLSR 40		DCOM 26	DGRB 81	CBLM 1	BLIN 15		BLSR 181	BLSR 112	CBLT 1	BLSR 16
BTOT 36		DGBR 46	DSEP 6	CCYC 2	BLJR 50		CBLM 13	BTOT 25	DCOM 336	CBLM 1
CBLT 1		DSEP 1	FCOP 1	DCOM 353	BLSR 113		CBLT 2	CBLM 1	DDGR 3	CBLT 1
CCYC 9		MEDM 2	MEDS 1	DGBR 226	CCYC 1		CUND 1	CBLT 1	DGRB 20	DCOM 359
CSYN 1		MEDS 19	MPEC 3	DISC 12	CKAL 1		DCOM 1526	CKAL 1	DISC 1	DDGR 1
DCOM 255		NUND 5	NEUR 6	DREJ 642	CSYN 1		DGBR 208	CSUN 1	DREJ 51	DGRB 35
DDGR 41		PCAL 1	NUND 11	DSEP 22	DCOM 980		DISC 12	DCOM 585	DSEP 9	DISC 1
DGBR 363		PNAC 5	PCON 1	DWTH 102	DGBR 715		DREJ 507	DGBR 331	FCOP 10	DSEP 10
DISC 11		PSTH 6	PECP 1	FACH 1	DGRY 78		DSEP 36	DISC 8	MEDS 3	FCOP 1
DPYC 10		TRAL 2	PLEP 1	FCOP 14	DISC 11		DWTH 74	DREJ 325	MHTW 2	FCTN 1
DREJ 535		WESC 1	PNAC 6	HOLT 1	DREJ 980		FCOP 36	DSEP 16	NUND 18	INCG 1
DSEP 4		WUND 2	PSTH 17	LSTP 4	DSEP 50		FPRT 1	FCOP 29	NEUR 4	LSTP 1
FCOP 5			TRAL 2	MEDH 6	FCOP 20		LING 1	LEPD 3	NUND 19	MEDM 1
FESC 1			WCAP 1	MEDS 111	FPAL 1		LSTR 1	MEDS 46	PCAL 1	MEDS 13
INCG 1			WUND 2	MPEC 5	HDEV 4		MEDS 2	MEUP 15	PCON 1	MHTW 1
INSC 1				HUND 2	HOLT 4		MHTW 18	MHTW 1	PECP 4	MPEC 1
LSTP 2				NEUR 15	LSTP 4		MMSI 14	MMSI 2	PNAC 41	HUND 1
HEDM 3				NUND 3	LSTR 2		NUND 22	MPEC 1	PSTH 20	NEUR 1
HEDS 60				PBRK 6	MEDM 37		NEUR 4	HUND 8	PUND 3	NUND 5
HEUP 1				PCAL 15	MEDS 569		NUND 41	NEUR 10	TPEL 4	PCAL 4
HFHC 2				PCYC 1	MEUP 1		PAPH 1	NUND 9	TRAL 7	PCRC 1
MMSI 2				PECP 18	MHTW 2		PBRK 1	PBRK 3	WUND 4	PECP 13
MPEC 2				PLEP 5	MPEC 3		PCAL 6	PCAL 8		PLEP 4
MUND 3				PNAC 6	HSOL 3		PCRD 1	PECP 20		PNAC 23
NEUR 6				PSTH 7	HUND 1		PCYC 1	PLEP 2		PSTH 15
NUND 17				PUND 1	NEUR 35		PECP 17	PNAC 20		PUND 1
OCTO 2				SEED 1	NUND 32		PLEP 3	PSTH 48		TRAL 6
PAPH 1				SMER 1	PBRK 3		PLXS 2	PUND 6		WCAP 1
PCAL 1				TRAL 12	PCAL 8		PMAC 111	STIG 1		WPLN 1
PCON 1				HCAP 1	PCYC 1		PSTH 105	TRAL 12		WUND 4
PECP 4				WESC 2	PECP 32		TMON 1	HCAP 7		
PLEP 6				HFSH 1	PLEP 22		TRAL 4	WPLN 3		
PLXS 1				HSJW 1	PLXS 1		WPLN 2	HSJW 1		
PMAC 72				HTTH 2	PMAC 59		HTTH 3	HUND 14		
PMAR 1				WUND 6	PFIN 2		HUND 18			
PPIN 1					PSTH 89					
PSTH 50					PUND 9					
PUND 1					SMER 7					
SEED 2					SFHN 2					
SMER 3					TFTR 1					
SFHN 1					TRAL 39					
TPEL 4					WCAP 2					
TRAL 26					WESC 9					
WCAP 1					WFAN 1					
WFAN 1					WFAN 1					
WFSH 1					WPLN 10					
WHYS 2					WSPR 4					
WPLN 2										

LISTING BY		LOCATION																			
LOC 33		LOC 34		LOC 35		LOC 35		LOC 36		LOC 36		LOC 37		LOC 38		LOC 39		LOC 40		LOC 41	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 280		SUM 977		SUM 2880		SUM 1896		SUM 1084		SUM 859		SUM 977		SUM 135		SUM 238					
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT	
ANNL	1	ALTH	1	ALTH	3	HCAP	5	ALTH	1	HESC	6	ANNL	15	ALTH	1	ALTH	1	ALTH	1	ANNL	4
ASTR	2	ANNL	8	ANNL	56	HESC	6	ANNL	65	WSJH	2	BLIN	20	ANNL	14	ANNL	27	ANNL	3	ASTR	1
BTOT	5	BLIN	11	ASTR	3	WSJH	1	ARTH	1	HSPR	1	BLJR	87	BLIN	3	BLIN	4	DCOM	27	DCOM	43
CCYC	2	BLJR	22	BLIN	257	HTTH	14	ASTR	4	HTTH	7	BLSR	140	BLJR	4	BLJR	1	DGBR	25	DDGR	2
DCOM	108	BLSR	50	BLJR	95	HUND	27	BLIN	19	HUND	16	CBLM	1	BLSR	5	BLSR	4	DSEP	3	DGBR	76
DGRB	23	CBLH	1	BLSR	208			BLJR	30			CBLT	1	CBLM	1	CBLM	2	FCOP	3	DSEP	9
DLGR	1	CCYC	14	BTOT	34			BLSR	48			CCYC	5	CCYC	2	CSUN	1	LSTP	1	FCOP	2
DMOT	1	DBLB	3	CAEN	2			BTOT	3			DCOM	285	CCYZ	1	DBLB	42	MUND	1	LSTP	1
DPYC	3	DCOM	303	CBAR	1			CAEN	1			DDGR	15	CKAL	1	DCOM	78	NEUR	12	HFMC	1
DSEP	10	DGRB	128	CBLM	5			CBLM	2			DGRB	147	CSYN	1	DDGR	44	MUND	2	MNSI	14
DUDS	34	DISC	1	CBLT	5			CBLT	1			DISC	5	DBLB	228	DGRB	270	PBRK	5	MUND	1
FCOP	7	DMOT	7	CCYC	15			CCYC	1			DPYC	17	DCOM	142	DISC	4	PECP	16	NEUR	6
INCG	2	DREJ	228	CFLE	2			CPYG	1			DSEP	16	DGRB	105	DPYC	12	PLEP	6	MUND	5
LSTP	1	DSEP	17	CPAL	1			DCOM	29			FCOP	19	DISC	11	DSEP	11	PMAC	11	PBRK	2
LSTR	1	FCOP	1	CPYG	1			DDGR	5			INSC	1	DLGR	28	FCOP	33	PSAR	1	PCAL	3
MEDH	8	HOLT	1	CSYN	1			DGBR	238			LSTP	1	DSEP	48	LSTR	19	PSTH	15	PCYC	1
MEDS	23	LSTP	2	DCOM	664			DISC	11			HEDS	1	FCOP	17	LSTR	1	STIG	3	PECP	16
MPEC	1	LSTR	2	DDGR	12			DPYC	66			MNSI	5	LSTR	4	HFMC	15			PLEP	13
MUND	10	MEDH	5	DGBR	411			DREJ	284			HPEC	2	MFWC	11	MNSI	17			PLXS	1
NEUR	1	MEDS	30	DISC	7			DSEP	21			NEUR	29	MNSI	27	HPEC	2			PMAC	9
NUND	10	MPEC	2	DPYC	30			DUDS	222			NUND	13	MPEC	1	MUND	5			PSTH	24
PECP	2	MSOL	2	DREJ	301			FCOP	51			OCTO	1	MUND	12	NEUR	37			SEED	2
PLEP	1	NEUR	9	DSEP	45			FMEG	1			PBRK	1	NEUR	13	NUND	29			SPHN	2
PMAC	7	NUND	5	FCOP	46			FPAL	1			PBRK	1	NUND	28	PBRK	1				
PSTH	6	PERK	8	INSC	1			INCG	1			PCAL	8	PCYC	3	PCAL	1				
SHER	6	PCAL	4	KOTT	1			LSTP	1			PCON	1	PECP	26	PCYC	2				
TRAL	3	PECP	16	LSTP	3			LYBR	2			PCYC	1	PLEP	37	PECP	110				
MUND	1	PLEP	9	MEDS	5			MEDS	5			PECP	36	PMAC	17	PLEP	77				
		PMAC	23	MNSI	8			MMCR	2			PLEP	7	PSTH	55	PMAC	34				
		PPIN	1	NPEC	7			MNSI	30			PMAC	81	PUND	3	PSTH	71				
		PSTH	29	MUND	3			NPEC	13			PPIN	1	SPHN	1	PUND	5				
		PUND	1	NEUR	60			MUND	4			PSTH	80	SFRS	1	SEED	2				
		SPHN	2	NUND	29			NEUR	229			PUND	12	TRAL	5	SHER	4				
		STIG	1	PAPH	1			NUND	29			SHER	1	MUND	3	SPHN	2				
		TRAL	15	PBRK	1			NUND	29			STIG	1			STIG	1				
		HESC	1	FCAL	19			PBRK	5			TRAL	9			TFBR	3				
		HHYS	2	PCON	2			PAPH	1			TRAL	2			TPEL	1				
		WPLN	1	PCYC	5			PCAL	26			HESC	1			TRAL	1				
		HTTH	1	PECP	54			PCYC	13			HSPR	1			HTTH	1				
		MUND	10	PLEP	21			PECP	53			HTTH	4			MUND	2				
				PLIN	1			PLEP	19			MUND	5								
				PMAC	121			PNAC	74												
				PPIN	2			PPIN	4												
				PSTH	186			PSTH	205												
				PUND	10			PUND	17												
				SEED	3			SEED	1												
				SEED	5			SNER	6												
				SPHN	5			SFRS	1												
				STIG	1			SPHN	1												
				THAL	1			TFBR	3												
				THON	2			TFTR	2												
				TRAL	20			TRAL	11												

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 42		LOC 43		LOC 44		LOC 45		LOC 46		LOC 47		LOC 48		LOC 49		LOC 50				
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES				
ID COUNT	SUM 2327 ID COUNT	SUM 1872 ID COUNT	SUM 563 ID COUNT	SUM 1539 ID COUNT	SUM 2826 ID COUNT	SUM 1787 ID COUNT	SUM 1928 ID COUNT	SUM 1686 ID COUNT	SUM 1891 ID COUNT													
ALTH	2	SEED	1	ANNL	19	ANNL	5	ANNL	10	ANNL	96	PUND	19	ALTH	1	AMPH	1	ALTH	1	ALTH	2	
ANNL	56	SMER	5	BLIN	17	BLIN	1	ASTR	1	ASTR	1	SEED	4	ANNL	26	ANNL	19	ANNL	5	ANNL	34	
ASTR	3	SPHN	2	BLJR	22	BLJR	3	BLIN	27	BLIN	18	SMER	2	BLIN	24	ASTR	2	BLIN	9	ARAC	1	
BLIN	16	STIG	3	BLSR	62	BLSR	7	BLJR	33	BLJR	61	SPHN	3	BLJR	38	BLIN	68	BLJR	7	BLIN	32	
BLJR	14	TCAR	1	BTOT	32	BTOT	17	BLSR	47	BLMT	1	SPRS	2	BLSR	24	BLJR	66	BLSR	9	BLJR	26	
BLSR	187	TMON	1	CBLM	5	CBLM	5	CBLM	1	BLSR	135	STIG	1	CAEN	1	BLSR	150	BTOT	14	BLSR	19	
BTOT	26	TRAL	9	CCYC	5	CCYC	3	CBLT	1	BTOT	49	TRAL	47	CBLM	1	BTOT	30	CCYC	3	BTOT	7	
CBLM	7	WESC	3	CKAL	1	CKAL	1	CCYC	15	CAEN	2	HCAP	2	CCYC	14	CCYC	13	CKAL	1	CCYC	9	
CBLT	4	WPLN	1	CPAL	1	DCOM	303	CPAL	1	CBLM	1	WESC	6	CPAL	1	CPYG	2	DBLB	11	CKAL	1	
CCYC	9	HSPR	2	CSUN	1	DDGR	1	DCOM	556	CBLT	6	HPJM	2	CSUN	1	CSUN	1	DCOM	281	CPAD	1	
CESS	11	HTTH	11	DBLB	40	DGRB	96	DDGR	8	CCYC	18	HSPR	5	DCOM	457	CSYN	4	DDGR	1	CSYN	2	
CKAL	3	HUND	18	DCOM	603	DISC	1	DGBR	264	CKAL	1	HTTH	24	DDGR	11	DCOM	680	DGBR	302	DBLB	15	
CSYN	2			DDGR	6	DPYC	8	DISC	11	CHRS	1	HUND	36	DGBR	373	DDGR	62	DGRB	196	DCOM	286	
DBLB	62			DGBR	469	DSEP	2	DREJ	308	CPAL	2			DISC	18	DGBR	57	DISC	9	DDGR	10	
DCOM	11			DISC	7	FCOP	4	DREJ	4	CPYG	1			DPYC	8	DGRB	73	DLGH	8	DGBR	386	
DDGR	3			DPYC	30	MFHC	1	DSEP	32	CSUN	1			DREJ	424	DISC	18	DMOT	6	DGRB	50	
DGBR	217			DREJ	351	MMSI	15	FCOP	4	CSYN	2			DSEP	46	DPYC	7	DREJ	67	DISC	25	
DGRY	7			DSEP	28	NEUR	15	INCP	1	CUND	2			FCOP	29	DREJ	150	DSEP	68	DPYC	54	
DISC	23			FCOP	12	HUND	6	LETT	10	DCOM	53			INSC	1	DSEP	57	DSPT	1	DREJ	525	
DPYC	52			FLUN	1	PBRK	2	LING	2	DDGR	20			LEPD	1	FCOP	20	FCOP	9	DSEP	103	
DREJ	103			MFHC	1	PCAL	6	LSTP	3	DGBR	169			LING	1	LSTP	1	HOLT	2	FCOP	23	
DSEP	85			MMSI	5	PCYC	1	MPEC	3	DGRB	95			LSTR	1	LSTR	2	MEDM	168	LEPD	1	
DUDS	485			MPEC	1	PECP	19	MUND	3	DGRY	83			MEDS	3	MEDM	4	MEDS	343	LSTP	11	
DWTH	52			HUND	3	PLEP	5	NEUR	11	DISC	18			MMSI	3	MEDS	42	MEUP	1	LSTR	2	
FCOP	98			NEUR	28	PMAC	14	HUND	20	DPYC	30			MPEC	4	MFHC	1	MPEC	4	MEDM	1	
FUND	1			HUND	15	PSTH	20	PBRK	1	DREJ	945			HUND	2	MLIM	1	MSOL	1	MEDS	9	
INSC	1			PCAL	4	PUND	2	PCAL	5	DSEP	48			NEUR	29	HMSI	2	MUND	3	MFHC	1	
LSTP	1			PCRD	1	TRAL	3	PCON	3	EUCH	1			HUND	34	MPEC	3	NEUR	3	HMSI	2	
LSTR	1			PCYC	4	WPLN	2	PECP	11	EUPR	1			PBRK	2	HUND	3	HUND	24	MPEC	2	
MDUN	1			PECP	14	HTTH	4	PLEP	34	FCOP	47			FCAL	13	NEUR	23	PCAL	3	HSTR	1	
MEDS	1			PLEP	14	HUND	4	PMAC	10	FGIL	1			FCYC	1	HUND	25	PCYC	1	HUND	3	
MFHC	4			PLIN	1			PSTH	46	INSC	1			PECP	20	PBRK	1	PECP	18	NEUR	22	
MHTW	1			PMAC	15			PUND	6	LSTP	5			PLEP	4	PCAL	10	PLEP	5	HUND	38	
MMSI	27			PPIN	2			SCBR	1	MDUN	2			PMAC	26	PECP	53	PLXS	1	PAPH	1	
MPEC	4			PSTH	21			SPHN	1	MEDS	4			PSTH	81	PLEP	24	PMAC	5	PBRK	1	
MUND	12			PUND	2			SPRS	1	MFHC	6			PUND	5	PMAC	110	PSTH	20	PCAL	9	
NEUR	128			SMER	2			STIG	2	MMSI	29			TPEL	2	PSTH	69	PUND	2	PECP	21	
NUND	42			TRAL	9			TFTR	1	MPEC	8			TRAL	26	PUND	7	STIG	1	PLEP	17	
ODON	1			THSC	1			TPEL	1	HUND	17			THSC	1	SMER	4	TRAL	46	PMAC	20	
PBRK	1			WESC	1			TRAL	15	NEUR	128			WCAP	3	SPHN	4	THSC	1	PSTH	77	
PCAL	21			HTTH	6			WCAP	4	NUND	47			WESC	4	TPEL	1	WCAP	1	PUND	3	
PCON	1			HUND	10			WESC	3	PBRK	3			WHYS	1	TRAL	19	WESC	1	SEED	1	
PCRD	1							HSJH	1	PCAL	29			HSJH	2	HCAP	2	WPLN	1	SPHN	6	
PCYC	2							HTTH	4	PCON	1			HTTH	9	HSJH	1	HTTH	2	TPEL	1	
PECP	100							HUND	7	PCYC	8			HUND	11	HSPR	1	HUND	21	TRAL	15	
PLEP	60									PECP	130					HTTH	15			HCAP	1	
PLYB	6									PLEP	39					HUND	20			WESC	1	
PMAC	103									PLXS	1									HTTH	4	
PPIN	3									PMAC	76									HUND	9	
PSTH	151									PPIN	2											
PUND	8									PSTH	228											

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LOC 51 ALL PAGES		LOC 52 ALL PAGES		LOC 53 ALL PAGES		LOC 54 ALL PAGES		LOC 55 ALL PAGES		LOC 56 ALL PAGES		LOC 57 ALL PAGES		LOC 58 ALL PAGES		LOC 59 ALL PAGES		LOC 60 ALL PAGES		LOC 60 ALL PAGES	
SUM 1784 ID COUNT		SUM 1223 ID COUNT		SUM 660 ID COUNT		SUM 2192 ID COUNT		SUM 3065 ID COUNT		SUM 2653 ID COUNT		SUM 1441 ID COUNT		SUM 2678 ID COUNT		SUM 1689 ID COUNT		ID COUNT		SUM 3363 ID COUNT	
ANNL	11	ALTH	9	ALTH	1	ALTH	6	ALTH	3	ALTH	15	ALTH	10	ALTH	1	ALTH	2	ALTH	2	PUND	8
BLIN	21	ANNL	57	ANNL	7	ANNL	33	ANNL	20	ANNL	69	ANNL	29	ANNL	17	ANNL	29	ANNL	47	SEED	3
BLJR	13	ASTR	2	ARAC	1	ASTR	3	BLIN	1	ASTR	2	DCOM	183	BLIN	2	ARAC	1	ASTR	1	SMER	3
BLSR	37	CUND	1	ASTR	1	BLEY	1	BLSR	1	CCYZ	1	DGRY	177	BLJR	3	ARTH	1	BLIN	37	SPHN	5
CBLM	1	DBLB	14	CSYN	1	BLIN	1	CBLM	1	COST	2	DISC	4	BLSR	4	ASTR	2	BLJR	26	STIG	1
CCYC	8	DBLG	12	DCOM	101	BLSR	6	CCYC	1	CSYN	1	DREJ	183	BTOT	1	BLIN	2	BLMT	1	TRAL	15
CCYZ	1	DCOM	79	DDGR	6	BTOT	1	CPYG	2	CUND	1	DSEP	41	CAEN	1	BLJR	1	BLSR	108	HESC	2
CSUN	1	DGBR	64	DGBR	51	CBLM	5	CUND	1	DBLB	27	DWTH	96	CBLM	1	BLMT	1	CAEN	2	HSPR	2
CUND	3	DGRB	53	DISC	6	CCYC	3	DBLB	95	DCOM	319	FCOP	32	CCYC	1	BLSR	1	CBLM	4	HTTH	5
DBLB	12	DISC	2	DREJ	7	CSYN	1	DCOM	642	DGRY	218	LSTP	20	DBLB	247	BTOT	34	CCYC	8	HUND	18
DBLG	24	DSEP	95	DSEP	51	DBLB	23	DDGR	8	DISC	17	MFHC	24	DCOM	290	DCOM	290	CBLM	1	CKAL	1
DCOM	163	FCOP	26	EUPR	1	DCOM	221	DGRY	310	DREJ	70	MMSI	1	DDGR	21	CBLT	1	CPYG	1		
DGRB	207	LEPD	1	FCOP	9	DDGR	136	DISC	8	DSEP	156	MUND	10	DGRY	169	CCYC	5	CSYN	1		
DGRY	173	LSTP	2	MFHC	6	DGBR	6	DPYC	123	EUPR	4	NEUR	43	DISC	9	CHOP	1	DBLB	14		
DISC	17	MFHC	12	MMSI	1	DISC	2	DREJ	708	FCOP	49	HUND	6	DPYC	46	CKAL	2	DCOM	845		
DFYC	24	MMSI	4	HUND	10	DPYC	50	DSEP	139	LSTR	22	PSRK	12	DREJ	1312	CUND	1	DDGR	17		
DREJ	780	HUND	9	NEUR	5	DREJ	676	DWTH	23	LSTR	2	PCAL	23	DSEP	48	DBLB	131	DGBR	80		
DSEP	15	NEUR	46	HUND	7	DSEP	102	FCOP	41	MFHC	21	PCYC	2	EUPR	1	DCOM	324	DGRB	28		
DWTH	115	HUND	19	PAPH	1	DWTH	31	LEPD	2	MUND	2	FECP	210	FCOP	35	DDGR	77	DGRY	58		
FCOP	12	PAPH	1	PBRK	4	FCOP	53	LSTP	11	NEUR	61	PLEP	58	INCG	1	DGBR	218	DISC	14		
LSTP	3	PBRK	7	PCAL	2	FCFN	1	LSTR	1	HUND	24	PLXS	2	LEPD	1	DISC	5	DPYC	68		
MEDS	1	PCAL	10	PECP	122	INCG	67	MFHC	16	PAPH	2	PLYC	1	LSTP	3	DREJ	229	DREJ	871		
MMCR	1	PCON	1	PLEP	33	LEPD	1	MMSI	146	PBRK	53	PMAC	106	MFHC	15	DSEP	16	DSEP	15		
MMSI	2	PCRS	1	PLXS	1	LSTP	12	MPEC	1	PCAL	24	PSTM	146	MMSI	67	FCOP	23	DWTH	316		
NEUR	15	PCYC	6	PMAC	61	LSTR	1	HUND	101	PCON	3	PUND	16	MPEC	1	FPAL	1	ETAC	1		
NUND	16	PECP	333	PSTM	149	MDUN	1	NEUR	51	PCRC	1	SEED	1	HUND	25	MEDM	1	FCOP	33		
OCTO	1	PLEP	115	PUND	5	MFHC	23	NUND	39	PCRS	2			NEUR	75	MFHC	2	FCFN	1		
PBRK	4	PLXS	2	SEED	1	MMSI	29	PBRK	2	PCYC	3			NUND	21	MMCR	3	FESC	1		
PCAL	3	PLYB	1	STIG	7	HUND	38	PCAL	13	PECP	669			PBRK	2	MMSI	86	FMEG	1		
PCON	1	PMAC	30	TRAL	1	NEUR	46	PCYC	3	PLEP	198			PCAL	6	HUND	5	FPRT	1		
PECP	8	PFIN	3	WUND	1	NUND	32	PECP	208	PMAC	124			PCON	1	NEUR	115	HOLT	1		
PLEP	9	PSTM	169			PBRK	7	PLEP	58	PSTM	425			PCYC	1	HUND	34	INSC	1		
PMAC	15	PUND	27			PCAL	12	FLXS	1	PUND	35			PECP	95	ODON	2	LING	1		
PSTM	30	SEED	3			PCON	1	PMAC	93	SEED	4			PLEP	18	PAPH	1	LSTP	2		
PUND	7	SPHN	4			PCYC	5	PSTM	157	SPFR	1			PMAC	38	PBRK	9	MEDS	2		
TRAL	14	STIG	3			PECP	217	PUND	16	SPHN	6			PSTM	79	FCAL	14	MFHC	5		
WESC	2					PLEP	80	SMER	1	STIG	16			PUND	3	PCRS	3	MMSI	75		
HPLN	2					PMAC	30	STIG	5	TRAL	3			SMER	3	PCYC	3	MMSI	75		
HSJH	1					PSTM	198	TCAR	1	HSPR	1			TRAL	8	PECP	69	MPEC	4		
HTTH	1					PUND	3	TFBR	1					HTTH	2	PLEP	29	HSTR	2		
HUND	10					SEED	4	TRAL	1					WUND	4	PMAC	61	HUND	26		
						SMER	2	HSPR	1							PSTM	117	NEUR	108		
						STIG	7	HTTH	1							PUND	9	NUND	46		
						TRAL	2	HUND	8							STIG	1	OCTO	2		
						HTTH	2									TRAL	1	PBRK	8		
						WUND	1									HSPR	2	PCAL	20		
																HTTH	10	PCYC	3		
																		PECP	107		
																		PLEP	16		
																		PMAC	63		
																		PSTM	200		

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 62		LOC 63		LOC 63		LOC 64		LOC 65		LOC 66		LOC 67		LOC 68		LOC 69		
LOC 61		LOC 62		LOC 62		LOC 63		LOC 64		LOC 65		LOC 66		LOC 67		LOC 68		LOC 69		
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		
SUM 1541		SUM 2361		SUM 4043		SUM 2102		SUM 113		SUM 1053		SUM 1279		SUM 483		SUM 7				
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
ANHL 10	ALTH 3	TRAL 14	ALTH 3	PUND 47	ANHL 22	DBLB 9	ANHL 6	ANNL 13	ALTH 1	DPYC 2										
ASTR 1	ANHL 29	HCAP 1	AMPH 1	SEED 1	ARTH 1	DDGR 57	BLIN 3	ASTR 1	ANNL 5	FLEP 2										
BLIN 2	ARAC 1	WESC 1	ANHL 45	SMER 18	BLIN 12	DGBR 4	BLJR 5	BLIN 15	ASTR 1	PMAC 2										
BLJR 1	ASTR 3	HPLN 1	ASTR 2	STIG 1	BLJR 9	NUND 1	BLMT 1	BLJR 11	BLIN 3	PSTH 1										
BTOT 7	BLIN 20	HSPR 1	BLIN 11	THRN 1	BLSR 11	PECP 1	BLSR 24	BLSR 24	BLJR 5											
CCYC 2	BLJR 11	HTTH 11	BLJR 3	TRAL 16	BTOT 7	PLEP 11	BTOT 17	CBLT 1	BLSR 2											
CESS 1	BLSR 18	HUND 11	BLSR 11	WESC 4	BTOT 7	PHAC 11	CBLT 1	CCYC 5	CCYC 2											
COST 1	CAEN 1		CBLM 13	HILY 2	CBLT 3	PSTH 15	CCYC 1	CPYG 1	DCOM 36											
CSUN 1	CBLM 8		CBLT 1	HSPR 4	CCYC 4	PUND 2	CPAL 1	DCOM 280	DDGR 65											
CUND 1	CCYC 4		CCYC 3	HTTH 11	CFLE 1	HTTH 2	CUND 1	DDGR 50	DGBR 223											
DCOM 716	CHOP 1		CKAL 1	HUND 23	CKAL 1		DCOM 333	DGBR 183	DISC 6											
DDGR 2	CKAL 1		CSYN 3		DBLB 104		DDGR 104	DISC 7	DPYC 13											
DGBR 53	CPAL 1		DBLB 95		DBLG 64		DGBR 88	DPYC 6	DSEP 15											
DPYC 27	CPYG 1		DBLG 227		DBRN 28		DGRB 123	DREJ 475	FCOP 2											
DREJ 215	CSUN 2		DCOM 843		DCOM 263		DISC 10	DSEP 14	LSTP 1											
DSEP 14	CSYN 3		DDGR 76		DDGR 172		DREJ 87	EUCH 1	HMCR 1											
FCOP 26	DBLB 39		DGRB 151		DGBR 194		DSEP 22	FCOP 11	MPEC 3											
INSC 1	DBLG 627		DGRY 28		DISC 11		FACN 1	HOLT 1	HUND 2											
LSTR 1	DCOM 625		DISC 22		OPYC 1		FCOP 11	LSTP 1	NEUR 13											
HEDS 3	DGRB 235		DLGH 1		DREJ 585		HOLT 1	HEDS 3	NUND 24											
MFHC 8	DISC 7		DPYC 20		DSEP 38		LEPD 1	MFHC 3	PCRC 1											
MMSI 41	DLBG 7		DREJ 701		DUDS 132		HEDS 1	MMSI 1	PECP 12											
MPEC 5	DPYC 14		DSEP 152		FACN 1		MPEC 1	MPEC 2	PLEP 7											
HUND 9	DSEP 45		DWTH 462		FCOP 24		NEUR 44	HUND 5	PMAC 3											
NEUR 99	FCOP 31		FCOP 92		LSTP 7		NUND 20	NEUR 16	PSTH 23											
NUND 41	FCTN 1		FCTN 1		MFHC 6		PAPH 1	NUND 29	PUND 6											
PBRK 1	FMHG 1		FPRT 1		HMCR 1		PBRK 1	PCAL 2	SMER 3											
PCAL 5	FPAL 1		INCG 11		MMSI 46		PCAL 4	PCYC 1	SFHN 1											
PECP 40	INSC 1		INSC 1		MMSH 1		PECP 47	PECP 24	SPMG 1											
PLEP 7	LSTP 1		LIMU 1		MPEC 8		PFUN 1	PLEP 9	TRAL 3											
PMAC 65	MFHC 7		LSTP 6		HUND 9		PLEP 20	PMAC 14												
PHAR 1	MMSI 15		LSTR 1		NEUR 51		PNAC 10	PSTH 38												
PSTH 116	MPEC 1		HEDM 3		HUND 39		PSFR 1	PUND 4												
PTAE 1	HUND 3		HEDS 3		PBRK 2		PSTH 28	SHER 2												
PUND 6	NCYC 1		MFHC 6		PCAL 7		PUND 6	SPHN 2												
STIG 1	NEUR 33		HTTH 2		PECP 36		SCBR 1	TRAL 13												
TRAL 3	HUND 66		MMSI 22		PLEP 30		SHER 1	HCAP 1												
HSJH 1	PBRK 1		MMSH 2		PLXS 1		SPHN 2	HSPR 2												
HTTH 2	PCAL 7		MPEC 1		PHAC 30		TRAL 4	HTTH 1												
HUND 4	PCRD 1		HUND 22		PSTH 60		HCAP 5	HUND 7												
	PCYC 2		NEUR 189		PUND 12		HTTH 6													
	PECP 109		NUND 87		SEED 3		HUND 8													
	PLEP 114		PBRK 6		SPFR 2															
	PMAC 70		PCAL 17		STIG 1															
	PPIN 1		PCON 2		TPEL 1															
	PSTH 119		PCYC 13		TRAL 16															
	PUND 20		PECP 129		WESC 3															
	SMER 5		PLEP 143		HTTH 19															
	SPHH 1		PLXS 1		HUND 17															
	STIG 1		PMAC 120																	
	TFBR 2		PSTH 160																	

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LOC 81		LOC 82		LOC 83		LOC 84		LOC 85		LOC 86		LOC 87		LOC 88		LOC 89		LOC 90		LOC 90	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 321		SUM 694		SUM 497		SUM 288		SUM 1341		SUM 548		SUM 1992		SUM 40		SUM 1592		SUM 863		SUM 863	
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT	
ASTR	1	ALTH	1	ANNL	2	ANNL	1	ANNL	4	ALTH	1	ALTH	2	BLJR	1	ALTH	5	ALTH	4	HTTH	1
DCOM	165	ANNL	2	BLIN	6	BLIN	2	BLIN	38	ANNL	5	ANNL	5	DDGR	6	ANNL	9	ANND	1	HUND	9
DDGR	4	BTOT	2	BLJR	6	BLJR	4	BLJR	57	BLSR	6	BLIN	20	DGBR	20	BLIN	56	ANNL	2		
DGRB	22	DDGR	37	BLSR	12	BLSR	9	BLSR	404	CCYC	1	BLJR	56	DISC	3	BLJR	125	BLIN	23		
DPYC	7	DGBR	140	BTOT	13	CCYC	1	CBLT	1	DCOM	128	BLSR	21	DPYC	2	BLHT	2	BLJR	43		
DREJ	18	DGRB	89	CAEN	1	CMES	1	DCOM	113	DGBR	47	BTOT	13	DSEP	2	BLSR	88	BLNT	1		
FCOP	4	DGRY	16	CBLM	1	DDGR	12	DGRY	276	DGRY	23	CCYC	1	NEDS	1	CBLM	17	BLSR	21		
LSTR	1	DISC	1	CKAL	1	DGBR	184	DISC	18	DISC	8	DCOM	540	PNAC	3	CBLT	33	CAEN	1		
NUND	2	DLGH	2	DBLB	1	DISC	1	DPYC	31	DREJ	215	DDGR	3	PSTH	1	CCYC	3	CBLM	6		
ODON	1	DPYC	8	DCOM	195	DPYC	1	DREJ	282	DSEP	2	DGRY	149	HUND	1	CESS	1	CBLT	10		
PCAL	1	DREJ	244	DGBR	81	DREJ	8	DSEP	22	DHWH	45	DISC	8			CFLE	1	CCYC	11		
PCYC	1	DSEP	5	DPYC	148	DSEP	2	ETAC	1	EGGS	1	DPYC	1			CKAL	1	CESS	4		
PECP	11	FCOP	6	FCOP	3	FCOP	4	FCOP	17	FCOP	5	DREJ	665			CKEL	1	CFLE	3		
PLEP	57	LSTP	1	MHSI	2	INCG	2	FESC	1	HOLT	1	DSEP	8			CPEA	2	CKAL	1		
PMAC	8	MHSI	73	NEUR	1	LYBR	1	NEDS	1	HEDH	3	DNTH	200			CSUN	1	COST	1		
PSTH	13	MUND	1	NUND	3	HEDH	3	HSTR	3	HEDS	28	FCOP	10			DCOM	198	CPAL	1		
SPHN	4	NEUR	20	PECP	2	HEDS	15	NEUR	19	HPEC	1	HDEV	1			DGBR	77	CSUN	1		
STIG	1	NUND	9	PLEP	1	MEUP	1	NUND	2	HUND	2	HOLT	6			DGRY	58	CUND	1		
		FCYC	1	PMAC	2	MHSI	1	PCAL	1	NUND	5	INCG	2			DISC	62	DCOM	41		
		PECP	7	PSTH	9	MUND	1	PECP	11	PBRK	2	LEPD	1			DPYC	96	DGBR	81		
		PLEP	1	PUND	2	NEUR	3	PLEP	1	PECP	2	LSTP	2			DREJ	354	DGRY	71		
		PMAC	6	TRAL	4	NUND	6	PMAC	4	PMAC	3	MEDH	8			DSEP	30	DISC	31		
		PSTH	15	HTTH	1	PBRK	1	PSTH	22	PSTH	4	MEDS	139			ETAC	1	DPYC	19		
		PUND	4			PCAL	1	PUND	3	TPEL	1	MEUP	3			FCOP	47	DREJ	210		
		TRAL	2			PECP	2	THON	8	TRAL	4	MFHC	1			INCG	2	DSEP	10		
		NUND	1			PMAC	1	HUND	1	WFSH	1	NMCR	1			INSC	1	ETAC	1		
						PSTH	8			HTTH	1	HPEC	3			LEPD	1	FACN	1		
						PUND	1			HSCZ	1	HUND	2			MFHC	1	FCOP	32		
						SMER	5			HUND	2	HUND	2			NMCR	5	INCG	1		
						TRAL	3			NEUR	4	NEUR	4			MHSI	12	MEDS	3		
						HUND	3			NUND	7	NUND	7			HSTR	3	MFHC	2		
										PASO	1	NEUR	10			NEUR	10	MHSI	10		
										PBRK	2	NUND	28			NUND	28	HPEC	3		
										PCAL	14	PCAL	2			PCAL	2	HUND	2		
										PCYC	2	PECP	44			PECP	44	NEUR	11		
										PECP	10	PLEP	10			PLEP	10	NUND	14		
										PLEP	3	PNAC	65			PNAC	65	PBRK	1		
										PMAC	10	PSTH	62			PSTH	62	PCYC	2		
										PSTH	22	PUND	3			PUND	3	PECP	25		
										PUND	5	SMER	17			SMER	17	PLEP	1		
										TPEL	4	TFBR	1			TFBR	1	PNAC	24		
										TRAL	23	TFTR	1			TFTR	1	PSTH	51		
										WESC	4	THON	26			THON	26	PUND	2		
										WFSH	3	TRAL	23			TRAL	23	SMER	7		
										HTTH	1	WESC	1			WESC	1	SPHN	1		
										HUND	5	HTTH	1			HTTH	1	THON	16		
																HUND	5	TRAL	35		
																HCAP	2				
																WESC	4				
																WHYS	1				
																WSJW	3				

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 91		LOC 92		LOC 93		LOC 94		LOC 95		LOC 96		LOC 97		LOC 98		LOC 99		LOC 100		LOC 101			
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES			
SUM 55		SUM 13		SUM 72		SUM 564		SUM 1044		SUM 210		SUM 263		SUM 286		SUM 690		SUM 1865		SUM 505		SUM 505			
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT			
DCOM	45	DCON	9	DCOM	58	ANHL	2	ALTH	1	ANHL	4	BLIN	6	BLJR	1	BLSR	1	ALTH	1	DCOM	502				
DPYC	2	HUND	1	DPYC	3	BLJR	1	ANHL	6	BLIN	4	BLJR	4	BLJR	1	DCOM	282	DCOM	679	ANHL	6	DSEP	1		
PECP	1	PLEP	1	DSEP	3	BLSR	1	BLIN	18	BLJR	1	BLSR	1	BLSR	1	FCOP	1	DSPH	1	BLIN	6	BLIN	6	NEUR	1
PMAC	1	PMAC	1	PLEP	4	CBLM	1	BLJR	15	BLSR	1	DCOM	211	NUND	2	NUND	2	NUND	1	BLJR	7	PSTH	1	PSTH	1
PSTH	3	PSTH	1	PSTH	4	DCOM	208	BLSR	4	CCYC	1	DGRB	11	DGRB	11	PECP	3	PECP	3	BLSR	10				
PUND	3					DDGR	4	CBLM	1	CFYG	1	DGRF	6	DGRF	6	PSTH	3	PSTH	3	CBLM	1				
						DGBR	301	CCYC	3	DBLB	17	DPYC	10	DPYC	10	PUND	1	PUND	1	CBLT	2				
						DSEP	1	DCOM	256	DCOM	104	DSEP	4	DSEP	4	TRAL	1	TRAL	1	CKAL	1				
						FCOP	3	DDGR	6	DGRB	18	NUND	3	NUND	3					CPEA	2				
						LEPD	1	DGRB	363	DPYC	17	PMAC	5	PMAC	5					CSUN	1				
						NUND	14	DISC	8	DSEP	5	PSTH	3	PSTH	3					CTYR	1				
						PCYC	1	DPYC	9	FCOP	6	TRAL	1	TRAL	1					DCOM	1270				
						PECP	6	DREJ	241	HOLT	1	NUND	1	NUND	1					DDGR	43				
						PLEP	4	DSEP	9	HEDS	1									DGBR	44				
						PSTH	11	FCOP	5	NUND	8									DGBR	23				
						PUND	2	HOLT	4	PLEP	3									DISC	7				
						TRAL	3	LSTP	1	PMAC	1									DPYC	15				
								HEDS	6	PSTH	11									DREJ	344				
								HFEC	2	TRAL	6									DSEP	7				
								HUND	2											DSND	6				
								NEUR	1											FCOP	10				
								NUND	22											FESC	1				
								PECP	3											NEUR	1				
								PMAC	16											NUND	24				
								PSTH	16											PCAL	1				
								PUND	1											PCYC	1				
								TRAL	22											PECP	5				
								HUND	3											PLEP	1				
																				PMAC	6				
																				PSTH	9				
																				TRAL	9				

LISTING BY LOCATION

LOC 102		LOC 103		LOC 104		LOC 105		LOC 106		LOC 107		LOC 108		LOC 109		LOC 110		LOC 111		LOC 112	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES									
SUM 739	SUM 378	SUM 441	SUM 1892	SUM 1879	SUM 755	SUM 391	SUM 417	SUM 1281	SUM 169	SUM 305											
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT																			
AICH 1	ANNL 1	ANNL 1	ANNL 6	ALTH 1	BLGR 3	ALTH 1	ANNL 1	ALTH 1	ALTH 1	DCOM 35											
ANNL 1	BTOT 3	BLIN 1	BLIN 95	ANNL 76	BLIN 12	ANNL 5	ASTR 8	BTOT 2	DCOM 28	DGRY 79											
BTOT 1	CSUN 1	BLJR 2	BLJR 74	BLIN 6	BLJR 4	ASTR 18	DBLG 31	DBLB 31	DGRY 20	DPYC 3											
DBLB 3	DCOM 97	CMRS 1	BLMT 5	BLJR 9	BLSR 12	CPAL 1	DCOM 148	DCOM 189	DPYC 1	DREJ 108											
DCOM 435	DDGR 7	DCOM 143	BLSR 126	BLSR 41	BTOT 24	DCOM 141	DGGR 23	DGBR 131	DREJ 79	DSEP 3											
DGRB 26	DGBR 123	DDGR 4	BTOT 118	BTOT 20	CKAL 1	DPYC 47	DPYC 23	DGRY 156	DSEP 4	DWTH 47											
DREJ 253	DISC 1	DGBR 24	CCYC 2	CAEN 1	DCOM 132	DSEP 2	DYLB 20	DPYC 8	DWTH 14	MEDS 7											
DSND 3	DPYC 19	DPYC 5	CSYN 1	CBLN 1	DDGR 4	DWTH 29	FCOP 5	DREJ 321	FCOP 1	NEUR 3											
NEUR 1	DREJ 114	DREJ 250	DCOM 440	CBLT 2	DGBR 111	FCOP 1	LYBR 2	DSEP 72	HOLT 1	NUND 5											
NUND 5	NEUR 2	NEUR 3	DDGR 42	CCYC 2	DPYC 9	NEUR 2	NEUR 5	DWTH 13	MEDS 13	PCYC 1											
PECP 2	NUND 4	NUND 4	DGBR 7	CMRS 1	DREJ 107	NUND 2	PCAL 2	FCOP 7	NUND 4	PECP 4											
PLEP 1	PLEP 1	PECP 2	DGRY 169	CPYG 1	DWTH 203	PCAL 1	PCYC 1	HOLT 35	PHAC 1	PSTH 3											
PSTH 3	PMAC 1	PSTH 1	DPYC 5	CSUN 1	FCOP 10	PECP 49	PECP 16	INCG 19	PSTH 1	FUND 2											
PUND 3	PSTH 3		DREJ 261	DCOM 433	HOLT 1	PLEP 14	FLEP 49	HEDS 101	TRAL 1												
TRAL 1	PUND 1		DSEP 1	DDGR 130	HEDM 2	PHAC 35	PHAC 43	HPEC 1													
			DWTH 244	DGRY 77	HEDS 25	PSTH 43	PSTH 34	MUND 1													
			FCOP 15	DPYC 11	MHTW 1	PUND 1	PUND 6	HEUR 11													
			FCTN 1	DREJ 218	MPEC 7			NUND 82													
			FGIL 1	DSEP 17	MSCZ 6			PBRK 1													
			FRHB 1	DWTH 324	MUND 1			PECP 13													
			HOLT 5	FCOP 22	NEUR 2			PLEP 1													
			LIMU 1	HOLT 23	NUND 6			PMAC 1													
			HEDM 2	MEDC 1	PCAL 1			PSTH 12													
			MEDS 68	MEDS 15	PCYC 1			PUND 1													
			MEUP 1	MFWC 3	PECP 4			TRAL 70													
			MPEC 16	MMSI 2	PHAC 19			HPLN 1													
			MSCZ 1	MPEC 5	PSTH 21																
			MUND 4	MUND 4	PUND 5																
			NEUR 6	NEUR 19	SHER 2																
			NUND 11	NUND 20	TRAL 17																
			PCAL 1	ODON 1	WDRY 1																
			PECP 20	PCAL 24	HESC 1																
			FLEP 5	PCRS 1																	
			PMAC 12	PECP 94																	
			PSTH 17	FLEP 41																	
			SPHN 5	PMAC 34																	
			TRAL 90	PPIN 2																	
			WDLN 1	PSTH 131																	
			WESC 2	PUND 5																	
			WTHH 6	STIG 3																	
			WUND 4	TFBR 4																	
				TMON 1																	
				TRAL 25																	
				HCAP 10																	
				WHYS 1																	
				WTHH 11																	
				WUND 5																	

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 113		LOC 114		LOC 116		LOC 122		LOC 123		LOC 124		LOC 125		LOC 126		LOC 127		LOC 128		LOC 129	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 1268		SUM 271		SUM 105		SUM 99		SUM 88		SUM 327		SUM 778		SUM 1106		SUM 630		SUM 333		SUM 1560		SUM 1560	
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT	
ALTH	4	DCOH	27	DGRY	51	BLMT	3	BTOT	12	ARTH	2	ANNL	2	ALTH	5	ALTH	2	ANNL	3	ANND	1	ANND	1
ANNL	2	DGRY	65	DSEP	10	BTOT	45	CCYC	1	BLIN	24	BLIN	18	ANND	1	ANND	1	BLIN	15	ANNL	1	ANNL	1
BLIN	1	DPYC	32	DWTH	40	CBLT	3	DFYC	6	BLJR	50	BLJR	36	ANNL	8	DLIN	35	BLJR	20	BLIN	35	BLIN	35
BTOT	1	DREJ	101	PNAC	2	DCOH	15	FCOP	19	BLSR	19	BLOD	1	BLIN	29	BLJR	33	BLSR	105	BLJR	95	BLJR	95
CBLT	103	DSEP	8	PSTH	1	DPYC	2	HOLT	4	CBLM	2	BLSR	147	BLJR	36	BLPL	6	CBLT	2	BLOD	1	BLOD	1
DCOH	75	DWTH	11	TRAL	1	DSEP	1	HEDS	19	CBLT	2	BTOT	3	BLPL	2	BLSR	182	CSUN	2	BLPL	1	BLPL	1
DGBR	118	HOLT	1			HOLT	1	HPEC	2	CCYC	2	CBLT	1	BLSR	247	CBLT	2	DCOH	145	BLSR	95	BLSR	95
DGRY	149	MEDS	6			MEDS	2	NUND	7	DGRB	117	CKAL	2	CBLM	2	CKAL	1	DGBR	7	BTOT	17	BTOT	17
DPYC	16	MUND	1			NUND	2	PECP	1	DISC	6	DCOH	195	CBLT	4	CHRS	1	DPYC	8	CBAR	1	CBAR	1
DREJ	471	MUND	6			PBRK	1	PNAC	2	DFYC	8	DGBR	41	DCOH	479	DCOH	249	ETAC	2	CBLM	1	CBLM	1
DSEP	45	PCYC	1			PCAL	1	TRAL	13	DSEP	9	DGRB	71	DGBR	34	DDGR	1	FCOP	6	CBLT	3	CBLT	3
FCOP	2	PECP	2			PECP	4	HPLN	2	ETAC	1	DISC	3	DGRB	20	DGRB	2	NEUR	2	CPEA	1	CPEA	1
HOLT	21	PNAC	1			PNAC	17			FCOP	8	DFYC	118	DISC	4	DFYC	7	NUND	1	DCOH	157	DCOH	157
INCG	6	PSTH	4			HNYS	1			NCEP	1	DSEP	14	DPYC	64	DREJ	17	PAPH	1	DGBR	20	DGBR	20
MEDS	55	TRAL	5			WUND	1			MNSI	1	FCOP	41	DREJ	12	DSEP	4	PCAL	1	DGRB	136	DGRB	136
HEUP	3									HSTR	1	FCTN	2	DSEP	10	FCOP	24	PCON	1	DISC	1	DISC	1
HPEC	1									NUND	5	MEDS	5	FCOP	27	INSC	1	PECP	6	DPYC	181	DPYC	181
HSCZ	1									ODON	3	HSTR	7	FESC	1	MEDS	7	PSTH	4	DREJ	350	DREJ	350
NUND	1									PECP	7	NEUR	12	NEUR	20	HSTR	7	THON	2	DSEP	2	DSEP	2
NEUR	26									PNAC	22	NUND	5	NUND	7	NEUR	6			DTOT	350	DTOT	350
NUND	39									PSTH	14	PAPH	1	OCTO	2	NUND	10			EGGS	1	EGGS	1
PCYC	3									PUND	2	PBRK	2	PCAL	3	PCAL	3			ETAC	2	ETAC	2
PECP	41									THAL	1	PCYC	1	PCYC	1	PCYC	1			FCOP	13	FCOP	13
PNAC	9									THON	2	PECP	19	PECP	29	PECP	10			FESC	1	FESC	1
PSTH	35									TRAL	7	PLYB	2	PNAC	2	PSTH	9			FPAL	1	FPAL	1
PUND	2									HCAP	3	PNAC	3	PPIN	1	SMER	4			INCG	1	INCG	1
TFBR	1									HESC	3	PSTH	11	PSTH	30	THON	1			HGHT	34	HGHT	34
TRAL	37									HSPR	1	PUND	3	PUND	2	TRAL	3			HEDS	2	HEDS	2
										HTTH	2	THON	7	SEED	1	NUND	1			MNSI	6	MNSI	6
										WUND	2	TREL	2	SNER	1					HPEC	1	HPEC	1
												TRAL	3	THON	11					HSTR	3	HSTR	3
														HTTH	1					NEUR	7	NEUR	7
																				NUND	11	NUND	11
																				OCTO	1	OCTO	1
																				PCAL	3	PCAL	3
																				PECP	2	PECP	2
																				PNAC	6	PNAC	6
																				PSTH	5	PSTH	5
																				PUND	2	PUND	2
																				THAL	1	THAL	1
																				THON	1	THON	1
																				TRAL	3	TRAL	3
																				HESC	1	HESC	1
																				YWHY	3	YWHY	3

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 132		LOC 133		LOC 134		LOC 135		LOC 136		LOC 137		LOC 138		LOC 139	
LOC 130	LOC 131	LOC 132	LOC 133	LOC 133	LOC 134	LOC 135	LOC 136	LOC 136	LOC 137	LOC 138	LOC 139						
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES
SUM 1829	SUM 239	SUM 499	SUM 2549	SUM 992	SUM 874	SUM 519	SUM 1159	SUM 332	SUM 40								
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT								
ANND 1	ANHL 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 28	WUND 9	ALTH 2	ALTH 6	ALTH 1	ALTH 1	ANNL 2	ANNL 1	ANNL 1	ANNL 2	ANNL 1				
ANHL 8	BLIN 20	ANHL 4	ASTR 1		ANNL 15	ANNL 50	ANNL 6	ANNL 16	CAEN 1	DGBR 17							
BLIN 77	BLJR 9	BLIN 16	BLIN 59		ASTR 2	CPAL 1	COST 1	ASTR 1	DCOM 46	DPYC 6							
BLJR 230	BLSR 58	BLJR 15	BLJR 271		DCOM 225	DBLB 14	CSUN 1	CSUN 1	DDGR 33	DSHD 3							
BLSR 414	CBLM 1	BLPL 1	BLPL 4		DDGR 80	DCOM 67	CSYN 1	DCOM 157	DPYC 2	FCOP 1							
BTOT 197	DCOM 108	BLSR 71	BLSR 540		DPYC 57	DDGR 15	DCOM 99	DDGR 132	DREJ 81	PECP 2							
CBLM 3	DISC 1	BTOT 28	CBLM 13		DSEP 1	DGBR 51	DDGR 69	DGBR 17	DSEP 1	PLEP 7							
CBLT 6	DODD 2	CKAL 1	CBLT 15		DUDS 90	DGRB 102	DGRB 60	DPYC 135	DWTH 25	PMAC 2							
CFLE 1	DSEP 12	DCOM 129	CCYC 2		FCOP 11	DREJ 32	DPYC 32	DREJ 163	FCOP 12	PSTM 1							
CKAL 2	ETAC 1	DGBR 3	CFLE 1		LSTP 48	DSEP 4	DSEP 7	DSEP 26	LEPD 1								
CPEA 1	FCOP 5	DGRB 21	CKAL 1		MFHC 4	EUPR 9	EUPR 1	DWTH 94	LSTP 1								
CUND 5	NEUR 7	DISC 1	CPRT 1		MUND 3	FCOP 29	FCOP 23	FCOP 78	LSTR 1								
DCOM 370	NUND 3	DODD 22	CSUN 3		NEUR 28	LEPD 2	FXNT 2	FMEG 1	NEUR 5								
DGBR 20	PCAL 4	DPYC 35	CTYR 1		NUND 3	LSTP 14	LSTP 3	LEPD 1	NUND 9								
DGRB 5	PECP 5	DREJ 99	DCOM 975		PAPH 1	MFHC 4	LSTR 2	LSTP 3	PBRK 1								
DISC 3	PSTM 2	DSEP 5	DGBR 66		PBRK 1	HUND 1	MFHC 1	MFHC 6	PCAL 1								
DPYC 85		ETAC 1	DISC 17		FCAL 7	NEUR 66	HUND 1	NEUR 12	PCON 1								
DREJ 209		FCOP 12	DSEP 85		PCON 1	NUND 9	NEUR 10	NUND 15	PCYC 2								
DSEP 26		INSC 1	ETAC 11		FCYC 2	ODON 2	NUND 26	PBRK 5	PECP 29								
ETAC 8		MEDS 1	FCOP 99		PECP 164	PBRK 17	PBRK 9	PECP 93	PLEP 47								
FCOP 23		HSTR 1	FCFN 1		PLEP 127	PCAL 31	PCAL 4	PLEP 116	PLXS 1								
FESC 4		NEUR 5	FESC 1		PMAC 40	PCRC 1	PCYC 1	PMAC 24	PLYB 1								
FRHB 1		NUND 3	FRHB 2		PSTM 75	PCYC 2	PDRN 1	PFIN 1	PMAC 6								
LEPD 1		NUND 2	HOLT 8		PUND 5	PECP 119	PECP 45	PSTM 43	PSTM 12								
MEDS 2		PECP 14	INCG 1			PLEP 72	PLEP 42	PUND 17	PUND 9								
MHSI 2		PSTM 6	HSTR 8			PLYB 1	PMAC 34	SPHN 1	SPFR 1								
MSTR 3		TRAL 1	NCYC 1			PMAC 48	PSTM 31		STIG 1								
NEUR 27			NEUR 11			PPIN 1	PUND 3										
NUND 17			NUND 13			PSTM 80	SEED 1										
ODON 1			OCTO 1			PUND 12	SPFR 1										
PCAL 6			PCAL 4			REGC 1	SPHN 1										
PCYC 2			PCYC 1			SEED 2											
PECP 25			PECP 110			SPHN 6											
PSTM 17			PLEP 4			STIG 2											
PUND 4			PLXS 1			HSPR 1											
REGC 1			PSTM 75														
THON 10			PUND 8														
TRAL 9			STIG 1														
HTTH 1			TCON 1														
WUND 2			TDPL 22														
			TFBR 1														
			THON 8														
			TPEL 4														
			TRAL 22														
			NCAP 23														
			MHYS 1														
			HOLH 1														
			HPLN 5														
			HPRI 1														
			HISJH 1														
			HTTH 6														

LISTING BY LOCATION

LOC 140		LOC 141		LOC 142		LOC 143		LOC 144		LOC 145		LOC 148		LOC 149		LOC 150		LOC 151		LOC 152	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 1347		SUM 776		SUM 348		SUM 343		SUM 111		SUM 488		SUM 623		SUM 1130		SUM 734		SUM 1211		SUM 957	
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT	
ALTH	3	ANNL	1	BLIN	1	ANNL	5	ANNL	2	BLJR	2	ANNL	4	ALTH	1	ANNL	8	BLIN	5	ANNL	11
ANNL	14	BLIN	5	BLHT	1	BTOT	100	BLHT	2	BLMT	1	BLIN	10	BLIN	8	BLIN	18	BLJR	3	BLIN	31
CAEN	1	BLJR	6	BTOT	174	CBLT	23	BTOT	18	BLSR	10	BLJR	16	BLJR	19	BLJR	44	BLSR	5	BLJR	59
COST	1	BLSR	15	CAEN	1	CCYC	1	CBLT	6	DGRY	366	BLMT	3	BLMT	8	BLMT	2	DGRY	732	BLSR	33
DCOM	392	BTOT	22	CBAR	2	CFLE	1	CFLE	1	DPYC	4	BLSR	41	BLSR	10	BLSR	29	DISC	14	DGRY	548
DDGR	247	CBLM	4	CBLT	20	CKAL	2	CKAL	1	FCOP	15	CBLM	2	CBLT	1	CBLM	2	DPYC	247	DPYC	61
DPYC	38	CBLT	1	CCYC	3	DCOM	102	CKEL	1	HOLT	4	CCYC	1	DGBR	81	CCYC	1	DSEP	21	DSEP	10
DREJ	201	CKAL	2	CESS	1	ETAC	2	DCOM	46	HEDS	14	DGRY	316	DGRY	417	DGRY	423	FCOP	15	FCOP	5
DSEP	12	CPYG	1	CKAL	1	FCOP	19	DPYC	2	MEUP	2	DISC	2	DPYC	277	DPYC	40	HOLT	7	HOLT	23
DNTH	6	CUND	1	DCOM	76	FGIL	1	FCOP	2	NEUR	3	DPYC	63	DSEP	32	DSEP	10	HEDS	5	MEDM	19
FCOP	95	DCOM	219	ETAC	2	HOLT	3	HFTR	1	PBRK	7	DSEP	8	ETAC	1	FCOP	6	HSOL	2	HEDS	38
LEPD	1	DGBR	1	FCOP	16	HEDS	1	HEDS	2	PCAL	1	FCOP	10	FCOP	30	HOLT	19	PECP	17	PLEP	1
LSTP	5	DODD	2	MNSI	1	MNSI	1	MNSI	1	PECP	5	HOLT	12	HOLT	14	MEDM	13	PLEP	9	PHAC	16
LSTR	1	DREJ	389	HSCZ	1	HSTR	1	NEUR	2	PHAC	3	HEDS	34	LING	15	HEDS	27	PSTH	26	PSTH	7
HFHC	6	DTOT	38	HSTR	1	OCTO	1	PCAL	3	TRAL	46	PECP	1	HEDS	6	PECP	2	TRAL	72	TRAL	84
HUND	2	ETAC	1	PBRK	1	FBRK	1	PECP	1	HUND	5	PHAC	19	NEUR	10	PHAC	14	HCAP	4	HTTH	2
HEUR	20	FCOP	10	PCAL	8	PCAL	6	PHAC	14	PSTH	11	NUND	3	PSTH	2	PSTH	2	HTTH	11	HUND	9
HUND	5	NEUR	8	PECP	5	PECP	3	PSTH	1	TMON	4	PECP	25	TMON	1	HUND	16				
PBRK	4	HUND	13	PHAC	6	PHAC	24	TMON	1	TRAL	56	PLEP	19	TRAL	62						
PCAL	5	PCAL	2	PSTH	3	PSTH	1	HCAP	1	HTTH	1	PSTH	44	HUND	11						
PCYC	5	PECP	12	PUND	14	PUND	12	HESC	1	HUND	9	TRAL	76								
PECP	62	PHAC	2	SMER	3	SPHT	1	HTTH	2			HTTH	4								
PLEP	85	PSTH	13	TMON	2	STIG	2					HUND	29								
PLYC	1	PUND	1	HESC	1	TMON	9														
PHAC	49	TMON	3	WHYS	2	TRAL	13														
PSTH	66	TRAL	3	HUND	2	WBLH	1														
PSUL	1	HTTH	1			HESC	1														
PUND	11					WHYS	2														
SEED	1					HPLN	1														
SFHH	4					HTTH	3														
STIG	1																				
TFBR	1																				
TFTR	1																				

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LOC 153	LOC 154	LOC 155	LOC 156	LOC 157	LOC 158	LOC 159	LOC 160	LOC 161	LOC 162	LOC 163	
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES
SUM 959	SUM 1080	SUM 867	SUM 732	SUM 707	SUM 480	SUM 797	SUM 1142	SUM 785	SUM 589	SUM 310	
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
ANNL 10	AHNL 21	ANNL 1	ANNL 5	ALTH 5	BLIN 12	BLIN 37	ANNL 4	ANNL 16	BLIN 5	ANNL 1	
BLIN 15	BLIN 29	BLIN 33	BLIN 21	BLIN 3	BLJR 15	BLJR 25	BLIN 13	BLIN 15	BLJR 3	BLIN 15	
BLSR 12	BLJR 31	BLJR 15	BLJR 19	BLJR 29	BLMT 8	BLMT 16	BLJR 32	BLJR 30	BLSR 13	BLJR 34	
CBLM 1	BLMT 36	BLSR 14	BLSR 25	BLMT 13	BLSR 17	BLSR 21	BLMT 5	BLSR 37	BTOT 9	BLMT 10	
CBLT 2	BLSR 17	CBLT 3	CBLT 5	BLSR 11	DGRY 236	CCYC 9	BLSR 59	DGRY 396	CSUN 1	BLSR 12	
DGRY 431	DGRY 529	DGRY 366	DGRY 75	CBLM 4	DPYC 36	DDGR 48	DGRY 286	DPYC 12	DGBR 213	CBLM 3	
DISC 7	DISC 10	DISC 6	DISC 8	CBLT 11	DSEP 17	DGRY 264	DISC 16	DSEP 30	DGRY 109	CCYC 4	
DPYC 123	DPYC 71	DPYC 128	DPYC 252	CSUN 1	FCOP 13	DPYC 43	DPYC 12	FCOP 19	DISC 4	DGRY 146	
DREJ 119	DSEP 29	DSEP 36	DSEP 39	DCOM 99	FGIL 1	DREJ 142	DREJ 274	HOLT 14	DREJ 117	DPYC 14	
DSEP 34	FCOP 3	FCOP 39	FCOP 35	DGRY 210	HOLT 18	HOLT 6	DSEP 28	MEDS 44	DSEP 5	DSEP 3	
FCOP 27	HOLT 59	HOLT 49	HOLT 53	DISC 7	MEDS 10	MSOL 4	FCOP 37	MMSI 17	DSPT 1	FCOP 3	
HOLT 39	MEDM 4	MEDM 2	MEDM 1	DSEP 12	PECP 9	PECP 39	HOLT 15	NEUR 19	FCOP 18	HOLT 7	
MEDM 2	MEDS 16	MEDS 10	MEDS 6	FCOP 21	PSTH 20	PMAC 30	MEDS 35	PECP 29	LEPD 4	MEDS 4	
MEDS 6	MPEC 13	MPEC 5	MPEC 5	HOLT 18	THON 2	PSTH 18	NEUR 14	TRAL 89	MEDM 4	HPEC 2	
MSCZ 5	MUND 4	OCTO 2	MSCZ 3	LEPD 5	TRAL 62	THON 1	NEUR 7	MUND 18	MEDS 68	PECP 5	
NEUR 2	PECP 19	PMAC 7	OCTO 4	MEDS 21	HUND 4	TRAL 76	PECP 14	HRZC 1	PLEP 1	PECP 1	
OCTO 4	PMAC 49	PSTH 31	PMAC 7	MUND 7		HUND 18	PECP 10	MUND 1	PMAC 18		
PSTH 19	PSTH 62	TRAL 102	PSTH 4	NEUR 14			PMAC 20	PCAL 2	PSTH 16		
TRAL 87	THON 6	HTTH 3	TRAL 142	HUND 9			PSTH 12	PMAC 3	THON 1		
WESC 1	TRAL 47	HUND 15	HTTH 6	PCAL 9			TRAL 218	PSPR 1	WCAP 6		
WUND 13	WCAP 3		HUND 17	PECP 17			WESC 12	PUND 1	HTTH 3		
	HTTH 7			PLEP 12			HUND 19	SMER 1	WUND 2		
	WUND 15			PMAC 19				TRAL 5			
				PSTH 55							
				PUND 1							
				SMER 3							
				SPHN 4							
				TPEL 2							
				TRAL 41							
				WCAP 1							
				WESC 1							
				WPLN 1							
				WSJN 15							
				HTTH 13							
				HUND 13							

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 164		LOC 165		LOC 166		LOC 167		LOC 169		LOC 170		LOC 172		LOC 173		LOC 174		LOC 184		LOC 186	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 326		SUM 48		SUM 29		SUM 27		SUM 22		SUM 19		SUM 26		SUM 10		SUM 188		SUM 715		SUM 390			
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT	
ANHL	2	ANHL	2	ANHL	2	ANHL	1	ANHL	1	ANHL	1	ANHL	3	ANHL	1	BLIN	1	ANHL	6	ANHL	2		
BLIN	4	ELJR	6	BLJR	2	BLJR	3	BLIN	2	BLMT	2	BLJR	3	BLJR	1	BLJR	3	BLIN	42	BLIN	17		
BLJR	11	BLMT	2	BLMT	3	BLNT	2	BLSR	2	BLSR	3	BLSR	1	FCOP	2	BTOT	3	BLJR	29	BLJR	49		
BLMT	4	BLSR	3	BLSR	1	BLSR	1	HOLT	3	FCOP	4	FCOP	2	HOLT	1	DDGR	2	BLSR	37	BLSR	12		
BLSR	14	CBLM	4	DGRY	1	DPYC	2	HEDS	2	HOLT	1	HOLT	2	HEDS	3	DGBR	53	CBLT	4	CBLM	5		
DGRY	135	CCYC	1	DPYC	3	FCOP	3	NEUR	2	NEUR	1	HEDS	7	HEDS	2	DLGH	30	DGRY	341	CCYC	6		
DPYC	47	DGRY	7	HOLT	3	HEDS	2	PCAL	1	TRAL	4	TRAL	5	NEUR	2	DPYC	1	DISC	5	DGRY	226		
DSEP	2	DSEP	3	HUND	1	PECP	1	PSTH	2	WESC	1	HTTH	3			HOLT	13	DPYC	47	DPYC	5		
FCOP	4	FCOP	4	PECP	1	PSTH	4	TRAL	3	HUND	2					HEDS	1	DSEP	33	DSEP	3		
HOLT	12	HPEC	3	PMAC	2	TMON	1	WESC	2							MEUP	1	FCOP	26	FCOP	10		
HEDM	6	PCAL	1	PSTH	3	TRAL	3	HUND	2							HUND	3	HOLT	18	HOLT	2		
HEDS	15	PECP	1	THON	2	WCAP	4									PECP	2	HEDM	6	PCAL	1		
PECP	1	PMAC	3	TRAL	3											PMAC	2	HEDS	54	PECP	8		
PHAC	8	PSTH	2	HTTH	2											PPIN	1	HPEC	4	FLEP	1		
PSTH	4	TMON	2													PSTH	1	PSTH	15	PSTH	18		
THON	4	HTTH	2													TRAL	69	TRAL	32	THON	2		
TRAL	46	HUND	2													HPLN	1	HTTH	2	WCAP	12		
HTTH	1															HUND	1	HUND	14	HTTH	7		
HUND	6																			HUND	4		

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LOC 190	LOC 191	LOC 192	LOC 193	LOC 194	LOC 195	LOC 196	LOC 197	LOC 199	LOC 201	LOC 202	
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SUM 1848	SUM 279	SUM 555	SUM 1937	SUM 1438	SUM 502	SUM 1173	SUM 723	SUM 106	SUM 242	SUM 1809	
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
ANHL 1	BLIN 5	ANHL 6	ALTH 2	ANHL 14	ANHL 2	ANNL 2	ANNL 2	ANNL 1	ASTR 1	ANNL 53	
BLIN 10	BLJR 2	ARAC 1	ANHL 20	BLIN 10	BLIN 1	BLIN 2	BLIN 2	BLIN 2	BLIN 10	CAEN 8	
BLJR 23	BLSR 8	ASTR 2	BLIN 4	BLJR 2	BLJR 1	BLJR 1	BLJR 7	BLJR 1	BLJR 21	CPAL 6	
BLSR 78	BTOT 3	BLIN 6	BLJR 2	BLSR 7	BTOT 1	BLSR 1	BLSR 21	CBLT 1	BLSR 26	CPYG 1	
BTOT 19	DGBR 63	BLJR 5	BLSR 14	BTOT 16	DBLG 19	BTOT 11	DCOM 78	DGBR 37	CBLT 3	CSUN 1	
CBLM 1	DISC 3	BTOT 6	CBLT 1	CAEN 1	DCOM 103	CBLT 1	DGRY 129	DREJ 27	CCYC 1	CSYN 10	
CBLT 2	DPYC 2	CBLM 1	CCYC 1	CBLT 3	DGBR 16	DCOM 96	DISC 6	DSEP 2	CKAL 1	DCOM 18	
DCOM 745	DREJ 93	DGBR 122	CSYN 1	CCYC 2	DGRY 35	DGRY 117	DPYC 32	FCOP 7	DCOM 76	DDGR 14	
DGBR 109	DSEP 2	DISC 6	CUND 1	DCOM 157	DISC 5	DISC 2	DREJ 258	HOLT 2	DGBR 49	DGBR 169	
DGRY 30	FCOP 6	DPYC 39	DCOM 66	DDGR 6	DREJ 178	DREJ 432	DSEP 19	LSTP 1	DPYC 1	DGRY 55	
DISC 5	HOLT 3	DREJ 244	DGBR 38	DGBR 54	DSEP 13	DSEP 19	DWTH 12	MEDS 8	DSEP 1	DLBR 33	
DLGH 10	MEDS 8	DSEP 6	DGRY 256	DGRY 319	DHWH 20	DHWH 275	FCOP 18	MEUP 3	FCOP 9	DLGR 79	
DPYC 1	MEUP 3	FCOP 5	DISC 11	DISC 13	FCOP 7	FCOP 28	HOLT 1	NEUR 5	FESC 1	DPYC 2	
DREJ 365	NLIM 1	HOLT 4	DLGH 90	DREJ 391	KOTT 1	HOLT 5	LSTP 1	NUND 5	MHSI 1	DSEP 4	
DSEP 23	NEUR 1	INSC 1	DPYC 4	DSEP 23	MEDN 2	INCG 1	MEDS 74	TRAL 5	NUND 5	EUPR 10	
DHWH 16	NUND 5	LEPD 1	DREJ 892	DWTH 36	MEDS 54	MEDS 58	MEUP 3	HCAP 1	PAPH 1	FCOP 147	
FCOP 32	PBRK 3	LIMU 1	DSEP 11	FCOP 32	MEUP 1	MEUP 2	MPEC 1	WESC 1	PECP 2	FCTH 1	
FRHB 1	PECP 1	MEDN 1	DWTH 90	HOLT 3	MPEC 2	MPEC 4	MSCZ 1	HUND 1	PLEP 1	FPAL 2	
HOLT 14	PHAC 1	MEDS 10	EGGS 1	INSC 1	MSCZ 1	NEUR 2	NEUR 5		PHAC 7	FXNT 1	
MEDH 1	PSTM 1	MPEC 3	FCOP 25	LEPD 1	NUND 5	NUND 23	NUND 4		PSTM 10	INSC 2	
MEDS 53	TRAL 58	NUND 2	HDEV 1	MEDH 2	ODON 1	PCAL 2	PBRK 3		PUND 1	LEPD 2	
MEUP 2	WESC 2	NEUR 4	HOLT 1	MEDS 215	PCAL 1	PCYC 2	FECP 4		SMER 2	LSTP 16	
MPEC 1	WPLN 3	NUND 11	MEDH 4	MPEC 1	PCYC 1	PLEP 2	PHAC 2		TMON 9	MHSI 1	
NEUR 1	WSPR 1	OCTO 1	MEDS 254	MSCZ 8	PECP 3	PHAC 7	FSTH 3		TRAL 1	MCOO 1	
NUND 49	WUND 1	PBRK 6	NEUP 3	NSOL 1	PLEP 1	PSTH 14	SHER 1		WPJM 1	NEUR 425	
PBRK 1		PECP 6	MPEC 3	MUND 3	PHAC 1	PUND 4	TRAL 18		WUND 1	NUND 11	
PCAL 1		PHAC 5	MSCZ 2	NEUR 5	PPIN 1	TRAL 55	HBLN 1			ODON 10	
PCYC 1		PSTM 1	MUND 5	NUND 13	PSTM 6	HCAP 2	HCAP 3			PAPH 3	
PECP 8		PUND 3	NCYC 1	PBRK 4	SPHN 1	WFSH 1	WESC 1			PBRK 1	
PLEP 6		SMER 3	NEUR 7	PCAL 3	TRAL 11	HPLN 2	WFSH 2			FCAL 23	
PHAC 5		SPHN 1	NUND 14	PCYC 1	HCAP 1		HPLN 3			PCON 4	
PSTM 10		TRAL 21	PBRK 2	PECP 8	WFSH 3		WUND 7			PCYC 2	
PUND 1		HCAP 6	PCAL 4	FLEP 4	HPLN 1					PECP 476	
TRAL 198		WESC 1	PCON 1	PHAC 10	WUND 3					PLEP 40	
HBLN 7		HOLH 1	PCYC 1	PSTM 15						PLXS 3	
HCAP 1		HSPR 1	PECP 15	PUND 6						PLYB 1	
HPLN 3		HTTH 5	PHAC 13	TRAL 16						PHAC 26	
HSJH 1		WUND 7	PPIN 3	HCAP 3						PPIN 1	
HTTH 1			PSTM 17	WESC 1						PSTM 120	
WUND 12			PTAE 1	WFSH 6						PUND 7	
			TRAL 29	WPLN 8						SEED 3	
			WCAP 1	HTTH 3						SPHN 4	
			WFSH 8	WUND 11						STIG 8	
			WPLN 4							TFBR 5	
			HSJH 1								
			HTTH 3								
			WUND 9								

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ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES				
SUM 157	SUM 299	SUM 497	SUM 1910	SUM 1178	SUM 1426	SUM 499	SUM 2471	SUM 836	SUM 273																	
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT																	
ALTH 1	ASTR 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 7	ANHL 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 1	ALTH 2	ALTH 1	ANHL 1	ALTH 2	HTTH 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 1	ALTH 2	HTTH 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 1	ALTH 1	ANHL 1			
ANHL 3	BLIH 35	ANHL 3	BLIN 13	BLEY 5	ANHL 1	BLEY 8	ANHL 4	ANHL 8	BLMT 1	ANHL 4	HUND 1	ANHL 8	BLMT 1	ANHL 4	BLEY 1	ANHL 8	BLIN 9	BTOT 2	ANHL 8	BLIN 9	BTOT 2	ANHL 8	BLMT 1			
DCOM 5	BLJR 27	BLIN 4	BLJR 30	BLIN 10	BLIN 10	BLIN 15	BLIN 1	BLIN 9	BTOT 2	BLIN 10	BLIN 15	BLIN 9	BTOT 2	BLJR 7	BLJR 14	BLIN 85	BLJR 28	DDGR 4	BLJR 7	BLSR 11	BLJR 6	BLJR 23	BLJR 14	BLIN 85		
DGBR 24	BLMT 10	BLJR 7	BLSR 11	BLJR 6	BLJR 6	BLJR 79	BLJR 187	BLMT 3	DGRY 43	BLSR 1	CBLM 1	BLSR 31	DPYC 2	EUPR 1	BLSR 62	BLPL 1	CBLM 1	CBLM 1	BLSR 31	DPYC 2	BLSR 1	CBLM 1	BLSR 580	BTOT 170		
FCOP 14	DDGR 1	BLSR 5	CBLT 1	CBLM 4	CBLM 5	CAEN 1	BLSR 580	BTOT 20	DREJ 133	DDGR 41	DCOM 253	CCYC 3	CFLE 1	DCOM 348	CFLE 1	DCOM 596	CBLT 2	CBAR 1	CBLM 1	DSEP 2	DCOM 48	CFLE 1	DCOM 596	CBLT 2	CBAR 1	
LSTP 1	DGBR 41	DCOM 253	CCYC 3	CFLE 1	DCOM 348	CFLE 1	DCOM 596	CBLT 2	CBAR 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
NEUR 4	DLGR 60	DGBR 48	CFLE 1	DCOM 348	CFLE 1	DCOM 596	CBLT 2	CBAR 1	CBLM 1	DCOM 348	CFLE 1	DCOM 596	CBLT 2	CBAR 1	DCOM 348	CFLE 1	DCOM 596	CBLT 2	CBAR 1	CBLM 1	DSEP 2	DCOM 348	CFLE 1	DCOM 596	CBLT 2	CBAR 1
NUND 4	FCOP 5	DISC 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
PERK 1	NEUR 1	DPYC 1	DDGR 2	DISC 18	DGBR 127	DGRY 26	CBLT 25	CCYC 1	HOLT 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
PCAL 4	NUND 13	DREJ 92	DGRY 294	DPYC 1	DGRY 69	DISC 7	CCYC 1	CSUN 1	HEDS 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
PECP 71	PECP 5	DSEP 2	DISC 6	DREJ 226	DISC 16	DREJ 44	CFLE 2	DCOM 133	MEUP 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
PLEP 3	PLEP 10	FCOP 5	DREJ 631	DSEP 32	DPYC 5	DSEP 7	CPAL 1	DGBR 114	NUND 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
PMAC 3	PMAC 6	HOLT 3	DSEP 12	FCOP 14	DREJ 173	DWTH 30	CSUN 1	DGRY 3	PECP 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
PSTH 14	PSTH 3	HEDS 12	FCOP 10	HOLT 9	DSEP 17	FCOP 1	CSYN 1	DISC 13	PSTH 2	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
SEED 1	PUND 2	HEUP 1	FESC 1	INCG 1	DSPT 1	HOLT 2	CUND 4	DPYC 149	PUND 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
STIG 3	SPHN 2	HPEC 2	FRHB 1	HEDS 53	FCOP 21	HEDS 31	DCOM 737	DREJ 103	TRAL 60	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
	WCAP 12	HSCZ 1	FUND 1	HEUP 1	HOLT 10	MNCR 1	DGBR 9	DSEP 7	HBLN 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
	WUND 3	NEUR 5	HOLT 104	NEUR 2	LEPD 1	NEUR 1	DISC 12	ETAC 1	HUND 1	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		NUND 4	INCG 2	NUND 15	HEDH 2	NUND 6	DODD 6	FCOP 18		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PCAL 2	MEDS 11	PECP 2	HEDS 48	PASO 1	DREJ 147	FCTN 1		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PCRS 1	MEUP 8	PLEP 1	HPEC 1	PCYC 1	DSEP 133	HOLT 14		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PCYC 2	HPEC 1	PMAC 1	MUND 1	PLEP 2	DTOT 115	HOLT 14		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PECP 4	MUND 1	PSTH 3	NEUR 1	PMAC 5	ETAC 1	INCG 2		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PLEP 1	NEUR 1	SMER 2	MUND 26	PSTH 6	FCOP 104	INCG 2		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PMAC 2	NUND 28	TRAL 222	PCYC 1	PUND 3	FESC 1	INSC 1		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PSTH 13	PCAL 2	WCAP 1	PECP 9	THON 1	HOLT 1	HCEP 1		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		PUND 1	PECP 4	HPLN 3	PMAC 8	TRAL 32	INCG 1	MEDS 28		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		SMER 6	PMAC 5	HSJW 1	PFIN 1	WCAP 1	INSC 1	MNCR 2		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		TRAL 11	PSTH 11	HSPR 1	PSTH 11	WDRY 1	LEPD 1	MNSI 5		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		HPLN 1	PUND 1	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		HTTH 1	SMER 1	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
		WUND 1	TOPL 1	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
			TFEL 1	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
			TRAL 406	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
			HBLN 3	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
			WESC 1	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
			HPLN 5	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
			HTTH 2	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
			WUND 6	HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
				HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
				HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
				HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	
				HUND 11	TRAL 164	HPLN 4	LIMU 1	NPEC 6		DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	CBLM 3	CBLT 1	DWTH 11	DCOM 280	DGRY 152	DDGR 2	DCOM 159	

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LOC 214		ALL PAGES																			
SUM 2568	SUM 573	SUM 516	SUM 3210	SUM 297	SUM 43	SUM 1638	SUM 1531	SUM 1394	SUM 330												
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ANND 2	ALTH 4	ANHL 6	ALTH 3	ANHL 1	DDGR 17	ALTH 1	ALTH 2	ALTH 2	ALTH 8												
ANHL 4	ANHL 14	BLIN 1	ANHL 38	ASTR 1	DPYC 8	ANHL 32	ANHL 9	ANHL 51	ANHL 7												
BLIN 57	ASTR 1	DBLB 19	ASTR 1	CPAL 1	FCOP 1	ASTR 4	ASTR 1	ASTR 2	ASTR 4												
BLJR 206	BLSR 1	DCOM 144	CAEN 5	CSYN 1	MFHC 1	CAEN 4	DCOM 474	BLIN 4	CPAL 1												
BLMI 4	CPAL 2	DSBR 96	COST 4	DCOM 68	PBRK 2	CPAL 1	DDGR 287	BLJR 1	DDGR 1												
BLSR 395	DBLB 47	LSTP 1	CPAL 5	DDGR 15	PCAL 1	CSYN 3	DGRY 5	BTOT 39	BTOT 1												
CAEN 1	DCOM 76	NEUR 4	CSYN 3	DGBR 14	PECP 6	DCOM 531	DPYC 159	CAEN 1	CAEN 1												
CBAR 3	DDGR 3	NUND 2	DCOM 762	DPYC 13	PLEP 2	DDGR 102	DSEP 3	CCYC 3	CCYC 3												
CBLN 7	DFGR 36	PBRK 2	DDGR 269	FCOP 25	PHAC 5	DGRY 6	EUPR 1	CKAL 1	CKAL 1												
CBLT 11	DGBR 44	PCAL 4	DGBR 228	FPRT 1		DPYC 41	FCOP 102	DBLB 63	DBLB 63												
CCYC 2	DISC 3	PCON 2	DGRY 7	NEUR 4		DSEP 17	INCG 1	DCOM 207	DCOM 207												
CDIT 1	DODD 2	PECP 96	DPYC 46	NUND 7		DWTH 6	LSTR 4	DDGF 6	DDGF 6												
CFLE 2	DPYC 1	PLEP 34	DSEP 43	PCAL 3		EUPR 2	LYCD 1	DDGR 3	DDGR 3												
CKAL 1	DSEP 19	PHAC 53	DSND 10	PCYC 1		FCOP 130	MFHC 11	DGBR 201	DGBR 201												
DBLB 30	DSND 6	PSTH 39	EUPR 6	PECP 55		FCTN 2	HMSI 1	DGRF 145	DGRF 145												
DCOM 709	EUPR 1	PUND 11	FCOP 106	PLEP 21		LEPD 2	MUND 2	DGRY 25	DGRY 25												
DGBR 345	FCOP 16	SPHN 1	FCTN 2	PLXS 4		LSTP 14	NEUR 13	DISC 3	DISC 3												
DISC 21	LSTP 9	TRAL 1	FINO 1	PHAC 18		LYBR 1	NUND 26	DLGR 16	DLGR 16												
DPYC 28	MFHC 2		FPAL 1	PSTH 31		MFHC 16	PBRK 3	DPYC 27	DPYC 27												
DREJ 182	MMSI 4		FXNT 1	PUND 10		MFHM 3	PCAL 4	DSEP 21	DSEP 21												
DSEP 206	MUND 7		INSC 3	SEED 1		MUND 20	PCON 2	FCOP 70	FCOP 70												
ETAC 4	NCYC 1		LEPD 3	SPHN 1		NEUR 102	PCYC 1	INCG 1	INCG 1												
FCOP 87	NEUR 6		LSTP 59	TFTR 1		NUND 27	PECP 122	LEPD 2	LEPD 2												
FESC 3	NUND 8		LSTR 25			PCAL 14	PLEP 107	LYBR 1	LYBR 1												
FGIL 1	FBRK 3		LYBR 1			PCON 5	PMAC 76	LYCD 1	LYCD 1												
FPRT 1	PCAL 5		MFHC 171			PCYC 1	PSTH 92	MDUN 1	MDUN 1												
FRHB 1	PCYC 4		MFHM 11			PDRN 3	PSUL 1	MFHC 2	MFHC 2												
HOLT 2	PECP 77		MUND 62			PECP 205	PUND 12	HMSI 1	HMSI 1												
LEPD 1	PLEP 33		NEUR 233			PLEP 191	REGC 2	NUND 4	NUND 4												
LIMJ 1	PHAC 45		NUND 48			NUND 102	SEED 6	NEUR 34	NEUR 34												
LSTP 1	PSPR 1		PBRK 2			PHAC 46	TFTR 1	NUND 20	NUND 20												
MDUN 1	PSTH 79		PCAL 14			PSTH 67		PBRK 4	PBRK 4												
MMSI 12	PUND 5		PCON 1			PUND 18		PCAL 18	PCAL 18												
HSTR 4	SPFR 1		PCYC 7			SEED 2		FCYC 2	FCYC 2												
NEUR 7	SPHN 2		PDRN 2			SPHN 6		PECP 94	PECP 94												
NUND 39	TRAL 2		PECP 223			SPRS 1		PLEP 101	PLEP 101												
OCTO 1	TRHZ 1		PLEP 327			STIG 1		PHAC 31	PHAC 31												
PBRK 4	HSFR 1		PLXS 2			TFTR 3		PPIN 1	PPIN 1												
PCAL 1	WUND 1		PLYB 1			THAL 1		PSTH 126	PSTH 126												
PECP 14			PLYU 2			TNSC 2		PUND 14	PUND 14												
PLEP 1			PMAC 265					REGC 2	REGC 2												
PMAC 108			PSTH 105					SPHN 5	SPHN 5												
PSTH 28			PUND 67					SPHT 1	SPHT 1												
PUND 4			SEED 4					STIG 1	STIG 1												
THON 5			SPFR 3					TFTR 2	TFTR 2												
TRAL 8			SPHN 22					TRAL 11	TRAL 11												
HCAP 3			STIG 2					HCAP 1	HCAP 1												
HSJM 2			TFTR 2					HESC 1	HESC 1												
HTTH 1			THRN 1					HILY 1	HILY 1												
NUND 6			TRAL 1					HSPR 2	HSPR 2												
								HTTH 9	HTTH 9												

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LOC 224		LOC 225		LOC 226		LOC 227		LOC 227		LOC 228		LOC 229		LOC 230		LOC 231		LOC 232		LOC 233	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 2862		SUM 32		SUM 50		ID COUNT		SUM 2706		SUM 1575		SUM 421		SUM 1437		SUM 1199		SUM 1025		ID COUNT	
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ALTH	9	ANHL	2	DDGR	16	ALTH	17	THSC	2	ALTH	2	ALTH	3	ALTH	3	ALTH	3	ALTH	2	ALTH	1
ANHL	72	DCOM	3	DPYC	14	ANHL	161			ANHL	55	ANHL	6	ANHL	51	ANHL	35	ANHL	22	ANHL	3
ASTR	17	DSEP	3	DSND	1	ASTR	22			ASTR	1	ASTR	3	ASTR	8	ASTR	8	ARAC	2	ANHL	32
CAEN	2	FCOP	2	FCOP	2	CAEN	1			CCYZ	1	CPAL	1	CCYZ	1	CPAL	1	ASTR	1	BLIN	128
CSYN	5	INCG	1	MFWC	1	COST	1			CPAL	2	DBLB	8	CPAL	1	DBLB	15	BLIN	35	BLJR	618
DCOM	461	NEUR	4	NUND	2	CPAL	2			DCOM	346	DCOM	39	CSYN	1	DCOM	178	BTOT	39	BLHT	7
DDGB	84	NUHD	1	PCAL	1	CSYN	1			DDGR	224	DDGR	17	DBLB	25	DGBR	14	CCYC	4	BLSR	642
DDGR	104	PCAL	1	PECP	2	DCOM	511			DGBR	45	DGBR	8	DCOM	77	DGRB	9	CPAL	3	BTOT	1
DGRB	213	PECP	3	PLEP	2	DDBL	10			DGRY	22	DGRB	19	DDGR	35	DSEP	7	CSYN	1	CBLM	26
DISC	3	PLEP	2	PMAC	1	DDGR	153			DPYC	54	DSEP	19	DGBR	61	EUPR	3	DCOM	303	CBLT	27
DSEP	24	PMAC	6	PSTH	5	DGBR	76			DREJ	92	FCOP	17	DGRB	83	FCOP	59	DDGR	135	CCYC	2
DSLQ	5	PSTH	4	PUND	2	DISC	94			DSEP	12	FCTN	2	DPYC	11	FCTN	2	DISC	8	CKAL	4
DSND	2			SEED	1	DPYC	91			EUPR	10	FXHT	1	DSEP	1	FFRT	1	DPYC	43	CSYN	1
EUPR	2					DREJ	12			FCOP	132	LEPD	1	DSND	1	LSTP	2	DSEP	53	DCOM	508
FCOP	77					DSEP	12			LEPD	7	LSTP	6	EUPR	2	LYBR	1	FCOP	35	ETAC	32
INCG	6					DSND	2			LSTR	18	NEUR	10	FCOP	66	MFWC	1	FCTN	1	FACN	1
LSTP	6					DUDS	4			LSTR	17	NUHD	5	FCRT	1	MHSI	1	INCG	2	FCOP	75
MFWC	8					EUPR	7			MFWC	9	ODON	3	FCTH	2	NEUR	35	LSTP	3	FESC	6
NEUR	29					FCOP	214			MHSI	1	PBRK	1	FPAL	1	NUND	5	MFWC	10	FGIL	1
NUND	25					FCTN	2			MUND	8	PCAL	3	LEPD	2	ODON	1	MHSI	2	MDUN	2
ODON	2					HFTR	1			NEUR	33	PECP	48	LSTP	6	PAPH	1	MPEC	3	MEDS	5
PBRK	3					INSC	3			NUND	34	PLEP	100	LSTR	1	PCAL	10	MUND	8	MFWC	1
PCAL	45					LEPD	5			ODON	1	PLXS	1	MFWC	1	PCON	2	NEUR	19	MHSI	8
PCYC	10					LSTP	35			PBRK	8	PHAC	53	NEUR	9	PCYC	2	NUND	31	MPEC	1
PECP	416					LSTR	2			PCAL	9	PSTH	29	NUND	26	PECP	299	ODON	3	MSCZ	2
PLEP	260					MFWC	12			PCYC	6	PUND	9	PAPH	4	PLEP	168	PCAL	4	MSTR	10
PLXS	2					MUND	3			PECP	161	SEED	3	PBRK	1	PMAC	206	PCYC	1	NEUR	9
PHAC	668					NEUR	349			PLEP	73	SPFR	2	PCAL	46	PSTH	108	PECP	35	NUND	22
PPIN	1					NUND	20			PLXS	12	SPHN	3	PCYC	2	PUND	18	PLEP	113	OCTO	1
PSTH	229					ODON	3			PLYB	1	STIG	1	PECP	128	STIG	1	PHAC	23	FBRK	2
PUND	52					PAPH	1			PMAC	30			PLEP	102	TFTR	1	PSTH	47	FCAL	12
SEED	8					PBRK	14			PSTH	107			PLXS	1	THSC	2	PUND	12	PCYC	3
SPHN	2					PCAL	63			PUND	23			PMAC	538			SEED	2	PECP	106
STIG	5					PCON	11			SEED	8			PSTH	116			SMER	2	PLEP	6
TFTR	3					PCRC	4			SPFR	2			PUND	16			SPFR	1	PHAC	10
THRN	1					PCRS	1			SPHN	3			SEED	1			SPHN	4	PPIN	1
TPEL	1					PCYC	16			TFBR	6			SPHN	2			TFTR	1	PSPR	1
						PDRN	3							STIG	1			TRAL	6	PSTH	48
						PECF	1							TRAL	1			WOLI	1	PUND	3
						FECP	374							ULOD	1			WSPR	1	REGC	1
						PLEP	258							WSPR	1			WTHH	1	RTMD	2
						PLXS	4											WUND	3	SMER	25
						PHAC	53													STIG	1
						PSTH	70													TFBR	1
						PUND	58													THAL	1
						SEED	12													TMON	17
						SPFR	4													TPEL	2
						SPHN	6													WCAP	1
						STIG	2													WESC	1
						TFTR	2													WHYS	1
						THAL	1													WPLN	5

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SUM 2420		SUM 452		SUM 527		SUM 1682		SUM 764		SUM 401		SUM 959		SUM 148		SUM 208		SUM 471		SUM 100			
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HTTH	1	ANNL	2	ANNL	4	ALTH	5	ANNL	7	ANNL	4	ANNL	4	ALTH	1	ALTH	1	ANNL	1	DGBR	88		
HUND	1	ASTR	2	BLIN	3	ANNL	21	ARAC	1	CSYN	1	CPAL	1	ANNL	1	ASTR	1	BLIN	26	PNAC	3		
		CAEN	4	BLJR	1	ASTR	6	ASTR	2	DCOH	76	CSYN	2	BTOT	1	BTOT	1	BLJR	74	PSTH	1		
		CSYN	3	BLSR	2	BLIN	2	BLIN	16	DDGR	82	DBLG	31	DCOH	70	DCOH	154	BLMT	13	TRAL	8		
		CUND	2	CPAL	1	CBLT	1	BLJR	13	DGRY	3	DCOH	201	DREJ	32	FCOP	2	BLSR	82				
		DDGR	192	CSYN	1	CMES	1	BLOD	1	DPYC	71	DDGR	30	FCOP	2	NEUR	1	CBLT	4				
		DGBR	3	DCOH	381	CPAL	1	BLSR	8	DSEP	1	DGRY	39	NEUR	5	NUND	2	CCYC	1				
		DPYC	42	DSEP	10	DBLB	30	CAEN	1	DWTH	6	DISC	3	PECP	18	PECP	8	CKAL	1				
		DSEP	4	FCOP	9	DCOH	647	CCYZ	2	FCOP	25	DPYC	110	PLEP	11	PLEP	15	DCOH	79				
		DWTH	13	MFHC	1	DGBR	123	CFAL	1	FCTN	1	DREJ	16	PNAC	2	PNAC	2	DISC	11				
		FCOP	37	NEUR	2	DISC	1	DCOH	494	LSTP	2	DSEP	18	PSTH	5	DSEP	18	DLGH	74				
		FXNT	1	NUND	14	DOOD	1	DDGR	2	LYBR	1	EUPR	4			PSTH	19	DSEP	13				
		LEPD	1	PECP	28	DFYC	1	DGBR	39	MFHC	1	FASP	1			HCAP	1	FCOP	10				
		LSTP	1	PLEP	32	DREJ	189	DPYC	2	NEUR	1	FCOP	110					FESC	1				
		LYBR	1	PNAC	13	DSEP	11	FCOP	7	NUND	2	FCTN	1					INCG	5				
		HUND	1	PSTH	15	EUPR	1	FFRT	1	PBRK	1	LSTP	3					LEPD	1				
		NEUR	14	SEED	1	FCOP	67	LSTR	1	PCAL	6	NEUR	74					LSTP	1				
		NUND	7	TRAL	3	LEPD	4	NEUR	7	PCON	1	NUND	29					MSTR	3				
		ODON	2	HCAP	4	LSTP	13	NUND	18	PCYC	3	PAPH	1					HUND	1				
		PAPH	1	HSJW	1	MFHC	1	PCAL	7	PECP	34	PBRK	12					NEUR	7				
		PCAL	3	HUND	1	HUND	1	PECP	15	PFUN	1	PCAL	1					NUND	8				
		PCON	3			NEUR	98	PLEP	75	NEUR	31	PCYC	1					PCAL	2				
		PCYC	1			NUND	12	PNAC	9	PNAC	10	PECP	145					PCON	1				
		PECP	32			ODON	2	PSTH	13	PSTH	30	PFUN	1					PECP	10				
		PLEP	26			PBRK	4	PUND	8	PUND	3	PLEP	23					PLEP	1				
		PLXS	1			PCAL	8	TPEL	2	SEED	2	PLXS	1					PLYB	1				
		PNAC	21			PCON	3	TRAL	3	TFBR	1	PNAC	26					PNAC	13				
		PSTH	19			PCYC	1	HCAP	1	TFTR	1	PSTH	49					PSTH	9				
		PUND	8			PECP	142	HSJW	2			PUND	13					PUND	1				
		SEED	2			PFUN	3	HUND	6			SEED	2					SHER	1				
		SPFR	1			PLEP	161					STIG	1					THAL	1				
		SPHN	1			PNAC	35					TFBR	1					THON	7				
		TFBR	1			PSIG	1					TRAL	3					TRAL	3				
						PSTH	64					HSPR	2					HCAP	3				
						PUND	11											HTTH	1				
						STIG	4											HUND	1				
						TRAL	3																
						HCAP	3																

LISTING BY LOCATION											
LOC 247	LOC 248	LOC 249	LOC 250	LOC 251	LOC 252	LOC 253	LOC 254	LOC 255	LOC 255	LOC 256	
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	
SUM 636	SUM 1598	SUM 831	SUM 1407	SUM 483	SUM 908	SUM 391	SUM 1005		SUM 3703	SUM 621	
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
ANNL 12	ALTH 1	BLIN 22	AICH 7	BLIN 27	ALTH 1	ANNL 4	ALTH 1	ALTH 2	PSTH 99	ANNL 2	
ASTR 2	ANND 1	BLJR 76	ANNL 1	BLJR 12	ANNL 9	ASTR 1	ANNL 20	ANND 1	PUND 3	BLIN 24	
BLIN 3	ANNL 2	BLSR 48	BLIN 84	BLSR 84	ARTH 1	CSYN 2	ASTR 2	ANNL 28	RTMD 1	BLJR 52	
DCOM 107	BLIN 25	CBLN 3	BLJR 361	CBLM 1	CSYN 1	DCOH 101	CAEN 1	BLIN 101	SMER 148	BLSR 134	
DDGR 25	BLJR 163	CBLT 4	BLMT 34	CBLT 10	DCOH 293	DDGR 33	COST 1	BLJR 358	STIG 1	CBLM 3	
DGBR 134	BLMT 16	CSUN 1	BLOD 1	CFLE 1	DREJ 117	DGBR 5	DCOM 205	BLMT 8	TDPL 1	CBLT 3	
DPYC 3	BLOD 1	DCOM 462	BLSR 335	CKAL 2	DSEP 11	DPYC 56	DDGR 157	BLOD 2	THAL 1	DCOM 146	
DREJ 10	BLSR 417	DGBR 54	CBLT 24	DDGR 1	FCOP 69	DSEP 3	DGBR 40	BLSR 175	THON 14	DGBR 81	
FCOP 4	BTOT 62	DISC 3	DCOM 286	DGBR 197	LEPD 1	DWTH 4	DGRY 4	BTOT 277	TPEL 1	DGRY 51	
LSTP 2	CBLM 1	FCOP 3	DGRY 118	DISC 17	LSTP 2	EUPR 2	DPYC 82	CBLT 32	TRAL 8	DISC 31	
NEUR 13	CBLT 26	LING 118	DISC 7	DCDD 12	HUND 1	FCOP 23	DREJ 3	CCYC 10	HCAP 4	DPYC 23	
NUND 10	CCYC 1	MNCR 2	DODD 3	DPYC 36	NEUR 18	LEPD 3	DWTH 3	CESS 1	HESC 4	DSEP 5	
PAPH 1	CESS 1	NUND 8	DPYC 38	DSEP 16	NUND 4	MFHC 3	EUPR 1	CFLE 5	WHYS 3	FCOP 32	
PBRK 1	CKAL 2	OCTO 1	DSEP 3	FCOP 33	PCAL 15	HUND 1	FCOP 52	CKAL 4	HPJM 2	FHEG 1	
PCAL 13	CSUN 2	PECP 2	ETAC 18	FHEG 1	PCON 1	NEUR 12	INCG 2	CPAL 1	HSJH 3	HSTR 1	
PCON 2	DCOM 529	PMAC 1	FCOP 25	FRHS 1	PCYC 2	NUND 8	LEPD 4	CPYG 2	WSPR 1	NEUR 1	
PCYC 1	DGRY 184	PSTH 6	FESC 1	HOLT 2	PECP 205	PAPH 1	LSTP 16	CSUN 2	WTHH 5	NUND 11	
PECP 55	DISC 6	PUND 3	FPAL 1	MMSI 1	PFUN 1	PBRK 1	LSTR 2	CUND 1	HUND 10	PBRK 1	
PLEP 100	DPYC 11	STIG 1	FPRT 1	NEUR 2	PLEP 24	PCAL 2	LYBR 2	DCOM 1284		PECP 1	
PLYB 4	DSEP 4	TRAL 11	INCG 2	NUND 8	PLXS 1	PCON 1	MFHC 25	DGBR 171		PLEP 1	
PMAC 49	ETAC 4	HSJH 1	INSC 1	PCAL 2	PMAC 33	PECP 53	NEUR 36	DGRY 144		PMAC 1	
PSPR 1	FACH 1	WTHH 1	MPEC 1	PECP 3	PSTH 90	PLEP 19	NUND 3	DISC 26		PSTH 4	
PSTH 50	FCOP 41		HSTR 4	PSTH 3	PUND 3	PLXS 4	PBRK 1	DPYC 53		SPHN 1	
PUND 22	FPRT 1		NEUR 3	SMER 1	SPFR 1	PMAC 22	PCAL 3	DSEP 14		THON 1	
SPFR 7	INCG 1		NUND 6	THAL 1	SPHN 1	PSTH 17	PCON 1	ETAC 61		TPEL 3	
SPHN 3	INSC 1		PCAL 2	THON 1	SFRS 1	PUND 7	PCYC 2	FCOP 47		TRAL 6	
STIG 2	LEPD 1		PCYC 1	TRAL 8	STIG 1	SPHN 1	PECP 95	FCTN 1		HCAP 1	
	LING 2		PECP 17		TFBR 1	TRAL 1	PLEP 105	FESC 4			
	LSTP 1		PLEP 1				PLXS 2	FGIL 1			
	MMSI 1		PMAC 3				PMAC 70	HOLT 1			
	HSTR 1		PSTH 4				PSPR 1	INSC 1			
	NEUR 3		PUND 1				PSTH 37	LSTP 1			
	NUND 5		RTMD 3				PUND 21	MCEP 1			
	PCAL 2		TDPL 1				SEED 1	MEUP 3			
	PCYC 1		TPEL 4				SPHN 2	MMSI 2			
	PECP 23		TRAL 1				SPRS 1	MPEC 3			
	PMAC 20		HFSH 1				TWSC 1	HSTR 11			
	PSPR 1		HSJH 1					NUND 2			
	PSTH 7		WTHH 1					NEUR 12			
	PUND 5		HUND 1					NUND 79			
	SMER 4							OCTO 214			
	THON 3							PASO 1			
	TRAL 4							PBRK 7			
	HCAP 2							PCAL 4			
	WHYS 2							PCON 2			
	HSJH 2							PCYC 2			
	WTHH 1							PECP 51			
	HUND 3							PLEP 3			
								PLYB 2			
								PMAC 175			
								PPIN 1			

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 259		LOC 260		LOC 261		LOC 262		LOC 263		LOC 264		LOC 265		LOC 266		LOC 267	
LOC 257		LOC 258		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 1935	SUM 1779	SUM 469	SUM 576	SUM 225	SUM 868	SUM 1643	SUM 1821	SUM 863	SUM 1693	SUM 515									
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT									
AICH 19	AICH 14	ALTH 3	ANHL 2	BLIN 18	ALTH 5	ALTH 3	AICH 48	ANMD 1	ALTH 3	ANNL 1									
ANMD 3	ALTH 1	ANHL 11	BLIN 9	BLJR 44	ANNL 7	ANNL 27	ALTH 4	BLIN 2	ANNL 19	BLIN 49									
ANNL 12	ANHL 3	ARAC 1	BLJR 27	BLSR 42	BLIN 4	ASTR 1	ANMD 1	BLJR 87	BLIN 31	BLJR 17									
BLJR 380	BLIN 20	ASTR 1	BLSR 201	BTOT 1	BLJR 58	BLIN 7	ANNL 11	BLOD 2	BLJR 255	BLSR 14									
BLHT 25	BLJR 254	CPAL 1	CBLT 5	CBLM 2	BLSR 144	BLJR 154	BLIN 11	BLSR 237	BLHT 2	CBAR 1									
BLSR 863	BLMT 3	CSYN 4	DCOM 251	CBLT 1	BTOT 20	BLMT 1	BLJR 8	CBLT 6	BLSR 302	CBLM 4									
CAEN 1	BLSR 655	DCOM 52	DGBR 44	CKAL 1	CBLT 12	BLSR 371	BLSR 1112	CCYC 1	CBLT 33	CBLT 1									
CBLT 73	BTOT 95	DDGR 78	DPYC 5	DCOM 82	CFLE 2	CBLM 2	BTOT 8	CFLE 1	CCYC 2	CCYC 2									
CKAL 1	CBLT 9	DPYC 53	DSEP 1	DGBR 14	CKAL 2	CBLT 27	CKAL 17	DCOM 59	CKAL 2	CSUN 1									
CKEL 1	CCYC 1	DSEP 4	ETAC 4	ETAC 9	CUND 1	CFLE 3	CKEL 2	DGRY 233	CKEL 1	DCOM 276									
CSUN 1	CSUN 2	DWTH 4	FCOP 2	FCOP 1	DCOM 369	CKAL 4	DGBR 305	DISC 6	DGRY 591	DDGR 2									
DCOM 217	CUND 1	FCOP 61	INCG 1	MSTR 1	DGBR 19	DCOM 291	FCOP 45	DPYC 6	DGRY 64	DGBR 79									
DGBR 95	DCOM 379	FPRT 1	NSTR 1	PECP 2	DISC 4	DGRY 240	FESC 6	DREJ 57	DISC 6	DPYC 2									
DREJ 3	DGBR 18	LSTP 2	NEUR 3	PSTH 1	DPYC 4	DISC 12	FGIL 1	DSEP 7	DPYC 36	EGGS 1									
ETAC 45	DISC 25	MFHC 3	NUND 3	SMER 4	DREJ 44	DPYC 49	INCG 24	ETAC 3	ETAC 58	ETAC 4									
FCOP 10	DODD 3	NEUR 39	OCTO 1	TDPL 1	DSEP 1	DREJ 80	LSTP 1	FCOP 49	FCOP 11	FCOP 4									
FESC 2	DREJ 96	NUND 11	PECP 4	TMON 1	ETAC 2	DSEP 4	MEDS 6	FESC 2	FESC 2	MCHT 14									
INCG 9	DSEP 12	PAPH 1	PMAC 1		FCOP 24	ETAC 12	MSTR 8	MCHT 1	FGIL 1	MMSI 17									
LEPD 1	DTOT 32	PBRK 2	PSTH 1		FESC 1	FCOP 35	NEUR 37	MEDS 1	MEDS 4	MPEC 2									
MCHT 2	ETAC 1	PCAL 2	SMER 1		HOLT 4	FESC 7	PBRK 42	MFEC 2	MMSI 2	NUND 8									
MEDS 2	FACH 1	PCON 3	TMON 1		INCG 3	FGIL 1	PCAL 21	MSTR 1	MSTR 4	PECP 2									
MMSI 2	FCOP 83	PCYC 2	TRAL 7		LIMU 1	HOLT 21	PCYC 1	NEUR 23	NUND 1	PLEP 1									
MPEC 1	INCG 4	PECP 58	HTTH 1		MCHT 1	INCG 2	PECP 51	NUND 5	NEUR 10	PMAC 3									
MSTR 7	LIMU 1	PLEP 17			MMSI 5	MEDS 7	PLEP 14	PCAL 2	NUND 40	PSTH 2									
NEUR 8	LSTP 1	PLXS 4			MUND 1	MMSI 7	PUND 1	PECP 22	OCTO 3	PUND 2									
NUND 5	MSTR 2	PLYB 1			NEUR 3	MSTR 18	TDPL 1	PMAC 2	PERK 49	TRAL 5									
OCTO 7	NEUR 5	PMAC 17			NUND 9	MUND 1	TMON 10	PSTH 17	PCAL 6	YHNY 1									
PCAL 6	NUND 7	PSTH 17			OCTO 2	NEUR 8	TRAL 22	PUND 1	PCON 1										
PCYC 2	PECP 19	PUND 9			PBRK 23	NUND 16	HCAP 1	TRAL 18	PECP 65										
PECP 51	PMAC 1	SEED 1			PCAL 3	FCAL 13	HPLN 2	HCAP 1	FLEP 19										
PLEP 4	PSTH 10	SPHN 1			PECP 41	FCYC 2		WFAN 3	PMAC 5										
PMAC 4	RTHD 1	SPMG 1			PLEP 3	PECP 81		HOLH 2	PPIN 3										
PSTH 25	SPHN 1	STIG 1			PMAC 4	PLEP 3		HSJW 1	PSTH 2										
PUND 7	TFBR 2	TFBR 2			PUND 1	PMAC 1		KUNO 1	PUND 40										
RTHD 1	TMON 1	TFTR 1			SMER 19	PSTH 57		YHNY 1	SPHN 1										
TDPL 1	TRAL 7				TMON 2	PUND 2			TMON 2										
TMON 21	HCAP 1				TRAL 19	RTMD 1			TRAL 8										
TRAL 6	HPLN 1				HPAL 1	SMER 34			HESC 1										
HESC 6	HSJW 1					SPHN 1			HSJW 2										
HNEH 1	HTTH 2					STIG 3			HTTH 1										
HSJW 2	HUND 4					TDPL 3			HUND 5										
HTTH 2						TMON 2													
HUND 1						TFEL 1													
						TRAL 15													
						HCAP 3													
						HESC 1													
						HPLN 1													
						HSJW 1													
						HSPR 1													
						HTTH 3													
						HUND 3													

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 268		LOC 269		LOC 270		LOC 271		LOC 272		LOC 273		LOC 274		LOC 275		LOC 276		LOC 277		LOC 278	
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	
SUM 272	SUM 2107	SUM 802	SUM 119	SUM 391	SUM 1186	SUM 904	SUM 1995	SUM 1776	SUM 477	SUM 180													
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT													
ALTH 1	ALTH 1	ANNL 1	BLIN 14	BLIN 19	AICH 5	AICH 2	AICH 2	AICH 45	AICH 3	ARTH 1													
BLIN 9	ANNL 7	BLIN 40	BLJR 19	BLJR 61	ALTH 3	ALTH 3	ALTH 3	ALTH 1	ANNL 1	BLIN 10													
BLJR 55	BLIN 56	BLJR 103	BLOD 1	BLSR 60	ANNL 9	ANNL 5	ANNL 57	ANNL 33	BLIN 6	BLJR 4													
BLSR 49	BLJR 286	BLMT 1	BLSR 20	CBLM 5	BLIN 1	BLIN 3	BLIN 12	BLIN 24	BLJR 22	BLSR 9													
CBLT 2	BLOD 5	BLSR 111	CBLT 1	CBLT 2	BLJR 154	BLJR 18	BLJR 97	BLJR 218	BLSR 48	DCOM 34													
CCYC 1	BLSR 520	CBLM 7	CSUN 1	CSUN 1	BLMT 21	BLSR 192	BLSR 185	BLOD 34	CBLT 12	DGBR 38													
CSUN 1	CBLT 52	CBLT 3	DCOM 23	DCOM 136	BLSR 615	CBLT 12	BTOT 1	BLSR 369	CFLE 2	DISC 1													
DCOM 65	CCYZ 1	CCYC 1	DGBR 15	DGBR 42	CBLT 51	CFLE 3	CBLT 47	BTOT 13	DGBR 282	DPYC 34													
DGBR 43	CFLE 2	CKAL 1	DPYC 7	DPYC 19	CFLE 1	CKAL 1	CCYC 3	CBLT 53	FCOP 22	DSEP 2													
DISC 1	CKAL 1	CSUN 1	DSEP 2	ETAC 2	CPAL 1	DGBR 255	CFLE 1	CCYC 4	FESC 1	FCOP 34													
DPYC 4	CPAL 1	DCOM 343	ETAC 3	FCOP 4	DGBR 125	DSEP 2	DGBR 1043	CFLE 1	HOLT 3	INCG 3													
ETAC 6	DCOM 1067	DGRY 132	FCOP 2	FESC 1	DISC 12	FCOP 31	DSEP 2	CSUN 2	INCG 1	NEUR 1													
FCOP 3	DISC 9	DPYC 10	NUND 3	FRHB 1	DREJ 30	FESC 2	ETAC 2	DGBR 484	MEDS 1	PECP 1													
INCG 1	DSEP 7	DSEP 1	ODON 1	NUND 3	DTOT 59	HOLT 45	FCOP 72	FACN 1	NEUR 2	PSPR 1													
JELF 1	ETAC 9	ETAC 4	PECP 1	OCTO 1	FCOP 17	MEDS 2	FESC 3	FCOP 30	NUND 8	PSTM 1													
NEUR 1	FCOP 11	FCOP 2	PFUN 1	PCAL 3	HOLT 1	MSTR 2	HOLT 25	FESC 8	PCAL 2	SPHN 1													
NUND 14	FESC 5	FESC 1	PLEP 1	PECP 2	NEUR 10	NEUR 8	INCG 14	INCG 6	PECP 7	TRAL 4													
OCTO 1	FRHB 1	INCG 1	PSTM 1	PHAC 4	NUND 11	NUND 1	INSC 1	MEDS 12	PLEP 1	WCAP 1													
PECP 2	INCG 1	NEUR 1	PUND 1	PSTM 7	OCTO 2	PBRK 13	MEDS 2	MMSI 13	PSTM 2														
PLEP 1	LIMU 1	NUND 9	TRAL 1	PUND 1	PBRK 1	PCAL 2	NMSI 10	MSTR 13	PUND 1														
PHAC 2	MSTR 3	PCAL 1	WHYS 1	SMER 11	PECP 17	PECP 48	MPEC 1	NEUR 27	TRAL 47														
PSTM 2	NEUR 3	PECP 6		THAL 1	PLEP 4	PLEP 2	MSTR 3	OCTO 2	WCAP 1														
TDPL 1	NUND 8	PSTM 8		THON 3	PSTM 10	SPFR 1	NUND 1	PBRK 61	WUND 2														
THON 1	OCTO 1	THRN 1		HCAP 1	PUND 3	TRAL 238	NEUR 25	PCAL 23															
TRAL 3	PCAL 2	THON 2		HTTH 1	SPFR 1	WBLN 3	NUND 6	PCYC 5															
WTTH 2	PECP 16	TRAL 9			THON 5	WCAP 1	PBRK 60	PECP 192															
	PLEP 1	HFSH 1			TRAL 9	WDRY 1	PCAL 10	PLEP 4															
	PHAC 4	WKEM 1			HCAP 1	WPLN 4	FECP 173	PHAC 2															
	PSTM 8				WKEM 1	WSJW 1	PLEP 13	PUND 2															
	THON 4				HOLH 1	WTTH 2	PHAC 3	TDPL 1															
	TRAL 1				WPLN 1	WUND 1	PSTM 12	TFTR 1															
	WDRY 1				WTTH 2		TDPL 1	THON 4															
	WHYS 1				WUND 2		THON 5	TRAL 81															
	WOLH 1						TRAL 85	WESC 1															
	WPLN 2						WBLN 2	WHYS 1															
	WSJW 1						WCAP 4	WTTH 1															
	WTTH 1						WDRY 1	WUND 3															
	WUND 6						WPLN 3	YHNY 1															
							WTTH 1																
							WUND 4																

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LOC 279		LOC 280	LOC 281	LOC 282	LOC 283	LOC 284	LOC 285	LOC 286	LOC 287	LOC 288	LOC 289											
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES										
SUM 1222	SUM 1172	SUM 746	SUM 1386	SUM 68	SUM 325	SUM 2398	SUM 181	SUM 180	SUM 305	SUM 895												
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT										
ALTH	1	ANNL	4	ALTH	2	AICH	6	BLIN	3	BLIN	19	AICH	38	BLIN	9	ANND	1	AICH	1	ALTH	1	
ANNL	2	BLIN	18	BLIN	18	ANNL	29	BLJR	5	BLJR	19	ALTH	3	BLJR	2	BLIN	32	ANND	1	ANNL	6	
BLIN	1	BLJR	157	BLJR	77	BLIN	9	BLSR	4	BLSR	9	ANND	2	BLSR	11	BLJR	12	ANNL	3	ARTH	1	
BLSR	403	BLMT	15	BLMT	1	BLJR	93	CBLT	2	CBLM	1	ANNL	11	CBLT	1	BLSR	9	BLSR	175	BLIN	9	
CBAR	1	BLOD	1	BLSR	195	BLMT	3	DCOM	34	CBLT	3	BLIN	55	CKAL	1	CBLT	2	CAEN	1	BLSR	5	
CBLT	21	BLSR	548	CBLM	4	BLSR	335	DGBR	12	CKAL	1	BLJR	55	DBLB	3	CKAL	1	CBLT	4	CKAL	1	
CFLE	6	CBLM	2	CBLT	25	BTOT	152	NUND	4	CSUN	1	BLHT	9	DCOM	61	DCOM	76	DDBR	81	CPAL	1	
CSUN	2	CBLT	39	CSUN	2	CBLM	15	TRAL	4	DGRY	40	BLOD	20	DDGR	3	DISC	6	FCOP	35	CTYR	1	
DGBR	525	CKEL	1	DGBR	356	CBLT	10			DISC	4	BLSR	1486	DGBR	22	DSEP	2	HUND	1	DBLB	6	
DISC	1	CSUN	1	DISC	2	CFLE	1			DPYC	12	BTOT	8	DODD	10	ETAC	2	NEUR	1	DDGR	74	
DSEP	1	DCOM	162	OPYC	6	CKAL	3			DREJ	40	CAEN	1	ETAC	1	FCOP	18	PBRK	1	DGBR	123	
FCOP	82	DGBR	82	ETAC	2	CSUN	1			DSEP	2	CBLT	72	FCOP	42	MSTR	2	PECP	1	DGBR	229	
FRHB	1	DISC	40	FCOP	15	CUND	1			DWTH	7	CCYC	2	FPRT	1	NUND	4			DPYC	13	
HFTR	1	DMOT	2	FESC	2	DGBR	205			ETAC	1	CFLE	1	MPCR	1	OCTO	1			DSND	16	
HOLT	8	DSEP	6	INCG	1	DISC	44			FCOP	109	DBRN	309	NUND	2	PECP	2			FCOP	19	
INCG	1	ETAC	1	MSTR	2	DREJ	131			HOLT	2	DGBR	20	OCTO	1	SPHN	1			LEPD	1	
INSC	1	FCOP	8	NEUR	1	DSEP	1			LYCD	1	ETAC	5	PECP	1	TRAL	8			LSTP	7	
HMCR	3	FESC	1	NUND	7	DTOT	87			NEUR	3	FCOP	103	PSTM	1	HUND	1			MFHC	11	
NEUR	9	FGIL	1	PECP	4	ETAC	2			NUND	8	FESC	4	SMER	8					MPEC	10	
NUND	2	HCEP	1	PLEP	1	FCOP	20			PBRK	1	FGIL	2							HUND	6	
PCAL	1	MEDS	2	PSTM	9	FCFN	1			PCAL	3	FLAM	1							NEUR	12	
PECP	26	MPEC	1	THON	2	FESC	6			PECP	9	HOLT	1							NUND	48	
PSTM	11	MSTR	3	TRAL	6	FGIL	1			PLEP	1	INCG	2							ODON	3	
TRAL	101	NEUR	14	WCAP	2	HOLT	5			PMAC	2	MEDS	6							PAPH	1	
WCAP	1	NUND	5	HSJH	1	LEPD	1			PSTM	2	MSTR	9							PCAL	2	
WDRY	1	PCAL	3	HTTH	1	MDUN	1			PUND	2	NEUR	14							PCYC	1	
WESC	1	PECP	20	WUND	2	MEDS	30			TDPL	3	NUND	5							PECP	56	
WHYS	1	PLEP	2			MPEC	1			THON	2	PCAL	7							PLEP	117	
WOLH	1	PMAR	1			HSCZ	1			TRAL	18	PCON	1							PLYB	1	
HTTH	2	PSTM	11			HSTR	10					PCYC	2							PLYC	2	
WUND	4	PUND	1			HUND	1					PECP	64							PMAC	39	
		THAL	1			NEUR	18					PLEP	6							PPIN	1	
		THON	1			NUND	6					PMAC	5							PSTM	32	
		TRAL	11			PCAL	9					PPIN	1							PUND	7	
		WESC	1			PECP	72					PSTM	42							SEED	1	
		HPLN	1			PFUN	1					PUND	4							SMER	1	
		WUND	4			PLEP	7					THON	14							SPHN	3	
						PMAC	4					TRAL	3							STIG	1	
						PSTM	7					WCAP	1							TRAL	8	
						PUND	14					HTTH	2							WBLN	1	
						RTHD	2					WUND	2							WESC	1	
						STIG	3													WOLH	6	
						THON	6													HTTH	4	
						TRAL	23													WUND	7	
						WCAP	5															
						HTTH	1															
						WUND	2															

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LOC 290		LOC 291		LOC 292		LOC 293		LOC 294		LOC 295		LOC 296		LOC 297		LOC 298		LOC 299		LOC 300			
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES			
SUM 244		SUM 78		SUM 142		SUM 408		SUM 170		SUM 70		SUM 33		SUM 40		SUM 47		SUM 34		SUM 95			
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT			
ANHL	12	ASTR	2	BLIN	1	ANHL	1	BLIN	1	DCOH	49	BLIN	1	ANHL	1	ALTH	1	DDGR	5	DDGR	2		
ASTR	4	DCOM	32	BLJR	1	BLIN	8	BLJR	1	FCOP	1	BLJR	1	DDGR	10	ANHL	1	DISC	1	DDGR	57		
DBLG	2	DSEP	8	BLSR	3	BLJR	4	BLSR	1	NEUR	2	DCOH	19	DDGR	8	ARAC	1	DPYC	9	DPYC	4		
DCOM	23	NEUR	3	BTOT	2	BLSR	17	DDGR	9	PCOH	1	NEUR	1	DPYC	5	DDGR	7	DSND	13	FCOP	1		
DDGR	18	HUND	2	DCOH	87	BTOT	10	DGBR	92	PECP	2	HUND	5	HUND	1	DGBR	14	FCOP	1	NUND	3		
DGBR	27	PCAL	1	DGBR	7	CBLM	4	DPYC	13	PLEP	11	PLEP	3	PECP	3	NEUR	2	PBRK	1	PAPH	1		
DPYC	5	PECP	1	DPYC	3	DCOH	168	DSEP	1	PHAC	1	TRAL	3	FLEP	7	NUND	3	PCOH	1	PCAL	1		
DSEP	4	PLEP	26	FCOP	2	DGBR	78	FCOP	2	PSTH	3			PMAC	1	PECP	4	PLEP	1	PECP	4		
FCOP	9	PHAC	2	LSTP	1	DLGH	8	LSTP	2					FUND	1	PLEP	8	PSTH	2	FLEP	10		
LEPD	1	FUND	1	NEUR	5	DMOT	2	NEUR	8					WCAP	2	PMAC	1	PODD	3	PMAC	4		
NEUR	6			PCAL	1	DPYC	16	NUND	2					HUND	1	PODD	3	PSTH	5	PSTH	5		
HUND	7			PECP	3	FCOP	10	PBRK	1							PSTH	2		PUND	1			
PBRK	2			FLEP	13	INCG	2	PECP	9										PUND	1			
PCAL	7			PHAC	1	LSTP	1	FLEP	18										SPHN	2			
PECP	63			PSTH	2	NEUR	11	PHAC	6														
PLEP	21			TRAL	8	NUND	5	PSTH	2														
PMAC	5			WCAP	1	PCYC	1	SPHN	2														
PSTH	25			HUND	1	PECP	15																
PUND	2					PLEP	14																
TPEL	1					PLXS	1																
						PSTH	6																
						PUND	3																
						TRAL	22																
						WCAP	1																

LISTING BY		LOCATION										
LOC 301	LOC 302	LOC 303	LOC 304	LOC 305	LOC 306	LOC 307	LOC 308	LOC 309	LOC 310	LOC 311		
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES
SUM 389	SUM 742	SUM 49	SUM 93	SUM 205	SUM 127	SUM 73	SUM 686	SUM 349	SUM 40	SUM 46		
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
ALTH 1	ALTH 4	ANNL 1	ANNL 2	ANNL 4	ANNL 1	ANNL 1	ANNL 2	ALTH 5	DDGR 8	DDGR 7		
ANNL 4	ANNL 49	BLJR 1	BLIN 1	BLIN 6	BLIN 1	ASTR 1	ARTH 1	ANHL 11	DPYC 11	DPYC 2		
ASTR 3	ASTR 1	DGBR 27	BLJR 2	BLJR 16	BLJR 3	BTOT 1	CAEN 1	DCOM 108	DSND 12	DSND 26		
DCOM 75	CAEN 1	DPYC 1	BLSR 1	BLSR 8	BLOD 3	DCOM 48	CPAL 1	DDGR 10	FCOP 1	NUND 1		
DGBR 21	DCOM 21	DSEP 1	CAEN 2	BTOT 1	BLSR 2	NEUR 2	CSYN 1	DGBR 65	NUND 2	PLEP 2		
DREJ 12	DDGR 11	FCOP 1	CSYN 1	CBLL 1	CCYC 1	NUND 2	DCOM 15	DREJ 11	PLEP 2	PHAC 5		
DSEP 10	DGBR 92	NEUR 1	DCOM 50	CCYC 3	DBLB 2	FECP 2	DDGR 109	FCOP 3	PHAC 2	PSTM 2		
EUPR 3	DISC 2	NUND 1	NUND 1	DDGR 11	DGBR 30	PLEP 4	DPYC 16	NEUR 10	PSTH 2	PUND 1		
FCOP 17	DLGR 25	PBRK 1	PCON 1	DGBR 80	DISC 5	PHAC 5	FCOP 40	PAPH 1				
LSTP 4	DPYC 1	PECP 3	PCYC 1	DPYC 1	DPYC 1	PSTM 6	LEPD 4	PCAL 2				
MFHC 3	DSEP 73	PMAC 5	PECP 10	DREJ 33	DSEP 5	SPHN 1	LSTP 1	FCYC 1				
NEUR 22	FCOP 5	PSTM 5	PLEP 12	DSEP 4	FCOP 1		LSTR 1	FECP 53				
NUND 8	INCG 1	PUND 1	PSTM 9	ETAC 1	MEDS 57		NEUR 77	PLEP 26				
PBRK 24	LSTP 13			FCOP 3	NUND 5		NUND 7	PLXS 1				
PCAL 3	MECR 29			FESC 1	PCAL 3		PAPH 1	PHAC 20				
PCYC 1	MFHC 46			HOLT 1	PCYC 1		PBRK 2	PSTM 17				
PECP 87	MHSI 26			MEDS 1	PECP 2		PCAL 3	PUND 5				
PLEP 41	MUND 10			MHSI 2	PSTM 2		PCON 1					
PLYC 2	NEUR 35			MPEC 1	TRAL 1		PCYC 2					
PMAC 34	NUND 86			MSTR 1	WUND 1		PECP 288					
PSTM 10	PBRK 1			NEUR 2			PLEP 44					
PUND 2	PCAL 3			NUND 1			PHAC 10					
SPHN 2	FECP 49			FECP 2			PPIN 1					
	PLEP 54			PLEP 2			PUND 48					
	PHAC 36			PHAC 6			STIG 3					
	PSTM 57			PPIN 1								
	PUND 2			PSTM 3								
	SEED 1			SPHN 1								
	SNER 5			TRAL 7								
	SPHN 2			HTTH 1								
	TFBR 1											

LISTING BY LOCATION										
LOC 312	LOC 313	LOC 314	LOC 315	LOC 316	LOC 320	LOC 321	LOC 322	LOC 323	LOC 324	LOC 325
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES
SUM 29	SUM 334	SUM 583	SUM 537	SUM 1566	SUM 248	SUM 46	SUM 458	SUM 106	SUM 179	SUM 65
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
DDGR 1	ANHL 10	ALTH 10	ALTH 2	ALTH 14	ALTH 3	CBLM 4	ALTH 2	ANNL 1	ANNL 2	ANNL 1
DGBR 16	ASTR 1	ANHL 31	ANHL 6	ANNL 22	ANHL 1	DCOM 25	ANNL 9	BTOT 3	BLIN 5	DGBR 42
DPYC 1	DGBR 18	ASTR 3	ASTR 1	ASTR 4	BTOT 18	FACN 1	BTOT 48	CBLT 2	BLJR 1	DOOD 8
FCOP 1	DGBR 64	DCOM 103	DCOM 114	CUND 1	CBLM 3	FCOP 2	CBLT 1	DGRY 46	BLMT 6	DSEP 6
NUND 1	DISC 2	FCOP 13	FCOP 12	DCOM 392	CCYC 5	HDEV 2	CCYC 6	DPYC 23	BLSR 26	NEUR 1
FBRK 1	DSEP 17	INSC 1	INSC 2	DGBR 10	DCOM 156	HPEC 1	CKAL 1	DSEP 3	CBLM 2	PERK 1
PLEP 3	DSND 1	LEPD 4	LEPD 1	DGRY 18	DPYC 10	NEUR 2	CPAL 2	FCOP 3	DGBR 91	PECP 2
PMAC 2	FCOP 13	LSTP 4	LSTP 2	DISC 2	FCOP 6	PECP 2	DCOM 314	NEUR 2	DISC 2	PLEP 2
FSTH 2	FCTN 1	MFHC 8	MFHC 3	DLGH 8	LEPD 1	PHAC 1	FCOP 5	NUND 2	FCOP 4	PHAC 1
TRAL 1	LSTP 1	NEUR 54	NEUR 43	DSEP 4	MEDS 2	PSTH 3	FCRT 1	PECP 1	MEDS 1	PSTH 1
	HEUR 17	ODON 2	ODON 1	EUPR 1	NEUR 4	STIG 1	FESC 1	PLEP 1	NEUR 7	
	NUND 8	PBRK 60	FBRK 60	FCOP 92	NUND 2	HESC 1	HOLT 2	PMAC 12	NUND 4	
	ODON 1	PCAL 11	PCAL 10	LEPD 5	PCAL 4	HUND 1	LEPD 2	PSTH 3	PECP 5	
	PERK 42	PCRC 2	PCON 1	LSTP 12	PCYC 1		LSTP 1	SPHN 1	PMAC 2	
	PCAL 4	PCRD 1	PECP 145	MFHC 21	PECP 5		MEDS 10	TMON 2	PSTH 2	
	PECP 50	PCYC 4	PLEP 37	NEUR 58	PMAC 1		HPEC 7	NUND 1	SMER 2	
	PLEP 21	PECP 65	PMAC 32	NUND 4	PSTH 13		HSTR 4	NUND 1	TRAL 6	
	PLYB 2	PLEP 45	FSTH 60	PAPH 1	THON 3		NUND 1	NEUR 2	WCAP 1	
	PLYC 2	PLXS 1	SEED 1	FBRK 60	TRAL 2		NEUR 1	PCAL 1	WRND 5	
	PMAC 26	PLYC 3	STIG 3	PCAL 20	WCAP 3		PCAL 1	PECP 10	HSJW 1	
	PSTH 31	PMAC 37	HSPR 1	PCON 2	HUND 5		PECP 7	PPIN 1	HTTH 4	
	STIG 2	PPIN 1	PCRC 2	PCYC 3			PPIN 1	PSTH 7		
		PSEL 2	PCYC 3	PECP 470			TMON 3	TRAL 1		
		PSTH 106	PECP 73	PMAC 108			TRAL 1	WCAP 1		
		SEED 1	PMAC 108	FSTH 146			WCAP 5	HESC 5		
		STIG 11	FSTH 146	PSUL 2			HPLN 4	HPTH 1		
			PSUL 2	PUND 4			HPTH 1	HUND 5		
			PUND 4	SEED 3						
			SEED 3	SPHN 1						
			SPHN 1	STIG 3						
			STIG 3							

LISTING BY		LOCATION																			
LOC 337	LOC 338	LOC 339	LOC 340	LOC 341	LOC 342	LOC 343	LOC 344	LOC 345	LOC 346	LOC 347											
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES									
SUM 96	SUM 21	SUM 21	SUM 94	SUM 151	SUM 216	SUM 470	SUM 296	SUM 703	SUM 837	SUM 398											
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT									
BLIN	6	DBLG	3	DSGB	11	ANNL	3	ALTH	1	ANNL	2	ALTH	2	ANNL	13	ALTH	4	ALTH	4	ALTH	3
BLJR	5	DGBR	4	DSGR	5	DBLG	47	ANNL	3	BLIN	4	ANNL	15	DGBR	32	ANNL	18	ANNL	16	ANNL	13
BLSR	3	NEUR	3	PMAC	5	DGBR	21	CPAL	1	BLJR	1	CAEN	1	DSEP	13	ASTR	3	ASTR	2	CPAL	2
DBLB	25	NUND	2			DSEP	1	DDGR	1	BLSR	12	DBLB	2	DWTH	30	CSYN	1	COST	1	DBLB	19
DGBR	29	PECP	5			PBRK	1	DGBR	53	DCOM	8	DDGR	2	EUPR	3	DBLB	22	CPAL	1	DDGR	5
DPYC	1	PLEP	1			PCAL	2	DSEP	1	DDGR	3	DGBR	126	FCOP	8	DDGR	5	CSUN	2	DGBR	35
DSEP	2	PMAC	1			PECP	1	FCOP	3	DGBR	72	DSEP	5	LSTP	2	DGBR	41	DBLB	137	DSEP	20
FCOP	2	PSTH	1			PMAC	17	MFWC	1	DISC	1	EUPR	1	MFWC	2	DGRY	18	DDGR	6	DWTH	40
FRHB	1	PUND	1			PSTH	1	NEUR	10	DPYC	13	FCOP	22	MUND	1	DISC	1	DGBR	148	EUPR	1
HDEV	1							NUND	2	DREJ	59	FPRT	1	NEUR	8	DSEP	5	DREJ	12	FCOP	19
LSTR	1							ODON	2	DSEP	1	LSTP	2	NUND	3	DWTH	81	DSEP	5	LEPD	10
MMSI	1							PAPH	1	FCOP	4	MFWC	5	PAPH	1	FCOP	39	EUPR	5	LSTP	2
NEUR	2							PCAL	5	LEPD	1	NEUR	21	PBRK	14	LSTP	1	FCOP	90	LSTR	1
NUND	1							PECP	16	LSTP	1	NUND	10	PCAL	20	MFWC	5	FCTN	1	MFWC	5
PECP	3							PFUN	1	NUND	2	PBRK	11	PCYC	2	NEUR	34	LEPD	7	NEUR	6
PMAC	3							PLEP	10	NEUR	7	PCAL	11	PECP	74	NUND	2	LSTP	4	NUND	3
PSTH	1							PMAC	31	NUND	3	PCYC	4	PLEP	12	ODON	2	MFWC	12	PBRK	32
PUND	1							PCAL	2	PCAL	2	PECP	92	PLXS	1	PBRK	30	MMSI	1	PCAL	5
SMER	2							PSTH	9	PCON	1	PLEP	37	PLYB	2	PCAL	10	NEUR	20	PCON	2
TRAL	5									PECP	4	PLYC	5	PLYC	1	PCON	2	NUND	10	PECP	49
WTHH	1									PMAC	1	PHAC	13	PMAC	5	PCYC	3	ODON	4	PLEP	47
										PSTH	7	PSAR	1	PSTH	42	PECP	204	PAPH	1	PLXS	1
										SPFR	1	PSPR	1	PSUL	1	PLEP	43	PBRK	42	PMAC	34
										TRAL	4	PSTH	66	PUND	5	PLXS	1	PCAL	16	PSTH	29
										HSJH	1	PUND	5	STIG	1	PMAC	35	PCON	1	PUND	5
										HUND	1	SEED	2			PPIN	1	PCYC	1	SEED	2
												SPHN	4			PSPR	1	PECP	88	SPFR	1
												STIG	1			PSTH	79	PLEP	83	STIG	6
												HSPR	2			PUND	7	PLXS	1	TFTR	1
																SEED	1	PHAC	74		
																SPHN	1	PSTH	34		
																STIG	2	PUND	1		
																HSPR	1	SEED	3		
																	STIG	4			

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ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 382		SUM 312		SUM 696		SUM 536		SUM 603		SUM 106		SUM 183		SUM 144		SUM 358		SUM 172		SUM 308		SUM 308	
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT	
ALTH	1	ALTH	2	ALTH	1	ALTH	4	ALTH	2	ALTH	2	ANNL	28	ALTH	2	ALTH	4	ALTH	3	ANNL	12		
ANHL	9	ANHL	24	ANHL	25	ANHL	4	ANHL	26	ASTR	1	CPAL	1	ANHL	4	ANHL	23	ANHL	7	ASTR	1		
CCYZ	1	COST	1	CAEN	4	CAEN	1	ASTR	1	DDGR	3	CSYN	1	BLSR	1	ASLN	1	DBLB	5	DBLB	6		
DGBR	49	DBLB	8	CPAL	3	CSYN	1	CAEN	1	DGBR	29	DGBR	20	DBLB	3	ASTR	1	DGBR	31	DGBR	2		
DSEP	8	DDGR	6	CSYN	4	DDGR	5	DBLB	20	DSEP	2	DSEP	4	DGBR	4	DGBR	62	DREJ	9	DREJ	1	DGBR	60
DNTH	19	DGBR	6	DDGR	11	DGBR	42	DDGR	2	DSND	2	EUPR	1	DSEP	4	DGBR	95	DSEP	3	DSEP	7		
EUPR	2	DGRY	36	DGBR	58	DSEP	4	DGBR	75	FCOP	5	FCOP	6	FCOP	5	DISC	7	FCOP	7	EUPR	1		
FCOP	33	DSEP	13	DSND	12	DSND	7	DGRY	6	NEUR	5	LSTP	3	LEPD	1	DSEP	1	LSTP	2	FCOP	17		
LEPD	2	DNTH	14	DNTH	199	DNTH	119	DSEP	21	PBRK	2	MFWC	3	LSTP	1	EUPR	1	LYBR	1	LSTP	5		
LSTP	3	EUPR	1	EUPR	3	FCOP	23	EUPR	2	PCYC	1	NEUR	7	MMSI	1	FCOP	6	MFWC	4	MFWC	1		
MFWC	2	FCOP	18	FCOP	38	LSTP	1	FCOP	31	PECP	12	PBRK	6	NEUR	4	LEPD	1	NEUR	6	NEUR	18		
NEUR	5	LSTP	3	INCG	1	MFWC	2	FCTN	1	PLEP	10	PCAL	7	NUND	1	MFWC	2	NUND	1	NUND	3		
NUND	3	MFWC	3	LSTP	2	MMSI	1	LEPD	1	PLYB	1	PECP	27	PBRK	1	NEUR	8	ODON	1	ODON	1		
PBRK	28	NEUR	17	MFWC	6	NEUR	3	LSTP	1	PMAC	14	PLEP	44	PCAL	1	NEUR	3	PCAL	11	FBRK	4		
PCAL	12	NUND	1	NEUR	11	NUND	3	NEUR	17	PSTH	13	PLYB	1	PECP	21	ODON	1	PCAL	4	PCAL	8		
PCYC	2	PBRK	20	NUND	5	PBRK	16	NUND	8	PUND	1	PMAC	1	FLEP	8	PBRK	8	PECP	25	PCRC	1		
PECP	52	PCAL	4	ODON	2	PCAL	10	PAPH	1	SEED	1	PSTH	14	PMAC	12	PCAL	11	PLEP	21	PCYC	4		
PLEP	53	FCYC	1	PBRK	17	PECP	166	PBRK	29	STIG	1	PSUL	1	PSTH	6	PCON	3	PMAC	13	PECP	46		
PMAC	15	PECP	32	PCAL	10	PLEP	40	PCAL	26	TFTR	1	PUND	5	FUND	2	PCYC	1	PSTH	23	PLEP	22		
PSTH	58	PLEP	19	PECP	67	PMAC	42	PCAU	1			SEED	2	TRAL	1	PECP	40	PSUL	1	PLYC	1		
PSUL	16	PLYC	2	PLEP	81	PMAR	1	PCON	1			STIG	1			PLEP	45	SPHN	1	PMAC	28		
PUND	3	PMAC	44	PLXS	7	PSTH	32	PECP	120							PLYB	1	STIG	1	PSTH	48		
SEED	2	PSTH	32	PMAC	85	PSUL	3	PLEP	44							PLYC	1			PSUL	2		
SPHN	2	PUND	2	PPIN	1	PUND	2	PLXS	3							PMAC	33			PUND	4		
STIG	2	SEED	1	PSTH	31	STIG	3	PMAC	37							PMAR	1			SEED	2		
		SPHN	2	PUND	4	TFTR	1	PSTH	83							PSTH	38			SPHN	3		
				SEED	3			PSUL	27							PSUL	2			STIG	1		
				SPHN	4			PUND	11							PUND	11			TFBR	1		
				STIG	1			SEED	2							SEED	1			TFTR	1		
								STIG	1							SPFR	1						
								TFTR	1							SPHN	1						
								HSPR	1							STIG	1						
																TFBR	1						
																TFTR	1						

LISTING BY LOCATION		LOC 361		LOC 362		LOC 363		LOC 364		LOC 365		LOC 366		LOC 367		LOC 368		LOC 369				
LOC 359	LOC 360	LOC 361	LOC 362	LOC 363	LOC 364	LOC 365	LOC 366	LOC 367	LOC 368	LOC 369	LOC 361	LOC 362	LOC 363	LOC 364	LOC 365	LOC 366	LOC 367	LOC 368	LOC 369			
ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES	ALL PAGES			
SUM 532	SUM 234	SUM 115	SUM 676	SUM 193	SUM 319	SUM 120	SUM 417	SUM 553	SUM 202	SUM 508	SUM 532	SUM 234	SUM 115	SUM 676	SUM 193	SUM 319	SUM 120	SUM 417	SUM 553	SUM 202	SUM 508	
ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT	ID COUNT
ALTH 24	ALTH 1	ALTH 1	ALTH 2	ANNL 10	ALTH 2	ANNL 3	ALTH 4	ALTH 11	ANNL 2	ANNL 5												
ANNL 25	ANNL 6	ANNL 10	ANNL 23	ASTR 1	ANNL 4	DDGR 7	ANNL 25	ANNL 16	ANNL 3	ARAC 1												
DDGR 2	ASTR 3	DBLB 12	ARAC 1	CSYN 1	DGBR 57	DGBR 50	CCYC 1	CPAL 1	BLHT 1	BLIN 7												
DGBR 24	DDGR 32	DDGR 4	CAEN 1	DGBR 37	DSEP 5	DISC 1	DCOM 39	DGRY 38	BLSR 1	BLJR 48												
DGRY 59	DPYC 6	DGBR 5	COST 1	DISC 1	FCOP 4	DSEP 4	DSEP 13	DISC 1	DBLB 1	BLMT 2												
DSEP 2	DSEP 6	DSEP 1	CPAL 2	DSEP 4	MFHC 3	FCOP 3	FCOP 10	DHHT 61	DDGR 10	BLOD 5												
FCOP 68	FCOP 15	FCOP 10	DDGR 3	FCOP 14	NEUR 7	FPAL 1	LEPD 1	EUPR 1	DGBR 105	BLSR 17												
FCTN 1	LSTP 2	LSTP 2	DGBR 112	LSTP 3	NUND 1	MFHC 2	LSTP 6	FCOP 26	DISC 2	BTOT 10												
FPRT 1	NEUR 3	NEUR 5	DSEP 38	MFHC 1	PBRK 4	NEUR 5	MFHC 2	LSTP 1	DLGH 12	CBLT 2												
LEPD 1	NUND 1	PBRK 3	FCOP 26	NEUR 4	PCAL 3	NUND 1	MUND 1	MFHC 6	DREJ 32	DISC 9												
LSTP 3	PAPH 1	PCAL 8	LEPD 1	NUND 2	PCYC 1	PBRK 1	NEUR 30	NEUR 16	DREJ 4	DPYC 63												
LSTR 1	PBRK 6	PCYC 2	LSTP 6	PBRK 7	PECP 162	PCON 1	PCAL 10	NUND 1	DSEP 4	DREJ 2												
MFHC 1	PCAL 2	PECP 12	MFHC 1	PCAL 5	PLEP 22	PECP 12	PCON 2	ODON 1	FCOP 1	DSEP 2												
NEUR 26	PCON 1	PLEP 5	NEUR 44	PCON 3	PLXS 1	PLEP 7	PCYC 1	PAPH 2	LSTP 1	DSEP 2												
ODON 1	PECP 58	PHAC 23	NUND 2	PECP 16	PHAC 7	PHAC 2	PECP 132	PBRK 25	NEDS 7	DTOT 27												
PBRK 41	PLEP 37	PSTH 6	ODON 2	PLEP 23	PSAR 1	PSTH 11	PLEP 14	PCAL 21	MHSI 1	DHHT 42												
PCAL 25	PHAC 18	PSUL 2	PBRK 8	PLYC 1	PSTH 30	PUND 4	PHAC 30	PECP 162	NUND 1	FCOP 16												
PCON 1	PSTH 20	PUND 3	PCAL 10	PHAC 9	PSUL 4	SPHN 1	PSTH 42	PLEP 19	NUND 3	HOLT 29												
PCRD 1	PSUL 5	SPRG 1	PCON 3	PSTH 47	PUND 1	TRAL 2	PUND 1	PLXS 1	PHAC 10	LEPD 2												
PCYC 2	PUND 9		PCRC 1	PUND 4		WTTH 1	STIG 2	PLYC 1	PSTH 2	MEDS 30												
PECP 84	SEED 2		PCYC 1			WSPR 1	WSPR 1	PHAC 82	PUND 1	MEUP 1												
PLEP 14			PECP 211					PSTH 42		MSOL 2												
PLXS 3			PLEP 38					PUND 4		MUND 2												
PLYB 1			PLXS 1					STIG 9		NEUR 2												
PLYC 4			PLYB 1					TCAR 2		PBRK 5												
PHAC 27			PLYC 4					WSPR 2		PECP 2												
PHAR 1			PHAC 22							PHAC 4												
PPIN 1			PSTH 95							PUND 2												
PSAR 1			PSUL 1							TRAL 59												
PSEL 1			PUND 10							HBLN 2												
PSFR 1			SEED 1							KCAP 1												
PSTH 67			SPFR 1							WESC 3												
PUND 9			SPHN 1							WFSH 2												
SEED 3			STIG 1							WPLN 10												
SPHN 2			WSPR 1							WSJH 1												
STIG 2																						
TCAR 1																						

LISTING BY		LOCATION									
LOC 370		LOC 371		LOC 372		LOC 373		LOC 374		LOC 375	
ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES		ALL PAGES	
SUM 634		SUM 175		SUM 68		SUM 55		SUM 325		SUM 493	
ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT		ID COUNT	
BTOT	11	BTOT	4	BLIN	1	ALTH	1	ALTH	1	ALTH	1
CBLT	2	CUND	3	BLJR	1	ANNL	1	ANNL	4	ANNL	1
CCYC	3	DTOT	112	BLSR	1	BLIN	3	ASTR	1	BLIN	5
DTOT	580	HOLT	3	DGRY	32	DGBR	17	CPYG	1	BLJR	35
FCOP	2	NUND	12	DISC	1	DISC	1	DGRY	132	BLSR	27
HOLT	3	PUND	32	DSEP	4	DSEP	4	DSEP	6	BTOT	55
MEDS	10	TRAL	7	HOLT	1	DWTH	3	DWTH	5	CAEN	1
MPEC	1	WUND	2	MEDH	1	MEDM	2	FCOP	16	CBLM	3
MSTR	1			MEDS	21	MEDS	16	HOLT	1	CBLT	36
NUND	9			HSCZ	1	HSCZ	1	LEPD	1	CCYC	1
TRAL	7			NEUR	2	PECP	1	MEDH	1	CKAL	1
WCAP	2			PECP	1	PSTH	1	MEDS	134	DCOM	6
WUND	3			TRAL	1	TRAL	3	MMSI	1	DGBR	71
						HESC	1	MSCZ	3	DGRY	42
								HUND	1	DISC	11
								PECP	4	DREJ	2
								PMAC	1	DSEP	1
								PSTM	2	DWTH	70
								TRAL	6	FCOP	31
								WCAP	1	HDEV	3
								HSPR	1	INCG	1
								WUND	2	MDUN	1
										MMSI	2
										MPEC	2
										MUND	2
										NEUR	8
										NUND	8
										ODOH	1
										PSRK	5
										PCAL	1
										PCYC	2
										PECP	14
										FNAC	1
										PSTM	18
										PUND	2
										RTHD	1
										STIG	1
										TMCN	4
										WCAP	3
										HESC	5
										WHYS	1
										WPLN	2
										WTTH	4
										WUND	1

Appendix 4. R mark down

Mazon Creek Paleoecology and Taphonomy

John Warren Huntley

2025-04-01

Table of Contents

#Setup for knitting RMarkdown file:

#Load the packages:

```
library(knitr)
library(tidyverse)
library(vegan)
library(NatParksPalettes)
library(ggmap)
library(maps)
library(mapdata)
library(viridis)
library(ggExtra)
library(ggrepel)
library(geosphere)
library(plotly)
library(ggribes)
```

#Install the primary data sheet:

```
Mazon <- read.csv("MazonRevisedCulled.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",")
```

Conduct the NMDS:

```
set.seed(123)
MazonThreeNMDS <- metaMDS(Mazon[,c(5:142)], distance = "bray", k=3, ma
xit = 999, trymax = 500, wascores = TRUE)
print(MazonThreeNMDS)
stressplot(MazonThreeNMDS)
plot(MazonThreeNMDS)
```

Extract NMDS1-3 scores:

```
SampleScores <- as.data.frame(scores(MazonThreeNMDS, choices = c(1:3),
display = c("sites"), tidy = TRUE))
SampleScores$sample <- Mazon$sample
SampleScores$grouping <- Mazon$grouping
attach(SampleScores)
```

```
SpeciesScores <- as.data.frame(scores(MazonThreeNMDS, choices = c(1:3)
, display = c("species"), tidy = TRUE))
attach(SampleScores)
```

Create objects for convex hulls of NMDS1/2 scores by 'grouping':

```
attach(SampleScores)
GroupHull12 <- SampleScores |> group_by(grouping) |> slice(chull(NMDS1
, NMDS2))
attach(GroupHull12)
```

```
GroupHull123 <- SampleScores |> group_by(grouping) |> slice(chull(NMDS2
, NMDS3))
attach(GroupHull123)
```

Plot NMDS1/2 and NMDS2/3 of samples classified by 'grouping':

```
attach(SampleScores)
attach(GroupHull12)

ggplot() + geom_polygon(data = GroupHull12, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=grouping), alpha=0.3) + geom_point(data = SampleScores, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=grouping), shape=21) + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "braidwood"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "kankakee"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "will"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "essex indet"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + scale_color_natparks_d("Triglav") + coord_equal(ratio = 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend.position = c(0.2,0.85))
```

```
attach(SampleScores)
attach(GroupHull123)

ggplot() + geom_polygon(data = GroupHull123, aes(NMDS2, NMDS3, fill=grouping), alpha=0.3) + geom_point(data = SampleScores, aes(NMDS2, NMDS3, fill=grouping), shape=21) + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "braidwood"), aes(mean(NMDS2), mean(NMDS3)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "kankakee"), aes(mean(NMDS2), mean(NMDS3)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "will"), aes(mean(NMDS2), mean(NMDS3)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + geom_point(data = SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "essex indet"), aes(mean(NMDS2), mean(NMDS3)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black")
```

```
= SampleScores |> filter(grouping == "essex indet"), aes(mean(NMDS2),
mean(NMDS3)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + scale_f
ill_natparks_d("Triglav") + scale_color_natparks_d("Triglav") + coord_
equal(ratio = 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(si
ze = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend
.position = c(0.20,0.85))
```

Export SpeciesScores as .csv, enter species grouping variables and re-import data to make figures:

```
# write.csv(SpeciesScores, file = "SpeciesScoresRevised.csv")

SpeciesScoresUpdated <- read.csv("SpeciesScoresRevised.csv", header =
TRUE, sep = ",")
SpeciesScoresUpdated$Habitat <- as.character(SpeciesScoresUpdated$Habi
tat)
SpeciesScoresUpdated$Clade <- as.character(SpeciesScoresUpdated$Clade)
SpeciesScoresUpdated$Tissue <- as.character(SpeciesScoresUpdated$Tissu
e)
SpeciesScoresUpdated$Habitat <- factor(SpeciesScoresUpdated$Habitat, l
evels = c("Terrestrial", "Freshwater", "Intermediate", "Marine"))
SpeciesScoresUpdated$Clade <- factor(SpeciesScoresUpdated$Clade, level
s = c("Plants", "Terrestrial Arthropod", "Amphibian", "Arthropod", "Aq
uatic Arthropod", "Fish", "Cnidarian", "Brachiopod", "Echinoderm", "Mo
llusk", "Hemichordate", "Worm", "Incertae sedis/Other", "Trace"))
SpeciesScoresUpdated$Tissue <- factor(SpeciesScoresUpdated$Tissue, lev
els = c("Lignin", "Chitin", "Shell", "Vertebrate", "Derm", "NoTissue"
, "Unknown"))

attach(SpeciesScoresUpdated)
```

Create color palette for Habitat groups and create convex hulls for Habitat groups:

```
HabitatPalette <- c("#8B6A04", "#75C80A", "#41E2DB", "#0B19F2")

HabitatHull12 <- SpeciesScoresUpdated |> group_by(Habitat) |> slice(ch
ull(NMDS1, NMDS2))
attach(HabitatHull12)

HabitatHull123 <- SpeciesScoresUpdated |> group_by(Habitat) |> slice(ch
ull(NMDS2, NMDS3))
attach(HabitatHull123)
```

Plot NMDS1/2 and NMDS2/3 of species grouped by Habitat:

```
attach(SpeciesScoresUpdated)
attach(HabitatHull12)
```

```
attach(HabitatHull123)
```

```
ggplot() + geom_polygon(data = HabitatHull12, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=Habitat), alpha=0.3) + geom_point(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=Habitat), shape=21) + xlim(c(-1.3,1.2)) + ylim(c(-1.3,1.5)) + scale_color_manual(values = HabitatPalette) + scale_fill_manual(values = HabitatPalette) + coord_equal(ratio = 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

```
ggplot() + geom_polygon(data = HabitatHull123, aes(NMDS2, NMDS3, fill=Habitat), alpha=0.3) + geom_point(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS2, NMDS3, fill=Habitat), shape=21) + xlim(c(-1.3,1.5)) + ylim(c(-1.1,1.7)) + scale_color_manual(values = HabitatPalette) + scale_fill_manual(values = HabitatPalette) + coord_equal(ratio = 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

Create color palette for Clade groups:

```
CladePalette <- c("#86db58", "#6f8fff", "#bb8b00", "#91286a", "#2adfac", "#ae002c", "#008937", "#ff7bbd", "#019f8f", "#fc642f", "#abca95", "#9f1a44", "#f7bb6d", "#5a541f")
```

Plot NMDS1/2 and NMDS2/3 of species grouped by Clade:

```
attach(SpeciesScoresUpdated)
```

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=Clade), shape=21) + xlim(c(-1.3,1.2)) + ylim(c(-1.3,1.5)) + scale_fill_manual(values = CladePalette) + coord_equal(ratio = 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS2, NMDS3, fill=Clade), shape=21) + xlim(c(-1.3,1.5)) + ylim(c(-1.1,1.7)) + scale_fill_manual(values = CladePalette) + coord_equal(ratio = 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

Plot NMDS1/2 and NMDS2/3 of species grouped by Tissue:

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill = Tissue), shape=21, size=3) + geom_rug(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, color = Tissue)) + xlim(c(-1.3,1.2)) + ylim(c(-1.3,1.5)) + coord_equal(ratio = 1) + scale_fill_viridis(option = "plasma", discrete = TRUE) + scale_color_viridis(option = "plasma", discrete = TRUE) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS2, NMDS3, fill = Tissue), shape=21, size=3) + geom_rug(data = SpeciesScoresUpdated, aes(NMDS2, NMDS3, color = Tissue)) + xlim(c(-1.3,1.5)) + ylim(c(-1.1,1.7)) + coord_equal(ratio = 1) + scale_fill_viridis(option = "plasma", discrete = TRUE) + scale_color_viridis(option = "plasma", discrete = TRUE) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

Make maps of location samples Import files for maps:

```
usa <- map_data("usa")
states <- map_data("state")
attach(states)
Illinois <- subset(states, region=="illinois")
attach(Illinois)
```

Make maps:

```
#Index map
ggplot() + geom_polygon(data=states, aes(x=long, y=lat, group=group), fill="white", color="grey10") + guides(fill=FALSE) + geom_polygon(data = subset(states, region == "illinois"), aes(x=long, y=lat), fill="black") + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + theme_void()

#State map
ggplot() + geom_polygon(data = Illinois, aes(x=long, y=lat), fill="white", color="black") + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + xlab("Longitude") + ylab("Latitude") + theme_void()

#Close up map of sampling localities by grouping
ggplot() + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat, fill=grouping), shape=21, size=2) + xlim(c(-88.85,-88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05,41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(legend.position = c(0.15, 0.2)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

Examine the proportion of duds (nodules without fossils) in each sample in the samples included in the NMDS ordination by biota.

```
attach(Mazon)

median(subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="braidwood"))
median(subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="kankakee"))
median(subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="will"))
```

```
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="braidwood"), subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="will"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="braidwood"), subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="kankakee"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="kankakee"), subset(Mazon$DudsPercent, grouping=="will"))
```

```
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_boxplot(aes(grouping, DudsPercent, fill=grouping), width=0.3, alpha=0.3) + geom_jitter(aes(grouping, DudsPercent, fill=grouping), width = 0.1, shape=21, size=2) + ylim(c(0,100)) + labs(x="", y="Percent Duds") + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend.position = "none")
```

```
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_boxplot(aes(grouping, NodulesTotal - DudsTotal, fill=grouping), width=0.3, alpha=0.3) + geom_jitter(aes(grouping, NodulesTotal - DudsTotal, fill=grouping), width = 0.1, shape=21, size=2) + labs(x="", y="Fossil Count") + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend.position = "none")
```

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat, fill=DudsPercent, size=NodulesTotal), shape=21, alpha=0.7) + xlim(c(-88.85,-88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05,41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_gradient(low = "#2CD5C4", high = "#861F41") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

Analyze richness and evenness of samples by grouping

Calculate estimated species richness for a sample size of 51 (the smallest sample size in Mazon) using rarefaction:

```
attach(Mazon)
```

```
Mazon$Rarefy51 <- rarefy(Mazon[,c(5:142)], sample = 51)
attach(Mazon)
```

Create boxplot and jitterplot of rarefied richness (n=51) by grouping:

```
attach(Mazon)
```

```
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_boxplot(aes(grouping, Rarefy51, fill=grouping), width=0.3, alpha=0.3) + geom_jitter(aes(grouping, Rarefy51, fill=grouping), width = 0.1, shape=21, size=2) + labs(x="", y="Rarefied Ri
```

```
chness (n=51)") + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() +
theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.text = elemen
t_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend.position = "none")
```

```
median(subset(Mazon$Rarefy51, grouping=="braidwood"))
median(subset(Mazon$Rarefy51, grouping=="kankakee"))
median(subset(Mazon$Rarefy51, grouping=="will"))
```

```
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$Rarefy51, grouping == "braidwood"), subset(Ma
zon$Rarefy51, grouping == "will"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$Rarefy51, grouping == "braidwood"), subset(Ma
zon$Rarefy51, grouping == "kankakee"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$Rarefy51, grouping == "kankakee"), subset(Maz
on$Rarefy51, grouping == "will"))
```

#Calculate evenness for each sample:

```
attach(Mazon)
```

```
Mazon$evenness <- diversity(Mazon[,c(5:142)])/log(specnumber(Mazon[,c(
5:142)]))
attach(Mazon)
```

Create boxplot and jitterplot of evenness by grouping:

```
attach(Mazon)
```

```
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_boxplot(aes(grouping, evenness, fill=group
ing), width=0.3, alpha=0.3) + geom_jitter(aes(grouping, evenness, fill
=grouping), width = 0.1, shape=21, size=2) + labs(x="", y="Evenness")
+ scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + theme(axis.tit
le = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size =
15)) + theme(legend.position = "none")
```

```
median(subset(Mazon$evenness, grouping=="braidwood"))
median(subset(Mazon$evenness, grouping=="kankakee"))
median(subset(Mazon$evenness, grouping=="will"))
```

```
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$evenness, grouping == "braidwood"), subset(Ma
zon$evenness, grouping == "will"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$evenness, grouping == "braidwood"), subset(Ma
zon$evenness, grouping == "kankakee"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$evenness, grouping == "kankakee"), subset(Maz
on$evenness, grouping == "will"))
```

```
attach(Mazon)
```

```
MazonRarecurve <- rarecurve(Mazon[,5:142], label = TRUE)
```

```

MazonRareCurveData <- map_dfr(MazonRarecurve, bind_rows) |>
  bind_cols(sample = Mazon$sample) |>
  pivot_longer(-sample) |>
  drop_na() |>
  mutate(n_seqs = as.numeric(str_replace(name, "N", ""))) |>
  select(-name)
attach(MazonRareCurveData)

```

#Insert grouping name as variable using case_when function

```

MazonRareCurveData <- MazonRareCurveData |>
  mutate(grouping = case_when(
    sample==2 ~ 'will',
    sample==4 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==5 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==6 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==7 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==8 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==9 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==10 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==11 ~ 'will',
    sample==13 ~ 'will',
    sample==14 ~ 'will',
    sample==15 ~ 'will',
    sample==16 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==17 ~ 'will',
    sample==18 ~ 'will',
    sample==19 ~ 'will',
    sample==20 ~ 'will',
    sample==21 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==22 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==23 ~ 'will',
    sample==24 ~ 'will',
    sample==25 ~ 'will',
    sample==27 ~ 'will',
    sample==28 ~ 'will',
    sample==29 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==30 ~ 'will',
    sample==31 ~ 'kankakee',
    sample==32 ~ 'will',
    sample==33 ~ 'will',
    sample==34 ~ 'will',
    sample==35 ~ 'will',
    sample==36 ~ 'will',
    sample==37 ~ 'will',
    sample==38 ~ 'will',
    sample==39 ~ 'will',
  ))

```

```
sample==40 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==41 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==42 ~ 'will',
sample==43 ~ 'will',
sample==44 ~ 'will',
sample==45 ~ 'will',
sample==46 ~ 'will',
sample==47 ~ 'will',
sample==48 ~ 'will',
sample==49 ~ 'will',
sample==50 ~ 'will',
sample==51 ~ 'will',
sample==52 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==53 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==54 ~ 'will',
sample==55 ~ 'will',
sample==56 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==57 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==58 ~ 'will',
sample==59 ~ 'will',
sample==60 ~ 'will',
sample==61 ~ 'will',
sample==62 ~ 'will',
sample==63 ~ 'will',
sample==64 ~ 'will',
sample==66 ~ 'will',
sample==67 ~ 'will',
sample==68 ~ 'will',
sample==70 ~ 'will',
sample==72 ~ 'will',
sample==73 ~ 'will',
sample==74 ~ 'will',
sample==75 ~ 'will',
sample==78 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==79 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==81 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==82 ~ 'will',
sample==83 ~ 'will',
sample==84 ~ 'will',
sample==85 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==86 ~ 'will',
sample==87 ~ 'will',
sample==89 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==90 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==95 ~ 'will',
sample==100 ~ 'kankakee',
```

```
sample==105 ~ 'will',
sample==106 ~ 'will',
sample==107 ~ 'will',
sample==108 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==109 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==110 ~ 'will',
sample==113 ~ 'will',
sample==123 ~ 'will',
sample==124 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==125 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==126 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==127 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==128 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==129 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==130 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==131 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==132 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==133 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==134 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==135 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==136 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==137 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==138 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==140 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==141 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==142 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==143 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==145 ~ 'will',
sample==148 ~ 'will',
sample==149 ~ 'will',
sample==150 ~ 'will',
sample==151 ~ 'will',
sample==152 ~ 'will',
sample==153 ~ 'will',
sample==154 ~ 'will',
sample==155 ~ 'will',
sample==156 ~ 'will',
sample==157 ~ 'will',
sample==158 ~ 'will',
sample==159 ~ 'will',
sample==160 ~ 'will',
sample==161 ~ 'will',
sample==162 ~ 'will',
sample==163 ~ 'will',
sample==164 ~ 'will',
sample==174 ~ 'will',
```

```
sample==184 ~ 'will',
sample==186 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==190 ~ 'will',
sample==191 ~ 'will',
sample==192 ~ 'will',
sample==193 ~ 'will',
sample==194 ~ 'will',
sample==195 ~ 'will',
sample==196 ~ 'will',
sample==197 ~ 'will',
sample==201 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==202 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==203 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==205 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==206 ~ 'will',
sample==207 ~ 'will',
sample==208 ~ 'will',
sample==209 ~ 'will',
sample==210 ~ 'will',
sample==211 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==212 ~ 'will',
sample==213 ~ 'will',
sample==214 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==215 ~ 'will',
sample==216 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==217 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==218 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==220 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==221 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==222 ~ 'will',
sample==223 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==224 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==227 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==228 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==229 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==230 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==231 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==232 ~ 'will',
sample==233 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==234 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==235 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==236 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==237 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==238 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==239 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==242 ~ 'kankakee',
```

```
sample==247 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==248 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==249 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==250 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==251 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==252 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==253 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==254 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==255 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==256 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==257 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==258 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==259 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==260 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==261 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==262 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==263 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==264 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==265 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==266 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==267 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==268 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==269 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==270 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==271 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==272 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==273 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==274 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==275 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==276 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==277 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==278 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==279 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==280 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==281 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==282 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==284 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==285 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==286 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==287 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==288 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==289 ~ 'will',
sample==290 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==293 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==301 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==302 ~ 'braidwood',
```

```
sample==305 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==306 ~ 'will',
sample==308 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==309 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==313 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==314 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==315 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==316 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==320 ~ 'will',
sample==322 ~ 'will',
sample==324 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==328 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==330 ~ 'will',
sample==331 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==332 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==333 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==334 ~ 'will',
sample==341 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==343 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==344 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==345 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==346 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==347 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==348 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==349 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==350 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==351 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==352 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==353 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==354 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==355 ~ 'kankakee',
sample==356 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==357 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==358 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==359 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==360 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==361 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==362 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==363 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==364 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==366 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==367 ~ 'braidwood',
sample==369 ~ 'will',
sample==375 ~ 'kankakee'))
```

`attach(MazonRareCurveData)`

Plot rarefaction curves for all samples:

```
attach(MazonRareCurveData)
ggplot() + geom_line(data = MazonRareCurveData, aes(x = n_seqs, y = value, group=sample, color=grouping)) + geom_vline(aes(xintercept=51)) + labs(x="Sample Size", y="Taxa") + scale_color_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend.position = "none")
```

Create maps displaying the proportion of samples made of terrestrial, freshwater, and marine taxa

Create the variables:

```
attach(Mazon)

Mazon$TerrProp <- ((ALTH+ANNL+ASTR+LEPD+LSTP+LSTR+NEUR+ODON+PAPH+PASO+PBRK+PCAL+PCON+PCRC+PCRD+PCRS+PCYC+PDRN+PECO+PFUN+PLEP+PLIN+LYCO+PMAC+PMAR+PPIN+PSAR+PSEL+PSPR+PSTM+PSUL+PTAE+PUND+SCBR+SEED+SPFR+SPHN+SPMG+SPRS+STIG+TCAR+TFBR+THAL+THRN+TWSC)/NodulesTotal)
Mazon$FreshProp <- ((ARAC+CAEN+CCYZ+COST+CPAL+CSYN+EUPR+FCTN+FMEG+FXNT+HFTR+INSC+FWCL+PLXS+REGC+TFTR+WSPR)/NodulesTotal)
Mazon$MarProp <- ((AICH+ANMD+BLOB+ESSX+CBAR+BELO+CCYC+CESS+CFLE+CHOP+CKAL+CKEL+CMES+CMRS+CPEA+CTYR+EGGS+ETAC+EUCH+ACAN+FESC+FGIL+FRHB+HDEV+HOLT+KOTT+LETT+LIMU+LING+MCEP+MCHT+MDUN+EDMO+MEUP+MHTW+MLIM+MYAL+PECT+MSCZ+MSOL+MSTR+NCYC+OCTO+TDPL+TMON+WBLN+WCAP+WDRY+WESC+WFAN+WFSH+WHYS+WEM+WOLH+WPJM+WPLN+WPRI+WSJW+WTTH+WUND+YWHY)/NodulesTotal)
Mazon$IntermediateProp <- ((AMPH+ARTH+SHRP+CPYG+CUND+FCOP+FCRT+FPAL+FISH+INCG+MUND+TPEL+TRAL+WILY)/NodulesTotal)
attach(Mazon)
```

Make the maps:

```
attach(Mazon)

ggplot() + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat, fill=TerrProp, size=TerrProp), shape=21, alpha=0.7) + xlim(c(-88.85,-88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05,41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_gradient(low = "lightgrey", high = "#8B6A04") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))

ggplot() + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat, fill=FreshProp, size=FreshProp), shape=21, alpha=0.7) + xlim(c(-88.85,-88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05,41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_gradient(low = "lightgrey", high = "#75C80A") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude",
```

```
y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat, fill=IntermediateProp, size=IntermediateProp), shape=21, alpha=0.7) + xlim(c(-88.85, -88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05, 41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_gradient(low = "lightgrey", high = "#66c7cb") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat, fill=MarProp, size=MarProp), shape=21, alpha=0.7) + xlim(c(-88.85, -88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05, 41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_gradient(low = "lightgrey", high = "#0B19F2") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

Plot a map of the samples that were removed for having $n < 50$

Create new .csv from original data file to identify these samples.

```
SamplesExcluded <- read.csv("SamplesExcludedRevised.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",")
attach(SamplesExcluded)
```

Make the map:

```
ggplot() + geom_point(data = Mazon, aes(x=long, y=lat, fill=grouping), shape=21, size=2) + geom_point(data = SamplesExcluded, aes(x=long, y=lat, size=DudsPercent), shape = 23, fill="red", alpha=0.5) + xlim(c(-88.85, -88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05, 41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

#Make a map for the SOM with sample number label and color-coded by group

```
attach(Mazon)
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_point(aes(long, lat, fill=grouping), shape = 21, size=4) + geom_text_repel(aes(long, lat, label=sample), size = 5, max.overlaps = 200) + xlim(c(-88.85, -88.16)) + ylim(c(41.05, 41.4)) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axi
```

```
s.title = element_text(size = 15))
#Export as PDF at 48x36 inch Landscape
```

#Compare taxonomic similarity of samples to geographic distance to help distinguish between three spatially distinct biotas and three biotas overlapping to some degree along a gradient

Construct the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index matrix

```
attach(Mazon)

bray_curtis_matrix <- vegdist(Mazon[,c(5:142)], method = "bray")
```

Construct a matrix of straight-line distances between samples based on latitude and longitude

```
attach(Mazon)
straight_line_distance_matrix <- distm(Mazon[,c("long", "lat")], fun =
distHaversine)
```

Convert the matrices to vectors

```
bray_vector <- as.vector(as.dist(bray_curtis_matrix))
straight_line_vector <- as.vector(as.dist(straight_line_distance_matrix))
cor.test(bray_vector, straight_line_vector, method = "pearson")
plot(bray_vector, straight_line_vector)
```

Create a single matrix containing bray_vector and straight_line_vector

```
Combined_matrix <- cbind(bray_vector, straight_line_vector)
```

Make that figure look presentable

```
ggplot(data = Combined_matrix, aes(bray_vector, straight_line_vector/1000)) + geom_point(alpha=0.1, color="grey") + geom_smooth(method = loess, color="#630031", fill="#CF4420") + xlab("Bray-Curtis Dissimilarity") + ylab("Distance (km)") + theme_classic()
```

Test for the significance of the correlation between the bray_curtis_matrix and the straight_line_distance matrix using the Mantel test

```
mantel_result <- mantel(bray_curtis_matrix, straight_line_distance_matrix, method = "pearson", permutations = 999)
print(mantel_result)
```

Test the assertion that there is a greater proportion of cnidarian specimens in Kankakee samples than in Will samples:

Create the new variable:

```
attach(Mazon)
Mazon$CnidarianProp <- ((ANMD+BLOB+ESSX+HDEV+OCTO)/NodulesTotal)
```

```
attach(Mazon)
```

Create the figure:

```
attach(Mazon)
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_boxplot(aes(grouping, CnidarianProp, fill=
grouping), width=0.3, alpha=0.3) + geom_jitter(aes(grouping, Cnidarian
Prop, fill=grouping), width = 0.1, shape=21, size=2) + ylim(c(0,1)) +
labs(x="", y="Proportion of Cnidarians") + scale_fill_natparks_d("Trig
lav") + theme_classic() + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
+ theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend.position =
"none")
```

```
median(subset(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping=="braidwood"))
median(subset(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping=="will"))
median(subset(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping=="kankakee"))
```

```
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping == "braidwood"), subs
et(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping == "will"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping == "braidwood"), subs
et(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping == "kankakee"))
wilcox.test(subset(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping == "kankakee"), subse
t(Mazon$CnidarianProp, grouping == "will"))
```

Make a map of cnidarian proportion values

```
attach(Mazon)
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_point(aes(long, lat, size = CnidarianProp)
, shape=21, color="black", fill = "#6A0DAD", alpha=0.6) + coord_fixed(
ratio = 1.3) + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + t
heme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text
(size = 15)) + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15))
```

#How is abundance of taxa with proximate or distal NMDS1 scores distributed across NMDS1? Are taxa with intermediate scores truly intermediate in distribution with respect to NMDS1 or are they broadly distributed across it?

Merge Mazon and SampleScores matrices:

```
AllMazon <- dplyr::full_join(Mazon, SampleScores, by = "sample")
```

Construct NMDS plot of taxa with their names:

```
attach(SpeciesScores)
ggplot(data = SpeciesScores, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2)) + geom_text(aes(label
= label))
```

Construct the plots:

```
attach(AllMazon)
ggplot(data = AllMazon, aes(NMDS1, MBCR)) + geom_point() + geom_smooth(
  method = "loess", color="#630031", fill="#CF4420") + theme_classic()
```

Create new data set for each grouping from AllMazon:

```
AllMazonRidges <- AllMazon %>%
  select(c(1:2,5:142,153:154))

AllMazonRidgesLong <- AllMazonRidges %>%
  pivot_longer(
    cols = 3:140,
    names_to = "Taxon",
    values_to = "Abundance"
  )
```

Create ridge plots for each grouping by taxon:

```
ggplot(AllMazonRidgesLong, aes(x = NMDS1, y = Taxon, fill = grouping.x
, height = Abundance)) +
  geom_density_ridges(
    aes(group = interaction(grouping.x, Taxon)),
    stat = "identity",
    scale = 1.5,
    alpha = 0.5
  ) +
  theme_minimal()
```

This figure is large an overwhelming. We need to make a simpler version that contains only the most abundant taxa.

```
total_abundance <- AllMazonRidgesLong %>%
  group_by(Taxon) %>%
  summarise(TotalAbundance = sum(Abundance, na.rm = TRUE))
```

Plot a histogram of taxon abundance:

```
attach(total_abundance)
ggplot(data = total_abundance, aes(x=TotalAbundance)) +
  geom_histogram(fill="skyblue", color="black", alpha=0.7) +
  theme_classic()
```

Make another ridgeplot including only taxa with an abundance of X specimens or more:

```
AllMazonRidgesLongFiltered <- AllMazonRidgesLong %>%
  filter(Taxon %in% total_abundance$Taxon[total_abundance$TotalAbundan
ce >= 500])
```

```

ggplot(AllMazonRidgesLongFiltered, aes(x = NMDS1, y = Taxon, fill = grouping.x, height = Abundance)) +
  geom_density_ridges(
    aes(group = interaction(grouping.x, Taxon)),
    stat = "identity",
    scale = 1.5,
    alpha = 0.5
  ) +
  scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")

```

#Is there a difference in the occurrence of traces (Diplocraterion and Trails, excluding coprolites, pellets, and other ichnofossil taxa that were culled) across assemblage types?

```

attach(Mazon)
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_boxplot(aes(grouping, ((TDPL+TRAL)/NodulesTotal), fill = grouping), width = 0.3, alpha = 0.3) + geom_jitter(aes(grouping, ((TDPL+TRAL)/NodulesTotal), fill = grouping), width = 0.1, shape=21, size=2) + xlab("") + ylab("Proportion of Trails and Burrows") +
scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + theme_classic() + theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15))
) + theme(legend.position = "none")

```

```

median(subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="braidwood"))
median(subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="kankakee"))
median(subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="will"))

```

```

wilcox.test(subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="braidwood"), subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="kankakee"))

```

```

wilcox.test(subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="braidwood"), subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="will"))

```

```

wilcox.test(subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="will"), subset((TDPL+TRAL/NodulesTotal), grouping=="kankakee"))

```

#How does the proportion of trails and burrows plot geographically?

```

attach(Mazon)
ggplot(data = Mazon) + geom_point(aes(long, lat, size = ((TDPL+TRAL)/NodulesTotal)), shape=21, color="black", fill = "#6A3C1A", alpha=0.6) + coord_fixed(ratio = 1.3) + theme_classic() + labs(x="Longitude", y="Latitude") + theme(legend.title = element_text("")) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 15)) + theme(legend.title = element_blank())

```

#The reviewers in the second round of review wanted us to: 1)re-run the nMDS without Essexella and Mazonomya to see if the three groups persisted, and 2) percent transform the data (prior to analysis), re-run the nMDS (using the “autotransform=FALSE” argument), and see if the results are consistent. Here we do that.

#Conduct the nMDS without Essesella (ESSX) and Mazonomya (EDMO):

```
set.seed(123)
LimitedMazonThreeNMDS <- metaMDS(Mazon[,c(5:13, 15:65, 67:142)], distance = "bray", k=3, maxit = 999, trymax = 500, wascores = TRUE)
print(MazonThreeNMDS)
stressplot(MazonThreeNMDS)
plot(MazonThreeNMDS)
```

#Extract the MDS scores from LimitedMazonThreeNMDS:

```
LimitedSampleScores <- as.data.frame(scores(LimitedMazonThreeNMDS, choices = c(1:3), display = c("sites"), tidy = TRUE))
LimitedSampleScores$sample <- Mazon$sample
LimitedSampleScores$grouping <- Mazon$grouping
attach(LimitedSampleScores)
```

```
LimitedSpeciesScores <- as.data.frame(scores(LimitedMazonThreeNMDS, choices = c(1:3), display = c("species"), tidy = TRUE))
attach(LimitedSampleScores)
```

#Create convex hulls for LimitedMazonThreeNMDS MDS1 and MDS2:

```
LimitedGroupHull12 <- LimitedSampleScores |> group_by(grouping) |> slice(chull(NMDS1, NMDS2))
```

#Plot the results of LimitedMazonThreeNMDS:

```
ggplot() + geom_polygon(data = LimitedGroupHull12, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=grouping), alpha=0.3) + geom_point(data = LimitedSampleScores, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=grouping), shape=21) + geom_point(data = LimitedSampleScores |> filter(grouping == "braidwood"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black", alpha=0.5) + geom_point(data = LimitedSampleScores |> filter(grouping == "kankakee"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + geom_point(data = LimitedSampleScores |> filter(grouping == "will"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black") + annotate(geom = "text", x=-0.5, y=-1.0, label="Stress = 0.15") + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + labs(title = "NMDS excluding Essexella and Mazonomya") + theme_classic(base_size = 15)
```

#Rerun the nMDS by first percent transforming rows and using the autotransform=FALSE argument and check for consistency #Create the percentage transformed data frame

```
attach(Mazon)
taxa_cols <- 5:142

MazonPercentageTransformed <- Mazon %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(RowSum = sum(c_across(all_of(taxa_cols)))) %>%
  dplyr::ungroup() %>%
  mutate(across(all_of(taxa_cols), ~ .x/RowSum *100)) %>%
  select(-RowSum)
```

#Conduct the NMDS on the percentage transformed data:

```
set.seed(123)
PercentageMazonThreeNMDS <- metaMDS(MazonPercentageTransformed[,c(5:14
2)], distance = "bray", k=3, autotransform = FALSE, maxit = 999, tryma
x = 500, wascores = TRUE)
print(PercentageMazonThreeNMDS)
stressplot(PercentageMazonThreeNMDS)
plot(PercentageMazonThreeNMDS)
```

#Extract the NMDS scores from PercentageMazonThreeNMDS:

```
PercentageSampleScores <- as.data.frame(scores(PercentageMazonThreeNMD
S, choices = c(1:3), display = c("sites"), tidy = TRUE))
PercentageSampleScores$sample <- Mazon$sample
PercentageSampleScores$grouping <- Mazon$grouping
attach(PercentageSampleScores)

PercentageSpeciesScores <- as.data.frame(scores(PercentageMazonThreeNM
DS, choices = c(1:3), display = c("species"), tidy = TRUE))
attach(PercentageSpeciesScores)
```

#Create convex hulls for PercentageMazonThreeNMDS MDS1 and MDS2:

```
PercentageGroupHull12 <- PercentageSampleScores |> group_by(grouping)
|> slice(chull(NMDS1, NMDS2))
```

#Plot the results of the PercentageMazonThreeNMDS:

```
ggplot() + geom_polygon(data = PercentageGroupHull12, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2
, fill=grouping), alpha=0.3) + geom_point(data = PercentageSampleScore
s, aes(NMDS1, NMDS2, fill=grouping), shape=21) + geom_point(data = Per
centageSampleScores |> filter(grouping == "braidwood"), aes(mean(NMDS1
), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="white", color="black", alpha=
0.5) + geom_point(data = PercentageSampleScores |> filter(grouping ==
"kankakee"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=24, fill="wh
ite", color="black") + geom_point(data = PercentageSampleScores |> fil
ter(grouping == "will"), aes(mean(NMDS1), mean(NMDS2)), size=5, shape=
```

```
24, fill="white", color="black") + annotate(geom = "text", x=-0.5, y=-  
1.0, label="Stress = 0.14") + scale_fill_natparks_d("Triglav") + labs(  
title = "NMDS with Percentage Transformed Data") + theme_classic(base_  
size = 15)
```